

SPREE: Shetland's Epistemological Tradition of Music Making

by

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ABSTRACT

This thesis engages with the social worlds of Shetlanders through active personal participation in the local music scene. I explore how locals articulate personal and social perspectives on the distinctiveness of Shetland's music scene by reflecting on their own social experiences. The *spre* is explored ethnographically as the key local practice that manifests the principles of an epistemological tradition – a way of knowing and being that is shared across multiple generations.

I explore the evidence for existing interconnected epistemological principles, including horizontality (supporting people of all ages, genders, socioeconomic classes, cultural backgrounds and musical skill level), interpersonal and intergenerational knowledge, resourcefulness and nuance of character appreciation. Individuals know, describe and manifest these principles in their own characteristic, personal and changing ways. The appreciation of individual idiosyncrasies, life stories and skills in Shetland is not necessarily aligned with a model of competitive individualism of neoliberal capitalism, but with a local principle of equality and horizontality, founded on *spre* practices.

Based on open principles, this epistemological tradition supports engagement with past, current and novel forms of musical expression, remaining open to outside influences. As a fluid, living form, understanding it requires a leap beyond static models of tradition that seek the preservation of idealised authentic forms, canonical-aesthetic orthodoxies, and social boundaries. The *spre* remains stable and resilient as a principled way of being, providing a model for interactions with locals and outsiders, and affording the growth of a closely-knit social support network.

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that I have composed this thesis on my own. It has not been accepted or submitted to any previous application for a degree. I have done all the work contained herein. All quotations have been distinguished by quotation marks and the sources of information specifically acknowledged.

Rodrigo Ferrari-Nunes

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Rodrigo Ferrari-Nunes
Leiden, The Netherlands
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TABLE of CONTENTS

ABSTRACT	[p. ii]
DECLARATION	[p. iii]
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	[p. iv]
TABLE of CONTENTS	[p. v]
LIST of FIGURES	[p. viii]
ABBREVIATIONS	[p. viii]
STRUCTURAL OUTLINE	[p. ix]

**CHAPTER 1: THEORETICAL FORMULATIONS
PHENOMENOLOGY, NECESSITY and INVENTION** – pp. 1-23

1.1. INTRODUCING SCENES and COMMUNITIES	[p. 1]
1.2. EPISTEMOLOGICAL POSITIONINGS	[p. 3]
1.3. THE EPISTEMOLOGICAL TRADITION of SHETLAND MUSIC-MAKING	[p. 4]
1.4. CREATIVE-CRITICAL REFLEXIVITY: HARMONIC ORTHODOXIES and EPISTEMOLOGICAL GROWTH	[p. 15]
1.5. CREATIVE FREEDOM and EPISTEMOLOGICAL GROWTH	[p. 19]
1.6. NUANCE of CHARACTER, JAZZ and CREATIVE CONSTRICTION	[p. 21]

**CHAPTER 2: HISTORY and LITERATURE REVIEW
MUSICAL ANTHROPOLOGY in SHETLAND** – pp. 24-91

2.1. INTRODUCING SHETLAND STYLE MUSIC MAKING	[p. 24]
2.2. POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS, ECONOMY and TRANSPORTATION	[p. 27]
2.3. ETHNOGRAPHIES of SHETLAND	[p. 30]
2.4. ETHNOGRAPHIES of RURAL BRITAIN – from LOCALISM to MOBILITIES	[p. 47]
2.5. BOUNDARY-PERMEABILITY: POSITIONALITY, POWER and MOBILITIES	[p. 61]
2.6. SHETLAND MOBILITIES and EARLY ETHNOGRAPHY	[p. 64]
2.7. SHETLAND’S ANTHROPOLOGICAL LEGACY: JAMES A. TEIT	[p. 66]
2.8. THE SHETLAND STYLE – NUANCE of CHARACTER	[p. 67]
2.9. BOUNDED STYLES and UNBRIDLED INFLUENCES	[p. 70]
2.10. UP HELLY AA – TENSIONS OF GENDER, HISTORY, and TRADITION	[p. 73]
2.11. TOURISM, BACKWARDNESS, and SCHOLARLY DISTANCE	[p. 80]
2.12. TRADITIONS and CULTURES: SPURIOUSLY GENUINE INVENTIONS?	[p. 83]
2.13. CONTRIBUTIONS to ETHNOMUSICOLOGY and ETHNOGRAPHY	[p. 87]

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY and ETHICS	<i>– pp. 92-107</i>
3.1. BASIC RESEARCH OBJECTIVES and QUESTIONS	[p. 92]
<i>DATA COLLECTION and MANAGEMENT TECHNIQUES</i>	
3.2. ETHNOGRAPHIC LOCATIONS: MUSIC MAKING PLACES and MOBILITIES MAP	[p. 94]
3.3. DATA RECORDING, MANAGEMENT, SHARING and BACKUP	[p. 95]
<i>ETHICS & METHODS</i>	
3.4. ORAL CONSENT PROTOCOL	[p. 97]
3.5. RESULTS, COPYRIGHT and CONFIDENTIALITY	[p. 98]
3.6. POLITICAL IMPLICATIONS in SHETLAND, SCOTLAND and the UK	[p. 99]
3.7. PARTIALITY STATEMENT	[p. 100]
3.8. SPONTANEITY and INVOLVEMENT	[p. 101]
3.9. CONVIVIALITY: FACE-TO-FACE FLEXIBILITY and FACEBOOK RESEARCH	[p. 102]
3.10. AUDIOVISUAL SERVICES: PROFESSIONAL AMATEURISM	[p. 105]
CHAPTER 4: The SPREE as EPISTEMOLOGICAL TRADITION and SOCIOMUSICAL PRACTICE	<i>– pp. 108-155</i>
4.1. INTRODUCTION: The SPREE and the SHETLAND FOLK FEST	[p. 108]
4.2. SPREE INTEGRATION	[p. 110]
4.3. DEALING with DISCORDANT CHARACTERS	[p. 115]
4.4. SPREE as SUPPORT NETWORK	[p. 117]
4.5. STYLISTIC INDEPENDENCE and EPISTEMOLOGICAL RESILIENCE	[p. 118]
4.6. CHARACTER APPRECIATION and the SPREE: ANARCHIC HORIZONTALITY	[p. 123]
4.7. EXPERIMENTING with STYLE: PERSONAL COMPLEMENTATION	[p. 125]
4.8. PATTERNING and APPRECIATING MUSICAL CHARACTER	[p. 129]
4.9. SPREE-STYLE SOUND ENGINEERING	[p. 132]
4.10. HIGH LEVEL MUSIC and the SPIRIT of the SPREE	[p. 133]
4.11. BECOMING ATTUNED to the SPREE MODE of BEING	[p. 136]
<i>CONCLUSION</i>	
4.12. PERSONAL HARMONICS and the SPREE	[p. 148]
<i>'BEING WITH' and SPREE MUSIC MAKING</i>	[p. 150]
CHAPTER 5: PRODUCTION STYLES in SHETLAND COMMUNITY as BUZZWORD and COMMUNITY as VALUE SYSTEM	<i>– pp. 156-193</i>
5.1. INTRODUCING <i>IGNITION</i> and <i>BACK from BEYOND</i>	[p. 156]
5.2. BECOMING INVOLVED WITH <i>IGNITION</i>	[p. 160]
5.3. <i>BACK from BEYOND</i> : CREATIVE MULTIPLICITY and APPRECIATION	[p. 163]
5.4. 'YOU DON'T KNOW UNLESS YOU'VE LIVED IT'	[p. 165]
5.5. PRESTIGE, VOLUNTEERING and COMPENSATION	[p. 168]
5.6. PERFORMING for <i>IGNITION</i>	[p. 170]
5.7. ONSTAGE with <i>IGNITION</i> : TIME DRAG and PARODY FLOW	[p. 176]
5.8. <i>SPREEING</i> against CREATIVE STERILITY	[p. 178]
5.9. IN STUDIO with <i>IGNITION</i>	[p. 181]
5.10. THE 'PROS DON'T SEE YOU' COMMUNITY THEATRE FORMULA	[p. 182]
5.11. SPIRITUAL CATHARSIS and NATIONAL EXPOSURE	[p. 184]
5.12. EPISTEMOLOGICAL DISCORDANCE and LOCAL PRINCIPLES	[p. 185]
<i>CONCLUSION</i>	
5.13. THE FLOW of CARING and INTERPERSONAL APPRECIATION	[p. 189]
<i>CARING for VOICE: CREATIVE MULTIPLICITY and MUTUALITY</i>	[p. 190]
<i>FREEDOM and the COMMUNITY PRINCIPLE</i>	[p. 192]

CHAPTER 6: EXPERIENCING CREATIVITY	<i>– pp. 194-235</i>
6.1. INTRODUCTION: CREATIVE REGULATION	[p. 194]
6.2. JAZZY <i>SPREEING</i> and CREATIVITY in ANTHROPOLOGY	[p. 198]
6.3. FOR FREEDOM in INVENTION	[p. 203]
6.4. BRANDON, NORMAN, HAYDEN, LEWIS and JOE: FUNKIFIED TRAD	[p. 205]
6.5. FEELING COMFORTABLE in the MEDIA ROOM	[p. 207]
6.6. DISCUSSION: CREATIVITY and FREEDOM from the GROOVE	[p. 223]
6.7. BOUNDLESS MUSICAL WORLDS – ENGAGEMENT and INTEGRATION	[p. 228]
6.8. INSTITUTIONALISED JAZZ EDUCATION and SOCIAL DYNAMICS	[p. 232]
 <i>CONCLUSION</i>	
6.9. CREATIVE COMPLEMENTARITY and INTEGRATION	[p. 235]
 CHAPTER 7: THESIS CONCLUSIONS	<i>– pp. 236-257</i>
7.1. CREATIVITY and FREEDOM: <i>SPREE</i> RESILIENCE	[p. 236]
7.2. EPISTEMOLOGICAL GROWTH and CULTURAL-CREATIVE INTEGRATION	[p. 242]
7.3. CULTURAL WISDOM, IDENTITY and MATERIAL METAMORPHOSIS	[p. 244]
7.4. RISK, INNOVATION, CHANCE, CREATIVITY	[p. 246]
7.5. HOLOGRAPHIC REVERBERATIONS of <i>SPREE</i> CHARACTER and STYLE	[p. 247]
7.6. STRUCTURAL ‘DAMAGE CONTROL’ – REGULATIONS	[p. 252]
7.7. CREATIVE MULTIPLICITY and FLOW – DISTRIBUTIVE, SHARED POWER	[p. 254]
<i>HORIZONTALITY and EPISTEMOLOGICAL TRADITION TRANSMISSION</i>	[p. 254]
<i>CREATIVE-CRITICAL RESONANCE, EPISTEMOLOGICAL GROWTH and TRADITION</i>	[p. 255]
 REFERENCES	<i>– pp. 258-281</i>
 ENDNOTES	<i>– pp. 282-301</i>

LIST of FIGURES

- Figure 1: Norman Willmore (left) and Ewan Nowak at the Lerwick Legion, December 7th 2013. Nowak edited, mixed and mastered the EP *Terra Firma* (Nomadia 2013a). [p. 86]
- Figure 2: Producer Tim Matthews setting up microphones on Lewis Murray's drum set during the recording of the album *Brandy from a Stranger* (North Country Fair 2015), at Aitkens, May 21st, 2013. [p. 91]
- Figure 3: Sociomusical Locations Map – The town of Lerwick. [p. 94]
- Figure 4: Project Website – audiovisual materials and supplements. [p. 96]
- Figure 5: *North Country Fair* rehearsing at Aitkens (left to right, Chris Thomson, Jim Quinn, Michael Williamson, Arthur Nicholson, Ewan Nowak and Lewis Murray). [p. 128]
- Figure 6: *Spreers* in action. Fetlar Hall, July 20th, 2014, 5:40 AM. [p. 155]
- Figure 7: DJ Lyall performing a hip-hop duo with Marjolein Robertson (not shown) and *Troppo Funk*, at the Lerwick Legion, on August 16th 2013. [p. 234]
- Figure 8: Brian Nicholson (right) and young High Level Music students, in a fundraiser concert for local music education projects. Clickimin Centre, September 24th 2014. [p. 257]

ABBREVIATIONS

BFB	<i>Back from Beyond</i>
NTS	<i>National Theatre of Scotland</i>
SADA	<i>Shetland Arts Development Agency</i>
SFF	<i>Shetland Folk Festival</i>
SIC	<i>Shetland Islands Council</i>

STRUCTURAL OUTLINE

This ethnography is organised as follows: the first three chapters cover its theoretical model, the published regional literature, and methodology. The fourth, fifth, and sixth chapters analyse ethnographic materials and experiences. The final chapter, enfolded ethnographic materials, theory, and discussions into concluding remarks.

Chapter One develops a range of concepts that inform the notion of epistemological resonance. I present Shetland *spreeing* practices as an epistemological tradition, highlighting the synergies between performance and cognitive processes instead of their separation. Throughout this chapter, I explore semantic-experiential links between creative freedom, horizontality, flow, critical reflexivity, and epistemological growth.

Chapter Two provides a critical review of the regional ethnographic literature, focusing on Britain, Scotland, and Shetland, and on issues of mobility. I challenge explanations based on notions of boundedness and localism, invented traditions, ‘locals’, ‘incomers’, and ‘outsiders’. I discuss how, from the standpoint of local nuance of character appreciation and interpersonal knowledge principles, touristic stereotypes and hasty research have misrepresented Shetland’s sociomusical inhabitants.

Chapter Three discloses and discusses the methodology and ethics supporting this ethnography. I explain my consent model, handling of copyrighted and sensible information, confidentiality, potential political implications, collaborative music making as methodology, and disclose the audiovisual services that helped to fund this work.

Chapter Four examines Shetland’s sociomusical *sprees* phenomena, and how *spreers* articulate the epistemological principles informing this tradition. Through the life stories of newcomers Gemma and Kirsty, and reflections on various examples and personal experiences, we learn how Shetland *spreers* accommodate incoming musicians and musics through the principles of mutual character appreciation, horizontality, and resourcefulness.

Chapter Five compares two large scale projects: the National Theatre of Scotland's *Ignition*, and the locally conceived *Back from Beyond*, from participants' perspectives. I describe how Shetland's involved inhabitants drew on social resources, face-to-face conviviality, and honesty to achieve 'creative multiplicity'. By following traditional epistemological principles, such as resourcefulness and horizontality, *Back from Beyond* managed, with a fraction of the cost, to outdo and outlast a 'national' theatre company. I argue that detached professional attitudes, common in the entertainment industry, are antithetical to the face-to-face, dialogical openness, honesty, and conviviality of epistemologies based on interpersonal knowledge and nuance of character appreciation.

Chapter Six engages questions of creativity, imitation, originality and musical training. I consider the role of musical experimentation, creative freedom and personal expression among young, jazz and trad influenced, Shetland musicians. Drawing analogies between indigenous storytellers, jazz musicians, and local youth, I show how Shetland's sociomusical epistemological tradition values experimentation and creative freedom.

Chapter Seven revisits core theoretical concepts, with a focus on deconstructive critical self-reflexivity, and summarises my findings. I highlight the importance of *spre* practices in the intergenerational transmission of Shetland's epistemological tradition of music making. I consider the effects of neoliberal ways of being on interpersonal knowledge, epistemological growth, mutuality and artistic freedom, connecting aspects of Epicurean *amicitia* (friendship) and horizontality with Shetland's *spreeing* tradition and its multiple lifelong connections. I propose ways of further investigating interpersonal knowledge, epistemological resonance, reverberations, tradition, and artistic freedom.

CHAPTER 1: THEORETICAL FORMULATIONS

PHENOMENOLOGY, NECESSITY and INVENTION

1.1. INTRODUCING SCENES and COMMUNITIES

In Shetland, local musicians seem to follow a general distinction between musical scene and community. The scene refers to all that is happening, including the activities of visiting artists and audiences. The sociomusical community encompasses all genres played locally, and includes everyone who is in any way musical and who maintains sociomusical relations, including inactive performers, musical and non-musical audiences and those involved with live productions.¹ For Shelemay (2011:362), who follows Straw's definition (1991:373), a music scene is 'that cultural space in which a range of musical practices coexist, interacting with each other within a variety of processes of differentiation, and according to widely varying trajectories of change and cross-fertilizations.' She argues, following Said (1990) and Shanks (1988), that the 'flexibility of "scene" makes room for musical groups that arise through different processes and for which "community" is not considered flexible enough to capture without modification' (Shelemay 2011:362). Thus, the scene refers to the flux of events taking place in Shetland whereas the sociomusical community refers to musical persons and those with whom they associate. Someone can be part of the sociomusical community without being active in the music scene, which comes to life through music making activities.² It is very likely that almost everyone living in Shetland is somehow connected to the music scene through family and friends unless they are temporary energy industry workers or tourists.

In this work, phenomenology means attention to descriptions of personal experiences of various connected actors, including the ethnographer, and commitment to engaging critically and reflexively with epistemological principles through which members of the Shetland music community organise their lives, and make sense of their own experiences

through interactions with others.³ Novelist Hermann Hesse (2000[1943]) inspired the key notion I call the sense of nuance of character appreciation and which provides a bridge between different analytical levels – from personal idiosyncrasies (a very important, valued notion in Shetland) to potentially contradictory general assertions about the collective, such as how individual locals identify with Shetland and understand it as a place with distinctive characteristics. It is important to keep in mind the potential for contradiction, even while making a case for coherence around shared principles, as I propose here. In Shetland the appreciation of individual idiosyncrasies, stories and skills is not necessarily aligned with a model of competitive individualism, but with a principle of equality and horizontality.⁴

A phenomenological perspective on musical experiences should recognise ‘the necessary emplacement of modalities of human existence within ever-shifting horizons of temporality’ (Desjarlais and Throop 2011:88). Participant experiences, as related in personal narratives or stories (Titon 1980, Cruikshank 1990, 1998) disclose foundational connections with other people, places, architectures, events, instruments, and express ‘embodied histories’ (Bourdieu 1990:56). Musical trajectories can be analysed and compared as ethnographic data linking different actors, ideas and materials with processes of enskilment and dynamic social engagement.

In this thesis, multiple personal trajectories are entangled and intertwined with one another to represent how Shetland’s sociomusical worlds are dynamically interconnected through placed, temporal and social processes that people experience as growth.⁵ This thesis contributes to anthropology with an ethnographically productive theoretical model and formulations in which the conception of epistemological harmonics is central.⁶ The resulting anthropological epistemology can be employed in the analysis of ethnographic, audiovisual, historiographic, cinematographic, artistic and other forms of sociocultural

data. In this work, the term epistemology refers to a knowledge system, and epistemologies refer to multiple knowledge systems, ways of knowing, learning and acting. By following a number of scholars and developing my own terminology, I understand a knowledge system as having several dynamic dimensions that can help us understand the formation of ethnographic subjects in fieldwork situations and in later analyses.

1.2. EPISTEMOLOGICAL POSITIONINGS

This thesis contributes to anthropology with its own formulations, ways of responding to and engaging with and reflecting on the sociomusical situations that I encountered during fieldwork. The formulations that I have constructed are founded on experiences and observations from documented field situations and narratives, avoiding what Goffman (1953:9) called bringing ‘field-data’ into a study as ‘an afterthought, merely to illustrate a point earlier arrived at’. Inevitably, however, our training precedes our coming into the field. We should be critically aware of where the ideas we adopt are coming from and how we are applying them. Our own sociocultural assumptions will always be put to the test, and that is probably why some of us pursue anthropology.

I position myself within an ethnographically oriented epistemological tradition which values listening closely to the stories in our ethnographic and cross-cultural encounters as ‘embodied knowledge’ (Goulet and Miller 2007), and developing lifelong friendships and relationships with the places and communities we engage with (see Cruikshank 1998:161, Goulet 1994, 1998, Goulet and Miller 2007, Nadasdy 2007). With time, music making became a form of ‘anthropological engagement’ (Low and Merry 2010:S207-S211). My social connections grew with the rhythms of sociomusical occasions and recurrent encounters with local friends. This manifested what Stoller called a ‘welcoming’ – ‘an opening of one’s being to the world’ that affords ‘mixing of head and heart’ (1997:xviii). I

am writing ‘in and with the facts and frameworks’ that emerged from my personal social engagement with Shetlanders, the narratives they offered, and the experiences we shared ‘in particular landscapes, emotional and social situations’ (Brady 2004:631).

1.3. THE EPISTEMOLOGICAL TRADITION of SHETLAND MUSIC-MAKING

This thesis describes how the epistemological tradition of Shetland music works, exploring its cultural ramifications, and presents evidence supporting its existence. An epistemological tradition implies the transmission of core principles that structure a way of being and acting that many local music practitioners share, and that, in this case, survives any influx of musical materials from various genres and styles into the isles and manifests itself in *sprees* related sociomusical practices. My use of the epistemological throughout this thesis refers to knowledge systems in general. Shetland’s living epistemological tradition seeks, in principle, new forms of musical expression and remains open to influences from the outside world, contradicting static models of musical traditions based on canonised repertoires. Its convivial, personal, and aesthetic flexibility, reflected also in other social interactions, is at odds with the rigidity of the hierarchical and bureaucratic managerialist, authoritarian, competitive and prestige oriented, centralised power order that is common to organisations operating in the professional entertainment industry world.

In the present model of local epistemological tradition, open principles that organise the logics of sociality and personal interactions are shared with and passed on to future generations, affording expressive fluidity and transformation (Lord 1960:100). In contrast, in a salvage-oriented model of tradition, the directive of preserving from change (implying the fear of cultural and linguistic extinction) a dominant canon and its aesthetic and expressive orthodoxies are often presupposed. As Bourdieu noted, the

conservation of the social order is decidedly enforced by what Durkheim called ‘logical conformity’, i.e., the orchestration of

categories of perception of the social world, which, being adjusted to the divisions of the established order (and thereby to the interests of those who dominate it) and common to all minds structured in accordance to those structures, present every appearance of objective necessity (Bourdieu 1984:471).

Some of the greatest practical challenges that Shetland's sociomusical tradition of conviviality and interpersonal knowledge faces are widely adopted hierarchical models and ideas of professionalism, the socially and psychologically damaging effects of imposed rules and regulations, and the potential for social disruption brought with the flow of oil and gas workers in and out of Shetland. Tourists, entertainment professionals without much local experience, but not short on assumptions about 'rural' areas and peoples, temporary and mobile oil and gas workers with similar expectations, sometimes behave with insensitivity to local values and expectations, places, interpersonal histories and social dynamics. Locals involved in the music scene are often openly at odds with such characters, even if they have been employed or are employed by the energy industry.⁷

Although tourism distorts the image of the local culture, reducing it to a consumable, stereotyped, and often perceived as patronising version, it brings business and interesting people to Shetland, whose inhabitants are often experienced travellers themselves. The epistemological tradition remains resilient despite cultural changes, by adapting to new sonic materials while keeping *spree* practices central to sociomusical practices. The case studies that I present and analyse in this thesis dwell generally upon epistemological tensions and resolutions that have coloured interactions in different creative projects and *sprees* in which I took part. Generally, *sprees* are whole nights of making and listening to music with friends and talking about life. The sociomusical *spree*, unlike Cohen's (1985) Whalsay *spree* version, is not confined to a particular island. I argue that the sociomusical *spree* is the central practice of Shetland's epistemological tradition of music making, particularly widespread among local music scene inhabitants.

The case studies I present show that the epistemological tradition of Shetland music making is living and changing while preserving with remarkable integrity its core principles – horizontality, enthusiastic support for people of all ages, genders and skill levels, interactive participation involving a large but (usually) manageable group of people, face-to-face conviviality, the fostering of interpersonal and intergenerational knowledge and nuance of character appreciation. Musicians aligned with these values are committed to making music according to such parameters, and promote harmonic epistemological resonances among themselves, coproducing timelessness. For Edith Turner, the imagination is timeless and ‘contains many different senses of time’ (1992:12). Harmonic resonances affect our sense of time, making it disappear in the grooves and flows of the moment, causing what I call timelessness, when the passage of time becomes irrelevant. An appointment with the dentist certainly does not feel like making music with friends. As Edith Turner (2012:50) notes, ‘anthropologist John MacAloon and the psychologist Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi, students in [Victor] Turner’s seminar in 1972’ were the first to use the term ‘flow’. It is a ‘state of the psyche in which our acts appear to follow each other in a united, organic way without our conscious participation’ (Turner 2012:50). According to Csikszentmihalyi, while ‘in flow we feel we are in control of the situation and yet at the same time we are fully absorbed, so that it seems to be in control of us’ (*In* Turner 2012:50). For Turner, in the flow of *communitas*, behaviour and consciousness are fused and ‘life is expanded and full of meaning’ (Turner 2012:50). In the present thesis, flow is closely linked with experiences of timelessness that take place when strong interpersonal epistemological resonance colours an interaction.

Co-participation in *sprees* with musicians from different cultural backgrounds promotes openness to new creative materials (i.e., stylistic and influential mobility), curiosity about cultural difference and personal geographical mobilities, and loyalty to

Shetland's social and geographic peculiarities. The first ethnomusicologist to visit Shetland, Patrick Shuldham-Shaw, found that Unst fiddler John Stickle 'always wanted to know' about musical materials and news from 'other places' and cultivated an 'extremely large and varied' repertoire (Shuldham-Shaw 1962:130-131). The social dynamics that feature in most sociomusical *sprees* manifest the principles of Shetland's epistemological tradition. Informal music sessions, and in particular the Shetland Folk Fest, among many other events that music scene participants organise, operate, promote and perform, follow the principles of the *sprees* form. Local businesses like High Level Music and WobblyGang, and collaborative projects like *Back from Beyond* (Chapter 5), and recurrent festivals are also attuned to these principles.⁸ They include, for instance, extensive interpersonal knowledge, intergenerational engagement, nuance of character appreciation and horizontality in power relations. Their simultaneous application results in the inclusive distribution of creative decision-making power. As Land and King show in a different setting, 'horizontal, autonomy, direct action and personal responsibility' are associated characteristics of 'non-hierarchical' organisations (2014:942).

The mythology surrounding historical characters presents them as emblematic examples of the distinctiveness of local character, reflecting the familiar appreciation that results from relationships founded upon extended interpersonal knowledge. Most prominently, multi-instrumentalist Peerie Willie Johnson (1920-2007) is often discussed as what I would describe as the quintessential embodiment of the epistemological tradition of Shetland music. One of the most striking qualities that the memory of Peerie Willie's character now epitomises, and which is an ideal value of Shetland's epistemological tradition of music-making, is a form of radical horizontality that views the other as an equal indiscriminately at first.⁹ Like a modern day Diogenes, Peerie Willie would not discriminate between the bones of aristocrats and slaves, and treated everyone as an equal,

rejecting elitism (see Bosman 2007).¹⁰ This personal characteristic manifests the principle of horizontality that the Shetland *sprees* promotes. Yet, some of those productively involved with the music scene may seek the spotlight more actively than others, becoming competitive and overstepping the horizontality principle that is founded on mutual support and encouragement, communication and cooperation. However, this ideal principle is manifested again whenever a sociomusical *sprees* is taking place. Everyone will have a say and be accounted for, recognised and respected. If, in daily life, things do not pan out as the principles of the epistemological tradition propose, everyone *is* an equal while a *sprees* is taking place.¹¹ Locals involved with music in Shetland, many of whom will become more familiar to the reader as we progress, and to whom this ethnography is highly indebted, are aware of these core principles and manifest them in their lives in their own characteristic, personal, changing, and even contradictory ways.

Strong interpersonal knowledge flows among Shetland's sociomusical scene inhabitants, developing a social sense perception attuned to the appreciation of life changes affecting others. The formation of this metaphorical sense of engagement affords the formulation of various discussions that include informal debates on how current and future events may affect the lives of their associates, whose past they understand sometimes too well. Such intimacy and familiarity sometimes compel people to move away because they feel 'claustrophobic', imagining that everyone knows and watches their every move. Many eventually spend extended periods in the outside world, forming their own perspectives on Shetland and other places through personal-social reflections on experienced differences. In this way, they extend their knowledge and shape their current perspectives.

As Lakoff and Johnson argued, the 'ability to comprehend experience through metaphor' is akin to 'a sense, like seeing, or touching or hearing' since metaphors are 'ways to perceive and experience much of the world', 'a part of our functioning' as

‘precious’ as ‘our sense of touch’ (2003:239). Science, argue Lubart and Getz (2010:287), develop with ‘the negation of “wrong” metaphors by “progressive” ones’ (Bachelard 1986, Hesse 1966, Kuhn 1993). Metaphors afford perspectives contingent on cultural contexts and ‘on the individual’s knowledge of the specific semantic domain’ (Lubart and Getz 2010:287). Thus, novel theories and formulations are often ‘rejected because the amount of information is too great or the gap is too wide between the listener’s knowledge base and the proposed idea’ (Lubart and Getz 2010:287).¹² The notion of epistemological resonance seeks to perceive, describe and understand the phenomenal effects of the conceptual environments we inhabit and grow with, learning to sense through ideas and actions. Our personal epistemologies, various aspects from multiple experiences with others and reflections, convictions, ethical principles, and logical formulations, shape our emotions, influencing our actions in the diverse situations we encounter. Epistemological resonance is grounded upon personal and social, conceptual and experiential foundations. It responds constantly to dynamics of discordance and harmonisation played out in interactions, personal reflections, inner (i.e., memory and imagination) and place based reverberations. These dynamics are inextricably linked to core epistemological principles that individuals hold and sometimes share with various, intimate and public, social circles. Indeed, feelings and thoughts are intertwined. Yet, epistemological resonance does *not* require ‘an effort at feeling-thought’ as Wikan’s resonance (1992:463), and Schutz’s (1951) ‘tuning-in’ require. As Bergson suggests, personal epistemologies are adaptations to a ‘state of reciprocal implication and interpenetration’ with the world (1944[1911]:207).

As complex systems of logical associations, epistemologies work to fine-tune our perceptions, understandings and emotions. Working like sense organ extensions, they perceive and organise social and personal phenomena through the synergies between intellect and body. Knowledge systems work alongside sense organs to filter, examine,

focus, feel, and interpret the world, social experiences, and the humans and other animals we engage with. Following Gregory Bateson's idea, I argue that, as sense organ extensions, epistemologies 'are transducers or pathways for information' (Bateson 1972:324). A transducer is a type of filter that transforms, in the case of an epistemology, experiences into organised sensorial data framed through the related conceptual formulations and principles that emerge from particular knowledge domains. Concepts, their particular aesthetic forms, and the ways in which they connect to one another, are like lenses into the world and into oneself, producing focus, direction, intent, and potential for resolution and growth, depending on what they are. For Whorf, 'metaphorical language' that seems confusing, produces 'through art, a result of far-reaching value – a deeper aesthetic sense leading toward a more direct apprehension of underlying unity behind the phenomena so variously reported by our sense channels' (1956:156). Concepts work together to inform logical formulations, strongly influencing how people organise and collaborate (e.g., a musical group, film crew, theatre production, creative project, arts agency), and how they relate to one another and feel about their interactions.

The perceptions that flow from interpersonal knowledge, and nuance of character appreciation are reinforced by many sociomusical encounters and personal-social relationships. Currently, some of the most fundamental and established, powerful representations and modes of transmission of the epistemological tradition are the sociomusical *sprees* that take place informally throughout the year, and are formally epitomised and celebrated ritually every year in the Shetland Folk Festival, which encourages musical 'all-nighters' through extended music sessions.

The ethnographic chapters of this thesis explore the shifting social dynamics and discordances that participants experienced through local projects and events, and how external organisational models challenged and contradicted local ways of organising and

interacting. By identifying epistemological principles and their corroborating ethnographic evidence, I show how locals have engaged these challenges productively and proposed their own solutions. Examples of well-attended festivals and projects organised with attention to local principles of community that I experienced include *Back from Beyond*, Shetland Folk Festival, the Accordion and Fiddle Festival, and also Glusstonberry, The Buffet Rock Festival, The High Level Music Gala Concert, and Unst Fest.

Spree practices, with their aesthetic variety (i.e., the mixing genres and styles) and multifarious social configurations, manifested through related social activities, are prime examples of harmonic, integrative, participatory, friendship-oriented, potentially transforming practices. They also afford the formation of lifetime bonds among participants and the places they inhabit to share the timelessness that *spreeing* provides.

Spree co-participation is a learning experience for the musically inclined. Younger people get to play together with more experienced players who welcome and encourage their participation. The more experienced players learn new things from one another and share various stories about things that are going on and musics that they have been discovering in their musical activities and travels. Extended periods sharing music in this way in a positive environment reinforces the attunement of participants to a shared epistemological resonance. By acting according to *spree* principles, participants filter out much of the potential for negative interactions, so creativity may flourish and be shared in the freedom that the horizontality of interpersonal knowledge and intergenerational engagement affords.¹³ They also legitimise actions that promote the sense that music making and enjoyment is something for everyone, that it can be enjoyed while parallel conversations are taking place, even among musicians, and with people walking in and out of the room, leaving or joining those having a tune as they please. There is a close similarity between the elating social effects of *communitas* (Turner 2012) and the

phenomenon of harmonic epistemological resonance that are manifested during sociomusical *sprees* in Shetland. For Edith Turner (2012:10), ‘communitas is revealed through the flow of music and harmony, often the way the joy of the community is communicated’. Communitas is a state of collective epistemological harmonisation, whereupon discordances and their effects are overshadowed, yet not erased, by a feeling of what Turner calls the ‘joy of the community’ (2012:10). One of the purposes of the epistemological tradition of Shetland music making is the reproduction of this feeling of joy, which comes into being through social connections that afford the flux of strong streams of interpersonal knowledge involving close friends, their families, and other people and places from various parts of the world.

Through participation in sociomusical *sprees* and the cultivation of genuine lifelong friendships, a resonant personal alignment with the epistemological tradition emerges and forms a sense of ‘co-alignment’ in interpersonal relationships. Thus, the community ‘searches for resonances of its entire group, together, in a celebration of our giving ourselves to each other’ (Turner 2012:206). The feeling of harmonic epistemological resonance sprouts from a ‘technical know-how’ that affords us to ‘create an intersubjective ambience in which regulated relations between one person and another flourish’ (Descola 2013:5). This ‘intersubjective ambience’ generates a groove flow among people attuned to the same, similar or compatible epistemological principles. These principles are generated and sustained logically by shared practices and the conceptual formulations that explain them, linking them to other concepts and principles. All semantic-conceptual elements in the network resonate together, from individual to individual and socially. Thus, what I call the sense of truth is the result of the holographic resonance formed by the ways in which every concept relates to every other concept through associated logical formulations.¹⁴ These are individually distinct but also relatable,

communicable, and translatable, based on personal experience and the interplay of accepted and disputed semantic definitions. Logical formulations stem from taken-for-granted core principles, producing a *sense of truth*, a powerful force behind the incorporation and naturalisation of various personal and cultural or collective assumptions. Concepts are not simply abstract mental phenomena disconnected from physical realities. The concepts we employ play a central mediating role in the embodiment of experiences that we later reconstruct and explain via epistemological formulae. Through rhythmic repetitions (i.e., knowledge groove carving), concepts and their supporting formulations crystallise as truth power and become naturalised.¹⁵ As Bourdieu noted, past experiences are active as ‘schemes of perception, thought and action’ that legitimise established practices (1990:54). In the encounter between incorporated history (*habitus*) and objectified history (*field*), perception schemes and categories manifest as a ‘feel for the game’, that is, for anticipating ‘the future inscribed in all the concrete configurations on the pitch or board’ (Bourdieu 1990:66). Adopted perception categories, theories, and tastes, afford particular feelings and thoughts, shaping one’s epistemological resonance quality.

By referring to Shetland as a community, sociomusical inhabitants weave the abstraction of community with Shetland’s undeniable physicality, organising ideas according to epistemological principles and formulae. By considering these logical formulations, their mutual associations and dissimilarities, we can appreciate how epistemological principles connect all dissimilar views to Shetland *spreeing* practices. The metaphors people use reveal how they ‘represent and think about abstract concepts’ and ‘result from literal interactions of the body with the world’ (Glenberg 2010:587). What I found in Shetland’s music scene was the ‘result of the search [for resonance] by such a body of musicians for the whole group’s alignment’ that was equally ‘overwhelming’

(Turner 2012:206).¹⁶ In other words, there is a strong relationship between the principles and theory of the *spree* and the related practices that they engender.

The different ways in which ethnographers present their data reflect their own particular theories of culture – varying anthropological epistemologies that they apply to transform information they collected in the field into social scientific terms (see Ruskin and Rice 2012).¹⁷ Therefore, ethnographers present their own views of how *culture* works through personal interpretations of materials. Whilst making sense of ethnographic materials, they apply epistemological filters and lenses, reaching explanations that previous theoretical predilections, choices, and frameworks are attuned to reproduce.

A key tension hinges upon the relationships between individuals and collectives: how can everyone be unique and yet share understandings regarding local cultural identity, or not!? As it turns out, anthropologists share an interest in sociocultural diversity and the integration of multiple modes of being and thinking about the world. The principles of translatability (i.e., semantic negotiation), multiplicity of experience, nuance of character and idiosyncrasy work together here. I follow Deleuze (1987, 1988) and Hesse (2000[1943]), who argued for anti-orthodox invention by necessity and the translatability of abstract thought. For Deleuze (1987), we should not become victims of the dreams of others, for they can take over our lives. We should resist becoming comfortable with labels such as Marxian, Foucauldian and similar cliquey markers and labels.

Deleuze (1987) argued that *necessity* should inspire us to generate, fabricate (*fabrique*), make, create, and invent (*inventer*) new theoretical concepts. Hesse realised that one's terminologies for dealing with worldly phenomena and experiences are personal and not fully transferrable. Thus, I should also 'leave it to you to do with my story whatever you like' and to 'substitute terms of your own for mine' (Hesse 2000[1943]:244-245). My intention is that readers will generate their own interpretations and build up their

own visions and theoretical images. This translation of data into presentable material is always highly personal, as the concepts and logics that readers take to heart will filter my ideas, generating anthropological reflections. We can apply different theories to the same dataset just as effectively (Barnes and Bloor 1982 *In* Bourdieu 2004:19). With this relativistic point in mind, in agreement with the ideal of anti-orthodoxy, I aim to present how my own model operates and to break it down into its elementary components.

1.4. CREATIVE-CRITICAL REFLEXIVITY: HARMONIC ORTHODOXIES and EPISTEMOLOGICAL GROWTH

Epistemological principles are never in complete and perfect harmony with one another within and outside personal ways of thinking and being. They can be in relative harmony depending on how definitions and limitations are shared. Divergent definitions are bound to generate contradictions and paradoxes in interactions – semantic confusion, tensions and uncertainties.¹⁸ The notion of epistemological discordance theorises such experiences. Orthodoxies are examples of almost complete systemic epistemological harmonisations, where the coherence between principles, logical formulations, actions, and concepts is very strong. This should make orthodoxies almost impermeable to logics that challenge their core principles. The ‘permanent revision’ to which dispositions are subjected, is ‘never radical, because it works on the basis of the premises established in the previous state’, even though *habitus* ‘change constantly in response to new experiences’ (Bourdieu 2000:161). Since Marcel Mauss’ (1973[1934]) essay on the techniques of the body, which influenced Bourdieu’s ideas on *habitus* and *hexis*, ‘there is no culture-free mode of greeting, eating, of making love, or even of attainment of physical shape and size’ (James 1996:90). ‘Bodily *hexis*’, for Bourdieu, is a ‘basic dimension of the sense of social orientation’, and ‘a practical way of experiencing and expressing one’s own sense of social

value' (1984:474). Ochs and Schieffelin conceived of '*hexis* or bodily involvement as the medium for gaining practical knowledge' (2011:13).

Orthodoxies may become powerful but are never unbreakable. With exposure to critical, discordant and reflexive principles – concepts that hold one another together coherently from completely different epistemological standpoints – orthodoxies can be dissolved, resolved, transformed, discarded or reformulated.¹⁹ The next step would be a transformation that could or not be described as epistemological growth, depending on how the elements are reformulated. An orthodox epistemological system is characterised by slow critical dynamics, with powerful central convictions and principles (e.g., 'the end of knowledge' or 'theory of everything'). According to Ingold, anthropology is 'yoked to an academic model of knowledge' that is deterministic and 'authoritative' and seeks for an ultimate 'truth' – a veritable 'dilemma' (Ingold 2011:15).

The principle of meditative and intellectual creative-critical reflexivity seeks to discover potential resolutions for discordances, achieving epistemological growth – the reformulation, through alternative formulations, of the epistemological *sense* or how we 'feel-think' (Wikan 2012) about the world, ourselves, others, our memories, experiences, and so on. In other words, the way we feel in situations is in a direct dynamic relationship with the way we understand them. This is clearly demonstrated in the relationships I have fostered during fieldwork – having arrived as a complete stranger, I later became integrated with a strong and visible section of the music scene, cutting across several genres. The contrast between how I felt on my first and on my last heavy metal event in Shetland is directly related to how little and later how well I knew those who bring the scene to life. Whereas in the first event I was on high alert, I was involved enough in the last event to know all the organisers personally (i.e., we had *spreed* together), many of the bands, and I was also performing. It was only sustained, long-term, social involvement

with individuals on a daily basis that readjusted my distorted first impressions and expectations to the realities of Shetland's sociomusical community.²⁰

By adopting anti-orthodox and open-ended epistemological principles, we can make epistemological growth possible. In other words, open-mindedness to learning new forms and expressions is more likely to lead to epistemological growth than sophisticated reformulations or orthodox re-adaptations are. Thus, epistemological growth (which ultimately affects how the world is perceived, as a sensory apparatus expansion) could be radical and deconstructive when older core principles have been completely discredited. Alternatively, it could be relatively superficial, when outlying and supporting conceptual bundles and their logics are reformulated in light of freshly accepted ideas that do not require one to discard or critically revise the primary position of the core principles in operation. For Whorf, the 'ability to conceive theories' develops from a conscious awareness of 'linguistic devices' (1940:2). Acquiring a 'larger range of relational or logical devices than are found in one's own language can augment conceptual ability and play a role in the advancement of science' (Whorf 1941 *In* Lee 1996:26). Similarly, for Deleuze (1987), philosophy is about coming up with novel concepts and formulations that make sense in our personal experiences. Whorf's reflexive linguistic thinking and relativism supports the pursuit of epistemological growth, as 'metalinguistic awareness' generates a 'reflexive impact on the overall state of rapport of an internalized linguistic system' (Lee 1996:26). However, we should keep in mind an important distinction between 'internalized linguistic system' and a principled epistemology: although both are systems of related ideas that humans connect to make sense of present realities, a linguistic system is an abstraction that is logically multifarious in potential, and amorphous until a subject uses them, manifesting an epistemology. In other words, English allows for the existence of multiple simultaneous and potentially incompatible epistemologies, whereas an orthodoxy,

be it academic, religious or professionally oriented, seeks to have a similar logical effect across multiple languages. Hence, one of the ways in which proselytising religions spread is through the translation of their sacred texts into multiple languages.

In order to harmonise words perfectly in relation to the orthodoxy and its practices, extended layers of meaning and cultural associations must be washed away, something achieved through redefinition, as in Orwell's 'Newspeak' (Orwell 1973). Then, instead of indexing and referencing cultural metaphors and situations, the same words are reconstructed to index the matrix text, the most authoritative and valued, which then becomes a solipsistic source of all logic. Similarly, people who live according to completely different epistemologies can still communicate about basic things using the same linguistic system, but as soon as they talk about their personal views on reality and life, misunderstandings can emerge, increasing the potential for discordance and also epistemological growth, critical reflection and logical reinforcement. In other words, logical challenges to core principles may also work to reinforce and refine a theory, its practices and formulations instead dismissing them.

Epistemological challenges are like barriers to be transposed, but if they dissolve core principles, rendering them suddenly obsolete, the whole logical structure holding the knowledge system together can collapse, leading to major epistemological reformulations. Challenges and discordances drive processes of epistemological growth and transformation. Bourdieu (1988, 1990) promoted discordances as critical reflexivity on naturalised schemas, and Bateson in the 'threat of chaos' involved in shifting a 'whole system of abductions' (1979:143). After epistemological reformulations, operational core principles are fundamentally changed. The actual changes involved can be analysed as aspects of *habitus*, expressed through *praxis*, and bodily *hexis* in time and space.

1.5. *CREATIVE FREEDOM and EPISTEMOLOGICAL GROWTH*

This thesis deals with questions of creativity, improvisation and imitation, because they were central to the narratives I collected in Shetland. These questions are of great analytical relevance in studies of sociomusical practices, providing a nuanced departure from Ingold and Hallam's (2007) discussion of imitation, improvisation, and creativity. In Shetland, creative experiences were entangled with the feeling of freedom and the impression that one is having liberty to choose.²¹ Creative freedom is a delicate feeling. It can easily be spoiled by hierarchical and divisive relationships in artistic contexts. Definitions of creativity have been proposed and debated for decades. Inspired by the synthetic-transcendental principles found in *The Glass Bead Game* (Hesse 2000[1943]), I critically engage the discordances from competing positions on creativity.

For Ingold and Hallam, creativity and 'cultural improvisation' are inextricably linked (2007:20). Improvisation, they argue, is a social process of engagement 'configured, narrated and reflected upon in discourse' (Ingold and Hallam 2007:20). In this sense, the production of 'anthropological scholarship' involves improvisational creativity (Ingold and Hallam 2007:21). For them, improvisation is *generative*, giving 'rise to the phenomenal forms of culture' that people experience; *relational*, as it is 'continually attuned and responsive to the performances of others', and *temporal*, as it 'embodies duration' (Ingold and Hallam 2007:1).²² Ingold and Hallam (2007:2) challenge Liep's (2001) static binary distinction between 'conventional' and 'true' creativity by reinstating Bruner's (1993:326) position: that people construct 'culture as they go along' and respond 'to life's contingencies'. I agree that improvisation 'is the way we work' (Ingold and Hallam 2007:1), to express personal and social epistemologies. Yet, I analyse other ways of linking improvisation with creativity, by addressing relationships between imitation, creative freedom, power dynamics, personal growth, voice, character, originality, and

various nuances, intensities, and degrees of creativity. I focus on social-historical tensions in the jazz world, and on conceptions and experiences of creativity that I encountered among Shetland musicians, in order to address the question of freedom, imitation, and creativity in musical practice. For Wilf, Lévi-Strauss ‘problematized the Romantic idea of the free and autonomous creative agent’ with the *bricoleur*, who works with a ‘catalogue of a previously determined set consisting of theoretical and practical knowledge, of technical means, which restrict the possible solution’ (Lévi-Strauss 1966:19 *In* Wilf 2014:399). Here, improvisation involves the ‘selection and recombination’ of ‘building blocks’ that conform to ‘culturally prescribed parameters of style’ (Gell 1998:215, Liep 2001:2, Nettl and Russell 1998, Selfbridge-Field 2001, Lord 1960 *In* Wilf 2014:398-399).

According to work in the cognitive sciences, creativity ‘ultimately depends on the mental experience of individual minds – both for its manifestation and appreciation’ (Gardner 1993 *In* Brand 2013:229). Gardner (1993) found that ‘problem solving in general can be improved by the use of relevant analogies, similes, and metaphors’ (*In* Brand 2013:230). In Gardner’s (1993) study of creative genius, which focused on the works and accomplishments of ‘Kepler, Galileo, Newton, Picasso, Leonardo da Vinci, Einstein and Michelangelo’, the ‘comparison processes underlying metaphors and analogies figure prominently’ (*In* Brand 2013:230-231). People of all ages ‘tend to be influenced by their current conceptual knowledge structures and reach beyond these constraints only with difficulty’ (Brand 2013:231). Further, the ‘accumulation of ‘vast amounts of knowledge’ can afford ‘creative breakthroughs’ (Winner 2000 *In* Brand 2013:231). Hence, the pursuit of conceptual variation and exposure to different ways of negotiating everyday phenomena symbolically can generate novel insights *considered* creative. Studies on cognition and creativity view conceptual combinations as social inventiveness, revealing the ‘salience of

diversity in experiences and abilities within and across individuals in providing the fertile conditions necessary for the occurrence of useful combinations' (Brand 2013:231).

In Shetland, social support and personal encouragement provide the grounding for genuine creative experiences to emerge from and to flow with feelings of freedom.²³ For Wikan, the 'key concept "emotion"' should be substituted with 'feeling-thought' or 'feeling-thinking' (2012:317). My research suggests that feelings and thoughts emerge and change in response to immediate social worlds and according to personal epistemological conditions. Among Shetland's sociomusical scene inhabitants, feelings and thoughts that highlight the mutual appreciation of character and the comforting familiarity of interpersonal knowledge are aligned with the principles of the epistemological tradition and the harmonising effect of the sociomusical *spree*.

1.6. NUANCE of CHARACTER, JAZZ and CREATIVE CONSTRICTION

Many jazz performers and connoisseurs (in Shetland and elsewhere) believe that institutionalised insistence on imitation within a competitive educational system, and the cloning type of improvisation this system engenders, has a limiting effect on students' personal sense of creativity, emotional and expressive freedom. This problem, which Wilf (2012) does not consider, compels us to nuance Wilf's use of Ingold and Hallam's (2007) conceptualisation of the relationships between imitation, creativity and improvisation.

My fieldwork in Shetland revealed a challenge to the notion that imitation is necessarily creative in a personal sense, for both jazz players and jazz appreciators. It is acceptable that reading someone else's notes from a score is creative, in the sense that it brings something out into the world, generating a phenomenon that can be experienced anew every time. Yet, if we read same Shakespeare poem a hundred times, we interpret more than invent. Our interpretation may be inventive and unique, but the words are still

Shakespeare's. We could whisper or shout the same text with various different intonations, voices and emotions (see Lynch 2001).²⁴ We could enjoy playing the same song hundreds of times, feeling something different every time. Yet, we may also wish to grow beyond our current repertoires, and restrictions that lead to feelings of creative discomfort, time drag and boredom (e.g., restriction to stylistic canon, genre, pressures of parents, directors, teachers and conductors). 'Parental expectations for musical behavior', argued Csikszentmihalyi, 'often create great stress, and sometimes a complete breakdown' (1990:112). Children whom parents force to play piano or fiddle, and do repetitive drills and scales, often lose interest in playing music altogether (Csikszentmihalyi 1990:112).²⁵ Standardised and authoritarian teaching strategies often make playing music feel like a chore. Project participant and musical collaborator Hayden Hook reported feeling 'bored' and 'constricted' while 'having to play what's on the music all the time' playing cello in an orchestra at a specialised musical high school in Aberdeen. He is now a jazz student at the Amsterdam Conservatorium, where I visited him in October 2013, and filmed his very first recital for the other students and teaching staff. For him, the programmatic style of teaching institutionalised in jazz programs can be just as problematic as in classical music education – the standardisation of drills, and the regimen of transcribing solos in order to perform them and have them judged goes against his sense of creativity and freedom. Brandon Cole, who was about to become a film student in Stirling at the time, asked his musician friends, Norman Willmore, Joe Watt, Hayden Hook and Lewis Murray, whether 'that kind of intense musical tuition almost makes you want to do something else?' Joe laughs, 'yeah' and Norman proposes that 'you just want to break the rules' especially as 'a teenager as well'. Still, Norman loves 'classical music so much as well' as doing jazz gigs.

Educators, musicians, and scholars recognise the institutionalisation of jazz in school programs as a problem rather than a development because it usually requires students to

assimilate a ‘conservative mythology surrounding the music’s development and their relation to that narrative’ (Bakkum 2013:50). This institutionalisation of jazz education represents also a break from an epistemological tradition that valued the informality of apprenticeship learning alongside more serious informal studies and plenty of gigging and being involved with the worlds of other musicians – the social setting outside the protection of academic institutions. This is far from being news. Not only jazz started with and developed into its so-called classical period (roughly from the 1940s to the 1960s) through a tradition of master-apprentice relationships and conviviality – a highly social mode of learning and sharing skills – but also many musicians in jazz history have made stances against imitation. Lester Young, for instance, felt he had to change his way of playing all the time, because he felt uneasy and constricted when others imitated him so well. So Lester had to leap forward. ‘I try not to be a repeater pencil’, Lester Young once remarked (Porter 1981:12). For many jazz musicians, nuance of character, creativity, and originality are linked, and they shun imitation. However, the practice of quoting is different, as in scholarship. Master improvising musicians often learn conventions in order to break and eventually unlearn them, so that they can achieve a sense of freedom through mastery of their personal relationship with the form. The solo is among the most important, pleasurable, and difficult aspects that jazz improvisational practices offer for our understanding and appreciation and also as path for developing a sense of personal voice and character in relation to other musicians.

CHAPTER 2: HISTORY and LITERATURE REVIEW

MUSICAL ANTHROPOLOGY in SHETLAND

2.1. INTRODUCING SHETLAND STYLE MUSIC MAKING

As Campbell (1997:13) noticed, ‘music making in Shetland’ is ‘of a particularly high-quality.’²⁶ ‘Shetland undoubtedly has a reputation among ‘those living in and outside the islands’ (Campbell 1997:22). The proportion of proficient performing musicians in Shetland’s population has no parallel in the United Kingdom and possibly anywhere else.²⁷ The vast majority of experienced Shetland music makers and performers are not professional musicians, although some make a living teaching and performing alongside other activities. The widespread nature of ‘high quality’ musicality among Shetlanders whose primary professions do not involve music making still puzzles locals, even active music scene participants. Some readily propose that there ‘are no professional musicians in Shetland’. Bryan Peterson, then the Music Development Officer for Shetland Arts Development Agency (SADA), told me that it would be important to understand how and why Shetlanders become so musical.²⁸ My answer to this question comes from the analysis of the Shetland *spre* and the principles of the local epistemological tradition. Locals who wish to become professional musicians (as many in their late teens and early twenties do) must try their luck in cities like Glasgow, Edinburgh and London. This sociocultural phenomenon has never been studied in detail. My fieldwork sought to address this challenge. This ethnography contributes to answering this question, through participation in musical projects, festivals and events, and through interviewing a number of Shetlanders about their musical trajectories, use of technologies, with an emphasis on mobilities (of people, technologies, instruments, ideas and influences).

The opening of the Mareel venue on August 25th 2012 in Lerwick marked the beginning of an important moment in Shetland’s artistic history. Mareel is an architectural

hub of mobility and creativity, showcasing local and visiting musicians and visual artists, hosting workshops and university-level arts and music classes, showing mainstream and alternative films, and having the capacity to broadcast and record concerts and events. Mareel is, overall, a social and musical place central to this project. Mareel cost over 12 million pounds sterling and its design went through a consultation process that most locals who attended found to be spurious and corrupted by egocentric architects and other commercial interests. We can certainly confirm that, for most sociomusically involved locals, the consultation process for Mareel, as would be expected in architectural projects of that size in the neoliberal age, at least when it comes to taking into consideration the positions of experienced local musicians and sound engineers, was a sham. Despite all of its shortcomings, architecturally and organisationally, Mareel is a place that promotes learning music and production skills, live sound engineering, recording, and performance. As such, it is invaluable to the community, potentially affording access to some of the latest technologies of sound production and to local experts on music making, recording and performance. Modifying SADA's prescriptive and hierarchical organisational model to follow local principles would lead to improvements. Alternatively, having been founded on principles of trust and horizontality, local models achieve the distribution of creative decision-making power and interpersonal knowledge. The business model that SADA adopted during my residence in Shetland did not follow these local principles.

Some pointed to the irony that a number of design mistakes became ongoing production issues at Mareel but its architects were still nominated for a prize. The main front bathrooms share walls with the concert hall, so one hears the closing of doors and flushing of toilets during a concert or recording session in the auditorium. Mareel became the focal point of an impassioned, ongoing, socioeconomic and political controversy regarding arts investment in times of austerity, budget cuts, and country halls with pressing

economic issues. Following the principle of resourcefulness, many local musicians, intellectuals, families, groups and working people value Mareel and visit the facility daily, undaunted by controversies. There, they attend classes, watch films, meet with friends and musicians for tunes and gossip, or just have a coffee or a drink while enjoying the view of the sea and conversations. In my experience, Mareel worked as a social meeting place, where I could be certain someone I knew would show up anytime.²⁹

As Campbell (1997:13) pointed out, ‘whilst Shetland is often associated primarily with traditional music, there is in fact a very diverse music scene in the islands with individuals of all ages being involved in a broad range of musical genres’. My preliminary engagement with the music scene in Shetland unveiled a complementarity of styles and instrumentations greater than the fabled quibble between fiddles and accordions, old and present ‘fiddle traditions’. Musicians that play recent and ‘old’ Shetland tunes in the ‘traditional’ style may also be involved with rock, metal, punk, funk, jazz, bluegrass, and more.³⁰ In the late 1990s, ‘country music’ was ‘especially popular’ and ‘rock, classical, folk and blues, jazz, techno and world music’ had a ‘relatively high profile’ (Campbell 1997:13). Pam Swing, whose thesis focused on fiddle teaching in Shetland schools, noticed that ‘[m]ost musicians in Shetland have an eclectic repertoire drawn from many sources’ (1991:290). Many Shetlanders agree that ‘the image of music in Shetland’ found in ‘tourist brochures’ highlights ‘fiddling’ disproportionately and should be ‘updated’ to include ‘the diversity of musical activity in the islands’ (Campbell 1997:23).

Before a performance at the Islesburgh Community Centre hall, one of the older organisers of the 25th Accordion and Fiddle Festival disclosed his love for the Australian hard rock band *AC/DC*, very popular throughout Shetland. Musical practices add layers of permeability to the symbolic boundaries that Byron (1983) and Cohen (1985, 1987) found in studies that did not focus on music making as a nexus of community. Throughout

Shetland, music making brings people from all available ages, genders, socioeconomic status and cultural background together. The traditional repertoire is by no means bound to Shetland compositions. This ethnography explores mobile social relations in Shetland's music scene through co-participation in music making processes, and attention to how local music makers and lovers talk about their trajectories and creatively engage the world with sociomusical practices.

2.2. POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS, ECONOMY and TRANSPORTATION

Shetland is the northernmost archipelago in the United Kingdom, with a population of about 23 thousand residents, where music making is highly valued as an important symbol of local tradition and identity.³¹ A flight from the Scottish mainland takes about 1.5 hours and the ferry crossing from Aberdeen takes about 12 hours. There are 15 inhabited islands in Shetland, and more than 100 in total, covering 1,468 km² and approximately 2,702 kilometres of coastline (SIC 2011:4). At the time I first arrived in Shetland, in October 2012, the latest statistical information accounted for 22,767 people in the entire archipelago (SIC 2011:11). There are no reasonably accurate censuses for the Shetland population 'before the mid-eighteenth century' and the maximum-recorded number was 31,670 in 1861 (Thomson 1983:150-151). For about a century until 1969, Shetland's population declined, resulting in a 'predominantly elderly age structure' (Thomson 1983:150). After falling to 'nearly 17,000 in the mid-1960s', Shetland's population 'rose by 31% between 1971 and 1981 as a direct result of oil related activity' (SIC 2010:9). With the 'end of oil construction activity' in the early 1980s the population declined, and in the 'early 1990s the population level became fairly stable' and remained so until now (SIC 2010:9). The largest island is the 'Mainland' (899 km²) where Lerwick (pop. 9,164), Scalloway (pop. 3,067), Levenwick (pop. 2,689), and Brae (pop. 2,545), Shetland's largest

settlements, are located (SIC 2011:4-11). Yell (212 km², pop. 1,030) is the second largest island, followed by Unst (120 km², pop. 623), Fetlar (38 km², pop. 86), Bressay (28 km², pop. 384) and Whalsay (23 km², pop. 1,130), according to *Shetland in Statistics* (SIC 2011:4-11). Papa Stour is the least populous island, with 24 people in 2001; about 100 people lived there in 1931 and, after World War II, only 55 (SIC 2010:10).

In 1998, Shetland's economy was valued at £761 million (SIC 2010:11). This was revised in 2005, according to the 'combined total output of all economic sectors' to £705 million (SIC 2010:11). In 2011 the unemployment rate was the lowest in Scotland at 1.3%, contrasting with Edinburgh (3.2%), Glasgow (6.3%), the national averages in Scotland (4.3%) and Great Britain (3.8%) (SIC 2011:12). Shetland's Gross Regional Domestic Product was revised to £333,403,150, equating 'to a GRDP per capita of £15,245' (SIC 2010:11). Oil throughput at the Sullom Voe terminal peaked in 1984 at 58 million tonnes or 1.2 million barrels per day (SIC 2011:27). By 2009, it fell to 197,074 barrels per day, and by 2010 it grew slightly to 206,785 barrels per day or about 10 million tonnes, less than 1/5 of the 1984 record (SIC 2011:28).¹ As oil production declined, tourism grew. Visitors to Shetland went from spending £6.9 million in 1986 to £16.4 million in 2006 (SIC 2011:26). Whereas 3,564 cruise liner passengers arrived at Lerwick harbour in 1981, there were 30,843 in 2010, an 865% increase in 29 years (SIC 2011:26). The 'creative industries' in Shetland were estimated to generate £25 million annually, with 367-460 jobs (EKOS 2008:3). Scottish government and European Union agricultural assistance grew from £2.22 million in 1986 to £9.27 million in 2010 (SIC 2011:24).

Sheep production has led the agricultural economy for the last 25 years with more than double the value of all other sectors combined – £3.28 (out of £6.02) million in 1986, growing to £5.10 (out of £8.89) million in 2010 (SIC 2011:24). Cattle production, in the same period, grew from £0.86 million to £1.56 while liquid milk production grew from

£0.90 to £1.47 million (SIC 2011:24). The fishing industry caught 86,752 tonnes of fish with a value of £80,494,357 in 2010 (SIC 2011:17). The estimated turnover value in fish processing grew from £25 million in 1991 to £162 million in 2010 (SIC 2011:20). If all sectors combined yield about £705 million, fishing and fish processing £242 million, agriculture £8.89 million, the creative industries £25 million, much of the remaining £429 million should be from oil.

There are 1,047.6 km of roads in Shetland, and 15,514 registered vehicles (SIC 2011:34). The southernmost settlement accessible by road is Sumburgh in the mainland, 40 km from Lerwick, and the northernmost is Haroldswick in the isle of Unst, 88 km from Lerwick (SIC 2011:4). In 2009, 84,679 people visited the Shetland Museum and Archives (SIC 2011:26). There were 403,483 bus passengers in 2010 (SIC 2011:34). In 2009, inter island ferries carried 795,500 passengers and 371,451 vehicles, 260,399 passengers to Yell, 205,000 to Bressay, 162,541 to Whalsay, and 157,778 to Unst (SIC 2011:32). In 2010, 112,241 passengers and 17,427 accompanied cars journeyed from Aberdeen to Lerwick via NorthLink ferry services (SIC 2011:35). Shetland airports received 424,220 passengers and 26,818 aircrafts in 2010 (SIC 2011:38). These figures indicate travelling within Shetland, to and from the outside is very common. Such movements have intensified in the 20th and 21st centuries due to technological advancements, but they were also relatively common previously through seafaring. By the early 1800s there were about 2000 Shetlanders working out at sea, travelling long distances and bringing back stories and things from other parts of the world to their families, spawning the tradition of *Hamefarins* (Johnston 2010).³² The people of Shetland have remained very mobile, and even those who have not travelled much benefit from the stories they hear and retell. The present ethnography addresses the effects of such mobilities in the epistemological tradition of Shetland music making. In general, personal mobilities generate stylistic

diversity in sociomusical interactions, shaping how people make sense of others' individual trajectories and belonging to local and international sociomusical networks.

2.3. *ETHNOGRAPHIES of SHETLAND*

The ethnographies of Shetland published in the 1980s emphasised the 'symbolic boundaries' of communities within Shetland, such as Whalsay and Burra, and focused on the impacts of the oil industry and models of development on former social structures (e.g., Byron 1983, Renwanz 1981, Cohen 1987, Church 1989). Music making is not a focal point in these works. Swing (1991) is the last ethnomusicological thesis based on long-term fieldwork in Shetland, conducted in the late 1970s. Like its predecessors, Cooke (1986) and Shuldham-Shaw (1947, 1962), it focuses on fiddling. Elements of the epistemological tradition of Shetland music making are present in these works. For instance, Shuldham-Shaw observed that Unst fiddler John Stickle 'was always interested in people and in what was going on not only locally but in the world outside, and was particularly pleased if the outside world took an interest in Shetland and its traditions' (1962:131).

Decades later, Swing's (1991) interview with a young Debbie Scott revealed how Tom Anderson's canonization of tradition was shaped by static stylistic models and restrictions that romanticised the heroic role of the fiddler. The result was a restrictive canon-based reconstruction of a romanticised 'fiddle tradition' at the expense of a complex sociomusical world and the living arts scene in Shetland. This multiform world of art making in Shetland is also entangled with economic, political, and market pressures. Currently, austerity measures have been curtailing access to public funds for the arts, intensifying the competition for resources and the need for resourcefulness in a time of scarcity. This generates an interesting, productive tension in Shetland, because, for local musicians who are infused with the spirit of the Shetland *sprees*, it is important to foster an

environment of mutual support, collaboration, horizontality in personal relations and the appreciation of character, running against the individualistic competitive imperatives of the market.³³ Just as there are competing ideas of creativity that have to be discussed in detail in this thesis, there are also different senses of individuality that emerge from my analysis – the neoliberal type of individualism that emerges in competitive market based relationships, and the individualism that emerges from the sense of nuance of character appreciation featured in sociomusical *sprees* practices.

By the late 1990s, the construction of the fiddle as Shetland's instrument and the fiddler as the carrier of tradition had achieved dominance, affecting the school system, curtailing children's access to different instruments, restricting their choices. Shetlanders felt that there was 'significant need' for 'guitar tuition in schools' to 'complement existing traditional fiddle tuition' (Campbell 1997:20). Shetland's 'reputation for high quality guitar playing', she wrote, was largely 'attributable to Peerie Willie Johnson' (Campbell 1997:20). According to Pam Swing, Tom Anderson made stylistic choices to define the Shetland tradition based on 'personal preferences' (1991:260). However, she concluded that 'the tradition is shaped' by those preferences (1991:260). This formulation restricts the notion of tradition to a collection of stylistic elements, missing the resilience of the epistemological tradition of Shetland music making, in principle irreducible to stylistic choice or repertoire restrictions bound to a single instrument. As King (2011) shows, performing traditions are growing and changing, alive and entangled with the choices of those who live them. Genuine traditions in 'Sapir's sense', King's research suggests, encourage 'individuals to fulfil their maximum potential through harmonious pursuit of a living tradition' (King 2011:102). We may ask, how does the 'epistemological' modify tradition in this formulation? Moreover, how does it differ from a 'musical' or 'cultural' tradition? Although an epistemological tradition is a sociocultural phenomenon, the point

is to shift the focus from the exclusivist aesthetic bias that is common in salvage ethnography studies of musical traditions and to highlight the importance of ways of being, thinking, learning, and understanding the world that are passed on in a process of personal growth.³⁴ Focus on the epistemological frees us from concentrating solely on the aesthetic elements of particular artistic traditions, highlighting the potential of resilient principles to provide ideal ground rules for social interactions. Furthermore, it makes sense in Shetland's context, where idiosyncrasy complicates such facile definitions of collective style, and people 'remember the noted fiddlers of the past as distinctively individualistic' (Cohen 1987:191). This indicates that locals recognise and value the particular characteristic, personal styles of each player. So the question arises, 'if everyone develops their own very particular way of playing music, what do Shetland musicians have in common?' The short answer is their devotion to the sociomusical *spree* and the epistemological tradition it represents, as Cohen (1985) recognised in Whalsay without putting much emphasis on its sociomusical aspects.

Within an epistemological tradition that emphasises personal character, voice, variation, and experimentation, the artificial solidification of tradition into a collection of exclusivist stylistic-aesthetic elements will always fail, because that puts on hold the development of character in the present, in relation and conversation with the living world. The notion of an authoritatively defined aesthetic canon is simply incompatible with the principle of experimentation that is key to understanding Shetland's epistemological tradition of music making. Moreover, I am not trying to define a Shetland way of life, but demonstrate how, *within* the Shetland music scene, the sociomusical *spree* and its associated institutions and expressions (i.e., festivals and creative hubs such as homes and schools, country halls, etc) promote several epistemological principles that insiders to the scene understand and agree with but do not often articulate – we are dealing with what

locals refer to as ‘unwritten rules’. This does not mean there are no deviations from these principles, but they remain historically resilient because they provide an invaluable platform for developing musicianship, understanding and appreciating what others can contribute, feeling connected and relevant, and free to experiment. Adopting these principles helps one to relieve and resist the pressures that dominate the competitive music business, where being successful often means making money. This means that *spreers* experience a sense of creative freedom, through social encouragement and support, and compose original songs and tunes that are personally and socially meaningful, and therefore valuable enough, regardless of commercial success.³⁵ Anderson’s impetus to restrict Shetland’s tradition to a canon evokes a patriarchal model of priestly authority that parallels the tensions that have emerged in discussions surrounding relationships between jazz history canonization and institutionalised educational curricula. There, ‘jazz ideologues’ proclaimed the music to be a ‘fixed culture’, defined by exclusivist and deterministic stylistic requirements, and groomed it according to the expectations and ‘homogenizing tendencies of the marketplace’ (Nicholson 2005:238-241).

In Shetland, however, as Black (1995) suggests, the arrival of the oil industry fuelled a redefinition of Shetland way of life, compiled from age-old practices. For her, ‘the advent of North Sea Oil, and the perceived threats it brought’ led to the ‘fabrication’ of a Shetland ‘way of life’ (Black 1995:271). The practice of ‘cultural accounting’, she argues, started when Shetlanders began wondering about the ‘possibility of structural change’, and began defining ‘familiar norms’ they considered ‘worthy of retention’ (Black 1995:271). Renwanz (1981:2) argued that there were unfounded fears and anxieties in Shetland at the time of the ‘oil boom’. She believed the ‘slogan’ of a ‘Shetland way of life’ was invented to counteract such fears and to boost Shetland’s image in the national and international political stage, in a form of identity politics (Renwanz 1981:3). However, when she asked

residents what this threatened and disappearing Shetland ‘way of life’ was, ‘they could not answer’ (Renwanz 1981:4). In respect to the music scene, the first wave of oil exploration in Shetland had different effects. Oil money and opportunities brought new musicians to Shetland in the 1970s and allowed locals to invest in musical equipment that they could not afford previously. Differently from the situation I encountered, oil workers in the 1970s and 1980s were often housed away from Lerwick, which spared the public live music scene from the social pressures they face on account of their presence (e.g., Bevington 2014, Johnson 2014, Cope 2015).³⁶ Other European communities have also strategically constructed localist identities to boost cultural capital and attract investment. The construction of a collective identity from the ‘top down’ has been used as a powerful branding tool for increasing the ‘visibility’ of an area, ‘selling local products, attracting outside resources, and engendering a stronger sense of identity’ (Lee et al. 2005:274).

Black’s research relied on long and demanding, gendered questionnaires rather than on participation with the local community, leading her into adopting the position that ‘there was no such thing as a way of life in Shetland’, but ‘numerous different ways of life, with various occupations’ that have ‘meant different things to different people’ (1995:270-271).³⁷ Black’s list of ‘various occupations’, however, curiously excluded music, but included ‘crofting, working as a clerk and as either a docker or fish packer, involving very different routines’ (1995:271). Yet, in Shetland, music can be an occupation – there are many music teachers and sound engineers – and a form of leisure that requires a lot of dedication. Fiddler and fine artist Gemma Graham, who moved to Shetland in the fall of 2013 from Fife in the Scottish mainland, noted how locals like Gary, Lewie and Erik Peterson, as well as Maurice Henderson, are known as musicians, not for the occupations they have – Erik is also known as Shetland’s goalie. Gary is one of the most recognisable characters in Shetland, plays constantly with *No Sweat* and *Hom Bru*, multiple *Up Helly*

Aa Jarl Squads, and so on, but works at the harbour. Their way of life is much more aligned with music making than with their occupations, which become almost irrelevant – they are simply ways of dealing with the practicalities of the world and maintaining a level of economic independence.³⁸ What is certain is that they are living like musicians, that they are all active participants in pretty much every Shetland Folk Festival, and that they go out of their way for having a *spre* together and with others. Black, however, conflates the notion of a ‘way of life’ with ‘occupation.’³⁹ In my personal experiences, every musician revealed having their own personal way of life, while sharing music and having *sprees* together as the most valuable and necessary local-traditional sociomusical practice.

Black’s (1995) results exemplify the potential pitfalls of prescriptive research that relies on structured questionnaires rather than on direct experience and participation. The fact remains that sustained personal participation in local social life, attention to what people do and how they interact with one another, in addition to what they have to say about what they are doing, reveals social patterns that cannot be appreciated from the predetermined and prescriptive framework of standardised questionnaires, which are easier to process because of their formal, administrative and bureaucratic nature. Alternatively, living among research participants bears the potential for thickening the researcher’s social engagement to the point that previous expectations are challenged. Personal, daily involvement, reveals social relations and nuances of character that could not be appreciated from the perspective of the detached ‘questionnaire investigations’ that appear to presuppose ‘uniformities which perhaps do not really exist’ (Leach 1967 *In* Malkki 2007:167). My fieldwork in Shetland found a ‘wide range of sociological phenomena which are intrinsically inaccessible to statistical investigation of any kind’ (Leach 1967 *In* Malkki 2007:167). However, when those phenomena are identified, their existence could

be easily confirmed using a statistical method, like trying to find out how many active Shetland musicians are involved with *spree*-oriented sociomusical practices.

Black insists that the Shetland ‘way of life’ was a ‘fabrication’ spawned by irrational fears – the threat of cultural dissolution with ‘the advent of North Sea Oil’ (1995:271). She focuses on an effort at cataloguing practices rather than understanding the sociocultural relations between Shetlanders and the world. Similarly, the cataloguing quest Tom Anderson spearheaded in Shetland ironically sought to protect a living tradition from its supposed imminent extinction, by curtailing and restricting young musicians’ inner urge to explore fresh creative materials and experiment with new technologies. It reflected a retro mood that was out of tune with an anarchic and sponge-like epistemological tradition best characterised by Peerie Willie Johnson’s non-judgmental personality and how it still resonates with people. Cohen (1987:191) reported that Whalsay fiddlers ‘distance themselves from the style established in Lerwick by the celebrated Tom Anderson, as rather formal and overtly strict in tempo’. However, there were other influential musicians active in Lerwick whom Cohen (1987) does not mention, and there were more musical interactions between Whalsay and Lerwick than Cohen implied. While Tom Anderson is not considered an outstanding fiddler in technical and stylistic terms like Willie Hunter, he was the key player in institutionalising fiddle instruction in local schools, and also one of the original founders of the Shetland Folk Fest. Anderson’s version of tradition is sustained by the song archive he personally collected and the publications under his name.

After Anderson’s death, the archive became the object of a dispute that many locals still lament as messy and unnecessary. Some experienced local musicians have pointed out that Anderson’s occupation as an insurance agent influenced his cataloguing method and also his conception of tradition, attuned to the salvage efforts of the period. Eventually, Anderson enforced a stylistically restricted version of the ‘old tradition’ which drove away

some of his own select ‘star’ students, such as Catriona McDonald and Debbie Scott, as Swing shows in detail (1991:272-309). Debbie Scott learned the fiddle from Tom Anderson in Lerwick from age eight, kept taking lessons from Anderson after her parents moved back to Papa Stour, and was living on her own in Lerwick at age sixteen (Swing 1991:297). At around 1984-1985, Debbie Scott, then sixteen, enjoyed ‘rock and punk’, and her favourite fiddler was Rodney Miller from New England (Swing 1991:302-303). Scott thought that Tom Anderson was ‘trapping’ younger students by not allowing them to ‘do their own thing’ (Swing 1991:299). Anderson’s stylistic demands contradicted his claim that there is a ‘living tradition of Shetland fiddle music’ (Anderson and Swing 1978:iii) because it sought to restrict and bind rather than foster the growth of what is in fact an epistemological tradition characterised by its ability to transform and reinterpret new materials, in a constant search for novelty of expression and immediacy in the present.

Anderson would react negatively when young fiddlers stretched outside the stylistic limits he imposed, but characters like Peerie Willie and Billy Kay would encourage them to experiment. Debbie Scott ‘worked on developing her own personal style’ without ‘specializing in any style’ (Swing 1991:302). Contentious from the start, the notion that Shetland’s music students should conform to repertoire and stylistic restrictions that supposedly represented Shetland’s culture, contradicted the longstanding epistemological tradition of broadminded resourcefulness and character appreciation, and ultimately failed. After all, as Billy Kay told me, Stevie and Amanda, his friend Peerie Willie, at present the most iconic of Shetland’s musicians – a guitar player and bassist, not a fiddler – was ‘always experimenting’. Anderson’s tradition could remain alive only within the parameters that he himself prescribed, which included the aesthetic imperative that experimentation with other instrumentations and styles threatened real tradition.

For Robert Innes, Stirling University's Director of Continuing Education, '[f]iddle music is the music of the Shetland islands', the one that is 'descriptive of the land, the sea, and the sky' (Innes *In* Anderson and Swing 1979:i). This hyperbolic view supports Anderson's recapitulation of tradition. The 'essence of Shetland', fiddle music, for Innes, is an 'encapsulation of an island way of life', and contains the power to describe 'the sea with the evening serenity of a still voe or the majesty of crashing equinoctial rollers' and 'the splendour of a summer sunset' and 'the spell of scurrying winter clouds' (Innes *In* Anderson and Swing 1979:i). This lyrical, romantic formulation suggests that by just playing the notes off the page on a fiddle, Shetland's landscapes and distinctive 'island way of life' would magically manifest to our delight. Yet, when we look at the themes for songs written by living and dead Shetland composers, even in the fiddle tradition, they are directed to friends and family. For Debbie Scott (2007), the point of listening to *Selkies' Song* is to enjoy her 'dear friend' Willie's 'inimitable and unmistakable sound', who 'greatly influenced' her music and inspired her with 'humility and modesty'.

Ronström (2010:268), whose only source for Shetland music is Forsyth (2007), claimed that traditional music in Shetland 'is seen as naturally growing out of the landscape, producing a continuous musical geography of distinct local musics'. This interpretation strikes me as romantic and distant, and it does not account for the fundamental role of personal and social relations in efforts at song and tune composition and performance in Shetland. Most tunes and songs pay tribute to meaningful personal stories and characters more than they seek to describe and evoke landscapes. The notion that Shetlanders see traditional music as 'naturally growing out of the landscape' (Ronström 2010:268) is at best an exaggeration. Even the constant rhythms of boat engines are known to have helped make 'tunes fly', inspiring new compositions in Shetland (Cooke 1986:94).⁴⁰ For Ronström (2010:268), Forsyth (2007) found in Shetland a

‘traditional musical mindscape full of references to an old-fashioned world of small homesteads in remote and isolated islands.’⁴¹

Cohen (1987:191) claimed that Alan Tulloch and the fiddle maker Jimmy Arthur ‘saved the Whalsay fiddle tradition from virtual extinction under the onslaught of the ‘country and western’ craze’. However, during a visit to the Whalsay Boating Club on October 6th 2012, I found that Alan Tulloch’s repertoire consisted of Canadian and American, Appalachian and Cajun tunes. Tulloch played a similar repertoire at Cullivoe hall, in Yell, at the 25th Shetland Accordion and Fiddle Festival, and again when I watched him playing informally at the Islesburgh Community Centre in Lerwick.⁴² Cohen himself reported Tulloch’s insistence that ‘there was never any orthodoxy in Whalsay fiddling’ (1987:191). Although people ‘from other parts of Shetland may speak of a ‘Whalsa’ style’, the Whalsay fiddlers themselves ‘eschew any such notion and remember the noted fiddlers of the past as distinctively individualistic’ (Cohen 1987:191).

In the last 40 years, the main ingredient missing from ethnomusicological works and ethnographies of Shetland in general is the direct involvement with the local sociomusical scene in order to appreciate its connections and crossovers. Shetland ethnographies and other scholarly works based on questionnaires have failed to grasp the importance of the music scene in everyday Shetland life, and how social relationships fostered through sociomusical networks continually transcend class, gender, age, occupation, cultural and national divisions or boundaries. Some of the gravest threats to the nuance of character appreciation sense that grows and develops from sociomusical interactions and networks in Shetland – one of its gifts to the musical community – include the impersonal and exploitative ideologies and practices of the corporate managerial world, and the regulatory, rule-binding, bureaucratic mentality of the State.⁴³ These external forces impose a number of obstacles and barriers that restrict rather than foster people’s creative projects, local

commercial ventures, and performing opportunities. However, the resilience of the principles of Shetland's epistemological tradition of music making have been relatively successful in dealing with such challenges and their effects so far.

High Level Music's recent expansion and its success come from a significant struggle against these external forces, overcome by direct personal engagement with customers, music students, established local musicians, parents and children, and the elderly. People know they will be well received and recognised anytime they come into the store, that they can enjoy a conversation with Fiona and Brian, Arthur and Maggie and even a tune.⁴⁴ In commercial music store chains, one frequently encounters a stranger treating you like a stranger customer, who will only get the salesperson's attention by demonstrating an intention to buy something expensive. Every time that I visited High Level Music I learned something valuable about the local music community from Brian and Fiona. By making the shop like a home, they bring character to commercial town life, a character that has been watered down by the combination of dominant neoliberal models and restrictive, time-wasting regulations.

The epistemological tradition of Shetland music values the personal characters of meaningful people, their sociomusical relationships, and teaches one to appreciate their expressions in music. For those who have not lived in Shetland but visited as tourists, local traditional fiddle music may evoke the landscapes they visited in their travels through the islands, perhaps even listening to this music while travelling. We can suppose that, at least to some, listening to this music from a fiddle may bring to life memories of visited Shetland landscapes that reverberate with meaning. Yet, viewing Shetland's music as a social phenomenon adds much to the suggestion that landscapes are the main subject of this music. Shetlanders may indeed translate their personal feelings of certain landscapes into music, but the listener will not see those landscapes unless they visit and inhabit them.

Back from Beyond, the subject of Chapter 5, sponsored trips for Shetland musicians, poets, artists and film production crews to various inspiring landscapes around the islands. The resulting creative productions reflected on experiences in those places, and a public concert was arranged in which artists spoke about their travels to those places.

Shetland's traditional scene incorporates and reinterprets creative materials from various perceived origins, such as Irish, Norwegian, Appalachian, Cajun, Canadian, Country and Western, Gypsy and Jazz Standards, Bluegrass, Scottish Dance Music, reflecting a vitality of engagement with the world that is central to *spree* practices and values. For instance, the appreciation of character in other peoples and places, making, sharing, and talking about music in the moment, becoming knowledgeable about other places and cultures through travelling and family connections are all interconnected valued practices. These factors are linked to a maritime mobility, replete with influential migrations, visitations, and encounters with cultural difference, providing a sounding board for reflecting on and understanding how social background and relationship to Shetland affects the formation and appreciation of local characters.

The *spree*, as core practice and epistemological tradition, and, thematically, Shetland music, reflect personal and social relationships with local characters and people from around the world. Reflections of personal and social experiences in environments around and beyond Shetland come in the form of stories and musics shared around the table and the hearth (at least in this ethnography). The music locals make seems to be constantly celebrating and reflecting personal relationships and stories (from serious to humorous), community sociability and conviviality, important life changing events (e.g., marriages, funerals, album releases), as well as Shetland's oft revered and promoted landscape magic, but always through the lens particular experiences provide.

Swing observed students going ‘through a period of rebellion against the teaching of their fiddle instructor, especially Tom Anderson as the first step in forming their own independent approach’ (1991:276).⁴⁵ Young musicians quickly discovered music as a way to explore the world and grow, shedding the need for acting as romantic guardians of a repertoire mausoleum for a ‘disciplinary force policing creativity’ (Nicholson 2005:48). Anderson’s formulation of tradition contradicted the principles and spirit of the *sprea*. As a museum-piece compilation and restrictive model of static culture, Anderson’s reformulation strongly supported young people’s engagement with local music, which is very valuable, but it unfortunately also sought to reinforce Anderson’s recognition as the authority on Shetland’s musical tradition – a discordant mixture of community spirit and egocentrism that is perceived as distasteful from a community perspective. However, from an image-oriented marketing perspective, the internationally renowned stereotype of the Shetland fiddler is useful for attracting tourists, especially with the promotion of young and good looking fiddle champions. Thus, Anderson’s restricted traditionalism worked, albeit unwittingly, as a neoliberal marketing platform, selecting and privileging elements from Shetland repertoires and harmonising them with watered down urbanite romantic expectations and fantasies surrounding rural and faraway traditions, obscuring a thicker understanding of what is happening with Shetland’s sociomusical world and its inhabitants. As one middle-aged university educated Shetlander who grew up inspired by the British and American folk scene of the 1960s, the punk and new wave scenes of the 1970s and 1980s, Anderson’s formulaic model of ‘Fair Isle jumper-wearing uptight old men bearing fiddles and tradition’ was something to steer far away from as an adolescent. For him, it represented a retrograde and conservative traditionalism disconnected from the world, where actually important things were happening, especially beyond Shetland. ‘Traditional Shetland music’, Anderson maintained, ‘is played by some old fiddlers’, the

‘Folk Society Band and the Shetland Fiddlers Society’ (*In* Anderson and Swing 1978:v). However, the current living tradition of Shetland music, far from being a regurgitation of canonized anthologies and compositions circumscribed by strict instrumentation, stylistic limits, and songs composed by living old fiddlers, actually remains immediate and relevant to musicians’ sociomusical and personal concerns, transcending the limits of authoritarian conventions by adapting to and adopting musical ideas from the world, reflecting personal experiences and also market-imposed constraints and fashions (see King 2011).

In Forsyth’s view, Tom Anderson contributed to the development of music in Shetland with a ‘collection of traditional tunes’ and ‘an extant school fiddle program’, Willie Hunter Junior with ‘a contemporary style of fiddling influenced by the fiddling styles of mainland Scotland’, Ronnie Cooper with ‘new ideologies of tune composition’ and Peerie Willie Johnson with ‘the development of a new style of guitar accompaniment for traditional Shetland fiddling influenced by the jazz-style guitarists of the early 20th century’ (Forsyth 2007:50). However, my conversations with one of Shetland’s most experienced guitarists, Brian Nicholson, revealed that Peerie Willie’s style also drew on early American country music from Texas, not just jazz. Peerie Willie was also instrumental in popularising in Shetland the gypsy comping rhythms associated with the music of Django Reinhardt (1910-1953).

Some locals told me that Tom Anderson, in his reinvention of the fiddle tradition, ignores Ronnie Cooper’s popular tunes because of the latter’s independence. Willie Hunter Junior also taught the fiddle in Shetland schools. Moreover, Peerie Willie’s comping style influenced Ronnie Cooper’s compositions and ‘traditional’ piano comping styles.⁴⁶ Nicholson demonstrated for me on his instrument how some of Cooper’s compositions were written with particular chord progressions associated with Peerie Willie in mind.

Willie Hunter Junior provided ‘quality control’ for Cooper’s compositions, in Sunday afternoon sessions (now no longer active) at The Lounge bar in Lerwick.

Tom Anderson sought to fill a self-selected position of authority and control over a model of tradition that was discordant with the *spree*-based, charismatic, open-minded and unpretentious outlook of musicians like Peerie Willie. As fiddler Debbie Scott wrote in her CD release with Peerie Willie, *Silkies’ Song*, released after his death in 2007 – ‘Willie was totally devoid of ego’, and ‘showed the greatest humility and modesty of anyone I know’. These attitudes result from the principle of horizontality that is key to the *spree*. Debbie’s words in the liner notes reflect how the local epistemological tradition values intergenerational engagement and nuance of character – ‘Forgive the shortcomings of a young fiddler’, Debbie pleads, ‘and sit back, listen and enjoy the inimitable and at once unmistakable sound of Willie’s guitar on what was to become one of the relatively few recordings he did as main accompanist’ (Scott 2007).

Resident musicians remained closely interconnected, sharing multiple personal and sociomusical networks, and constantly engaged with a variety of musical genres, forms of instrumentation, particularities of the various different islands and places around and beyond Shetland. Most importantly, Shetland’s sociomusical inhabitants are socialised to become increasingly appreciative of complex idiosyncrasies – the nuances of character that emerge and grow in social dimension from every person through recurrent interactions. Storytelling among them often focuses on shared sociomusical experiences that carry a socially binding and harmonizing effect. This means that music making in Shetland works like an elixir for kindling personal relationships that can transcend barriers of age, gender, political affiliation, nationality, socioeconomic status, and taste, such as strict adherence to modes of instrumentation and prescribed models for traditional musical styles. This anti-hierarchical, inclusive effect, results directly from the resilience of the living

epistemological tradition – a *modus operandi* grounded on community-oriented principles that find continuous expression, renewal, and perpetuation or historical intergenerational transcendence, through a set of principle-oriented practices that I have synthesised under the rubric of the *sprees*. Many who are not instrumentalists or singers, just musical appreciators and friends, are welcomed into *sprees*. Musicians pay attention to audiences and to how they respond to their live public performances and at *sprees* hosted at local homes, and often comment on those reactions. Hosts and musicians value their presence and impressions as friends (with sincere, perhaps constructively critical assessments to share), listeners and music supporters. What I call the nuance of character appreciation is by no means restricted to musicians in Shetland. Also, musicianship in Shetland is spread throughout many professions, as Campbell (1997) shows.

The principles of the epistemological tradition of Shetland music – a valued possession and a treasure for the community’s social health – have been carefully sustained by those who embody it, and have been so far overshadowed by the historical-academic emphasis on a single instrument (i.e., the fiddle) or no instrument at all. To balance this bias, my objective is to focus on intersecting personal trajectories, collaborations, and the complexity of Shetland’s sociomusical world.

Arguably, the principles of the epistemological tradition of Shetland music making have spawned a form of kinship founded on sociomusical relations rather than bloodlines – an alternative kinship mode that works in parallel with familial connections – that seems to be in harmonic alignment with the locally held notion that, among Shetlanders, ‘everyone is somebody else’s cousin’ and other permutations.⁴⁷ This phenomenon will strike outsiders who get to know people from Whalsay, for instance, it is often meant as a joke, but not really. Whalsay, after all, and some other Shetland islands have maintained small populations for hundreds of years. Locally designed projects like *Back from Beyond* (see

Chapter 5) encourage musicians and other artists to begin fostering personal, creative and inspirational relationships with places and people around Shetland that they might not have had a chance to know before, reinforcing even further sociomusical networks and drawing special attention to the characteristics of Shetland artistic life, its personalities and surroundings. As Titon (2008:37) notes, the ‘experience of music making’ for ‘various cultures around the world’ is ‘an experience of becoming a knowing self in the presence of other becoming, knowing selves’. Instead of ‘autonomous’ selves, the ‘profoundly communal experience’ of music making suggests the idea of ‘emergent’ and ‘connected selves, enmeshed in reciprocity’ (Titon 2008:37).

2.4. ETHNOGRAPHIES of RURAL BRITAIN – from LOCALISM to MOBILITIES

In parallel with these internal developments in Shetland, from the late 1970s into the 1990s, ethnographers of Britain and Scotland also sought, in various ways, to define the cultural parameters and social and ethnic boundaries of the localities they studied, conceptually containing them within those parameters. This focus shifted in the early years of the new millennium, with the increased popularity of ethnographic studies focusing on movements, cross-cultural fertilisation, hybridity, mobilities and the primacy of sense experience. The ‘ethnography of movement’ (Vergunst 2011) that resulted has been developed in various directions since the publication of Urry’s (2007) mobilities paradigm foundation statement. I will now condense and analyse some of these conceptual-historical anthropological developments as featured in a selection of ethnographies of Britain and Scotland that have emerged roughly in the last 30 years.

The present project challenges the explanatory power and clarity of ethnographic frameworks that seek and find ‘clear-cut boundaries’, by presenting active Shetland musicians drawing on musical ideas and technologies from Shetland and mostly elsewhere, and making strong bonds with people and music from other places and cultures through personal trajectories in unfolding social worlds. As Kearney (1995:558) points out, in the late 1990s, ethnographers started seriously questioning the stability of cultural and social identities, which ‘escape in part from either-or classification and become defined more by a logic of “both-and-and[n]” in which the subject shapes partial, overlapping identities with other similarly constituted decentered subjects that inhabit reticular social forms’. Historically, Shetland’s sociomusical culture has questioned, disrupted, challenged and crossed geographical, social and symbolic boundaries in order to understand its distinctive place in the larger world and find expression in the present. Shetlanders often speak of how mixed Shetland actually is – characters from Scottish, English, Dutch, Norwegian, Spanish

and other backgrounds have established strong bonds throughout the islands and have become local, just as Shetlanders have established strong roots in places like Canada, Australia, New Zealand, South Africa, and the United States, following maritime routes established in colonial times. Since the introduction of the fiddle in the islands in the 18th century, fishing ships would have fiddlers onboard to ‘enliven them,’ and fiddlers from different ships and origins would ‘meet and try their skill’ (Johnson 1971:125 *In* Cooke 1986:12). Back in Shetland, children would gather around the fire to listen to fiddlers play ‘in the long winter evenings’ tunes that reflected Shetlanders’ historical maritime mobilities, including several ‘likely very old’ Norse and Scottish ‘fairy tunes’, and even ‘Yaki, i.e., Eskimo tunes’ which sometimes had ‘different names in different parishes’ (Johnson 1971:125 *In* Cooke 1986:12). Active fiddlers have told me that various tunes that are supposedly from Shetland are not originally so, but have become localised through widespread use, eventually becoming naturalised as ‘Shetland’ with time.⁴⁸

In the early 1990s, as Nadel-Klein argues, the ‘relationship between localism and marginality’ was a ‘key issue for Europeanist ethnography’ (1991:513). Ethnographies of Britain asserted the uniqueness of communities that ‘possess and express distinct traditions, strong boundaries, and rigid dichotomies between insider and outsider’ (Nadel-Klein 1991:502). For instance, Parman’s study of the Free Church of the Scottish Highlands argues that one could know a culture by ‘the marks and signs that establish clear-cut boundaries’ (1990:303). Nadel-Klein agreed with Cohen (1982:1) that the media’s portrayal of ‘British society as homogeneous’ does ‘great violence to the strongly felt distinctiveness of local communities’ (Nadel-Klein 1991:501). For her, localist assertions of identity are pervasive in British society (Nadel-Klein 1991:500). Yet, in her view, ‘demands for land and labor’ have the power to create and destroy the ‘distinct way of life’ of many Scottish communities (Nadel-Klein 1991:502). Shetland’s sociomusical

world, in my experience, is permeable, socially extensive, and requires face-to-face participation for appreciating in detail. In this sense, religious precepts or the mass media cannot define it or change it, *spreers* and their activities do. This nuance is not captured in Nadel-Klein's (1991) statements about 'local communities', 'British society' and the 'media' because these categories are too unspecific. When it comes to contemporary Shetland, a focus on 'bounded identities' and the exclusivist binary of 'insider and outsider' (e.g., McFarlane 1981) can obscure the extensive relationships Shetlanders (musicians or not) have historically fostered in other places. Such a dichotomy is insufficient to describe the differences that exist in Shetland. Although one may choose to speak of 'local communities' generally, doing so contradicts the premise that these communities are as unique as they are complex. Yet, experientially and analytically in terms of scale, small rural communities are quite unlike urban areas, and it would be reasonable to suppose commonalities between places we choose to classify as such. My attention to personal trajectories and their mobility revealed a network of sociomusical pathways that transcend the limits of an anthropological imagination on 'boundaries'. Thus, a 'life-line, a trajectory of growth' emerged from participants' present and historical trajectories (Ingold 2000:144), and the purpose of the present work is to give it shape.

McFarlane (1981:119) argued that the idea of an incomer 'as indicating a real, fundamental division of local society' is a 'relatively new phenomenon' and emerged 'during the first stages of the so called "oil era" in Shetland (1971-1979)'. Shetlanders in McFarlane 'view their relationships with incomers so negatively' (1981:128). Yet, he focused exclusively on 'models of local society held by the native population of Dunrossness', a settlement of about 1500 people in mainland Shetland (McFarlane 1981:119), and includes no personal account of living as an incomer in Shetland.⁴⁹ From the limitations of his Dunrossness sample and without support from extended fieldwork or

participation in local daily life, McFarlane claims that the ‘identities incomer and Shetlander, and the stereotypes associated with them, have become the main language in terms of which conflicts between individuals and groups are discussed, and in terms of which people’s behaviour is evaluated’ (1981:134). This assumption may actually reflect McFarlane’s (1981) theoretical choice to concentrate on local and incomer divisions that were also typical of other studies of small communities in Britain at the time.⁵⁰ However, as Goffman noted, conceptualising it as ‘backstaging’ (1956:25), Shetlanders are often self-aware that they are performing an image of themselves to others, and may use the fact that outsiders do not know local ways to mislead them with designed impressions. McFarlane’s (1981) conclusions are based on counting instances of negative and positive stereotypes and summarising them. McFarlane presents his characterisations on tables (1981:125,126) and does not flesh out personal narratives or witnessed experiences of situation in which negative stereotypes were enacted and central. He concludes that ‘Shetlanders presented a rather cosy image of themselves’ (McFarlane 1981:126). In my experience, Shetlanders can use very ‘negative’ words toward one another intending anything from serious criticism to pure comic jest, and delivering something ridiculous with a straight face denotes mastery of deception as comic technique.⁵¹ The quality of the relationship dynamics between individuals, the resonance between their affinities and differences, shapes those exchanges. Hard word play is very common in Shetland, and simply counting what researchers may consider being negative or positive stereotypes does not catch the nuances one can intend by playing with words.

Attention to Goffman’s observations of Shetlanders committing ‘acts of disrespect against each other that would ordinarily be cause of great offense’ (1953:324-327) can allow us to balance the image McFarlane (1981:128) suggests, ironically stereotypical, that ‘Shetlanders view their relationships with incomers so negatively’. Participant Joe Watt

wrote to me via Facebook messages on June 3rd 2013 that ‘the more horrible a thing we feel comfortable saying about you, the more we trust you, Max [Tyler] more so than me’. Joe Watt also wrote, ‘although I do occasionally make a joke at your expense, lovingly though, if I wasn’t doing that it means I’m not thinking about you’. This signals the fact I observed in multiple occasions throughout my two-year residence, that Shetlanders engage creatively with word play that others outside their personal circle might class as offensive. Yet, knowing how to take insult in public is like a mode of integration. Succeeding in not being personally offended and engaging in creative retaliation is more like a bonding ritual, and signals social maturity and integration.⁵² ‘Humorous putdowns’, argues Murphy, ‘as a form of teasing, have the peculiar character of potential contentiousness’, and mixes friendliness with antagonism (2015:4). Murphy is aware that ‘[t]easing and putdowns can be risky when people don’t know each other well – potentially evolving into unease or downright conflict (Lampert and Ervin-Tripp 2006 *In* Murphy 2015:4). Moreover, In ‘everyday life, people crack jokes and spout witticisms, and although individuals do not do so for the same reasons or to the same effect, it is nonetheless undeniable that humour is a routinely taken-for-granted aspect of everyday life’ (Murphy 2015:2). In fact, I witnessed several *sprees* in which local musicians who have a very good reputation in the community fell asleep and were immediately subjected to having different things balanced over their heads (e.g., empty beer cans, hats, socks), inserted into their mouths or noses, photos tagging them on Facebook posted immediately. I imagine that many outsiders to this culture of conviviality and humour would find this unflattering and abusive, but I could not find a single Shetlander who took it as such. This indicates that knowing how to laugh with others at one’s own expense is, at least among seasoned *spreers*, a form of social wisdom and participation.

From the perspective of Shetland's music scene and practices, an automatic negativity toward incomers seems as unlikely now as during the oil boom era or before. Yet, from the perspective of the effects of oil development, such negativity is founded on experience with transgressors. In any case, McFarlane (1981) does not reveal how such boundaries are negotiated, reinstated or transcended in practice. For McFarlane, the relationship between local and incomer 'is given over-riding importance in Shetlanders' sociological perspectives' (1981:119). My social and musical encounters with Shetlanders revealed a system of affinities among multidimensional emergent individuals in which being an incomer was no disadvantage, but willingness to participate in daily social life, play and humour, regardless of local or incomer status, was paramount for fostering lasting resonances with local connections. As Murphy (2015:4) suggests, subjecting group members to one's humour can foster a 'sense of solidarity'. Participation 'in the course of everyday life' affords ethnographers with 'a fruitful position to discover the seriousness in humorous moments typically taken for granted as "unserious"' and to represent how locals renegotiate 'culture and nuanced interpersonal meanings' (Murphy 2015:4).

For McFarlane (1981:134), conflicts are underlying 'the dualistic, dichotomised perspectives on society held by Shetlanders'. In sociomusical relationships the negativity McFarlane (1981) found in the oil development context between locals and incomers does not exist or it is not significant enough to generate tensions. In fact, active members of the music scene in Shetland are often enthusiastic about visitors and incomers, and returning locals who have been residing elsewhere. Shuldham-Shaw's personal trajectory and legacy in Shetland is an example. An Englishman, Shuldham-Shaw came to Shetland as an ethnomusicologist in the 1940s, documented many local tunes and wrote and performed a number of his own compositions locally. One still hears some of these tunes in The

Lounge through the hands of Shetland fiddlers. The song ‘Rosemary Brown’, for instance, is a local favourite that I have heard many times at traditional sessions at The Lounge.

The model of incomer introduction that McFarlane claims to have changed is very similar to the model of introduction that I experienced in Shetland as an incomer or outsider. According to McFarlane, in this older model of introduction, ‘individual incomers (the “soothmoother” type) were assimilated with relative ease into individual social networks centred in neighbouring villages’ (1981:127). At that time, McFarlane notes, ‘[t]here were comparatively few incomers and they were dispersed among the native population’, fostering relations ‘out of simple necessity’ or ‘advice’ and ‘help with building’ (1981:127). For McFarlane (1981:127), many first incomers have constructed a ‘rather cosy view of life in Shetland’ because they were pursuing the ‘meaningful “community”’. Yet, ‘these individuals tended to establish their closest relations with the bearers of Shetland tradition, the older Shetlanders’ (McFarlane 1981:127). In McFarlane (1981:128), Shetlanders point out that ‘incomers had to become part of the local community’ in the past and ‘now they no longer need to’. As McFarlane (1981:127) notes, ‘older Shetlanders’ fostered links between incomers and the local community, helping them forge reputations that would eventually affording them the feeling of belonging ‘to different local communities’.⁵³ These incomers of the past ‘were willing to participate in local events, stand about and chat with the neighbours’, lacked ‘exclusive networks of their own’, and ‘depended upon Shetlanders for socializing and favours’ (McFarlane 1981:128). Moreover, for McFarlane, Shetlanders rate incomers according to respectability, how long they have resided in Shetland, and how much ‘social investment’ they give to their locality (1981:123). McFarlane’s presentation of this model assumes that this method of introduction and eventual naturalisation has been changed and remained active only ‘up until recently’ (McFarlane 1981:127). Yet, as my research shows, *spree* practices and

principles provide Shetlanders and incomers with a mode for fostering connections beyond a supposedly naturalised binary division between generic incomers and Shetlanders.

Since my intention was to understand the local sociomusical world, I became involved with its inhabitants, conversing with residents on a daily basis. My local network extended with increased involvement with residents and the accumulation of new relationships, based on introductions by native Shetlanders and residents of various age groups, sometimes working together. For instance, an introduction of outsiders that takes place during a sociomusical *spre* could be done in the presence of various already known musical collaborators to someone who arrives later and knows everyone but the outsiders. In this sense, a group introduces a new arrival to an unknown local whose local contacts brought to the *spre*. Under a microscope, those relationships grow from epistemological affinities with the principles of the *spre* and the resonance they afford in interactions. The distinction between incomer and local is not sufficient to describe the process of familiarisation that I experienced personally and also observed among incomer musicians like Gemma Graham and Kirsty North (featured in Chapter 6). New resident outsiders are often at the mercy of locals for making and establishing social contacts, especially in the music scene. Yet, the willingness to participate in local social and cultural life in whatever role is usually enough for beginning to link one's personal interests to the affinities and activities of various residents.

The 'division of local society', which McFarlane found among Dunrossness residents in the early 1980s, 'emerged from the creation of incomer networks' (1981:128). Yet, McFarlane also notes that 'real incomers', current residents who were born outside of Shetland, 'are not all the same to Shetlanders' (McFarlane 1981:123). For McFarlane, these incomers 'have numerous subdivisions, defined along various dimensions' (1981:123), but he focused on negative stereotypes instead. To nuance this view, we

should note that Shetland's social world is historically built upon various kinds of 'incomer networks'. The binary division, reflected superficially in language, is grounded upon a general sense of the attitudes of temporary energy industry workers, as experienced or reported, and a fear associated with the potential long term effects of their influx in high numbers. As such, it is not directed to generic incomers and outsiders, and people are still assessed on a personal, face-to-face manner through *spreed* practices.

As McFarlane notes, 'temporary residents' whose 'supposed commitment to Shetland' ends with the end of 'the construction phase of the oil era' are considered 'less respectable' and earn the label of 'oilies', 'potential troublemakers who need to be amused, policed and, above all, contained' (McFarlane 1981:124). As Millar (2007:118) points out, with the discovery of North Sea oil in the 1960s and 'its rapid exploitation in the 1970s', considerable 'social change' struck the northeast of Scotland. He notes that 'the presence of a number of large oil companies in Aberdeen has led to an influx of generally well-heeled immigrants who, characteristically, only settle in the city for a few years' (Millar 2007:118). These temporary workers 'and their children' have 'either been unwilling or unable to create network ties within local communities, including assimilation towards the local variety' (Millar 2007:118). In some areas, 'incomers have outnumbered locals' and relations 'between longer-term residents and locals' are strained by tensions around rising housing costs (Millar 2007:118). In Shetland, this tension is also very acute, and the influx of temporary oil workers and contractors (instead of long term residents) is associated with the rising prices and difficulties of locals in finding affordable housing. Elsewhere in Scotland, incomers were 'described as 'white settlers', a term with resonances in the history of British Imperialism (Jedrej and Nuttall 1996 *In* Millar 2007:118).

The evidence that I encountered suggests that many Shetlanders view themselves as seafarers and incomers to other places, and understand local social configurations as

inescapably mixed, sustaining the notion that no single group or nationalist identity can exclusively claim Shetland as its own. The principle of resourcefulness, often evoked beyond the music scene to describe living with the hardships of the past (i.e., extreme weather, wars), supports nuance of character appreciation, leading incomers to be assessed according to their social and practical skills and potential for collaboration with locals and their activities.⁵⁴ Musical practices are international (or universal) enough so that tastes and affinities can be shared among the most unlikely incomer and local candidates. Music making and the social scene that surrounds it in Shetland, and most particularly *sprees* practices, benefit from the potential for intercultural connections that music loving (a wider phenomenon than music making) affords.

The middle age and young Shetlanders I know were interested in my experiences as an outsider, and invited me into their homes. They have friends and family scattered around the world and are often well travelled. Among their close friends, there are always locals and outsiders from various places, and those who have found partners and settled. Some moved to Shetland because of job opportunities afforded by the oil boom of the 1970s and became integrated in the music scene (e.g., Stevie Hook and Jim Quinn). They are not isolated cases. People in Shetland are well aware that being an incomer or a Shetlander does not make anyone better or worse. What seems to matter most, however, is how people relate to one another, and whether they are willing to *sprees* according to the unwritten 'rules of the game' (Bourdieu 1977:58, 201) which one can only learn by paying attention and playing along with *spreers*.

Renwanz (1981) and Black (1995) found that the threats perceived with the arrival of the oil industry generated interest in specifying a local 'way of life'. Pressure for cataloguing and even concocting authentic traditional traits arises with the fear that incomers, introduced artificially and in large numbers at once, may replace and erase local

ways. However, as Campbell (1997) noted in her thorough questionnaire-based survey report, one of the main concerns of Shetland musicians' was the unrealistic portrayal of Shetland's music as 'traditional fiddling' (e.g., Anderson and Swing 1979). In other words, local musicians expressed concern with the stereotyping of their epistemological tradition of music making as confined to fiddle music. For them, Shetland has strong musical traditions, but they are certainly not limited to fiddling, which the post oil-era salvage model, alongside Tom Anderson's invented tradition (Swing 1991) sought to promote to outsiders. Even if most agree that music making is integrated in local ways of living and worth preserving as a tradition, its scope certainly ventured beyond traditional fiddle music. A 2006 BBC documentary focusing on *Up Helly Aa* portrays Shetland's music tradition as stylistically homogeneous and fiddlers as its keepers. BBC (2006) constructed a marketable form of Shetland uniqueness based on stereotypes, obscuring the complexities of intersecting sociomusical trajectories and mobility practices that challenge and transcend the thin portrayal of Shetland as an isolated place steeped in fiddle music and inauthentic romantic Norse tradition (e.g., Grydehøj 2011).

Skiffington (1991:276) was concerned with issues of ethnic boundaries in a 'small village'. She concentrated on divisive dynamics between 'Locals and Incomers' (Skiffington 1991:265). Her analysis of community belonging and 'boundary-making' drew inspiration from Barth (1969) and Cohen (1982). In Skiffington (1991), sociopolitical alliances were more closely related to economic class than to status as 'Incomers or Locals'. The so-called 'boundary' between 'incomer' and 'local' became irrelevant when it came to establishing sociopolitical relations. Thus, 'some well-to-do Locals find more in common with the interests of wealthy land owners, Local or Incomer, than with crofters' (Skiffington 1991:274). Conversely, 'the Local shop owner or contractor' had more in common 'with the Incomer attorney or banker than the crofter, fisherman, or waitress'

(Skiffington 1991:275). For Skiffington, ‘continual, dynamic change’ affected the boundaries articulated (Skiffington 1991:276).

Cohen (1985b:94) noted that a number of researchers working ‘in inland areas of northern England’ and ‘much further north in the British Isles’ have encountered the ‘symbolic demarcation of ‘local’ and ‘incomer’. For him, symbolism is versatile and malleable, which makes it ubiquitous as ‘a means of expressing the distinctiveness – the boundedness – of community’ (Cohen 1985b:94). For him, the Whalsay *spree* is a ‘symbolic form whose content has been transformed but whose continuity masks or limits the trauma of change’ (Cohen 1985b:95). The concepts of epistemological resonance and reverberation add nuance to the notion of boundaries, and emphasise permeability. They describe how bodies respond to environments that are not restricted to the physical world, including how semantic associations between ideas and their logical force, harmonised in recurring practices, may drive people to connect and form strong relationships, despite the potential restrictions of symbolic boundaries. Although Grydehøj (2011) has recently argued that strong divisions between ‘outsider’ and ‘incomer’ exist in Shetland, my personal experiences with the local sociomusical world prove that ‘outsider’ and ‘incomer’ status do not prevent connections.⁵⁵ Stevie Hook and Jim Quinn moved to Shetland in the 1970s and became integrated into the sociomusical community. In fact, my opinion of life in Shetland was often sought precisely because I once lived elsewhere. For many, outside perspectives lead to valuable critical reflections on local ways and performances.

The lifelong friendship between Billy Kay and Peerie Willie, for instance, transcended socioeconomic class differences. Billy was from the enterprising commercial class, and Peerie Willie lived without many possessions. According to local lore, Peerie Willie never even owned his own guitar. This supposedly unlikely friendship shared in a passion for the character of the local music, jazz and experimentation. Billy Kay provided

the facilities for sociomusical gatherings and recordings. *Sprees* would happen at Billy Kay's studio in his Lerwick home throughout the 1950s and 1960s, before the institution of the Shetland Folk Festival, and included visitors from many places and music influenced by American jazz forms. Billy Kay supported Stevie Hook over the years in myriad ways, and bequeathed different recording equipment for Stevie, including rare 'classic' reel-to-reel machines, when he passed away, at age 93, before the 2014 SFF. It was clear that Billy was passing the baton so to speak to Stevie, that he saw in Stevie someone who would, almost like a successor, carry on the techie tradition and sociomusical community spirit that Billy exemplified with his life-line trajectory. Among the characters that have contributed to Shetland music, Billy Kay is one of the most respected. Knowledgeable local music lovers still cherish and value his legacy.

Although Shetlanders foster strong relationships with local land- and seascapes, they continuously journey beyond them and identify with their trajectories around the world. Many have lived in large urban centres for their education, and some young Shetlanders I have met are already travelling the world working in the mercantile shipping industry.⁵⁶ Gray's (1999:455) work on Scottish shepherds avoided explanations based on symbolic boundaries, and focused instead on how 'farmers relive their image of Borders identity everyday in their treks'. Gray (1999:440) explored how shepherds from the Scottish borders 'encounter the hills, perceive them, and invest them with significance'. For him, places are imbued with the cultural values, morals and details present in the stories people tell about them, serving as repositories 'of distilled wisdom' (Basso 1996:62-63 *In* Gray 1999:443). He sought to uncover processes of 'identity making' that generate places in the hills and which form attachments to them as people 'implicate a historicized image of themselves as people *of* the Scottish borders' (Gray 1999:440).

More recently, ethnographers of Britain and Europe, and social scientists in general, are increasingly recognising the relevance of mobilities and bodily experiences. As Feld (2000:148) noted, ‘the global dominance of mediated musics in the twentieth century signalled to ethnomusicology that its uncritical naturalisation of “authentic traditions” was in trouble’. With this predicament in mind, ethnomusicologists ‘incorporated insights from popular music studies to effect a shift from studying bounded and discrete musical worlds to ones created out of contact histories and colonial legacies, out of diaspora and hybridity, out of migration, urbanization, and mass media’ (2000:148). Anthropologists thus began conceiving of identities as changing phenomena and dealing with aspects of experience that had personal and social dimensions. They found that identities follow the logic of “both-and-and[n]” of ‘globalizing reticula’ and ‘rhizomes’, and are like ‘hypertext’ in that they can connect any point to any other point through ‘direct intratextual links’ (Kearney 1995:558). These links form ‘decentered systems of networks’ that are similar to ‘the Internet and the human brain’, suggesting rhizomatic and reticular imagery – ‘the form and physiology of nomadic transnational and global communities that flourish outside the striated space of the state’ (Kearney 1995:558-559). In her work among young Scottish Pakistanis in Edinburgh, Karen Qureshi (2006:207) argued that their ‘diverse mobilities’ constructed ‘trans-boundary communicative spaces where meanings of identities are exchanged, reflexively debated, and played with’. She argued that concepts like ‘identity’, ‘culture’, and ‘belonging’ are problematic and tend to disguise plurality (Qureshi 2006:224). Similarly, D’Andrea (2006:95) encountered ‘interrelations between global hypermobility and subjectivity formation’ in neo-nomadic lifestyles.

Noting the ‘importance of ethnographic work in the context of sensory experience’, Lund (2005:40-41) argued that ‘senses are integrated by the way in which the living body

moves'. Vergunst (2011:215-216) emphasised the importance of engagement with the practices of participants in ethnographic explorations of mobilities and the 'continuing relevance of bodily skills'. My project contributes to studies of Scotland and Britain by looking at how mobilities, technologies of music making, musical creativity and social life in Shetland challenge anthropological interpretations of localism and marginality, boundaries, homogeneity and diversity. I propose that concepts such as epistemological resonance, discordance and harmonisation, interpersonal knowledge and nuance of character appreciation are useful for understanding Shetland sociomusical phenomena.

2.5. BOUNDARY-PERMEABILITY: POSITIONALITY, POWER and MOBILITIES

Anthony P. Cohen (1986:1) argued for an anthropology focused on how 'people mark out their immediate and intimate social identities, those boundaries of the social lives which demarcate most powerfully and meaningfully their sense of similarity to and difference from other people'. Before Cohen's (1987) work on 'symbolic boundaries' in Whalsay, Reginald Byron (1983:47) argued that the island of Burra was 'an involuted society, of remarkably uniform and homogeneous character' by 1971. This changed when development and diversity, and 'waves of change' brought about by North Sea Oil development in 1979 'washed away its insularity' (Byron 1983:54). The fundamental difference between Byron's (1983) approach and Cohen's (1986) is that whereas Byron imagined cultural diversity as the outcome of mainstream economic development, Cohen saw the complete opposite. Cohen and Byron are fundamentally at odds when it comes to the question of homogenisation and industrialisation. For Cohen (1986:1) the 'mainstream forces of economic, political and administrative life attack the structural bases of local diversity and replace them with a veneer of homogeneity' (1986:1).⁵⁷

Since the isle of Burra is only 12 miles from Lerwick and 4 from Scalloway (Byron 1983:50), Byron may have overplayed the myth of ‘uniform homogeneity’.⁵⁸ Byron (1994) emphasised the strength of social boundaries and tried to define the cohesive ‘maritime household’ in Northern Europe, but also pointed to social changes brought to local communities by structural forces. For him, ‘fishing vessel’ workers formed a ‘closely bound group’ subjected to changes imposed by the larger economy (Byron 1994:289). Yet, by the 1990s, ‘fishing families are almost everywhere heavily outnumbered in communities by summer vacationers, weekend second-home owners from the cities, and office and factory workers’ (Byron 1994:289). Imagining ‘closed and bounded rural communities’ merely ‘perpetuates the myths of rurality as a preserve of old traditions’ (Lee et al. 2005:281). Black (1995:303) argued that ‘contrary to popular belief, Shetland does not have an insular society’. For her, Shetland has an ‘acute and alert history’ of mobilities and interactions ‘with the wider world through trade, something outsiders appear to have overlooked in their perception of Shetland on the eve of the oil boom’ (Black 1995:303).

Clifford (1986a:22) argued that islands are in constant motion, since ‘one cannot occupy, unambiguously, a bounded cultural world from which to journey out and analyse other cultures’. The cultural analyst is positioned within ‘global movements of difference and power’ (Clifford 1986a:22). Acknowledging positionality is an essential reflexive objective of this project. Reality on the ground utterly disrupts the outsiders’ romantic idea of bounded islands and rural communities. As one middle-aged Shetlander told me, ‘if you want isolation, don’t come to an island’. In the case of Shetland’s 21st century sociomusical scene, the abstract and symbolic boundaries that earlier ethnographers found are constantly being challenged by practical connections based on affinities that transcend geographic and linguistic boundaries. As Sara Cohen (2012:164) noted, musicians often

participate in worlds that ‘overlap and intersect’ and enter into ‘complex relationships with music institutions and events elsewhere, thus extending beyond local boundaries’.

During the 25th Shetland Accordion and Fiddle Festival, held from October 11th to 15th, 2012, local families hosted about 70 visiting musicians. Shetlanders believed that music would ‘stagnate without the impetus of visiting musicians’ even though ‘local musicians were often very active in outlying areas’ (Campbell 1997:15). My early experiences as a participant in the weekly traditional music sessions at The Lounge, playing percussion, and the positive reception of my research project locally also corroborated this point. In addition, throughout 2013 and 2014, convincing evidence emerged for the fact that sociomusical *spree* participation has nothing to do with one’s place of origin. In fact, as Shuldham-Shaw (1962) already suggested, Shetland musicians are interested in people and musics from abroad.

In the 21st century, anthropologists have approached the imposition of abstract topographic boundaries as a feature of colonialist bureaucratisation. It stems from unfamiliarity with physical and social landscapes and generates boundaries ‘with distant roots’ (Cruikshank 2005:213-214). King (2009:146) prefers to ‘avoid the term boundaries’ and to engage with the ‘fuzzy-edged qualities of cultural margins’. The notion of ‘cultural margins’ attends to the effects of ‘globalization processes’ in the ‘most remote margins’ of the world (Wang et al. 2014:23).⁵⁹ Yet, this paradigm, which privileges a distanced view from outside, is challenged by the mobility of Shetland’s inhabitants and visitors and the historical vitality of sea routes that have led Shetlanders to establish strong roots in several, mostly English speaking and commonwealth related countries around the world.⁶⁰

Various Shetland musicians maintain lifelong friendships and personal relations with people from around the world, and are at least as connected as metropolitan dwellers. Billy Kay, who served in the British army as a reconnaissance expert from 1940 to 1945,

pointed out that there are many Shetlanders who have ‘been around the world once or twice’. The efforts of some anthropologists to draw boundaries around their subjects, cultural or otherwise, and cast them with definitive ‘identities’ mirrors the colonial effort of splicing the landscape and its inhabitants through abstracted colonial maps for the sake of domination and control. Accepted theories based on a limited canonized range are coercive structures of meaning that prevent ‘free play’ (Clifford 1986b:110). I will attend to how distinctions between musical practices, instrumentations and social arrangements become significant in Shetlandic contexts while coexisting mobilities challenge constructions of identities as bounded and limited. In fact, the sense of nuance of character appreciation challenges the notion of identity altogether, pointing to its central limitation – a tendency for relying on averaging generalisations.

2.6. SHETLAND MOBILITIES and EARLY ETHNOGRAPHY

There are also places around the world where Shetlanders have not only strong sociomusical and kinship engagements, but also creative and inspirational ones. Most local musicians develop personalised and ‘eclectic’ repertoires ‘drawn from many sources’ (Swing 1991:290). Shetlanders have established and maintain strong connections with English speaking countries outside Britain, the United Kingdom, and Ireland – particularly Australia, New Zealand, South Africa, Canada and the United States. Shetlandic historical migration patterns followed the trade lines carved alongside British colonialist expansion, which are now firmly established. However, because of the oppressive and exploitative colonialism Shetlanders experienced in the hands of imported Scottish lairds, the sensibilities of a number of historically informed Shetlanders are aligned with those of indigenous peoples in the colonies, who suffered similar, and ultimately direr fates on the hands of colonialists. Shetlanders, for instance, were forced to speak English in school –

although not as extreme and violent as what indigenous peoples suffered in residential schools, this enforced the idea that Shetland's language was inferior and not worth learning. This oppressive experience still bears a fresh mark in the memories of middle-aged locals, such as Amanda Pearson. The song *Pressgang* that Michael Williamson wrote for his project *Brandy from a Stranger* (2015), with *North Country Fair* (NCF), speaks of Shetlanders' resistance to naval and military drafting by colonial forces, informing a sense of local culture constructed around a strong sense of sociocultural, economic and political autonomy and independence, and the close association of creativity with freedom.⁶¹

Colonial dispossession imposed on the Cherokee was similar to how the 'Shetland laird' held 'his estate under absolute personal title, in relation to the hapless crofter' (Bloom 2002:505). Shetlanders were subjected to the oppression of Scottish lairds, invaders who brought to their land an ideology of dependence on the state and submission to its regulations and taxes. By the nineteenth century, the 'crofter-fishermen population' of Shetland 'had been reduced to a serf-like status' and only began to emerge out of it 'around the middle of the nineteenth century' (Theodoratus 1979:163). Colonial authorities encouraged landlessness 'in the name of market efficiency' and considered dispossession necessary for producing disciplined labour (Murray Li 2010:387). Crofters in Shetland had their lands taken away by the authorities and were reduced to a condition of dependency, having to give to the lairds most of what they produced. Some crofters refrained 'from improving the appearance' of their cottages, knowing that improvements would signal that 'increased rents could be extracted from them' by the lairds (Goffman 1956:25).

2.7. *SHETLAND'S ANTHROPOLOGICAL LEGACY: JAMES A. TEIT*

Equipped with such historical sensibilities, Franz Boas' collaborator, Lerwick-born James A. Teit (1864-1922), grew up in colonial conditions and eventually used his knowledge to fight for indigenous rights and autonomy after migrating to British Columbia. Boas praised Teit as a 'man of sterling worth' who, inspired by 'his warm sympathy' for the 'suffering' and 'difficulties' of local Indians, helped founding an association for the protection of Indian rights (Boas 1923:103). Teit was 'thoroughly conversant' with the 'languages and customs' of the Thompson Indians, and conducted 'joint labours' with Boas from 1895, when they first met in British Columbia 'until his death' (Boas 1923:102). Teit travelled to Spence's Bridge, British Columbia, at age nineteen, 'to join his Uncle John Murray, who had settled there years earlier' (Wickwire 1993:541). Nineteen is the same general age in which many Shetlanders in the present generation leave the islands to find their path. Hayden Hook, Max Tyler, Martha Thomson, Chloe Robertson, Norman Willmore, Lewis Murray and Joe Watt are all musical characters in this ethnography that have left Shetland between 2013 and 2014, at around the same age as Teit, who died before returning, but who regularly communicated with friends in Lerwick by post. The archives at the Shetland Museum in Lerwick keep Teit's original correspondence, which is available for study and can be easily copied.

Like a number of other Boas associates, Teit fought to break down colonialist, racial and political boundaries (Boas 1923:102). Teit's sensibility and empathy towards indigenous peoples probably stems from Shetlandic historical experiences with colonialism. Teit considered working for the welfare of his Indian associates 'the most important task of his life' (Boas 1923:103), but as his letters to Lerwick show, now in the Shetland archives, Teit never forgot Shetland.⁶² The struggle against colonialist and nationalist oppression and control, against division and segmentation is both at the heart of

Teit's anthropology and life project. Teit's outlook reflected important principles of Shetland's epistemological tradition as expressed in sociomusical practices – horizontality, an insatiable curiosity for the world at large, inquisitiveness, respect for difference and commitment to social justice, diversity, integration and communication. Teit's first collaboration with Boas focused on music, and they used an Edison recording machine' to capture 'forty-five songs over a three-day period', mostly sang by women (Wickwire 1993:544). Boas and Teit's 1897 song collection 'includes a strong female presence' and is 'among the very earliest' of its kind (Wickwire 1993:544).

Under Edward Sapir's direction, Teit 'spent years recording Native songs, in both the southern and northern interior of British Columbia' (Wickwire 1988, 1993:552-553). Attention to how growing up in Shetland influenced the development of Teit's character is missing in Wickwire (1988).⁶³ The centrality of music to Teit's approach, with singing and storytelling taking the spotlight and his adoption of available recording technologies, suggests that elements of what I call the current epistemological tradition of Shetland music were already a part of Teit's upbringing. Close attention to sociomusical connections and personal trajectories is key for understanding the formation of character, a locus for the keeping and passing of shared cultural values.

2.8. THE SHETLAND STYLE – NUANCE of CHARACTER

Very skilled local musicians and experienced listeners certainly recognise a Shetland style that contrasts with ways of playing similar material in closely related musical areas with strong forms of fiddle-oriented music, such as Orkney, mainland Scotland, Ireland, Norway and Britain. There are also as many personal styles as there are experienced musicians. Within larger regional differences, Shetland's distinctiveness includes a taste for faster tempos and for the rhythmic-melodic, fluid punctuation pulse of Peerie Willie's

comping style, reminiscent of Django Reinhart's gypsy jazz. This realisation, however, just scratches the surface of how experienced local fiddlers and listeners can recognise the styles of other local players. For instance, it is clear that a blindfolded Maurice Henderson could easily pick out Bryan Gear's playing in a crowd of fiddlers anytime. Yet, even with passionate devotion to their instrument, most Shetland fiddlers are not seeking the power to define, regulate and perpetuate a prescribed tradition bound to stylistic formulae and repertoire restrictions – they all have clearly articulated personal styles. Their sense of character is strengthened by their involvement with different musics.

Most of the contemporary Shetland fiddlers and musicians in this ethnography are passionately involved with various forms of music, transcending the artificial barriers of style and taste imposed by the orthodox model of tradition. Each character has developed their own taste through years of listening, studying, and performing. However, most active local musicians share the ethos of the *spree* – a special, comfortable and safe place of freedom of expression and enjoyment, where new ideas can be tried out and developed, where time loses meaning until it's finally time to leave, sometimes deep into the next morning, in alternating cycles of storytelling, jamming and listening to music together. I remember how, in one of my first overnight house parties in the winter of 2012, with Maurice Henderson and Jonny Polson, how Maurice spontaneously insisted on learning one of the songs I knew from the Brazilian Samba and Bossa Nova tradition. It was probably the first time I played anything of the sort to anyone in Shetland, and I could not foresee that my participation in the local scene would lead to a performance of the same tune in the 2014 Shetland Folk Fest, with an intergenerational band of locals.

What engaged and involved Shetland fiddlers and other instrumentalists are seriously and passionately concerned with, as I aim to demonstrate, is making sure that *spree* sessions continue to exist, not only privately through all night musical sessions, but also

publically and in community settings through events organised with personal, fundraised or publically available arts funding. SADA's popular event Fiddle Frenzy produced a canonical selection of Shetland tunes as part of its tourist-oriented educational packet. The short compilation does not reflect, most especially, the creative output of current Shetland fiddle composers, but simply conforms to the expectations of beginner level fiddle enthusiast tourists who are content with learning the basics of Shetland's fiddling tradition as a distinctive, authentic and sanitised brand.

Despite the clean branding scheme, Fiddle Frenzy includes free concerts by respected resident fiddlers, some of which also serve as instructors for master class attendees, mostly beginning tourist fiddlers coming to Shetland for a first time and enthusiastic young fiddlers. Still, the Fiddle Frenzy publication that SADA produced in 2014 is very polished, well put together, and attractive – and, as such it makes for a valuable contribution to local history. The festival also brings local fiddlers together with visitors for sociomusical activities, and a mini-*spree*. The more serious sociomusical *sprees* are guaranteed to happen at every Shetland Folk Festival (May) and at the slightly more traditional music oriented Accordion and Fiddle Festival (October). Yet, for seasoned *spreers* Maurice Henderson, Lewie Peterson and Lois Nicol, there is room for much more *spreeing* throughout the year. They decided to organise a *spree* in Fetlar entitled 'For the Love of Folk presents: North Atlantic Sessions' in the summer of 2014. It started with a musical a night at the Carnegie Hall in Sandwick, Southern Mainland, and a concert and overnight *spree* in the isle of Fetlar involving many resident musicians (see Guest 2014b). This event, which I was tasked with filming and audio recording, contributed greatly to the development of my notion of Shetland's sociomusical *spree* as a meaningful symbol for sociomusical practices that reflect the principles of the epistemological tradition of Shetland music. Other *spree*-oriented events have also contribute to this understanding – I

was an audience member in the 2012 Shetland Accordion and Fiddle Festival (SAFF), musician at the 2013 Shetland Jazz Festival, stage technical support to Stevie and Amanda at the 2013 Shetland Folk Festival, filmmaker at the *Back from Beyond* trips to Unst and Noss in 2013, and performer with the Quinttet at the 2014 Shetland Folk Festival.

2.9. *BOUNDED STYLES and UNBRIDLED INFLUENCES*

Careful reading of Shetland's ethnographic and ethnomusicological literature reveals a paradox: while some researchers portray individual fiddlers as the bearers of particular island traditions, their own actions and words in the same literature do not match this interpretation. This problem is more apparent in Cooke (1986), Cohen (1987) and Cooke's student Forsyth (2007). For Shuldham-Shaw (1947:76), Shetland's playing styles and tunes had 'a curious Irish flavour', a phenomenon he associated with the fact that 'so many Shetlanders' were sailors and 'mixed with the Irish population' in the ports of 'Liverpool and Glasgow.'⁶⁴ For Popperwell (1984:244), Norwegian 'musical influences continued to reach Shetland' even 'after the lapse of Scandinavian sovereignty in 1469'. Traditional themes found in Shetland music and cosmology, such as 'trows' and their tunes are also found in Celtic ('fairies'), Irish ('little people'), and Scandinavian ('trolls') contexts, and point to shared cultural-historical experiences (Evans-Wentz 1911, Nicolson 1978, 1981, Popperwell 1984, Hillers 1994).

Fiddler John Stickle from Unst, according to Shuldham-Shaw (1962:130), 'always wanted to know what [he] had found in other places'. Stickle 'was always interested in people and in what was going on not only locally but in the world outside, and was particularly pleased if the outside world took an interest in Shetland and its traditions' (Shuldham-Shaw 1962:131). Stickle 'knew most of the standard repertoire of Scottish and Irish tunes' and he was an 'admirer of Scott Skinner' (Shuldham-Shaw 1962:131).⁶⁵ Neil

Gow (1727-1807) and James Scott Skinner (1843-1927), both Scottish, are still influential among Shetland fiddlers, but their tunes are not considered local because they were not composed in Shetland.

Shuldham-Shaw (1962:130) found that it was ‘almost impossible to describe in words’ Stickle’s ‘style of playing’. Between the ‘number of different styles to be found in Shetland’, one seemed ‘the most truly indigenous’ to him, ‘a lyrical style that has more in common with Ireland than Scotland’ (Shuldham-Shaw 1962:130). He claimed that he felt this ‘lyrical quality’ while appreciating ‘the poetry’ and ‘the architectural shape of any tune’ (Shuldham-Shaw 1962:130-131). Describing one style or another as ‘more or less indigenous’ seems somewhat contradictory in the light of Shuldham-Shaw’s earlier claims about Shetlanders ‘mixing’ with other music makers through seafaring. The solution to this dilemma is that there is no single ‘indigenous style’ in Shetland from which other styles derive – people are crafting their own personal styles with the tools that are available and that arrive in Shetland, including various musical instruments, recording technologies, from vinyl records to the CD and now the Internet. Shetland musicians influenced one another stylistically, and in terms of repertoire and taste for genre diversity.

The experimentations of Peerie Willie and others with various genres helped to shape the tastes of subsequent generations of musicians. The influx of new musics through commercial media, radio, television, and the Internet, far from breaking this connection, reinstates the experimental approach toward outside musics that Peerie Willie incorporated, even if new musicians are not modelling their playing on Willie’s.⁶⁶ In contrast with Tom Anderson, Peerie Willie did not seek to salvage a waning tradition, but encouraged others to experiment. As such, experimentation requires the transgression of stylistic rules. This movement is aligned with the spirit of the *spree* and the malleability and adaptability of its practices. Thus, the community orientation of sociomusical practices

represented by the *spre* and the principles of the epistemological tradition remained relatively stable and historically resilient. Songs and tunes that have been composed in Shetland retain a connection to the land that transcends the geographical origins of the composer. Thus, theoretically, tunes and songs composed in Shetland by outsiders or new residents attain local status. Most importantly, the style of behaving in sociomusical interactions is more stable than the aesthetic demands of any genre. People are given the freedom to sound as they please if they so wish, but they can also become aligned with a particular style, exploring the possibilities it affords.⁶⁷

Forsyth (2007:53) considers Debbie Scott to be ‘the only living fiddler who has maintained the distinctive Papa Stour fiddle style’. Swing’s (1991:297-306) interviews with Debbie Scott, as well as Scott’s own words in Forsyth (2007) contradict this claim, based on Debbie Scott’s playing of Papa Stour tunes that sound like nothing else from other places around Shetland. This does not make Debbie the keeper of the Papa Stour tradition – rather, it means she knows rare tunes composed in Papa Stour that sound very distinctive. In 2014, local jazz pianist and vocalist Carol Jamieson, leader of the function band *Love Shack*, that specialises in soul and funk pop songs and featured Norman Willmore on sax and his partner Jane McLaren on vocals, shared with me tunes that she had written with her friend Debbie Scott, one of which was a fiddle and piano tribute to *Iron Maiden’s The Number of the Beast* (1982). According to Forsyth, Debbie Scott ‘describes her own fiddle style as a ‘mixing of the distinctive old traditional style of Shetland with the contemporary styles from outside Shetland’ (2007:53).⁶⁸ Confusion exists around what exactly constitutes style and how it should be defined – we find various conceptions of personal styles, island styles, country styles, picking and bowing styles, composing and comping styles.

2.10. UP HELLY AA – TENSIONS OF GENDER, HISTORY, and TRADITION

Most Shetland musicians take part in *Up Helly Aa* celebrations, which take place every year from late January to mid March, in various locations. Whalsay, however, stands out as the only relatively populous island that has not generated its own local kind of *Up Helly Aa*. Whalsay people are, nevertheless, consummate masters of the *spree* as a social form, and have also fostered strong rock and roll and metal loyalties. Some of the same *spree*-active Shetland musicians may play in several different *Up Helly Aa* festivals, always for an entire night. As some of the most important annual festivals, all different *Up Helly Aa* festivals involve a great deal of social interaction and music making throughout Shetland, bringing warmth to the coldest winter months. The Lerwick version is distinct mainly because of strict gender roles, as women are not allowed to ‘guize’ in a squad, and must act as hostesses and cooks. The other nine rural festivals ‘offer an opportunity for women to be guizers’ (Murray 2007:46).⁶⁹

There is only one ‘Jarl’ squad focused on the Viking theme, whereas most squads are devoted to current popular themes (i.e., ‘anything goes’), and cross-dressing is common even in the Lerwick version. The stereotype that Shetland’s *Up Helly Aa* festival is a ‘Viking’ celebration held only in Lerwick often affects secondary research. Blaikie (2001:354), in a comparative study about ‘Scottish Islands’, reproduced this notion. Dow (2009:149), without referring to published research, simply stated that the festival ‘draws on Shetland’s Viking heritage’. The Norse iconography is based on a British version of Viking history, ‘an obvious pastiche of the past’ (Brown 1998:26). The working-class originators of this romantic pastiche conceived of it as a creative tongue-in-cheek joke, after ‘tar-barrelling’ was banned in Lerwick (Smith 1993).⁷⁰

Bronwen Cohen (1983:478) argued that the festival ‘was no spontaneous, popular creation, but developed as an orderly and controlled form of celebration that answered the needs of the City Fathers’. For her, this imposition allowed intellectuals to project into the

future their ‘romantic exploration of Shetland’s Norse past’ (Cohen 1983:478). Brian Smith (1993) dismissed Cohen’s (1983) claim by presenting archival evidence, and Brown (1998:42) followed his lead. For Brown (1998:43), Church (1989) mimicked Cohen’s (1983) argument by claiming that an ‘ideological manipulation’ in the ‘late nineteenth century’ created the festival. Smith (1993), however, argued that the festival ‘*was* a spontaneous popular creation in all its phases’ (In Brown 1998:45). For Brown (1998:42), Smith demonstrated ‘the complexity of the origins and transformation of the festival’. Having accumulated ‘an unmatched personal file of notes’, Smith drew on extensive source materials, ‘including fleeting but vital references in local newspapers and criminal-court records’ (Brown 1998:44). For Smith, the festival was an urban movement ‘created and refined by generations of young men’ who were ‘radical in everything except in their relations to women’ (Smith 1993 In Brown 1998:45).⁷¹

In the Delting *Up Helly Aa*, there are at least two squads ‘made up entirely of Lerwick women’ who often wear ‘their husbands’ costumes from the Lerwick festival’ (Murray 2007:46). There is a tension between Lerwick women who accept the gender segregation and wish the festival tradition to ‘continue unchanged’ and those who argue for ‘equality and the right for women to join the precession’ (Murray 2007:47-48). The male-only Lerwick *Up Helly Aa* committee refuses to ‘even enter a dialogue on the subject’ but Equal Opportunities legislation requiring ‘public authorities to promote gender equality and eliminate sex discrimination’ may change this in the future (Murray 2007:48).⁷² Those who challenge the power of the Lerwick committee may fear social sanctions. Helen Robertson, for instance, felt ‘persecuted’ when ‘she challenged her exclusion from the junior festival’ while in school (Murray 2007:43). The junior festival becomes gendered in primary 7, ‘on the eve of puberty’, contradicting the directive of ‘equal opportunities’ in education (Brown 1998:26). Murray (2007:45) found that ‘83% of

teenage boys attending the Anderson High School' in Lerwick 'were against the idea of women's inclusion' in the festival while 'two thirds' of teenage girls in the same school 'did not wish to be hostesses in the future' (Murray 2007:45). Male guizers who attended 'both Lerwick and rural festivals' found that rural festivals were 'more relaxed', and 'more inclusive', and that they had 'much more fun with women in the squad' (Murray 2007:38).

In 2006, a BBC documentary focusing on Lerwick's *Up Helly Aa* suggested there are traditions within traditions. The documentary greatly capitalises on the word 'tradition' as a badge of distinction that seems to exclude the 'contemporary'. Reference to islands as sources of traditional style are used to convey a sense of exoticism and isolation. The documentary claimed that Shetland exports people and culture, but ignores how Shetland has been importing people, culture, and materials for centuries. The BBC (2006) does not even suggest that accordionists and other instrumentalists have their own or are part of the same 'tradition', as this term is reserved for fiddling.

Nevertheless, when the video shows musicians on top of the Viking-styled galley that will be burned at the festival precession, two accordionists are playing with the band. I recognised them as James Leask and Sandy Legget, the former a local and the latter a deeply involved incomer resident. The BBC production does not even identify them, giving fiddlers such as Chris Stout from the band *Fiddler's Bid* the spotlight instead. For the BBC (2006), fiddlers and Viking-clad guizers are the rightful heirs of the Shetland tradition. When the Lerwick brass band is shown accompanying the Jarl Squad precession, the BBC is silent on the question of tradition (i.e., there are no fiddlers). The kilt-clad pipe band appears parading but likewise evokes no comments on tradition. They only discuss tradition in terms of fiddling. They refer to members of the Jarl Squad as 'Viking warriors', but show them visiting elderly homes, hospitals, and singing. The BBC (2006) dedicates a very small segment of the programme to portraying women's traditional

hostess and catering roles. After this, the narrator finally mentions that incorporating ‘outside influences’ is part of Shetland’s tradition, a point that seems inconsistent with the overall emphasis on fiddlers as the bearers of tradition, and the dismissal of accordionists and other instrumentalists and their participation in present traditional practices.

The BBC (2006) documentary simply reproduced the stereotypical vision, in conformance with thin touristic brochures, that local musical traditions are limited to and represented by fiddlers more than others. The ‘notion of fixity is reserved for history’, notes Christina Toren (1988:713). For her, traditions are *not* uniform, static and immutable – they are ‘transformed and transforming’ processes (1988:713). This position echoes the arguments of Handler and Linnekin (1984) and King (2004) and is also sustained by my experiences with the Shetland *spree*.

Grydehøj’s (2011:131) assertion that Shetland’s prevailing identity concept is ‘anti-modern’, ‘anti-Scottish’ and ‘self-consciously informed by Norse romanticism’ is unrealistic. My interactions with local musicians involved with Lerwick and rural *Up Helly Aa* celebrations, arguably the main source of ‘Norse romanticism’, strongly contradict these claims. Musicians invited me to participate in one rural version of the festival as a ‘guizer’. Jonathan Church (1989), an outsider anthropologist, was invited to take part in Lerwick’s Jarl Squad. Grydehøj’s (2011) argument, based on short-term observations during Lerwick’s *Up Helly Aa* is not thoroughly researched. Grydehøj (2011) does not engage with anthropological theory, and ignores most regional ethnographies (e.g., Black 1995, Church 1989, Cohen 1987, Renwanz 1981).⁷³ The 25th Shetland Accordion and Fiddle Festival I attended shared venues, organisers, performers, participants (or audiences) and songs with *Up Helly Aa*. The festival welcomed, hosted and featured many outside musicians and attendees. For the most part, participant hostesses do not perceive the ritual incorporation of gender roles during the night of the Lerwick *Up Helly Aa*

festival as oppressive.⁷⁴ When it comes to Shetland's epistemological tradition of music making, difference is a strength, not the potential for dissolution and degeneration – the local tradition of music making can only be destroyed with the disappearance of lifelong face-to-face interactions and the socio-creative power of interpersonal knowledge.

Shetland musicians, whose experiences are shaped by an extensive local history of mobilities, are constantly on the lookout for musical materials to experiment with and creatively transform. Early in the 'modern history of Shetland (and of the modern world economy), its social organisation was geared to production for external markets' (Smith 1986:43). The surrounding sea must be understood as a pathway to the rest of the world. Shetlanders are not socially, physically or technologically isolated from the rest of the world. Some point to the proverbial anecdote: urbane tourists, who chat with crofters assuming they are isolated, learn, as the conversation progresses, that the supposedly 'isolated' crofters travelled more and farther than themselves.

Francis Collinson's landmark publication, *The Traditional and National Music of Scotland* (1966), reinforces a certain bias against the accordion in favour of the fiddle. Eydmann (1999:595) noted that Collinson (1966) 'rightly devoted considerable space to the fiddle, bagpipe and harp traditions but failed to mention the accordion even once'. Eydmann (1999:595) argued that 'folklorists and commentators on Scottish music' have tended to dismiss the accordion as 'a prop of 'tartanry', part of the kind of 'haggis and heather' music against which the agenda of post-war folk revival is set'. The accordion certainly holds a special place in traditional and popular music making in Scotland but the explanation for its lower status may be due to its appearance in the British Isles of the 1830s, at the 'end of the period commonly regarded as the 'Golden Age' of Scottish fiddle music' (Eydmann 1999:595). The accordion was being taught professionally in Aberdeen in the late 1830s, (Eydmann 1999:596).

Thomas Glen, a music dealer based in Edinburgh, started buying accordions from London in September 1838, and by 1850 he was purchasing over 60 per year (Eydmann 1999:596-597). Although, for Cohen (1987:191), the ‘fiddle is Shetland’s musical instrument’ and ‘the accordion is Scottish’, neither is the fiddle Shetlandic nor is the accordion originally Scottish. Both instruments were invented elsewhere and brought into Shetland from the outside through trading and as travelling gifts, and have been widely welcomed as technologies for music making.⁷⁵ For instance, Campbell (2008) makes the case that the fiddle is more central to Scottish music culture than the accordion. Shetland musicians have included accordions (and other instruments) in their musical practice as a positive creative choice that does not exclude or compete with the fiddle, in a historical process of harmonic and melodic complementarity dating from the first half of the 19th century. Thus, no single instrument is more or less Scottish or Shetlandic. An instrument thus becomes as Shetlandic as those who use them, but at the same time its particular origin, trajectory and performance stories are carefully considered.⁷⁶

We find the notion that accordions and fiddles are antagonistic instead of complementary reproduced in Katherine Campbell’s *The Fiddle in Scottish Culture: Aspects of the Tradition* (2008). In her view, after its arrival in the 19th century, the accordion ‘became a rival to the fiddle since it was capable of greater volume’ and ‘highly suitable’ for playing at dances in ‘large spaces’ (Campbell 2008:153). For her, it was only ‘through adaptations such as the stroh violin – a violin with a horn attached’ and amplified or electric fiddles that ‘the fiddle has been able to compete’ (Campbell 2008:153). However, my experiences in trad sessions in Shetland provide a different picture. Both instruments have been merged in the formation of a number of ‘Accordion and Fiddle’ clubs founded throughout the Shetland isles (see Nolan 1983).⁷⁷ By October 2012, the ‘Fiddle and Accordion Festival’ reached its 25th anniversary, celebrating the synergy

between these instruments throughout Shetland. Not only are accordionists deeply interested in the fiddle music of incomer participants and others, but they are also, most notably, quite able to control the volume of their accordions to meet the volume of other musicians. Shetland-born fiddler Aly Bain and accordionist Phil Cunningham have demonstrated this synergy for decades in Scotland and beyond (see Stevenson 2004).⁷⁸

The only amplified instrument in the weekly traditional music sessions I attended at The Lounge bar every Wednesday since October 3rd 2012 was the electric bass. Not even the acoustic guitarists (arguably of a lower volume than a fiddle) sought amplification for their instruments. It is essential for musicians who seek to join an informal, acoustic jam, to be proficient at controlling the loudness of their instruments. Hence, listening to others is paramount. As a snare player in these sessions, I tuned into what other musicians were doing by watching their movements, listened closely to the music and reflected my attention on my instrument. I breathed with the melodies and let my rhythms respond to the feelings that emerged. I made the point of personally asking one of the accordionists at The Lounge bar jam on October 24th 2012 about volume and playing with fiddles, and whether he controlled it. He told me that if he did not know a song well, he would play very softly, and find his place in the musical space by corresponding his volume to that of other instruments. Also, having recognised him as one of the unnamed accordionists featured on top of the *Up Helly Aa* 'Viking' galley in the BBC (2006) documentary, I asked him what he thought about the tendency in media reports about Shetland to focus on fiddlers and to ignore everything else, to which he responded that he was already used to it.

2.11. TOURISM, BACKWARDNESS, and SCHOLARLY DISTANCE

The popular stereotype that portrays Shetland as the place of ‘fiddle traditions’ and the charge of backward ‘anti-modern’ Norse romanticism (Grydehøj 2011) have undermined and underestimated the history of Shetlanders’ creative engagement with musical and cultural materials, artistic styles and technologies, forming a stereotype that excludes the important dynamics of change, mobility and continuity that are fundamental elements of the local music scene. In one case, the restricted image of the heroic fiddler is an example of a tourism-oriented marketing strategy that promotes romantic images such as Shetland’s supposed isolation, static fiddle tradition, cultural authenticity and the uniqueness of its landscapes, at the expense of diversity and variation (i.e., nuance of character appreciation). Curiously, in order to raise cultural capital to a quantified, averaged out touristic audience (expected to be clueless regarding local history), the current commercial branding strategy invents a generalised, under nuanced version of local tradition – a bland/branded authenticity based on essentialist stereotypes.

The charge of being ‘anti-modern’, on the other hand, seems to be the result of hasty and unbalanced research methods that do no justice to the participant observation standards that Goffman took to the isle of Unst in the late 1940s. This charge reinforces the notion of an isolated people disconnected from the world, whereas locals have always been creatively engaging with sound engineering technologies and multiple instruments from around the world.⁷⁹ There is a tradition of resourcefulness in engagement with technologies that is still alive today, even after its foremost iconic character, Billy Kay, passed away at age 93 before the 2014 Shetland Folk Festival. Billy Kay was known for having built entire telescopes, polishing the mirrors by hand, putting together complicated jazz organs, and collecting and using productively high end recording equipment. People like Stevie Hook, Jonathan Ritch, Adam Priest, Rory Gillies, Fraser Mouat, Brian Nicholson, Kenny

Johnson, Ewen Thomson, Ewan Nowak, Peter Gear, John ‘The Wolf’ Polson, Chris Thomson, Arthur Nicholson, David Hammond, Bryan Peterson and JJ Jamieson are all participants in this line of musicians who foster other advanced technical skills, mediated by their engagement with new technologies and musical materials.

The image of the Shetland fiddler has been undermined and exoticised as a promotional stereotype designed for the tourist market, just as the image of the historically clueless traditionalist Viking has. This development is linked with the rise of commodified models in the cultural industries that started to emerge in the 1980s, leading to the current state of affairs, an image-based approach to tourism that views consumers as reduced statistical entities that should be seduced by generalised, washed out, yet somehow clever and creative marketing. In reality, even with the very clear and dominant presence of the fiddle as an expression of Shetland musical excellence, local fiddlers are far from being locked into convention and a static model of a prescribed traditional repertoire and style, and work across many genres and instrumental combinations. Campbell (2007:1) noticed that ‘one person [she] met’ described a number of residents as ‘cross-over people who were involved not with just one, but several genres of music’. In addition, local recording and live sound engineers, like Stevie Hook and Jonathan Ritch, must adapt their skills to capture and give shape to music of very diverse sonic qualities from a variety of vocalists, acoustic and electric instrumentalists, in different venues. The business of live sound engineering in Shetland requires this flexibility.

Image-management and commercially minded fabrication of a brand is not an important concern of the local epistemological tradition – it is considered irrelevant in contrast with the importance of multidimensional personal character engagement. However, undeniably, local groups have adopted commercial techniques to promote their music, which is apparent in the covers of CDs by younger Shetland artists, many of whom

have since moved away to pursue a professional career. A number of musicians invited to perform at the Shetland Folk Fest may also adopt commercial strategies in order to carve a niche in the market.⁸⁰ This is not necessarily so in the case of local SFF bands, some of which, like the Quintet in 2014, was a collaboration of local musicians who were all involved with other, some with various, musical projects. There was no commercial intent – we were playing music that Jimmy and I just loved, even if the songs, with all melodies and harmonies composed by Tom Jobim, had been commercial successes in the 1960s. We were not selling tickets, we were not making money; we were just coming along for another wonderful Folk Fest ride.

Locally, however, image building and management is about participation and sharing rather than commercial, paid for, contracted marketing. This means that word of mouth and direct experiences build up reputations. This works alongside the tendency to speculate from gossip-based formulations that, as a side effect, generate the basis for the formation of exclusivist cliques and circles while also keeping watch on what others are doing more out of friendly concern than out of malice. Nevertheless, the specific content of tales about others really depends on the personal perspective of the individual who first formulates and gives it momentum. As Besnier (1989:336) notes, while some researchers argue that only insiders can gossip, and that ‘gossip is precisely geared to emphasize the boundary between insiders and outsiders’ (e.g., Gluckman 1963, 1968; Handelman 1973) others ‘choose to view gossip as a self-serving tool’ that some individuals use ‘to further their interests at the expense of others’ (e.g., Cox 1970, Paine 1967, 1968). Shetlanders have pointed out that gossip is both a blessing and a curse – its main function is to keep the community safe from abusers. However, there are those who, not knowing enough about someone, end up ‘making up’ the details ‘to fill up the gaps’. Ultimately, this give and take between experience and invention, projection and concern represents a strategy for keeping

the community safe. As initially unknown people begin taking up character shape and dimensionality by engaging social world and knitting relationships that grow with time, earlier fears about their intentions begin to dissolve, personal-social affiliations grow, and closer friendship circles crystallise and take root. Similarly, locals find that touristic brochures, commercial branding strategies, and hasty scholarship obscure local dynamics.

2.12. TRADITIONS and CULTURES: SPURIOUSLY GENUINE INVENTIONS?

The tension between genuine and spurious traditions reflects an intellectual uneasiness with colonialism and nationalism as deeply interrelated top-down forms of ideological control and identity design. Analyses of the impact of structural violence and colonialism on indigenous peoples contribute to this uneasiness (e.g., Farmer 2004, Ferrari-Nunes 2011). Sapir (1924:411) was among the first anthropologists to draw distinctions between ‘spurious’ and ‘genuine’ culture. He blended a romantic critique of industrialist oppression and an individualist sensibility for the satisfaction of ‘creative and emotional impulses’ (Sapir 1924:411). For him, the ‘great cultural fallacy of industrialism’ was the ‘harnessing of the majority of mankind to its machines’ (Sapir 1924:411). For King, ‘[s]purious models are those which fall into nationalistic traps of essentializing specific traits, or insist in the correspondence of race, language, and culture’ (2009:146). He noted that Sapir’s focus on the community’s spiritual consciousness drew on a ‘Nietzschean understanding of the proper relationship between individual and collective’ (King 2009:146).⁸¹ For Sapir, ‘conformity with tradition’ should be dispensed with, and argued in favour of ‘conformity with the essential nature of one’s personality’ (1924:422). In other words, Sapir was arguing that creative freedom is essential for personal growth.

In folklore studies, Richard Dorson (1950) ‘coined the neologism *fakelore*’ to emphasise the ‘spuriousness of invented tradition’ (Gailey 1989:153). Dorson’s (1950,

1959) ‘fakelore’ referred to ‘the creation of alleged ‘folk’ products’ which popular writers concocted through ‘nonexistent sources’ (Porter 1993:67). For Gailey (1989:154), ‘invented traditions’ gained political prominence ‘in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries’ in association with the ‘rise of nationalism’, providing identity-enforcing ‘symbolic objects and activities’. This point suggests that ‘culture’ and ‘tradition’ are almost interchangeable. Thinking etymologically would lead to ‘culture’ as an ontological growth process and ‘tradition’ as the mechanism for sharing it and passing it along. Customs and practices incorporated by any given tradition cannot simply emerge *ex nihilo*. For Marchand (2007:24), ‘tradition is a state of mind – a recurring nostalgia for an idealised past, or the desire for a utopian future’. Handler and Linnekin (1984:288) argued that the binary ‘genuine or spurious’ is ‘inappropriate when applied to social phenomena, which never exist apart from our interpretations’. For them, since cultures are constantly changing, only the ‘new’ exists, even if it might be valued as traditional (Handler and Linnekin 1984:273). If ‘tradition is always defined in the present, all spurious traditions are genuine’, and ‘if genuine tradition refers to the pristine and immutable heritage of the past, then all genuine traditions are spurious’ (Handler and Linnekin 1984:288). Contemporary traditions are ‘significant practices’ that might be ‘represented as being linked to the past’ but ‘are continually reinvented in the present’ (King 2004:60).

Although the ideological homogenisation project of nationalist traditions may not be spurious, they are still symbolically violent. Their acceptance must be promoted and inculcated through enforced, regimented and structured educational regimes, ideological propaganda, symbolic and ritualistic practices. All around the world, ‘residential schooling has served as a key aspect of nation-state attempts to control and assimilate indigenous populations’ (Bloch 2005:540). As a ‘coercive imposition’, residential schools in Canada sought to erase ‘attachment to [indigenous] identities’ with the full support of the colonial

legal system (Tully 2008:225, 263). More recently, the mass-media and entertainment industries have taken up that role by transforming ideological abuse into pleasure (Bourdieu 1996, 2001).⁸² For Abu-Lughod (1997:110), the ‘hegemonic or ideological – and thus power-related – nature of mass-mediated cultural texts in the service of national, class, or commercial projects is undeniable’. The limited historical perspectives of mass indoctrination naturalise the incontestability of certain traditions. For Hobsbawm (1983:1), nothing seemed ‘more ancient, and linked to an immemorial past, than the pageantry which surrounds the British monarchy in its public ceremonial manifestations.’ The processes through which traditions are promoted, passed on, accepted, resisted, and imposed may be studied ethnographically in a history of power. The survival of traditions depends upon how they are handed down to future generations. Their contestation can lead to collapse, partial or full, and to adaptations. In an epistemological tradition like Shetland’s, a collection of associated ways of being and the principles in which they are founded are shared with younger generations, resident and visiting outsiders as a model. The idea that political, nationalist traditions are invented to homogenise and control populations ideologically has been around for centuries. In the eighteenth century, landlords who sought to justify the unequal laird-tenant relationship as naturally arising from life in ‘an isolated group of islands’ re-wrote and re-interpreted Shetland’s history (Smith 1986:42).

Seeking to distinguish ‘traditional’ from ‘national’ musics in Scotland, Collinson (1966:3) imagined a boundary coinciding ‘roughly with the end of the eighteenth century’. For him, ‘traditional’ music excludes songs ‘written for and disseminated by the printing press and not by oral or aural transmission’ (Collinson 1966:3). Nationalisms, in Scotland and elsewhere, are created through the strategic selection of traditional symbols that are subsequently spread from positions of power. This process harnesses cultural capital and symbolic power for the official ‘State’ and progressively harmonises the population

according to the nationalist orthodoxy.⁸³ Cohen (1996:802) argues that the nation is a ‘grand generalization that does not discriminate among, and says nothing specific about, its individual members’.⁸⁴ Agents with political power canonize symbols selected from existing traditions or invented anew, and spread them through propaganda and other instruments of power (e.g., laws, statutes, definitions). Gordillo (2014:137) notes how the nostalgia of nationalist revivals is ‘essentialist, grand, totalizing’. As we have seen already, there are unresolved tensions between different models of tradition in Shetland’s musical history. The fiddle tradition re-invented by Tom Anderson in the 1970s, as detailed in *Swing* (1991), clashes with the outward looking musical practices of past and current musicians and their epistemological tradition. Anderson’s traditionalism generated stereotypes about Shetland’s music nationally and internationally and excluded from its canon a large sector of musical practitioners, obscuring their mobilities (e.g., in ideas, instruments, and geography), their sense of drive for personal-artistic development, novelty and flexibility of association.⁸⁵

Figure 1: Norman Willmore (left) and Ewan Nowak at the Lerwick Legion during *Nomadia's* EP launch concert, December 7th 2013. Nowak edited, mixed and mastered the EP *Terra Firma* (*Nomadia* 2013a).

2.13. CONTRIBUTIONS to ETHNOMUSICOLOGY and ETHNOGRAPHY

Shuldham-Shaw produced short publications (i.e., 1947, 1949, 1962), and was followed by Peter Cooke (1986) decades later. Both focused exclusively on collecting fiddle music and viewed new technologies negatively. Swing (1991), drawing on materials collected in the late 1970s and early 1980s, only looked at fiddling. Forsyth's (2005) MPhil is not available, and her short article only focused on fiddling (i.e., Forsyth 2007). These works pay little or no attention to the larger social networks of music making in Shetland. Campbell (1997) identified focusing on the diversity of Shetland's musical life as a local and academic priority, but this diversity has never been studied. Conventional ethnographies of Shetland paid little or no attention to musical practices or the mobilities of Shetlanders, and focused on boundary making and the cohesion of identity instead (e.g., Byron 1983, Renwanz 1981, Cohen 1987, Church 1989). My project contributes to this body of knowledge by investigating the diversity of Shetland's musical practices, and by attending to issues of identity politics, development and mobility.

In my pre-fieldwork visit to Shetland in the fall and winter of 2012, many conversations with locals already confirmed that Campbell (1997) was correct, and that attention to the diversity of musical scenes is a local priority. The social life surrounding Shetland's many festivals is largely unexplored. Such events are ideal environments for investigating mobility patterns, intersecting networks of social relationships and collective organisation (see Urry 2007:37, 235, 239). The experiences and memories of past events and festivals are pivotal in the social life of music makers and lovers. Some of the most avid attendees of musical events are not musicians, while most musicians are also involved with other professional and political activities. Social connections between music making, other professions, politics and mobilities have seldom been explored ethnographically in Shetland. Many Shetlanders find that the 'fiddling and knitting', 'backward romantic

Viking’, and ‘sheep and pony’ stereotypes do not reflect Shetland’s far-reaching, creative, and historical engagement with the contemporary world. Resident Shetland musicians are rarely music professionals, and engage with a number of different professions in order to pay their bills, including but not limited to office workers for different branches of the local government, service positions in bars and restaurants, grass cutting, education, commercial fishing, care taking, agricultural quality control, environmental conservation, planning, addiction counselling, joinery, crofting, and more.

This project contributes to an emerging body of ethnographic scholarship on music-scenes and the mobilities of musicians, instruments, technologies and ideas (e.g., Bennett 2004, Beer 2010, Born 2011, Packman 2011, Bates 2012, Cohen 2012, Nóvoa 2012, Tironi 2012). Global flows of people, new communication technologies and the mobilities of local styles can characterise the ‘trans-local quality of a music scene’ (Bennett 2004:23). The musics of mobile devices can represent social histories by capturing the ‘details of everyday movements, connections and mobilities’ (Beer 2010:481). In Shetland, digital recording devices were popular among people of all ages, and were used to record live concerts and sessions, sociomusical *sprees*, for collecting ideas for new songs and tunes. There is a contingent convergence between musical and social formations (Born 2011:385). Cultural politics and ‘socio-professional networking’ are intertwined in the lives of musicians in Bahia, Brazil (Packman 2011:420). Attending to the social life of musical instruments is a rich source of ethnographic information (Bates 2012). Participants’ musical articulations, drawings and maps challenge the notion of fixed boundaries in contemporary landscapes (Cohen 2012).

Touring musicians value and identify strongly with their mobilities (Nóvoa 2012). Shetland musicians also carry their personal knowledge of other places as part of who they are socially. They tend to be well acquainted with the experiences of their associates

around the world. In other words, *where you have been* also contributes to the sense of *who you are* to others. The fluidity, mobility and transience of Santiago's experimental music scene inspire creative ways of presenting ethnographic information (Tironi 2012). The present ethnography links all of these threads, by looking at people flows, communication technologies, mobility and politics of identity, professional and social networks by supporting a 'wider, less text-based' audiovisual methodology that can 'decenter texts as a core unit of analysis' (Faudree 2012:520, 530).

Shetland's living musical tradition is epistemological rather than affixed to a set of aesthetic definitions and reflects people's engagement with their social relationships and the world. In other words, the music comes into being through 'communicative and improvisational events, with real-time emergent properties, involving human and nonhuman agents in the context of pre-existing yet malleable genres and constraints' (Wilf 2014:397). The principles of the living epistemological tradition of Shetland music I have identified are partially shared symbolic associations and often tacit understandings that provide a 'relational framework of conventional contexts' that enable communication and 'are never *absolutely conventionalized*' and do not remain 'identical for all who share them;' rather, they remain 'loose-ended, incompletely shared, in process of change, and may or may not be consciously learned, in the sense of "rules"' (Wagner 1981:37).

Wagner argues that 'the rather tenuous and poorly understood thing that we speak of optimistically as "communication" is only possible to the degree that associations *are* shared' (1981:37). There is a 'vast, continually changing and constantly augmented set of differentiating controls' guiding 'conventionally prescribed tasks', which include 'modes of conduct and personal deportment' (Wagner 1981:66). However, such controls 'are not intended to be "performed" or followed as a "code," *but rather used as the basis of inventive improvisation*' (Wagner 1981:66, original emphases). Such conventional

controls, once well understood, are improvisational frameworks that are elastic and mouldable – an expert can stretch and transcend the limitations of such controls through tricks that involve ‘exaggeration’, ‘mockery or buffoonery’ (Wagner 1981:66). These controls, for Wagner, are therefore ‘themes to be “played upon” and varied, rather in the way that jazz lives in a constant improvisation of its subject matter’ (Wagner 1981:67). Similarly, for de Certeau ‘invention is not unlimited and, like improvisations on the piano or on the guitar, it presupposes the knowledge and the application of codes’, implying therefore ‘*a logic of the operation of actions relative to types of situations*’ (1984:21). He argues that ‘[e]very society always manifests somewhere the formal rules which its practices obey’ (de Certeau 1984:21-22). Those formal rules are hidden in plain sight, ‘already visible’ in ‘the specific *games* of each society: games which as operations are disjunctive, because they produce differentiating events, give rise to spaces where *moves* are proportional to *situations*’ (de Certeau 1984:22, original emphases). In Shetland, the sociomusical *spre* is, for many, both a ritual and a way of living. It is based on an idealised model for human interactions that emerged from the social activities of Shetland musicians. This model sets up the ‘controls’ (Wagner 1981), the logic of ‘formal rules’ (de Certeau 1984) harmonising ‘agents’ experiences’ with ‘constant reinforcement’ expressed by ‘individuals and collectives (in festivals, for example) improvised or programmed (commonplaces, sayings)’ in shared experiences (Bourdieu 1990:58).

The sociomusical *spre*, as an epistemological tradition, follows the logics that its own principles afford. It is almost as if the best features of local music making culture have been condensed into a *modus operandi* and transposed into various manifestations, in public festivals and private homes.⁸⁶ Homes that host *sprees* are open to unknown visitors, as long as well-known friends introduce them. The place of origin or association to a particular Shetland island by birth or family ties have no influence on whether the host will

get along with the introduced person or not. Yet, someone who shares a degree of interpersonal knowledge with the host must make the introduction. Homes that host sociomusical *sprees* challenge the binary of public and private. Various sociomusical *sprees* take place throughout the year, and during Shetland Folk Festival editions, in homes such as WobblyGang and Aitkens, which are shared among many friends, and are part of the sociomusical fabric of life in Shetland.⁸⁷

Figure 2: Producer Tim Matthews setting up microphones on Lewis Murray's drum set during the recording of *North Country Fair's* album *Brandy from a Stranger* (2015), at Aitkens, May 21st, 2013.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY and ETHICS

METHODOLOGY

3.1. BASIC RESEARCH OBJECTIVES and QUESTIONS

The initial purpose of this ethnographic project was to trace and document the personal and musical trajectories (mobilities) and social relations of music-makers in Shetland. The general organising question was ‘how is music-making experienced?’ Understanding the diversity of Shetland’s musical scenes and how they are socially organised was the main research objective. My own music making experience opened many doors, and I became increasingly connected with local musicians, playing jazz live in several occasions, and joining the local band *SpootHawk* as bass player, performing and recording its first album.

Engagement with the social life of musicians and the organisation of local musical festivals and events was an important goal, achieved beyond my initial expectations. I produced, filmed, edited, released and licensed music videos for different local bands, such as *Wind Up Projectiles*, *The Revellers*, *Teevliks*, *North Country Fair*, *Nomadia*, *SpootHawk*, and for singer songwriter Arthur Nicholson. By the end of fieldwork, in April 2014, I had created a 10-minute video that put together bits of performance and interview footage covering about 15 months of music materials in a number of locations.⁸⁸ I also observed closely how rock concerts and festivals were organised, and performed with Jim Quinn and other locals at the 2014 Shetland Folk Festival.

Finally, this project sought to understand how participants engage with technologies of music making such as instruments, written music, recording equipment, audio and video, and architectures (live venues, studios, and other social spaces). These objectives were summarised in the following general questions:

1. Concerning musical trajectories (mobilities) and social relations:

-How and why have individuals learned to play and perform in public?

- Which people directly influenced their musical education and experiences?
- Who have they played with, formally and informally?
- What places (inside and beyond Shetland) have people visited, and played in?

2. Concerning the diversity of musical scenes:

- What different musical genres do people play and listen to?
- Which events have they participated in as audience, organisers and/or performers?
- Which venues have they performed in?

3. Concerning Shetland's musical festivals:

- How are musical festivals organised in Shetland?
- How have people experienced different festivals in the past?
- How important are musical festivals for people?

4. Concerning technologies and architectures:

- Which different instruments do people play?
- What technologies do people use for learning music?
- How do people compose and record music?
- How do different venues help shape people's musical and social experiences?

These questions served as starting points for recorded interviews and informal conversations. However, my involvement in projects such as *Back from Beyond*, and the National Theatre of Scotland's *Ignition*, as stage helper to Stevie Hook and Amanda Pearson at the 2013 Shetland Folk Festival (SFF), live mix video editor at the 2013 Glusstonberry Festival, as musician on the 2014 SFF, and as participant in a number of recordings, gave me personal access to backstage operations, where people could be observed as they carried out their duties.⁸⁹ These questions were valuable entry points. Moreover, direct personal involvement gave me access to knowledge that would not be available had I remained inflexible in relation to the questions proposed in the beginning.

DATA COLLECTION and MANAGEMENT TECHNIQUES

3.2. ETHNOGRAPHIC LOCATIONS: MUSIC MAKING PLACES and MOBILITIES MAP

In preparation for fieldwork, I created an interactive ‘Google Map’ showing public places and venues around Shetland in which participant observation, music events, formal and informal interviews were most likely to take place.⁹⁰ Clicking on place links in the map reveals some contextual information about each place, a sketch of my first personal experiences there, and may contain images and other links. I roughly ordered places according to their distance from 'Home Base,' where I lived from October 2012 until October 2013, when I moved to Aitkens, a place that was constantly teeming with sociomusical activity, and where I resided until October 2014.

Figure 3: Sociomusical Locations Map – The town of Lerwick.

3.3. DATA RECORDING, MANAGEMENT, SHARING and BACKUP

I collected textual, audio, audiovisual, and musical materials for this project. Textual materials include descriptions of personal experiences written on the computer and on paper. Textual notes would become the core source of ethnographic data if digital methods failed. However, information was safely stored and backed up into multiple hard drives, despite the large size of the collection (roughly three terabytes of ethnographic material stretching from January 28th, 2013 until September 24th, 2014). I organised all materials according to the participant(s) and the occasion(s) concerned, noting name, age, gender, occupation, place of residence, musical practices, instruments, bands, groups, associations (family members and places), collection date, time and place. Many photographs (1,996 in total) were posted as Facebook albums for Shetlanders to see and share. Initially, I thought residents would be annoyed if strangers took and posted photos. Yet, most Shetland musicians are glad to have their work valued and documented. I was constantly encouraged, and sometimes even softly pressured, to take photos and post them online. Interviews were recorded in video and audio devices simultaneously to limit the potential for unforeseeable loss of materials. All of this helped to prevent the loss of data.

If participants so desire, raw audiovisual files with their interviews may be extracted from my database and converted into their preferred format. This is available to every participant, and it has been left open. Some requested and received immediately copies of their interviews while others expressed no interest in having them. However, I have and will respond and conform to research participants' requests for access to their interviews. Participants were encouraged to contact me at any time and for any reason. I have kept in touch with participants via email, Facebook and Skype, on and off the field. We also met, whenever necessary and possible, either for follow-up conversation recordings, for adding or removing information, or any other request. I considered emails to be potential sources

of valuable information. Relevant Facebook conversations, posts and status update discussions were also collected. Finally, I have created the website <www.shetlandspree.com> as a central audiovisual supplement to this thesis. There, this ethnography's musical projects and audiovisual media can be organised and accessed.

Figure 4: Project Website – audiovisual materials and supplements.

ETHICS

3.4. ORAL CONSENT PROTOCOL

In order to secure oral consent, I performed a series of actions. Initial conversations with potential participants were based on the contents of the project's Information Sheet: first, I would explain that the information may be used for a doctoral study on current Shetlandic musical practices affiliated with the University of Aberdeen and the departments of Anthropology and Music. I then asked whether they had any other questions. I avoided presenting the information too technically or bureaucratically, allowing for natural conversations to take shape, and promoting a cordial atmosphere.

I noticed quickly that written consent was considered highly inappropriate. The most appropriate forms of communication are face-to-face interactions and personal messages. One standard *ethical* approach to collecting data in the field is to present forms for *informants* to sign. Yet, in communities where people build trust relationships through recurring face-to-face interactions, and regularly run into one another on the street, official documents can inhibit the growth of potential connections. They formalise the relationship between ethnographer and locals in the field, acting as contracts of rupture, taking over the experience as pivotal. Such forms can damage the potential for improvisatory flexibility and the growth of common friendships and memories.

Bringing up the need for signing forms among participants who feel that regulations and bureaucracy are burdens could be a serious ethical mistake, compromising insight on how relationships grow. In other words, among those whose attitudes flow from the '*Sprenciples*' that make up the epistemological tradition of Shetland music making, demanding the signing of official documents may prove that you don't understand their values, and guarantee that you'd be remembered as the person with the contracts, looking to extract information.⁹¹ People would have reasons to leave you alone, or provide cut and

dry, contrived answers to structured questionnaires to be analysed in isolation. I secured informed consent through face-to-face and online interactions, and recorded over forty audiovisual interviews by the end of my fieldwork. Interpersonal knowledge and trust are important among Shetland music scene inhabitants, and official documents are unnecessary obstacles to fostering meaningful relationships. Once residents knew me well personally, they were glad to openly contribute to the ethnography, recognising its significance as a contribution to Shetland's sociomusical history.

Although no anonymous participants gave long interviews, I chose not to identify individuals who might have expressed delicate critical positions. Potential participants were made aware of their editorial control over collected materials, which they may review and modify. The content of this thesis was discussed throughout the writing period with locals directly (through Skype), and shared with those who expressed interest in reading it.

3.5. RESULTS, COPYRIGHT and CONFIDENTIALITY

Collected musical materials will be shared with creative contributors at their request. They co-own copyrights for collaborative compositions that I personally and actively participated in. They may exploit co-owned materials commercially or otherwise in whatever way they wish. No materials, textual or otherwise, shall be submitted for publication in any form without consent from the participants that are identified and featured. Participants will receive updates on reports, presentations, media and publications arising from the fieldwork including them. A number of participants have requested that I keep under my strict editorial control and prevent all access to their interview materials. They have the final word on who else gets to access the raw information, which only myself and those who may assist me professionally have access to in order to work on anthropological questions, presentations and publications that derive from materials I

collected. Anonymised participants were made aware that their identities might be unintentionally revealed by other details in the study.

Participants only took part in formal interviews after confidentiality and potential problems were discussed, research objectives, and the processes of collection, classification, feedback sharing, and transformation of audiovisual information were disclosed. This project remains open to participants' suggestions. The materials that have not been analysed or employed in this dissertation are valuable for future anthropological work. I acted and will continue to act according to reasonable standards of appropriateness and politeness, and to the ethical research standards devised by the University of Aberdeen and the Association of Social Anthropologists of the United Kingdom.

3.6. POLITICAL IMPLICATIONS in SHETLAND, SCOTLAND and the UK

The materials I produce regarding current musical scenes can potentially help to balance the stereotypical views held outside of Shetland (discussed before), which are often propelled by mass-media and recent research efforts based on little or no fieldwork that claimed Shetlanders are 'anti-Scottish' and 'anti-modern' (e.g., Grydehøj 2011). Such claims have proven to be largely unfounded and politically damaging, and the present work provides an overdue corrective. Providing a balance based on extensive fieldwork experiences is positive for Shetland and Scotland, and also contributes to local history. Shetlanders are often well spoken and expressive on political issues, and their opinions are not usually homogeneous and may shift. Economic development issues are usually at the forefront of political debate. My project arrived in Shetland in the middle of controversies regarding funding for the now completed Mareel venue and other development efforts.⁹²

3.7. *PARTIALITY STATEMENT*

The main characters in this ethnography have not been selected because they are the most important people in Shetland music today, but because they have entered in contact with my world, and in some cases our worlds have merged. Therefore, my sample is partial and is not intended to cover the experiences of every active Shetland musician. My research findings make me sceptical of the traditional ethnomusicological framing of and focus on participants as ‘innovators in a tradition’, ‘key figures’, ‘ordinary or typical individuals’, and ‘normally anonymous audiences’ (Ruskin and Rice 2012:304). The ‘vast majority of musical ethnographies’ that Ruskin and Rice surveyed ‘focus on innovators and other key figures who play some important role in their musical culture’ (2012:304).⁹³

My approach sets out from a different standpoint – all individuals have key roles, not because they are innovators, but because they are immersed in the sociomusical scene through various roles: musicians (including DJs), live sound engineers, camera operators, volunteers, recording engineers, composers, arrangers, venue staff members, hall volunteers, audience members, promoters, teachers, riggers, drivers, joiners, shopkeepers, parents, wives, husbands, siblings, cousins, band members and so on. These are some general roles particular individuals can assume even simultaneously in some situations. Ultimately, individuals influence and are influenced by their social networks, and this is also how their persona emerges in the words and actions of others around them. Focusing on a single so-called exceptional individual can obscure the social relationships that make them seem ‘exceptional’ in the first place. Thus, others play a major role in constructing anyone’s social perception. My experiences in Shetland showed me, again and again, that people are as ordinary as unknown, and as exceptional as well known. Thus, my realisations are partial to my experiences as a participant in the Shetland music scene.

3.8. *SPONTANEITY and INVOLVEMENT*

I sought to collect materials that were considered spontaneous rather than contrived and prepared, and thus my interviews were semi-structured or unstructured, open to adapt to the model that the participant in focus would feel more comfortable with. Instead of imposing a designed prescription, my model sought to accommodate the particular characters of participants, and from that place of familiarity and relaxed engagement, wait for their unique trajectories to emerge, and from those speech acts, including mine, to seek for regularities, logical agreements and differences in how symbols of locality, identity, and the *modus operandi* of the music scene were experienced, constructed, and changed with the passage of time. From this grounding on experience, I show how the particular understandings individuals hold, as well as how their positions and roles in the music scene, their social relations and public expressions, are often in harmonic relationship with and reflect the organisational principles of Shetland's living musical tradition and its practices, most particularly the Shetland *spre*.

Ingold finds 'no contradiction' existing 'between participation and observation', and recognises a dependency linking both activities together. He is critical of the 'cut and run' approach to fieldwork data collection and argues for restoring 'knowing to where it belongs, at the heart of being' (Ingold 2013a:6). His intention is to 'refute the division between data collection and theory building that underwrites social science' (Ingold 2013a:6). He finds it 'fundamentally unethical' that apparently many ethnographers disguise 'as social scientists' to enter the worlds of others 'by stealth, feigning invisibility, or under false pretences by claiming we have come to learn from teachers whose words are heeded not for the guidance they have to offer but as evidence of how they think, of their beliefs and attitudes' (2013a:5). There's a 'double bind', claims Ingold, in the attempt to 'do justice to the ethnographic richness and complexity of other cultures' (a relativist

ideal), ‘while simultaneously opening up to radical, speculative inquiry into the potentials of human life’ (Ingold 2013a:6). He points to a couple of stark choices, turning people into ‘unwitting mouthpieces for philosophies of salvation’ or ‘abdicating’ from engaging ‘in critical dialogue’ (Ingold 2013a:6).

I take responsibility for the construction of the theory upon which this thesis is fundamentally based, by forming and disclosing my personal epistemology. This framework rests upon the notion that ways of knowing are shaped by how conceptualisations are creatively joined in logical formulations. These formulations may become submerged through the process Bourdieu (2000:179) and others called ‘naturalization’ or, alternatively, become the focus of critical and reflexive inquiries, which lead to the potential demystification and dissolution of their symbolic power. In other words, one of the ultimate ideals of this epistemology is to undermine naturalised constructions and to understand their limitation and effects. Such intellectual exercise may afford the gradual development of reflexive consciousness regarding personal ways of thinking. Here, Kant’s (1992:268-275) notion of cognitive horizons is analytically useful to conceptualise the growth of our engagement and participation in fieldwork situations.

3.9. CONVIVIALITY: FACE-TO-FACE FLEXIBILITY and FACEBOOK RESEARCH

Shetlanders may use Facebook in ways that contrast with how people in more anonymous, urban contexts generally use the service. People often use Facebook to share memes that become viral, encouraging forms of mediated conviviality. Varis and Blommaert called this ‘the production of a social-structuring level of engagement in loose, temporal and elastic collectives operating in social media environments’ (2014:1). Shetland online collectives grow from face-to-face interactions and might not be as ‘elastic’ as looking at random samples of memes gone viral on the Internet may

indicate. In Shetland, Facebook engagement is an extension of face-to-face conviviality, affording personal and social interconnectedness and intergenerational engagement.

Shetlanders in general and *spree*-committed musicians in particular, share a larger degree of interpersonal and intergenerational knowledge than what seems to be the case with the majority of urban dwellers I know.⁹⁴ Although I believe that high levels of interpersonal knowledge are common to Shetland and to other small communities, I am speaking strictly from the perspective of a section of the local music scene, as represented by my personal friends and acquaintances, all formed through my engagement with musical people there since October 2012. Their social networks are established mostly through face-to-face interactions over long periods of time, which include a large number of ‘all night’ *spree*-style yearly celebrations (e.g., 10 different *Up Helly Aa* fire festivals, various music festivals, gigs, weddings, concerts and parties).

I would warn against using social media environments as a starting point for research, since it can lead to a slanted image of what actually happens on a day-to-day basis. People are far more interesting and nuanced in person than their online profiles suggest, regardless of the convenience associated with processing data from social media sites. Therefore, the conjunction of involvement with social media as a participant, and living in the community is essential, especially if research focuses on musical people and events. Currently, Facebook is a major source of information on events and gigs in Shetland, and almost everyone in the islands seems to have an active profile, which is useful for keeping up with friends already made.

We should keep in mind that there is a strong division affecting Shetland culture and local people recently, namely the impacts of the oil and gas industry, and the influx of disconnected workers from elsewhere with a low level of culturally sensitive education and commitment to local values. In addition, a section of the population remains opposed to the

arts in general – these are usually anonymous commentators on online threads who find public funding for the arts somehow abhorrent. Oil and gas workers, overwhelmingly men, are largely disconnected from the musical community. Although, conceivably, some might choose to stay because of the local music, people and culture, as Stevie Hook and Jimmy Quinn did in the 1970s, that would be more unlikely now than before. This is partly due to how social media involvement takes up time previously available for face-to-face relationships, and because building sociomusical relationships takes a lot of time.

Usually, residency is a prerequisite for forming lasting sociomusical relationships. My success in getting ever more involved and connected was due to my daily full-time commitment to fostering mostly direct, face-to-face relationships, and being open to improvise regarding where I would be and who I would go spend time with, on a daily basis. Eventually, Shetland friends wanted to remain in touch through Facebook, and now I share with them from 100 to 200 ‘common friends’, all met personally, not just added to build up networking connections. If I had been working part time, I would not have developed social relationships to the same extent, and would have missed many opportunities to engage, as I would be watching the clock constantly. Thus, freedom from regimented scheduling afforded a flexibility that allowed me to dedicate most of my time to fostering musical relationships and activities. Gradually, improvisational flexibility attuned me to the tasks and social worlds of various study participants, affording involvement in various events that emerged from the flow of daily activities. This methodology is closely aligned to (and is at least partially inspired by) the Athapaskan way of being that Ridington (1988) describes. As Ridington notes, Athapaskan people value ‘the freedom to live as one chooses, to move when and where one pleases, and to schedule, order, and arrange one’s life as one wishes’ (Savishinsky 1974:80-81 *In* Ridington 1988:104). Athapaskan people view freedom and flexibility as cognates, highlighting their

‘individualism, anti-authoritarianism, and independence’ (Ridington 1988:104). As among Shetland’s music scene inhabitants, ‘a complex and well understood system of interpersonal interdependence’ supports the ‘individualism, flexibility, and autonomy reported for subarctic people’ (Ridington 1988:105). Living with flexibility led me into situations that would be inaccessible through limiting, structured research schedules.

3.10. AUDIOVISUAL SERVICES: PROFESSIONAL AMATEURISM

Discordances between professionalism and amateurship in Shetland are common. Whilst the *spree* and the epistemological tradition promote conviviality and informality in artistic collaborations, survival demands monetary compensation, with or without musical skilled work. Musicians and sound engineers may do professional quality work for a favour or a pittance. Occasionally, for friends, they record, edit, perform, mix, master, and do live sound for no compensation. This is, however, a personal choice. Simultaneously, some are willing to pay, for similar tasks, the same people willing to work for free. Thus, those carrying out those tasks may choose not to charge, and barter could follow. At WobblyGang, for instance, joinery work was once exchanged for recording services.

My productive involvement with different projects led to various outcomes. As favours, I worked on the live video *Means to an End* by *Wind Up Projectiles* (2013b), the photography and cover design for *Nomadia’s Terra Firma* EP (2013a), and their EP launch promo video (2013b). I received a symbolic fee for making Arthur Nicholson’s (2013b) video *Ready to Go*, the photography and cover layout for his album *Sticks & Stones* (2013a).. *North Country Fair’s* (2013) *January Again* video was bartered for SD cards. Arthur and Michael drove me to Whalsay on two different occasions to collect footage. Andy Steven licensed and broadcasted at 60 North the videos *January Again* and *Ready to Go*, along with a modified edit for *The Revellers’* video *Lower the Rope* (2013), originally

produced as part of *Back from Beyond*. 60 North insisted on acquiring broadcasting rights ‘in perpetuity’, but provided a compensation of £400 per video.

Tensions involving skilled work, compensation and volunteering expectations played out in my experiences with *Back from Beyond*. Publicly funded projects force organisers to gather and rely on volunteers while converting their work hours into project funds. The film postproduction work I conducted classified as skilled work rather than volunteering, while the project operated with what was pretty much a shoestring budget. Yet, all audio engineering work was properly compensated and accounted for. The expertise involved time consuming and detailed work on a par with film editing. Noticing this unintentional miscalculation, Jonathan Ritch, who recorded, edited, mixed and mastered most *Back from Beyond* materials, told me that there should be compensation for my work, and also room in the budget for that purpose. I consulted with over a dozen personal friends, and the consensus was reached that the work deserved compensation. BFB organisers managed to rectify their miscalculation. This never happened with *Ignition*, which never compensated local musical performers.

The Revellers decided to compensate me from their own pockets and on their own accord. They saw the value and appreciated the work that went into their video, and the quality of the results. They also knew that I was experiencing financial issues, with no funding for my research. On September 13th 2013, I ran into Magnus Bradley, from *The Revellers*, as I was walking out of Mareel late in the afternoon. He confirmed that I received no compensation for my videos, and told me, ‘if you put something together, we [*The Revellers*] will get you something’. Sometimes I edited at Mareel’s mezzanine. Erik Peterson, also from *The Revellers*, often approached me there to chat while I worked. By previewing my work, he appreciated the technical and detailed nature of meticulous video

editing. Non-experts usually take for granted the oft-invisible sound and video engineering work. They rarely wonder about the creative process and enjoy the final product instead.

As this story took wings as gossip, the tension between an amateur-based, community-oriented romanticism and professionalism embellished it. Soon, one version cast me as a mercenary ransoming the videos. Project organisers knew better, but gossipers peripheral to the story spiced it, adding that an exploitative foreigner was making outrageous demands. This echoed an earlier rumour, from 2012, which caricatured me as an illegal immigrant running away from personal issues, an image that conformed to a stereotype of newcomers. I experienced a range of responses to my presence, from close scrutiny and familiar closeness, to distanced distortion. Eventually, friends intercept and correct the caricatures of gossipers, dissolving them as quickly as they were spread.

CHAPTER 4: The *SPREE* as EPISTEMOLOGICAL TRADITION and SOCIOMUSICAL PRACTICE

4.1. INTRODUCTION: the SPREE and the SHETLAND FOLK FEST

The Shetland *spree* is a social form, the central expression of the epistemological tradition of music making. The Shetland *spree* is wholly integrated into the sociomusical network of Shetland and its active music scene. As one of the most important forms of socialisation among local musicians, the *spree* is also the preferred method for hosting and socialising with visiting musicians. The *spree* refers, more generally, to a whole night with friends, making and listening to music together and talking about life. *Spreeing* for ‘successive nights’ on ‘major festive occasions’ allows the ‘*spreers* to revisit numerous landmarks of their social lives so that they are not forced into arbitrary choices of destination’ (Cohen 1985:313). In the summer months, when the sun barely comes down and then readily comes up, it will be day already and *spreers* continue as if half an hour, not several hours, elapsed. Sociomusical *sprees* can include moments of listening to records and dancing, but the main focus is on staying up all night making music together.

The Shetland Folk Fest (SFF) promises and delivers many *sprees* every year. The Islesburgh Centre becomes the SFF club, where everyone can mingle, experience and play music together until around four in the morning. A proper Folk Fest *spree* does not end at this time – it continues through insider all-night jams and mingling sessions that stretch beyond breakfast time and often into the next afternoon for the most experienced *spreers*. Sociomusical *sprees*, highly attuned to the principles of the epistemological tradition of Shetland music, are ritually reproduced multiple times every year during the Shetland Folk Festival. Tickets are sold out quickly to a predominantly local, enthusiastic audience. Unsurprisingly, therefore, the *spree* is a central concept in the announcement published on February 4th 2014, at the Visit Shetland website – self-titled ‘The Official Site for Shetland Tourism’ – in a press release disclosing the year’s Folk Fest line up:

Announcing 16 eclectic visiting bands representing genres from traditional folk to gypsy jazz to gospel as well as nearly 50 diverse local bands, organisers hope there will be something to whet everyone's appetite when the island's four day *spree* of fabulous music, sessions and sleep deprivation gets underway on the 1st Mat. With all the visiting acts booked by Davie Henderson, who passed away suddenly in the middle of January, the 34th festival will be in his honour.

Local promoter, journalist and music supporter Davie Gardner wrote on Davie Henderson's Facebook page on the night after Henderson's untimely and unexpected death. He referred to Henderson as 'the most prominent member' of the Shetland Folk Festival committee, and noted, 'I don't deny we had many a *spree*'. Gardner looked forward to 'the *spree* it always wis', like the 'countless *sprees* we got inveigled with'. Both are very well known non-musician *spree* participants, facilitators of music in the community, people who connect locals to musicians outside Shetland.

The first album of the Fetlar *spree* organiser, Maurice Henderson's former band *Fullsceilidh Spelemannslag* is called '*Spreefix*', again pointing to the importance of *spree* practices and how they characterise the music. The *spree* can 'fix', implying that a '*spreefix*' is needed to set one right. This grammatical wordplay, adopting the function of the prefix for the *spree*, makes it the substance of the fixing that the music represents. The '*spreefix*' becomes a cure, remedy and tonic, and also a semantic classifier, a standard of quality linked to the creative process that the *spree* implies. On November 24th 2014, Maurice posted the following status update on his Facebook page:

Back today from a great weekend *spree!* in Kleiveland, Osterøy with some of the Haltadans crew. Great hospitality at the Kleiveland's, superb music sessions, concert, workshops, parties and grub. Fine to catch up with many of our good Norskie friends and make some new ones. Hope to see some of them over in the new year for a Shetland *spree!* We flew back with the new Bergen Air flight this morning. Just over an hour from Bergen to Sumburgh, I recommend it, very handy! Flying Thursday and Mondays.

Martha Thomson, referring to local jazz colleagues Hayden and Max who were away at university, wrote to me on February 3rd 2014, ‘Can’t wait till the boys come down for a *spree*’, referring to an upcoming sociomusical night. Joe Watt wrote a script for Lewis Murray to speak in the promotional video we produced for *Nomadia* (2013b), spinning the *spree* as a promotional device in an instrumental rock context:

Hi, I am Lewis Murray from the band *Nomadia*. We’ve just finished recording our debut EP and we’re going to launch it into the stratosphere on December 6th at the Lerwick Legion. Whether you’re young or old, fat, thin, tall, short or a miniature interstellar space marine planning the destruction of and desecration of mankind, let along for some pumpin’ instrumental rock, drams and a good old *spree*.

The rhetorical strategy here touches upon some Shetland themes, such as eclecticism, the dramatic-comic use of hyperbole, slang, the modern space age consciousness of rock and roll and the traditional pull of the ‘good old *spree*’. In all these examples, we see the centrality of the notion of *spree*, from write-ups about the SFF to memorable moments with loved ones, always in association with sociomusical contexts.

4.2. *SPREE INTEGRATION*

Bypassing the less involved commercial model of professional music, SFF visiting artists must take the 12-hour ferry ride into Shetland. This, according to Stevie Hook, makes visiting musicians understand better the distance that separates Shetland from the mainland, the sense of distance, and encourages them to mingle with other musicians, since they have nowhere to run to. A plane ride could get someone in and out of Shetland overnight or even on the same day, whereas that would be impossible on the ferry. SFF visiting artists are suddenly ‘stuck’ in Shetland, and have to make the best out of it. Since the whole place is infused with a musical spirit, mingling through the music becomes easy, and the sessions start getting hotter on the Saturday night. The crescendo of sociomusical

interactions, night after night, provides a host of opportunities for getting to know people musically and for *sprees* to emerge.

The bus and ferry rides, from Lerwick to country halls and back, are full-on sociomusical *sprees* and are enjoyed thoroughly by participants. After the performance at the country hall, return trip bus *sprees* are unparalleled events of collective enjoyment and freedom – people enjoy multiple conversations and even simultaneous jams in different parts of the bus. People are singing songs, conversing, sharing drink, playing and listening to tunes all the way back to Islesburgh Centre. Buses may return from various country halls in close succession, intensifying the party vibe at the ‘festival club’, where multiple jam sessions are occurring simultaneously and serious session connoisseurs gather to play music and mingle socially until closing time.⁹⁵ Islesburgh closes (or people are asked to leave) with the sun already coming out, and *spreers* seek a place to play until breakfast time, when they usually head to the Harbour Café for a meal – that is the ‘way it’s done’.

During the 2013 SFF, Aitkens hosted ‘Cajun’ Louisiana singer and fiddler Cedric Watson and washboard player Desiree Champagne, who played along with many locals, an occasion that Arthur Nicholson recorded on his mobile phone. On another night in 2013, Desiree ended up at DJ Lyall Halcrow’s flat, playing along with Marjolein’s freestyle Shetlandized rap, with Hayden, David Noblett, Cara McDiarmid and others.

In 2014, one *spree* brought together many experienced local musicians into an unforgettable night. A sociomusical *spree* manifested at Aitkens soon after the 2014 SFF Final Fling, starting at around 5:30 in the morning.⁹⁶ Aitkens was then operating as the *spree* central, as it has done for years. After the jazz guys went back to WobblyGang to sleep, after 5am, Maurice Henderson, Bryan Gear, Kevin Henderson, Lewie and Erik Peterson, Kris Drever, John-William Halcrow, Jacky Clark and others started coming up the stairs – they had been playing all night already at Islesburgh, which had just closed.

The whole atmosphere got immediately reenergised and music flowed for hours until the call was made to move the session to the Harbour Café for breakfast. An intense sociomusical *spree* erupted, with a multitude of people who knew each other very well for many years sharing the same space in full appreciation of what was happening and who was present. Similarly to what Geertz (1973:424) observed elsewhere, here too ‘a set of persons engrossed in a common flow of activity and relating to one another in terms of that flow’ formed what Goffman (1961:9-10) called a ‘focused gathering’. Csikszentmihalyi’s ‘flow’ is a ‘theory of optimal experience’, a state of engagement in which ‘nothing else seems to matter’ (1990:4). The flow affords an experience that ‘is so enjoyable that people will do it even at great cost, for the sheer sake of doing it’ (Csikszentmihalyi 1990:4). He argues that music ‘helps organize the mind that attends to it’, reducing ‘psychic entropy, or the disorder we experience when random information interferes with [our] goals’ (Csikszentmihalyi 1990:109). Similarly, Shetland *spree* participants know that the purpose of the *spree* is playing together all night, unconcerned about time. Banjo player and *spreer* Lewie Peterson explained his position on May 18th 2013,

The social aspect of playing, that’s the main reason why most of us probably do it, to be honest. There’s only so much satisfaction that you get from the actual playing. It’s more the networking that can happen after, it’s the fact you can bond with people over it, and the fact that it starts conversations, that’s probably the main reason why I do it.

Lively conversations sprinkle everywhere, a few *spreers* collapse into cosy naps, perhaps still holding fast to a can of drink, while the high-energy music keeps pulsing away in the background, like a lullaby for weary *spreers*, rocking the walls of the old town jail (i.e., Aitkens), now converted into a hurricane of vibrant and ecstatic creativity. After a few hours, everyone descended into the Harbour Café – it was taken over by musicians and other SFF participants, including members of the committee. 2014 was a very important and emotional year for many there, because, for some, it would be the first time that they

would be at the Harbour Café, during and after Folk Fest, without Davie Henderson – his passing was unexpected, and it hit the music scene like a doomsday earthquake. When I arrived home on the day that news from his death began circulating, Michael was grieving – nothing else mattered – it was time to remember the good times he had with his friend, and with so many others, over decades of *spreeing*; it was time for reflection, for crying, for laughter, and for toasts on the name of another irreplaceable, unforgettable character whose place left a massive hole that could never be refilled. The poor cook at the Harbour was, again (as in previous years), completely overloaded, sweating hard to get all the breakfasts prepared. As the staff called the breakfast numbers, the whole crowd gathering inside would cheer and ask for speeches from the lucky ones who were about to eat, and as soon as they started speaking, the crowd would roar again, muffling the speech with noise.

Following the breakfast at the Harbour Café, some of the most serious SFF *sprees* participants return to a home session, and some even continue playing all day at the Lounge. After some rest, the cycle restarts on the next night at Islesburgh, until Monday night, when the Final Fling takes place – a night reserved for musicians, volunteers, and production crewmembers. Performances and sessions occur simultaneously again, and the *sprees* continue as usual into past breakfast time. The overnight element of the *sprees* is fundamental, providing a ritual clock for a transformation, a feat of endurance that makes time disappear, something unforgettable that leads to personal growth and reflection.

The freedom to experiment and the potential for mingling through chance encounters can lead to unpredictable and unexpected musical outcomes. The open-minded sociomusical ambience invites participation and sharing of one's own music with appreciative listeners. *Spreeing* is also a platform for learning, enjoying, and talking about new materials. The audience is constantly shifting and moving around, from one jam room to another, and people are not expected to be quiet when musicians are playing. In fact,

locals often make their way through several drinks, and if they decide to be loud – which is often meant to accompany humour – others, even if annoyed, will just let them be.

Furthermore, there is no conservatism regarding repertoire or instrumentation, as every instrument available is just as valuable. If someone's playing makes somebody else uncomfortable, it is part of the learning experience that the situation is flexible enough to accommodate. Ideally, there is no hurry and no need to show off or impress anyone. The point is simply to let the music happen. As some join in, others take breaks and engage in conversations. Someone may doodle something on an instrument alone while others may talk about and listen to music. Somebody may choose to follow along with what is playing through the stereo. That may be stopped when someone feels like sharing a tune. Others will listen when the tune is played, but some may continue their conversations or move into another area. People circulate in an improvised fashion, navigating face-to-face situations, or settling into an involved conversation. With some people, like Joe Watt, it was easier to jam. We jammed in free and improvised ways often at WobblyGang or at Aitkens, often with Hayden Hook and Norman Willmore, whenever we could. We shared life stories, played, listened to, and talked about various musics, allowing musical ideas to emerge spontaneously, invented, recycled, and rearranged. There were other countless jams involving various *spreers*, including characters featured in this ethnography, such as Maurice Henderson, Michael Williamson, Arthur Nicholson, and Ewan Nowak.

4.3. *DEALING with DISCORDANT CHARACTERS*

Very much like in Indian Classical music, the presence of discordant characters can spoil the mood for a proper *spree* (Khan 2005).⁹⁷ Full social integration is paramount. Discordant characters are not welcome and their access is curtailed when they break the unwritten rules of conviviality, sometimes immediately. I have witnessed the expulsion of such discordant characters from sociomusical *sprees* in different occasions, after they spoiled the overall positive feeling colouring all interactions. Hangers-on looking for a party would often follow us back to Aitkens after a gig. Word about ‘after parties’ can spread rapidly during gigs, gathering momentum, and potentially leading into very crowded situations. For this reason, sometimes the host would ask guests not to bring back too many hangers-on after a gig. ‘After-parties’ rarely became sociomusical *sprees*, with musicians playing all night – they were often simply house parties, with people mingling and dancing to various forms of recorded music instead of making music together.

Aitkens, however, the Lerwick home where I resided for a year, operated as a *spree* temple for insiders. An ‘open door policy’ for weekends and special occasions was common, and unfamiliar characters would sometimes join the session. Michael told me that so many people were around that only after ten years after he bought the house that he finally had a day by himself in it. One night, a heavysset man followed one of our female friends over. He was a local, but not someone directly involved in music circles. After a few drinks and some time, she was dancing on her own and ‘letting go’ as we sat around the coffee table and chatted. The unknown man gets up and starts moving quite close to her in a suggestive way. After she moves away from him, he sits next to Michael, the session host, and whispers something indecent in his ear about her, as if Michael should automatically find it amusing. Michael did not snap, he just informed him ‘this is my friend you’re talking about – you’re not welcome here, I think it’s time for you to leave’,

immediately escorting this ‘element’ out of the party. Disrespect of this kind is intolerable and, of course, very rare, considering how many sessions do take place. In most cases, *spreers* and serious session devotees are well acquainted with one another.

Sometimes visiting band members abuse local hospitality – a heavy metal band from the ‘south’ came up to Shetland with maddened fans. They loudly demanded an encore at the Legion, while locals scratched their heads! So that all bands may play, a very tight schedule must be followed. If one band abuses their time slot, others will not get a chance to perform. And yet, at that night in the Legion, complete strangers who followed their ‘favourite band’ on the boat up to Shetland, believing they are following the best band in the planet, and ignoring completely the locals and their ways, insist on an encore by screaming and chanting together while the other bands and sound engineers sigh and wonder, ‘when will they realise it’s time to shut up?’ and ‘why are they doing this anyway?’ Even visiting artists who perform at the SFF may not get access to a local *spre* unless they fit in with the rules of operation and engage socially on a personal level with people – if they are stand-offish or think they are too good for everyone else, they will stay alone. Some artists, on account of a typical pride and sense of superiority, end up not getting involved – hubris keeps them isolated. What I call the superlative syndrome is particularly common among musicians anywhere, but relatively rare in Shetland.

4.4. *SPREE as SUPPORT NETWORK*

Once my circle of friendships began broadening, it was clear that some people interacted better and had more to talk about with certain people and avoided others. The different ways of seeing the world that each person espoused seemed to contain the answers for how their various relatively harmonic and discordant relationships, panned out in practice. Despite an overall systemic tendency for discordance, some chose their friends according to affinity – harmonic epistemological resonance.⁹⁸ Currently, the neoliberal mode of production provides most of the discordant and parasitical, systemic epistemological background that affects everyone (see Ganti 2014, Wilf 2014), through commercialism in art, governmental regulations and the energy industry. In the 19th century, systemic constrictions came in the form of laird colonialism, eliciting creative local responses (e.g., Goffman 1956:25), and in the centuries before that, various conflicts are recorded associated with commercialist competition for local resources (Smith 1977).⁹⁹ Individuals who are more interested in supporting rather than competing foster long-term relationships that are harmonised with the principles of the epistemological tradition of Shetland music, providing a counter-current to the reigning commercial rationality. Seasoned *spreers* are very supportive – a characteristic that outside musicians who become involved with the local music scene quickly notice.

For instance, fiddler and artist Gemma Graham, a participant in the 2014 Fetlar *spree* who moved to Shetland in the fall of 2013, reports a ‘feeling of togetherness’ and a ‘feeling of being supported’ in Shetland’s music scene. This feeling of cooperation, support and trust takes shape over long years of sustained, harmonised interactions among long-time friends that are all together responsible for keeping the whole framework alive. This allows for the transmission of the epistemological tradition. People like Stevie Hook and Michael Williamson, like many other Shetland residents, continuously infuse the

music scene with vitality by hosting visiting musicians at home, sociomusical *sprees*, rehearsals, recordings, dinners, listening sessions, and enabling the potential for creative, spontaneous encounters to emerge and for interpersonal knowledge relations to be established, cultivated, maintained, growing in dimension.

4.5. *STYLISTIC INDEPENDENCE and EPISTEMOLOGICAL RESILIENCE*

Shetland's epistemological tradition of music making, and its most characteristic collective expression – the Shetland *sprees* – certainly do not depend on an institutionalised style of music to survive, such as traditional folk, country, gypsy jazz. This is because it is designed to work with any particular musical style that *spreers* as individual characters bring to the table, through a principled style of acting, learning, and knowing – what I see as a triadic relationship: *modus essendi* (style of being), *modus discendi* (style of learning), and *modus agendi* (style of acting), which can be included in a conception of a *modus operandi* (way of operating). The *modus* denotes both a way and a style – for thinking, acting, being, learning, and knowing – and humans and other animals manifest incorporated style. Experienced *spreers* express and are known for their own particular style, and usually act according to personal principles that are in harmonic epistemological relationship with the principles governing *sprees* interactions.

Shetland's epistemological tradition of music making is concerned with the transmission of values, especially those I have identified as the principles of social horizontality, interpersonal knowledge, intergenerational engagement, nuance of character appreciation, and openness to musical diversity. The conceptual framework of symbolic boundaries, although grounded on observations, represents a particular interpretation of social reality that remains incomplete and fails to account for the phenomena I have observed and experienced. Cohen's (1987) personal involvement with the yearly

sociomusical calendar and local festivals was periodical. Cohen's conceptual framework choice is attuned to historical and stylistic trends within anthropology. In Shetland, music making is more important to locals than any reading of Cohen (1987) suggests.

The awkwardness that Cohen's boundary-centred theoretical focus can cause in the current wave of mobility studies – what Büscher and Urry call the 'mobilities turn' (2009:99) – should not prevent us from finding value in its insights, and coming up with new ways of translating them into a more current ethnographic perspective.¹⁰⁰ There are certain epistemological differences between socially engaged Shetland musicians and visitors, but there are plenty of visitors who, almost seamlessly, become deeply involved with the local sociomusical world, making it their home and destiny, acting as if they were always meant to fit in. I was accepted and welcomed as an equal in an insider sociomusical environment in which Whalsay was tremendously important symbolically, representing cohesion and dissolution, change and stability.

Cohen (1985) recognised the cultural centrality of what he also called the *spree*, a 'matter of life' in Whalsay. *Sprees* are also just as important as funerals in people's lives in Cohen's Whalsay.¹⁰¹ For him, 'the *spree* and the funeral practice are symbolic statements of forms of organisation and solidarity which have been undermined empirically by the exigencies of modern economics and technology' (Cohen 1985:310). For Cohen, the *spree* and the funeral transformed and appropriated social change as part of Whalsay (1985:309). As social practices, the *spree* and the funeral illustrate the 'ways in which boundary-conscious members of communities 'manage' culturally insidious incursions of the outside world' by 'incorporating them and harnessing them to the task of intra-communal discourse' (1985:310). For Cohen, these forms have 'symbolic and affective' primacy and reflect 'the influence of social change' that makes them relevant and necessary (1985:320). Cohen argues that 'the organisation of both *spree* and funeral suggests that the resilience of

customary forms in circumstances which have diminished their structural significance is more than the expression of mere traditionalism' (1985:320). The *spree* encapsulates a knowledge system, designed, through historical sociomusical processes, into an ideal model for experiencing and transforming a diversity of cultural and musical materials. The *spree* retains a distinctive consistency as a model for interaction with diverse sociomusical worlds. As *spreers* experience and learn about social change and cultural difference, they reflect on local principles and interpret their impressions dialogically. Their discussions often focus on socioeconomic and political changes and their effects on living realities, making them relevant in personal, social and local levels.

Although Cohen (1985) does not quote local characters and their actual words directly, their meanings and interactions are summarised in a valid structural analysis. However, there is more to the sociomusical *spree* than we can infer from Cohen's Whalsay version (1985). As an ethnographer who lived for two years in Shetland, one year in the house of a Whalsay fishermen in Lerwick, and who participated in countless sociomusical *sprees*, Cohen (1985) provides a satisfactory level of independent confirmation to the centrality of the *spree* beyond Whalsay, supporting the notion that sociomusical *sprees* safeguard and keep Shetland's epistemological tradition alive. I have encountered the resilience of the sociomusical *spree* in Shetland's traditional epistemological principles, shared across various generations, and potentially enabling locals to transcend dependence on deterministic sets of aesthetic and stylistic motifs.

Cohen (1985:309) argued that imported 'alien structural forms' may 'threaten to displace the existing structural bases of the boundary' through modernisation.¹⁰² For him, subjection to 'substantial change' blurs 'the former edges' of community boundaries manifesting the need to have those lines 'redrawn' (Cohen 1985:321). Consequently, these symbolic boundaries become 'recourses of the expression of indigenous symbolism' and

the ‘re-statement or re-assertion of the boundary’ (Cohen 1985:309). In this way, the *spree* and the funeral are ‘media of symbolic marking’ (Cohen 1985:310). Cohen’s (1985, 1987) discussions emerge from a pivotal moment in the history of anthropological theory, when tensions regarding the validity of authoritative accounts were brewing. After Clifford and Marcus (1986) stormed the field with the ‘crisis of representation’ (Ingold 2014:385) ethnographers began reflecting critically on their own cultural and epistemological assumptions, finally realising that anthropological and scientific interpretations are not neutral. This led to ‘the incorporation of transdisciplinary approaches’, such as ‘feminism, deconstruction, film and media studies, new historicism, science and technology studies, cyborg anthropology’ and more (Fischer 2007:29). Epistemological critiques developed over the last 30 years (e.g., Marcus and Fischer 1999) regenerated a form of dialogue and collaboration whose roots go back to James A. Teit’s work. This movement renewed anthropological interest on how symbolic ‘social boundaries’ are transgressed, fluid, changing, and may undermine ‘former structural bases of boundary’ (Cohen 1985:307). The efficacy of this boundary ‘depends upon the outside world being unable either to recognize the boundary at all or to recognize it in terms in which it is defined by those *inside*’ (Cohen 1985:309). Yet, the resilience of *spree* forms does not ‘confront the threat of the new, the ‘outside’, in order to neutralise it (Cohen 1985:310). Instead, by incorporating novelty, the *spree* becomes more resilient. In other words, the *spree* and the funeral ‘reincarnate and exploit these apparent customary forms in new ways and for new purposes’ (Cohen 1985:310). This happens because the principles of the epistemological tradition – fundamentally ethical, moral and internally incontestable – survive independently of whether a particularly dominant and aesthetically defined expressive style thrives or deteriorates. Therefore, the epistemological tradition provides the ideal form (i.e., *spree*) and ethical framework (i.e., its principles) while individuals express their

own personal creative and musical qualities. Indeed, a shared vocabulary of musical styles and genres provides a platform for talking about music with friends and making sense of ways of playing and listening, *not* for policing others according to exclusivist formulations that promote traditionalist purism and aesthetic essentialism. Yet, while some people believe that tradition implies something narrow, static and already predefined, Shetland's epistemological tradition promotes experimentation and constant broadening of knowledge horizons and musical repertoires into self-determined personal directions.

A focus on boundary making and static, canonical traditions over-emphasises social segmentation, obscuring how Shetlanders, especially musicians, have always looked outward as well as inward for inspiration, new musical materials, experiences, stories, characters and technologies, and also for extending existing social relationships. Symbolic boundaries contradict Shetland musicians' constant engagement with novel materials and people – productive relationships that the Shetland Folk Festival encourages with an atmosphere of freedom and community. The potential for what jazz lovers call the 'sound of surprise' is always brewing in Shetland. Valuing novelty and experimentation is a feature of Shetland's epistemological tradition of music making and of the characters that have come to best represent it symbolically, like Peerie Willie, Ronnie Cooper, Tom Anderson and Billy Kay, whose experimental generation help fashion the current epistemological tradition, ritually and annually reproduced in the Shetland Folk Festival.

4.6. *CHARACTER APPRECIATION and the SPREE: ANARCHIC HORIZONTALITY*

In Cohen's analysis, the *spree* enables Whalsay people 'to experience a cultural continuity between past and present' through a reciprocity based 'co-operation' that is different from 'modern corporate' type of thinking that asserts a 'dependence on outside financial agencies' (Cohen 1985:314). This 'sociable reciprocity' that the *spree* kindles, for Cohen, encourages 'self-sufficiency and mutual interdependency' (1985:314). Most importantly, highlighting its anarchistic and horizontalizing resonance, the '*spree* has no economic value for its participants' (Cohen 1985:314). My experiences with the National Theatre of Scotland 'community theatre' and *Back from Beyond* (detailed in Chapter 5) show that people from 'the outside world' often act according to distorted expectations about Shetlanders and inflated assumptions about themselves. They project ignorance about the ways of small communities with their attitudes about themselves.¹⁰³

Cohen noticed that 'lurking beneath the inebriated hilarity of the *spree* is often a summation of one's social history and an expression of the ethos of belonging' (1985:313).¹⁰⁴ The ability to generate meaningful humour in conversations reflects the level of interpersonal knowledge enjoyed in a given situation. Interlocutors draw on their interpersonal familiarity, evoking shared experiences as stories – springboards for generating discourse they know will have a humorous social impact. The emergence of humour in convivial situations can lead into long discursive tangents and monologues, with nested narratives and storylines that transport interlocutors further away from the original subject, which may never be recovered in such an improvisational flow.

For Gemma Graham, 'you do have to have a bit more of a sense of humour here' and 'laugh things off a bit more' – 'I don't know', she tells me, 'if being in the city [makes] you take things more seriously, but I try and not take life so seriously'. Humour expresses interpersonal knowledge and familiarity as an endless string of local gigs, concerts by

visiting artists, house parties, and creative collaborations strengthen meaningful interpersonal connections. Cohen found the symbolic significance of the *spree* in its ‘egalitarian and reciprocal process’ and ‘composition’ (1985:314). He explains,

The importance of a *spree* used to be recognised by the ready willingness of a host or hostess to rise from their beds and admit late callers. In more recent years, the regular Saturday night *spreeing* of the younger people has come to be regarded as something of a nuisance, and so a simple signalling device of leaving on the outside light informs callers whether or not they will be admitted. But on the major occasions, most people are anxious to have visitors; and, at the end of a dance, there will be some competition about whose house the company should return to (Cohen 1985:313-314).

The present research shows that the significance of the Shetland *spree* includes a conjunction of symbolic, experiential and practical elements that frame how one acquires social and interpersonal knowledge. Moreover, the framework of symbolic boundaries is contradicted in musical practice, despite the fact that, especially for Whalsay people, dialect and accent – language based signifiers – are central to their sense of being Whalsay. For instance, Michael Williamson speaks strictly in the Whalsay dialect (unless he is making an impression) but only writes lyrics and sings in English, and will never sing in dialect, unlike many other Shetlanders who sing and write in dialect. Yet, he remains deeply connected and devoted to Whalsay and his family there, whom he visits often. Thus, Michael defines his musical genealogy through non-Shetland elements but strictly through his version of the dialect, which he speaks but does not sing.¹⁰⁵

The principle of openness to novel musical materials and instruments, regardless of whether they are from current artists or discovered through historical research, encourages the appreciation of various musical expressions and characters, from the novice and amateurish to the extremely skilled and virtuosic. Furthermore, through sociomusical hubs like Aitkens and the WobblyGang (i.e., homes and studios dedicated to social and musical activities), collaborations and friendships can emerge from the flow of personal relations.

In these places, musicians learn from one another, they share and appreciate together musics that excite them; and, with instruments close at hand, the night may turn into a spontaneous *spree*, depending on who shows up and the mood of the hosts.

In July of 2013, the *Back from Beyond* trip to Hermaness in Unst with *The Revellers* happened during Unst Fest and evolved into an all night *spree* and a musical session that was cut short by a pub manager from Glasgow who did not appreciate music, an attitude that caught some of our *spreers* by surprise. It was an odd contrast with The Lounge in Lerwick, where Derek Hendry, an experienced piano player, is the manager. At that time in Unst, we found someone who was in charge of a bar, but who, instead of joining the music, actually told us to leave, which greatly annoyed the *spreers* – with a local in charge, that would never have happened. In July of 2014, the North Atlantic Sessions event took place in Fetlar with the explicit objective of having an all-night sociomusical *spree*.

4.7. *EXPERIMENTING with STYLE: PERSONAL COMPLEMENTATION*

Starting in the 1940s, Peerie Willie and Billy Kay's love for jazz and traditional music led to the invention and the local popularisation of a new musical style, adding to the already existing eclectic repertoire – an amalgamation of various styles, genres, traditions, and everything that found its way into Shetland, by being brought in, shipped in, or even smuggled.¹⁰⁶ The canonization of certain aesthetic elements of Shetland's music, what Swing (1991) called Tom Anderson's 'invention of tradition', posed a discordant alternative to the *spree*, an older, eclectic model for sociomusical engagement.

Yet, formalities and preordained drills that some students experience as mechanical and impersonal forms of music teaching (i.e., 'by book not by ear'), were not necessarily included in Anderson's fiddle teaching model in Yell. Problems only seemed to emerge when young musicians stepped beyond the canonized repertoire that Anderson privileged.

Guitarist Eddie Lang, from Benny Goodman's band was one of Peerie Willie's main influences, a 'huge fan', as Brian Nicholson put it. Django transformed similar influences through his own style. Peerie Willie's style was subtle and misunderstood, since, unlike Django, Willie was not a virtuosic soloist. Early swing and blues were at the core of his playing, as Brian Nicholson told me at High Level Music, in March 2014,

You can really hear how [Willie] walked into that pulse and augmented it, but didn't do it in a way that obscured it or detracted from the music, he did it in a way that really complimented what was going on. Which was quite a gift, really to be able to talk effectively American blues and swing and move it into your own culture... within a very short time it was considered to be the way to accompany traditional tunes – like, anything else was... wrong. People see that as the proper way to do it. It takes a long time to establish something like that in a culture, you know, to change the culture like that...

Peerie Willie would demonstrate his ideas on the guitar to others who approached him with their own examples. But they 'were not quite there', while Willie, in contrast, was 'a natural' who 'never went to college', Brian continues. The first time he met Peerie Willie, Brian snuck into the bar to watch him play in a Saturday lunch time session at the Lounge. But Peerie Willie was not playing guitar. Brian was 15 and playing in *Da Frustra* dance band. Peerie Willie could be seen playing the drums, double bass, piano, trumpet, and the fiddle then. Brian notes that Peerie Willie seemed to be bored with the guitar, because every time he picked it up, people approached him to ask for guitar demonstrations, and he just could not be bothered sometimes, he just wanted to have a drink and 'enjoy the company'. 'I can understand that', Brian tells me.

When Peerie Willie started playing with Debbie Scott, according to Brian, his most interesting playing started to come out. Listening to *Selkies' Song* (2007) inspired Brian to learn more about Peerie Willie's playing. When Brian compared what he was doing to what Willie was doing, he realised it was quite different. After studying Willie's music over the years, Brian's position is that Willie played 'from a deep understanding'. In other

words, for Brian, Willie did not rely on pastiches of licks and tricks collected from disjointed and systematically learned parts, or ‘blocks of pre-learned music’ stuck together. This personal conviction, regarding the depth of voice and character in Willie’s music, inspired Brian to want to learn more about music in general. That ‘deep understanding’ that Brian found in Willie’s playing was not contrived technique, it was character, developed and transformed over many years of listening, playing, and experimenting.

If Peerie Willie had behaved like a business or record company executive, measuring artists according to their supposed potential worth in profits, or shaping his music and image according to commercial trends, he would not have become the iconic resonant symbol that he has. The moral lesson is that Shetland’s music community values humility and modesty more than what they perceive as arrogant, self-centred, exploitative, or, simply put, anti-community attitudes. These values, supporting horizontality, influence performers in the tradition to seek the joy of playing music with friends and getting to know new people, rather than achieving commercial success. Michael Williamson, following a non-commercial model for the release of *North Country Fair’s Liberty Follows* (2013) – a rock record that even includes the serendipitous participation of the internationally renowned Fair-Isle born fiddler Chris Stout and a number of other local musicians – found great joy in giving albums away as gifts, and even greater joy when his teenage daughter Shannon started to talk about how much she enjoyed his compositions, especially the drumming in *Pressgang*, from the upcoming album *Brandy from a Stranger*.

When Michael was first transfixed by Jimmy Quinn’s voice at a *Red Vans* concert in Whalsay, he did not even know how to play guitar, and thought he could never learn. Decades later, Jimmy became a driving force behind *North Country Fair*, an outlet for Michael’s compositions, which have all flowed serendipitously from present circumstances, taking shape through the contributions of the various musicians who have

participated in *North Country Fair* recording projects. Michael's session hosting skills, attuned to the conviviality principles of the *spree*, inspires him to keep his home open for hosting visiting musicians during various festivals. Aitkens became a traditional *spree* focus for SFF late night sessions for many years, contributing to Michael's character and charisma. Michael does not aim for complexity, complication, or virtuosity in his compositions. Rather, he lays down heartfelt and unpretentious harmonic, lyrical, melodic and rhythmic structures, and welcomes the spontaneous arranging ideas of his musical friends. Chris Thomson, for instance, plays with *North Country Fair* because he loves the songs, and is absolutely comfortable at Aitkens, where he is always welcome, like many others who share Michael's close circle of friends.

Figure 5: *North Country Fair* rehearsing at Aitkens (left to right, Chris Thomson, Jim Quinn, Michael Williamson, Arthur Nicholson, Ewan Nowak and Lewis Murray).

4.8. *PATTERNING and APPRECIATING MUSICAL CHARACTER*

Brian Nicholson was among the first students who received lessons from Tom Anderson in Yell in the 1970s. He learned some fiddle, starting at age 15, ‘which was great’, he says, ‘we were the first of that generation’. And ‘up until then’, Brian recalls, ‘if you wanted to learn music, you just hung out with other musicians who played and you picked up what you could from them’. Nobody who played in a band at the time received formal music education in local schools, as is common now. Brian was part of the first group of students who were given some sort of formal structure for studying music. The lessons were not organised around an academic system of music teaching, as Brian recalls,

It wasn’t really like formal music lessons, he came with a tune on a piece of paper, and the fingerings were all written in, but it was pretty much up to you how you played it. There wasn’t a ‘this is the right way to do it’ thing, so you just kind of had a go.

Brian preferred to play guitar, and learned it by following along with the piano. Brian notes that there are probably more musicians in the world now than there has ever been, but ‘there’s not so many all and out individual players’. ‘I don’t think the industry, really’, Brian continues, ‘encourages that kind of thing anymore, unless you’re very lucky to just happen to have the right kind of support’. The Shetland *spree*, however, supports the growth and development of personal voice, style, character and individuality through sustained horizontalizing interpersonal knowledge, mutual support, and the appreciation of those very traits that make one absolutely unique – or, as Debbie Scott wrote about Peerie Willie – their ‘inimitable and unmistakable’ qualities (Scott 2007).

Brian believes that grading students and subjecting them to drills can spoil their experience with music unnecessarily. For Brian, it is important to encourage young students, recognising that everyone learns in a different way. He explains this by making an analogy to a ‘blues and rock and roll’ way of seeing the world. ‘If you look at it from the point of view of blues and rock and roll’, Brian proposes, ‘the whole thing about that

kind of music' was 'to promote the individual and to get away from that [formulaic] kind of music: I do understand that [approach] for classical music, where it's very formal and it's very formulaic, and very clearly defined forms of music'.¹⁰⁷ I ask about whether there is a real need for a formal education.

Can you imagine you have to put somebody like Keith Richards through a grade? [chuckles] You know what I mean? It just doesn't sit with my vision of that kind... of what that kind of music is about... it just doesn't sit well, you know? You can't imagine how you could sort of formally educate these people to get to the stage so they could play the Rolling Stones... It was all about expressing the individual and doing something different and not being like the previous generation.

I mention to Brian how Stevie Hook is also very careful about what he writes regarding children and young students, aware of the potential negative long-term psychological consequences of judging, grading, classifying and comparing them. Both educators agree that they are facilitators helping children to develop a love for playing and for developing their personal voice.¹⁰⁸ Brian notes that the enforced grading inherent in standard UK music and general educational systems threatens to inhibit people's individuality. The mainstream musical education system seems to be reproducing older styles, with very technical players who are nevertheless not exciting to watch, even if they may be very useful to the music industry, recording commercial jingles and performing in backing bands for mainstream pop acts, when all that matters is playing exactly as written. Brian points out that BB King 'who's probably not technically the greatest guitar in the world', can play 'one note and the hairs go up on the back of your neck – there's no college that could have made a BB King – it just wouldn't happen'. 'Louis Armstrong', in Brian's opinion, is 'a really good example' of somebody that the 'college system could never produce' because such was the power of his unique character and style.

The Shetland Folk Festival could be compared to any other festival, and common features might be revealed, such as the production of a periodical convergence of

musicians from around the world. However, there are elements that make this festival characteristically Shetland, that could only be possible in Shetland, and not in cities like Aberdeen, Edinburgh, Glasgow or Dublin, or even in any small town. I am drawing attention to how, despite similarities and possible comparisons, which I discuss in the conclusion, there are Shetland specific characteristics that research participants recognise. This ‘Shetland feeling’ flows with and takes shape through the tone of sociomusical interactions, and also comes from a sense of local history and sociomusical practices like the *spree* and other forms of collaborative and productive conviviality, such as bands, rehearsals, gigs, after parties and so on. The potential differences from music sessions in other places can be appreciated through an analysis of the conversations I had with two musicians who have recently relocated to Shetland, Kirsty North and Gemma Graham (Chapter 4.10). Our conversations often dwelled on the differences they experienced playing in Shetland and elsewhere in Scotland.

According to Campbell (1997) there are more musicians in Shetland per capita than anywhere else in Europe. Music is a very important element of local cultural identity. However, it is not just a shared passion for music that gives the *spree* its Shetland flavour and ‘feeling’, as Norman Willmore calls it. Rather, locals experience Shetland as a place of sociomusical convergence, where multiple intergenerational friendships extend for lifetimes. Shetland, therefore, as a place, and the myriad of places within it – from islands, to beaches, peat banks, country halls, homes and tents – provide grounding and stability for those relationships to flourish and grow. High Level Music was the starting point of this research. It provides a fertile ground for flourishing sociomusical relationships in Shetland.

4.9. *SPREE-STYLE SOUND ENGINEERING*

Amanda Pearson, Stevie Hook and Jonathan Ritch, whom I observed in action in various occasions, take their live sound engineering seriously, and deal with the tensions of live performances without violating the principles of the *spree*. Ultimately, they are responsible for the quality of everyone's sonic experiences, which depends on their successful performance. The most intense and potentially discordant moments take place during concerts and sound checks, when people are moving equipment and setting up stages. These tasks require meticulous execution and involve complicated processes: organising and keeping track of multiple cables, microphones, PA speakers, monitors, various instruments and miscellaneous equipment, custom configurations for multiple performers, being ready for eventual technical issues, and so on. A less experienced stage helper could jeopardise sonic experiences by misplacing cables and equipment, forgetting to connect microphones, confusing inputs, dropping live microphones onstage, taking too long, getting lost in conversation, mistakes which require energetic responses from more experienced engineers. Their position as live sound sculptors and *spreers* often requires multitasking at a technical and social level. They must watch over everything happening onstage and make sure all issues are dealt with immediately. While they work, friends may approach them with random conversations, and they respond without being rude.

Generally, live sound equipment is hired, but occasionally bands provide their own sound equipment and operate it during the performance, which also allows them to make slightly more money. When I divided the bass duties with Hayden with the *Muddy Bay and the Deep Sea Rollers* in Yell, the band, headed by Arthur Nicholson, took care of the sound. At the 2013 South Mainland *Up Helly Aa* hop, *Maskarade* and *Muddy Bay* did the same.¹⁰⁹ Stevie Hook was the first to invest in a professional live sound system in Shetland, which almost left him penniless in the 1980s. Then, when event organisers tried

doing their own live sound, saving money, it often led to poor sonic results. Stevie sat at home with his new equipment for about a month. People soon began realising that it was worth contracting live sound services for local gigs. Eventually, most recognised that professional sound engineering greatly improved the concert experience and were willing to pay for it. Now, rarely a week goes by without live sound gigs scheduled for Stevie and Amanda, together or separately. Yet, instead of trying to dominate and control the live sound and music instruction markets, Stevie, and High Level Music, like Billy Kay did with Stevie, support the careers of others. Stevie, Fraser Mouat and Jonathan Ritch have passed one another jobs, shared equipment, recording and rehearsal space, working together on countless occasions. They act on love for the *spreeing* community daily. To witness others developing their own skills while having a good time is one of Stevie's greatest joys, reflecting the *Spreinciples* he likely inherited through a lifelong friendship with Billy Kay and others, over four decades of residency in Shetland.

4.10. HIGH LEVEL MUSIC and the SPIRIT of the SPREE

Brian and Fiona, Arthur and Maggie approach each person who enters High Level Music with a warm-hearted, personal type of engagement that is not only endearing but also of a quality that seems impossible to find among impersonal chain stores where people are eager to sell anything for a commission, ignore potential clients who do not appear to have money, and show no real curiosity in knowing who is entering their store, the standard treatment I have received in urban music stores as an anonymous outsider.

When I returned for the last time to Lerwick, on September 19th 2014, the day after the Scottish independence referendum, as soon as I stepped out of the bus and onto Commercial Street, I ran into John-William 'Deeb' Halcrow, drummer for *The Revellers* and *Dirty Lemons*. He expressed his disappointment with the results – like many other

active musicians, he supported Scottish independence. He was wearing his work clothes and going for lunch. After a quick catch up, I walked up the lane toward Aitkens and ran into the medical doctor and fiddler Catharine Brown, who was also deeply disappointed. As we chatted, on the top of the hill, we saw the singer Louise Thomason drive by, and they made eye contact, silently indicating their mutual disappointment with the results.

I dropped my stuff at home, and walked down to High Level Music. Once inside, Fiona offered me coffee, and the luthier and musician Kenny Johnson walked in for a yarn and some equipment, as he usually does. Brian and Maggie sat around the table in the corner, and started playing a selection of beautiful tunes, one after the other. I just sat and thought, ‘this must be one of the best feelings ever’. I just sat there, delighted, talking to Kenny about his travels to northern Portugal, listening to Brian and Maggie pulled out beautiful tune after beautiful tune, and I just realised what I already knew – that Shetland, its music and people, and memories like these would continue to pull me back to Shetland, over and over again. This was not a performance, and they were not studying or rehearsing for a future show, although it was undoubtedly practice – they were playing together because *that* is the spirit of the Shetland *sprees*, and this spirit is an important part of who they are. I became part of the tradition ‘while seeking to document the transmission process’, and I was being personally transformed through the ‘reciprocity and grounded action that is a surprisingly frequent outgrowth of the ethnomusicological research process’ (Shelemay 2008:141). There I was, reflecting on Michael’s lyrics for *Leaving*, sharing the last time in a while with these inimitable characters and the sounds of their music.

Fiona’s depth of knowledge, personal care, and attention to all who visit the shop flow naturally. The same is true of Brian’s deep interest for music of all styles and places, his musicality, life knowledge, and open hearted warmth; Maggie’s personable, horizontal attitude and fluent fiddle tone, and Kenny’s character depth, with a way of speaking that

compels attentive listeners to keep quiet and delight on story after story. As I already knew, this was too special to ignore. Such resonance was paradigmatic of my relationships with many others. Reverberations of similar memories abound, of times spent with Stevie and Amanda, Michael Williamson, *SpootHawk* and Troppo Funk, at Folk Festivals, with Stuart Polson, with John ‘The Wolf’ Polson, with Jim Quinn and others.

I tried thinking about whom I should thank for my time in Shetland, and the list I came up without looking anywhere for reference included over a hundred names of people who directly shaped my understanding of Shetland’s music scene and made me feel comfortable about reflecting critically on my own assumptions in consultation with them. And after I left High Level Music on that same day, I immediately ran into two of my (by now many) favourite characters, Maurice Henderson and the archivist Angus Johnson. Maurice had just returned from Alaska, where he performed with *Fiddler’s Bid*. While in Alaska, he traced one of his uncle’s graves, a Shetlander who had settled there during the gold rush. Angus, whose knowledge of historical materials and ability to be personable, convivial, and chat is impressive, started speaking. At that moment, something else happened as Maurice and I exchanged a meaningful look and nod, which meant that we recognised, were impressed with, and deeply respected the precipitous depth of Angus’ historical knowledge. We winked, deliberately, to ‘impart a particular message’ accorded to ‘a socially established code’ and ‘without cognizance of the rest of the company’ (Geertz 1973:6). At that moment of recognition, what I have called the ‘appreciation of character’ and was as clear as day. And this day was only unique because I was about to leave. I had various similar, familiar days, while living in Shetland. Those memories resound and reverberate as echoes with the pleasures of knowing how music, infused with the spirit of the *sprees*, brings people together in bonds that are unbreakable.

4.11. BECOMING ATTUNED to the SPREE MODE of BEING

Beyond my own experiences as an outsider in Shetland's music scene, how do other musical people, who also first encountered music making outside Shetland, get along with the local scene and experience its epistemological tradition? I spoke on camera with harpist Kirsty North and fiddler-fine artist Gemma Graham, who had recently moved to Shetland and joined the music scene. Gemma would later take part in Shetland's legendary *40 Fiddlers* group during the 2014 Military Tattoo in Edinburgh, along with Martha Thomson and Marjolein Robertson. Kirsty moved to Shetland for a conservation ecology job that she was excited about. She had also applied for different jobs, graduate positions that seemed easier to get, but getting her current job was a 'huge shock' as she had 'just graduated in July'. She became good friends with Claire Marie Thomason, who wrote and acted on a silent short film alongside Erik Peterson that I filmed, edited and helped to produce. Kirsty, Claire, Peter Keay, Chloe Robertson, Craig Birnie, Magnus Bradley and Michael Anderson and I performed as part of Claire's project 'T.R.O.W'. at the 2014 Buffet rock festival.¹¹⁰

At the time I spoke with Kirsty on camera, it was early 2014, still before the SFF, when we would perform with different groups. Yearly, there is a steady rise in anticipation until the arrival of the Folk Fest, the same anticipation that Martha Thomson's first interview, at that time before the 2013 SFF, also reflects. She worries about her upcoming performance at the SFF, which is quite a big deal locally. She explains that playing at the SFF is not like playing harp in a wedding, when there's no pressure and people are not paying much attention to what should be regarded as background music. At the Folk Fest she expects a level of ceremony and seriousness, 'people will be there to see me play with everyone else, so it's a bit more intimidating in a way', says Kirsty, 'but yeah, you know, I'm looking forward to it'. This conversation happens before her first SFF, when most

likely the most intense series of music sessions and *sprees* will potentially cross her way, complementing her perspective on Shetland's sociomusical life.

She tells me that she finds city life 'quite overwhelming' and does not like it, but studied ecology and conservation for four years at Aberdeen. She grew up in a village that was smaller than Lerwick, close to Inverness. Shetland is 'wilder' than other places for Kirsty, less agricultural. About a week after she arrived, Kirsty was already playing harp live, in Sandwick. 'I've had never done the whole session thing before', she tells me, 'I normally perform alone but I'm getting used to it'. The harp was welcomed immediately in local music sessions. 'I think they were just quite glad to have something different and new', Kirsty says. People joined in and it was 'quite interesting to find out', she tells me, 'how different a lot of the pieces I play are to what the Shetlanders play'. Tunes that are promptly recognised where she comes from are not well known in Shetland. It is a whole new learning experience for her, playing new tunes on the harp and being appreciated for sharing tunes that Shetland musicians and music lovers do not know well, at least yet. For Kirsty, Shetlanders 'appreciate something a little bit different'. For Kirsty, playing an instrument made getting to know people in Shetland easier.

Kirsty 'was not very [active] at all' as a musician while living in Aberdeen. But 'there was a session that I went to, occasionally, in Aberdeen, but there wasn't many people who went and there wasn't quite a strong presence', Kirsty tells me. 'I don't think I really knew anyone at uni who played actively any kind of music rather than folk, so it wasn't that strong'. When she was a student at the University of Aberdeen, she did know people who played in ceilidhs. She continues, 'I mean, I probably could [have gotten involved]... there was a Celtic society and stuff like that, so it probably did exist, but I was kind of busy with other stuff, and it wasn't... none of my friends did it'. Yet, she would still perform 'little solo stuff' for 'good pay' but 'it was kind of sporadic'. Still, it 'made

me practice’, says Kirsty. She got tired of living in Aberdeen, where she was only supposed to be a student. She went back home to recompose.

Shetland, however, is ‘nothing like’ her village. ‘I’ve never been to sessions back home or anything like that’, Kirsty points out a key difference. The Shetland *spree* sessions have a character of their own, demanding that time is forgotten for the sake of an overnight musical session where everyone is invited to pitch in. In Aberdeen, Kirsty played mostly duets with a friend. ‘A lot of my friends played various things and there’s lot more ceilidhs and stuff, so it was far more musical than Aberdeen, but not as actively musical as Shetland’, Kirsty says. ‘Back home’, she tells me, ‘it’s harder to get involved [...] whereas here [in Shetland] it’s just so easy...’ Kirsty began showing where locals played together. As soon as she joined them, she made new friends and started to follow the creative flow of the scene, getting involved with the projects that appeared in her way, which is similar to how it happened in my experience. When her ‘parents came up’ for a weekend, ‘there was something on pretty much every day that I could go to, related to music somehow’. The local music scene, compared to her experience elsewhere, is ‘very active’.

I go to two different sessions, and it’s quite interesting to see how different they are – but both of them are very welcoming – people that are even... are learning, basically, as well, so it’s not the case that ‘you have to be amazing’, which I was a bit worried about, I could imagine it would worry other people as well, but it’s very easy going and nobody really cares how good you are.

I point out how local master musicians are ‘very accepting’ of people at any level. ‘Very much so, which is really nice,’ Kirsty agrees. She goes to the Sandwick sessions and the ones ‘at Mareel on a Tuesday night’. She used to go to The Lounge, but on a quieter Tuesday session (i.e., not the traditional Wednesday session that makes the place famous) that was not happening at the time of our conversation anymore. ‘I would go to the one on the Wednesday, but I can’t trust on a harp in a busy bar’, says Kirsty. The acoustic harp is large, expensive and fragile, and during our project T.R.O.W. we wondered about the best

microphone and placement to get it to sound good onstage alongside percussion, vocals, guitars and bass. She eventually purchased a more practical electric harp that only requires an instrument lead connection and an amplifier, since she would clearly have to be using it onstage over and over in the future while in Shetland. Kirsty will ‘probably go along at some point anyway’ to the main session on Wednesdays at The Lounge, although that can get indeed too busy and cumbersome to find a proper spot for a delicate harp. Yet, regardless of how foreign or ‘alien’ (to echo Cohen 1985), cumbersome, fragile or soft sounding Kirsty’s harp is without proper amplification, what matters is that, immediately upon her arrival, she was encouraged to play in local sessions and join musical projects. Within months, she was already performing at the 2014 Shetland Folk Fest.

My encounter with Gemma Graham, then in her early thirties and a relatively new arrival in the Shetland music scene, took place at Mareel, where I first met her after she started working at the café bar, soon after she moved to Shetland. Gemma first started playing classical violin and orchestral music, but she eventually quit. She had a great violin teacher, but ‘she was a bit strict’, Gemma notices. The teacher would get Gemma to write all the scales on paper and then, Gemma tells, ‘put them in a hat, and then she’d like toss all the paper on the floor, and then she would just like pick each one out in random, and be like, ‘right, play this scale’, and that was just very stressful, there was no enjoyment in that [laughs]. It was stressful, it was like a nerve-racking thing, I wasn’t enjoying it’. ‘My dad was quite a big influence, in fiddle music’, Gemma tells me, ‘he listens to a lot of it, and Shetland music, so that’s kinda how I got into that, it was listening to his CDs’. ‘Long before I started playing myself, I was interested in kind of getting into fiddle music, folk music’. Her dad supported her appreciation for this kind of music. She recalls,

About two years ago, I started to get fiddling again, and started to play some tunes, and listening to music and started to play it, in a different approach, really, ‘cos I grew up in an orchestra environment, where it’s very much reading music, so you had the

structure to follow, but I want to open it up and take away from that and maybe learn by ear, or just like learn musics that felt more open when you were playing with other musicians, so take a whole new approach to it and just kind of have fun with it. I enjoyed playing growing up but I think there were limitations to it and you sorta felt like you were kind of having to – it's like a bit of a chore. I didn't want playing an instrument to be like that. It's now a point where I just really enjoy playing it and don't worry so much about where it's going, it's just enjoy playing with the musicians...

For Gemma, 'more open' music making involves the sense of freedom from judgment and competition.¹¹¹ We see that her impressions are aligned with the notion that freedom is a key element that distinguishes creative from constrictive experiences. She found that the 'one part that was enjoyable was playing with the orchestra' for 'you got a buzz being onstage, and you're playing in an orchestra, you got all these different instruments, different sounds going through, and it really gets you excited when you're playing'. After she stopped playing violin, however, Gemma 'took that [fun] side of [playing in an orchestra]' and decided that if she was 'going to pick [music] up again', something that she really wanted, she was 'going to enjoy it'. Gemma was about sixteen when she was playing in the orchestra, 'it was just kind of fun classical stuff we played with other schools'. 'I went to school in Fife and moved to Edinburgh when I was eighteen', Gemma tells me. She stayed for a year, then 'transferred to Aberdeen and spent two years there' before returning home. She studied marketing, which, she later realised, was not making her happy – 'it's kind of a chunk where I just sort of don't really think about much anymore' as 'it doesn't make any sense to what I do now' even if 'I do a little bit of marketing in an arts environment, but it's just a completely different time'.

I was just not happy, I didn't know why I wasn't happy, I just... at the time I couldn't figure out why I was... and I just remember sitting down with my mom, and she was like, 'well, this isn't working for you right now, so we need to figure out like what is that's not right', and she was like, 'you have to tell me what it is that you want to do', and I was just like, 'okay, well, I want to do art', and she was like, 'right, well, do it then, let's... you can do

this', just like, 'come back for a while and see how you get on'. I was lucky that she was... mom and dad were supportive enough to kind of let me do that.

I ask Gemma about arts marketing and general marketing and business, wondering about their differences. Gemma laughs when she thinks about that period of her life. I wanted to know how did she make the decision at that age, to get into business and marketing, 'to go business?' she replies, and explains, 'I think at the time in school I was just – I'm sure a lot of other people feel this, you go to a career's advisor, and they're not exactly all that helpful or give you the right guidance in the end'. The point is that, while living in a more anonymous urban environment, and having taken the typical, standardised, bureaucratic, impersonal, so-called 'aptitude' tests, she was diverted into a more common and conformist career path, one that turned art into business and robbed it of its magic. This path was defined by check marks on a checklist of possible options. This conventional approach, which turns people into statistical categories in checklists, is fundamentally different from the personalised treatment that people like Stevie Hook, Brian Nicholson, Fraser Mouat, Bryan Peterson, Alice Mullay and Jonathan Ritch give to their music and production students. Had she been exposed to the same artistic and open-minded people she eventually found in Shetland this diversion would never have happened. She recalls,

Well, you're eighteen and you sort of needed that guidance. You're just about to leave school and go to uni, so you start trying to think about help, about what you should do with the rest of your life, mostly. But my dad was just like – would accuse even like, 'what are you doing? You should be doing art and music', and I was like, 'no, no, no, I'm not doing that, I'm not doing that!' But, ultimately, a couple of years down the line, that's exactly what I came back to doing, so he was right, but' [chuckles].

At that time, she was 'definitely not playing' for school or college or anything, 'I didn't play at all', Gemma admits. She only did a recording with a friend who was musical – she did not have confidence to play at the time, and there were sessions in Aberdeen, but she was shy to join them. In Shetland the horizontal principle that underlies sociomusical

sprees generates a safe, comfortable, and stress-free environment that encourages participation.¹¹² ‘I never finished the marketing course, I just left it because I decided it was art that I wanted to do so I went back to college to do a portfolio course’. She did the first year of marketing twice, and then the second year, but ‘it’s really not worth talking about it’, Gemma laughs. I ask her about being happy with marketing or art and music. I tell her my own story, resisting the family pressure to become a lawyer or engineer, or something that people in my family understand better as a proper profession.

There is a pressure sometimes to not go down that creative plain, and maybe some people feel that from their parents, that they want them to [pursue] a more academic course, or have more of a steady career. I think I was lucky in that I had the support of my mom and dad. They weren’t forcing me to go down this business. It was a decision that I made, to do this course, but then everyone else who knew me well, and like, friends and family, they were all like, ‘why are you doing this, what are you not... this isn’t what we see you doing’ and I was... I know it was a stubbornness, just to, like, prove to people that I could do something else. I don’t know, I got no idea. I was young and a lot younger [laughs].

Her parents had lived in Shetland before, for a couple of years after they were married but have since returned to mainland Scotland. Eventually, her mom, a fiddle novice, decided to be student at Fiddle Frenzy, an educational festival organised by Shetland Arts. Her mom came back to Fife ‘raving’ about the festival and workshop to Gemma, who thought to herself, ‘I have to do this, it sounds fantastic’. But it took ‘about three, four years before I could actually get up for it’, she recalls. Fiddle Frenzy essentially brought Gemma closer to the fiddle. Her classical violin studies included no exposure whatsoever to fiddle material. She had no confidence about playing before because, in the classical music world in which her earlier experiences as a musician developed, unless she was in absolutely top technical form, she could not play. The competitive and technical aspects of practicing and polishing classical materials and technique ultimately bored Gemma and made music stale and unexciting. After her mom’s enthusiastic return from

Fiddle Frenzy, Gemma decided to start playing more. As a fine artist, she also began finding her own way, something that she felt was missing before, when she was pursuing studies in marketing. ‘Being in Shetland’, this ‘inspired place’, Gemma tells me, helped her drawings take off. Gemma goes ‘walking with the geology’ and ‘the coastal kind of formations’ and combines these experiences in her ‘insane line drawing’.

Gemma does artistic research by exploring landscapes. She sets out in solitude so that inspiration emerges from the places and situations she encounters. Since *Back from Beyond*, Gemma has been tapping into ‘local knowledge’ in order to find out spots to explore that are beyond the mainstream touristic routes. She heard about *Back from Beyond* during Fiddle Frenzy week, when she met Maurice Henderson, and learned that it focused on ‘stunning spots in Shetland’. Maurice told Gemma that his band *Haltadans* would be going to Foula for their BFB project. She made different trips to various places in Shetland to find inspiration, such as Saint Ninian’s Isle and Eschaness. ‘And I go on a small monologue about my feeling with the landscape’, Gemma explained. Having grown up in a picturesque seaside village, Gemma finds that the ‘Shetland landscape’ has a ‘more raw feeling to it, it’s more organic, more natural – I don’t even think about trees anymore, you forget that the trees were there’. She only noticed trees at the first time that she returned to Fife for holidays after moving to Shetland.

Line drawing ‘was always my kind of style’, says Gemma, ‘very intricate drawings’ with ‘repetition and mark making’ that took time and dedication to develop. There was something missing in her work, resolution based on a central theme, meaningfulness and resonance with a socially tangible audience – elements that she encountered in *Back from Beyond* soon after she returned to live in Shetland after her first Fiddle Frenzy. Her artwork before was ‘so abstract’, making it ‘maybe difficult if you were to make a connection with the work’. Gemma ‘wasn’t really quite happy with it’ and knew she ‘was

going to take it somewhere, [she] just didn't know where it was going'. The subject of the art seemed disconnected from the concerns of its audience, which was almost like a void with no purpose or direction. In Shetland, Gemma found that the feeling of a vital, meaningful connection with a responsive audience would start emerging again. Previously, she improved her textures, and developed her pattern and drawing techniques. Eventually, moving to Shetland helped her in 'making the connection with the landscape here and now', Gemma says. As she started to return to art after an incursion into the world of marketing, Gemma began listening to traditional music more. She appreciated how much her father loved this music, and her appreciation also grew.

In Shetland, Gemma's meaningful connections with people, music, landscapes and art fostered stronger sociomusical links. At the time of our conversation, Gemma felt completely at home in Shetland. Her friend Sarah Brown was the first to take her to The Lounge for a music session with locals. For Gemma, 'being involved in music' makes it 'quite easy' and 'natural' to 'meet people'. Inevitably, she notes, 'it's just going to happen'. 'And obviously', she argues, 'you're new here, and they want to get to know you as well, they want to find out about you'. For her, 'Shetlanders are really friendly, and they're interested' about 'why you come here, that kind of thing, as you would be if it was somewhere you lived and someone was coming in, you'd want to get to know them, and meet them and find out what they're about and stuff'. This echoes Lewie Peterson's suggestion that interpersonal knowledge in Shetland compels this curiosity not only among musicians. 'Not if you're in New York, maybe there they don't care so much', I suggest, evoking Weber's (1958[1921]) impersonal city and Simmel's (1971) 'metropolitan type'. 'Oh yeah, that's true', Gemma says, 'community feel, if you're just in the city, *no*'.

Gemma's father showed her a *Fiddler's Bid* tune once, believing it would change her mind and inspire her to play music again and get into traditional music. This tune

immediately ‘got her’. From her dad’s ‘perspective, it was like, you play the fiddle, just listen to this, and it will completely change your mind, you’ll want to get your fiddle out’. Gemma continues, ‘I listened to them, and I was like, ‘well, that’s incredible’. This was still just on CD. She could not predict that she would be joining Maurice Henderson from *Fiddler’s Bid* at the 2014 North Atlantic Sessions *spree* in Fetlar. ‘I think I went to see the Unusual Suspects before [*Fiddler’s Bid*]’, Gemma tells me, with Chris Stout playing, ‘so I kinda heard him play, and I was like, ‘wow’. Gradually, while attending the Scotts Music Group and the arts college in Edinburgh, she got more involved with folk music. But it was only after finally coming to Shetland in August 2013 that her fiddle playing took off. Playing an instrument is something that stays with you for a lifetime, Gemma thinks – like riding a bicycle, ‘it’s always there’. For Gemma, ‘*Fiddler’s Bid* music’ really ‘stands out at the time’ for getting her excited about Shetland music,

I’ve got family from Shetland, so Shetland’s always kind of been there, and mom and dad moved up here when they first got married, in the seventies. They spent a year here, so they got lots of stories. I kind of like heard about Shetland a lot, I got friends from here, and it always, Shetland’s always been there, there’s always been some connection with it. I always knew that I wanted to come to Shetland, so I think that the music side of it just kind of ignited that passion and that connection even more. I was just more excited about coming, I think, when I started to listen to traditional Shetland music. Then, finding out about this course, Fiddle Frenzy, and that you could sort of learn traditional tunes and play alongside other musicians, I was just like, ‘wow, this sounds great’, so...

It was Gemma’s mother’s first time playing the fiddle, and it posed quite a challenge, but Fiddle Frenzy made her love it.¹¹³ Gemma’s uncle John gave her mom a fiddle from the 1880s that had been in the family since the 19th century. She took the fiddle to Ewen Thomson, Martha’s father and Maurice’s band mate in *Haltadans*, for an adjustment and assessment. ‘I just found out recently from Ewen Thomson that it was a German fiddle’, Gemma tells me, ‘because it’s got these distinctive mother of pearl floral markings on the fingerboard and on the back as well’. She first thought it was from Norway, but the

markings made it ‘definitely German’. The fiddle had been taken to Australia and played over there sometime in its early life and was returned to Shetland. It surprised Gemma that the Shetland side of her family was not involved with the music scene. Sisters Catharine and Sarah Brown – a medical doctor and a nurse – introduced Gemma to the music scene. They decided to settle in Shetland for a while and come back not just because they found jobs. The fact that they had local ‘music connections’ was fundamental. The music side of Shetland is a ‘huge part for them’, and it keeps them coming back, Gemma remarks. She thinks that this is ‘why they do come back, and obviously the people as well, and you know just the whole Shetland environment but the music side of it has hugely influenced their time here’, she adds. ‘Well, music was such a huge part of why I came here’, Gemma said, ‘the decision to come was massively influenced’ by the fact that she gets ‘to play fiddle more, and learn tunes, and be around other musicians’.

Gemma finally decided to come up to Shetland and check out Fiddle Frenzy, to see what could happen. ‘It was just a complete turning point’, she points out, ‘a complete turning point to come up for [Fiddle Frenzy] because I ended up coming back here two weeks later’ [laughs]. The experience resounded deeply with her, and she realised Shetland was the right place for her at that moment. After the 2013 Fiddle Frenzy was over, while returning to the mainland, adds Gemma, ‘I remember getting on the ferry, and just feeling... just a sinking feeling like, ‘I cannot be leaving here right now, this is the last thing I wanted, I do not want to be getting on this ferry and going back down, and to Fife – I want to be back up here’. When Gemma arrived in Mainland Scotland, she had already realised she had to prepare her return to Shetland. ‘I got out of the boat’, she tells me,

reluctantly, and I could have stayed an extra couple of days, but my thoughts were, ‘no, I’m going to get back and figure out what I’m doing to do’. So I basically got back, got picked up in the train station, and I was like, ‘dad, I’m going back up to Shetland’, and he was like, ‘oh, I thought you were going to say that’ [laughs].

Gemma booked the ferry back within a couple of days and ‘sorted out a place to stay’. She got everything ready and was back up in Shetland with her stuff after a couple of weeks. ‘It just made sense to come back’, she explains, the ‘gut feeling’ she had about this decision made her realise she ‘just had to do it’. For her, ‘sometimes your intuition is the strongest thing you have’. Gemma’s family connections in Shetland informed her on how to behave appropriately, probably helping her to mingle more easily with locals. Usually, tourists who come looking for a fiddling holy grail in Shetland end up never experiencing a true home-brewed Shetland *spree*. Alternatively, they just might luckily stumble upon it.¹¹⁴ Still, access to music sessions and *sprees* is not closed for tourists, who often do not have the time to get to know locals well enough to be invited or the luck to be in a situation that evolves naturally from its social composition into a sociomusical *spree*. ‘I just had to come back’, Gemma admits, because ‘everyone knows that a week is not long enough to spend in Shetland anyway’. ‘In the end’, Gemma concludes, ‘it turned out to be a good decision – I feel like I finally got settled somewhere for the first time’. Fiddle Frenzy, she recalls, was ‘amazing’, a ‘great week’ with nice weather, and ‘some lovely folk’. For Gemma, who had ‘never been in that kind of environment before’, it was ‘very exciting’, ‘just playing tunes, learning tunes, and meeting other musicians’. I ask whether she was among the Fiddle Frenzy students who were photographed playing fiddle to the Northlink ferry as it sailed away, just outside Mareel. Whereas this activity was part of SADA’s promotion campaign, exclusively for tourists, I knew that Gemma was already knew serious session players. She barely remembered the Fiddle Frenzy promotion, as she was already taking part in ‘a lot of late night *sprees*’, Gemma laughs.

Having shed the hurry to succeed and prove herself as an artist, a great source of previous anxiety, Gemma now enjoys the ‘pace of life’ in Shetland, its ‘chilled aspect’ and potential to get ‘quite intense’ with ‘so much going on’. She speculates that ‘maybe that’s

why parties go until eight in the morning’, as to ‘create time, more time, there’s no time to sleep’. ‘Just forget about sleep in Shetland’, she warns. Sociomusical *sprees* are designed to turn off the participants’ concerns with schedule and time by converging their intentions in a flow. As being in the moment takes full precedence, becoming the overarching motive for everyone’s presence, sociomusical pleasures shape interpersonal resonances with character and relevance, and tunes and stories flow as communication channels.

CONCLUSION

4.12. PERSONAL HARMONICS and the SPREE

The logic behind the metaphor of epistemological resonance requires the presence of certain phenomenological elements. If there is resonance, there must be the potential for harmonics, since resonance is amplified through harmonics. The use of such metaphors does not transcend their analogy as interconnected physical phenomena recognised by physics, most particularly in quantum and string theory. It is precisely the reference to the phenomena of resonance and harmonics in acoustics that enables the metaphor to serve the purpose of investigating epistemological interactions. Ingold, for instance, draws from Bohm’s implicate order and quantum entanglement, as well as from selections in phenomenological literature, to form a vision of the world as an entangled unfolding of related life forms, growing and developing – ‘the storied world’ of ‘movement and becoming’ that is ‘caught at a particular place and moment’ and that ‘enfolds within its constitution the history of relations that have brought it here’ (Ingold 2011:160). Likewise, this ethnography grew organically from following and developing social relationships kindled through a common deep interest in music and in being there with people. Once these relationships were struck, they were seeded and started growing indefinitely, and continue doing so. Therefore, the world I encountered is social, but also very personal.

Anthropological theory is very useful for understanding structural relations, and there is no doubt knowledge can and should be revealed this way as well. However, participating in music making situations led me to develop personal relationships – friendships that afford a more thorough appreciation of local patterns than would have happened if I had insisted on maintaining a certain scientific distance. As Gemma Graham noted, ‘there’s more time for people here [in Shetland], and just making that time’. Playing music together, therefore, is intensely personal and social, and following the paths that these dimensions afford always leads to interesting results and creative possibilities. In other words, long-term ethnographic fieldwork, particularly when it involves a primacy of face-to-face interactions and daily engagement with the practices around the study focus, is essential for allowing for a valid structural vision to emerge. Certain patterns, especially within the social world, can only be appreciated after living in a place for a while. Moreover, cultivating strong circles of close friends with bonds of trust generates safe environments for ethnographers to bounce ideas around with locals, and ask for their impressions on what is emerging conceptually from the experience. Anthropologists go ‘study *with* people’ and ‘hope to learn *from* them’, argues Ingold (2013a:2). For Ingold (2013a:3), the imperatives driving anthropology and ethnography highlight fundamental differences between them – anthropology is ‘studying with and learning from’ while ethnography ‘is a study of and about’ (2013a:3). In other words, ethnography is documentary while anthropology is transformational and potentially transcendent.

'BEING WITH' and SPREE MUSIC MAKING

However generally valid, Ingold's dichotomy does not deal with the potential for ethnographic fieldwork fundamentally informed by an epistemology that focuses precisely on 'studying with and learning from'. Ingold bases his main argument on the grammatical and semantic differences between *of* and *with*. One indicates a relationship of possession and the other indicates a concurrent process between associated things. Ingold's main objective 'is to replace the anthropology *of* with an anthropology *with*' (2013a:8). He regards art 'as a discipline' that 'shares with anthropology a concern to reawaken our senses and to allow knowledge to grow from the inside of being in the unfolding of life' (Ingold 2013a:8). The present ethnography follows along the same lines. Social music making, as subject and methodology, served as a place for striking and kindling personal relationships embedded in local social networks and their extensions.

Music making with others, according to the *spree* model, can help us to reflect on our personal vulnerabilities and potentials, eventually helping to shed some of protective the layers and attitudes that may keep others distant, such as Georg Simmel's (1971:326) 'metropolitan type'.¹¹⁵ This reflexive interpersonal appreciation develops alongside the growth of interpersonal knowledge through sociomusical *spree*-style music making. Seeing others as creative beings with equal potentiality and appreciable personalities regardless of their musical skills, and seeing oneself as a constant work in progress, who once could not even get a sound from one's instrument, allows one to join others in communion and leave outside self-centred, individualistic assumptions (i.e., blockages). Ideally, the characteristics and attributes people carry do not make them better or worse, but make them different, and it is in those differences that Shetlanders tend to focus. Regardless of the mistakes and misadventures that one ends up involved with, all experiences and impressions contribute to one's image. If discordance arises from

disparate readings about one person, the savvy and experienced Shetlander will always set rumour aside and seek knowledge ‘straight from the horse’s mouth’. As a manifestation of harmonic epistemological resonance, it becomes more sensible and powerful as sustained personal engagement with others cultivates and extends its sensibilities. Working toward a performance with a band, for instance, requires a certain communion between its members, an understanding and ease for spending time together and getting the music to sound right. Achieving this collective harmonic resonance takes commitment to being social, and for becoming immersed in one another’s personal worlds, which is not meant to be always comfortable, but which affords the formation of deeper and more detailed interpersonal understandings. Shetland *spreers* express their understanding of the principles of horizontality and the appreciation of character by acting according to and in tune with them, in a relationship of harmonic epistemological resonance, even without having the words to describe these principles as such.

I spent about two years in Shetland, but it was only after a couple of Folk Fests and a great number of *sprees*, and finally a trip to Fetlar, that I had the insight for this thesis. I realised that Shetland’s sociomusical *sprees* form is the most important feature of the local living epistemological tradition of music making. It is sustained by personal and social pleasures of horizontality and the related principle of interpersonal nuance of character appreciation. Living by these principles strengthens interpersonal relations beyond superficial acquaintanceship. Furthermore, developing the sensibilities for grasping nuances of character becomes a constant source of pleasure, especially in the musical world. One attains nuanced character knowledge that leads to a satisfying appreciation of the *people* playing in addition to the *music* they are playing. As long as players are harmonised with the spirit of the *sprees*, namely the resonance of its epistemological principles, it does not matter what they play or how well they play, they are appreciated.

The present analysis explains how the *spree*, affording recurrent re-combinations of shared personal experiences, propagates and perpetuates such principles. These principles, as a whole, are profoundly anti-hierarchical and anarchist, in that they promote the appreciation and development of character and personality and, in order to do so, they must see through the veneer of artificial power relations, socio-economic class, and supposed age and gender differences. In addition, the expression of such principles is not bound to particular aesthetic imperatives but come across through nuances of character. The process of socialisation is ‘quasi-magical’ in its attribution of rank and status, ‘corresponding privileges and obligations’ that ‘tend to transform instituted difference into natural distinction’, producing ‘quite real effects’ that are ‘durably inscribed in the body and in belief’ (Bourdieu 1990:58). The epistemological tradition of Shetland music, however, through the artifice of the *spree*, seeks to neutralise the hierarchical sense of rank and artificial divisions based on age, gender and socioeconomic status, through a *modus operandi* grounded on interpersonal and intergenerational knowledge, the appreciation of character and the unwavering encouragement of personal musical development.

Because each character is equally valued and understood in his or her relative position in society, through their direct family and friend associations, shared experiences and biographical stories, those attuned to local ways of being, whether longstanding residents or locals, flag those who exhibit and project a sense of self-entitlement and superiority over others as being outside their harmonic circle. Some of these discordant characters hold powerful positions in businesses and production companies and act according to a hierarchical social order; others believe they come from a more urbane and sophisticated place. Whatever the case, once resident participants in the music scene who are attuned to its principle of horizontality have identified them, these discordant characters, often perceived as controlling and bossy, are avoided and satirised.

The horizontal, social levelling principle, when incorporated by participants in *spree* interactions, generates a harmonic epistemological resonance among them – a comfortable feeling of inclusion and belonging that, among other effects, can make the passage of time seem meaningless. Yet, *spreers*' intention for being in the moment intensifies, and responding to people's presence takes precedence over anything external – common preoccupations with the world outside are put on hold, and a strong, resonant 'flow' is established, distorting the 'sense of time' (Csikszentmihalyi 1990:71). The social situations that emerge then continuously develop and deepen one person's understanding of another's character, a sense of their biography and style. The music shared in such harmonised epistemological environments makes competition meaningless, because enjoying the moment involves appreciating others and moving together with them and the music, not proving superiority of any kind. Appreciation of character, then, is among the highest values that the *spree* facilitates, and it becomes a source of great personal and social pleasure that grows more satisfying and complex with time, as sociomusical circumstances bring those same people together again and again. For instance, when I listen to different bands, I remember details from the many experiences I had with those band members. This adds a lot of contextual nuance to how I experience their music, for it has the power to transport me back to those experiences in my imagination. In the case of *SpoorHawk* songs that I performed many times live and where I know some of the symbolic 'secrets' behind the lyrics – personal things that remain among band members – the effect is even stronger.

I also see the precession of notes in my imagination, and have flashbacks of being onstage in various Shetland venues, dancing freely with the music, surrounded by friends onstage and among the audience, and enjoying the electric atmosphere linking our personal sounds together. Music is the phenomenological element over, under, and through which all social interactions happen, for people's productions and performances reflect how their

stories and characters are developing in relation and association with one another. All participants have their own storyline that intersects with those of others, and those associations contribute to the formation of their character within the greater musical community. Once you become familiar enough with active music scene inhabitants, when they release new music, you feel involved and excited to listen and appreciate it, not only through the technical qualities of the sound, but through an understanding of the personal relationships among those involved.¹¹⁶ In this case, the music takes on layers of meaningfulness that mass produced commercial music cannot emulate or provide, because, for local composers, the process of creation and production is fundamentally social, and it can be appreciated as it develops through recurrent personal encounters.¹¹⁷

Alternatively, commercial music, produced strictly for a global, mass market, is usually produced following what Joe Watt calls general, well-tested market-based ‘formulas’ and ‘clichés’ to infiltrate people’s personal lives. The idea is that generalised formulaic language can be fit into anyone’s experiences, becoming meaningful this way. In the Shetland music scene, compositions often refer to familiar others and meaningful events, commemorating personal histories and relationships. The feelings that emerge from this system, of acknowledging and addressing friends and stories through compositions, are impossible to reproduce through mass produced, formulaic commercial music, which targets demographics and consumer patterns. Industrial music from elsewhere, produced all over the world, promoted on a global massive scale and available through information technologies, still provides a strong basis for early imitation and later musical development that runs in parallel with the local music scene. Yet, it does not elicit the same kind of local, personal and social responses because the source of the music is not available, that is, personal relationships among listeners and music makers are missing.

Within Shetland's scene, appreciators may know the composers well enough to accompany the artistic process, from composition to recording and release, through the sociomusical *spreeing* cycle. Shetlanders do not seek isolation from a commercially oriented music and art world; rather, they engage with it in various ways. Some embrace it and leave Shetland to become professional musicians, others engage with it periodically in occasional tours and festivals but stay in Shetland working other day jobs and filling their role in the community as passionately involved musicians. Some stay engaged locally with the cover music scene and follow avidly commercial music trends and contemporary artists from around the world. They may find some monetary compensation that helps with everyday expenses but does not replace the need for a regular 'day job'. People do not have to be the most successful musicians in the world to be passionately engaged with music making and comfortable with the safety net and creative materials that their social networks regularly afford.

Figure 6: *Spreers* in action. Fetlar Hall, July 20th, 2014, 5:40 AM.

CHAPTER 5: PRODUCTION STYLES in SHETLAND

COMMUNITY as BUZZWORD and COMMUNITY as VALUE SYSTEM

5.1. INTRODUCING IGNITION and BACK from BEYOND

In this chapter, I analyse the experiences of creative collaborators and Shetland musicians in two large projects that I became involved with in 2013: The National Theatre of Scotland's (NTS) production *Ignition*, and *Back from Beyond* (BFB), conceived and organised locally. Personal experience, formal interviews, and informal conversations provide the ethnographic materials discussed in this chapter. I focus on sociomusical experiences with *Ignition* and *Back from Beyond*, and participants' impressions of the differences between these projects.¹¹⁸ Distinct approaches to 'community' ultimately shaped their operational strategies and how locals perceived and engaged each project. The 'holographic correspondence' (Wagner 1986:51) of 'community', attuned to the epistemological principles behind each project, afforded different resonances and reverberations. Projects organisers constructed this organising principle according to their own ideas of what 'community' meant and what set of values it represented. For the musicians who participated in both projects, the contrast was sharp. Converging and flattening these different values into a harmonised notion of 'community' would obscure the partiality and positionality of each project's conception. As this chapter shows, the notion of 'community' that *Ignition* directors adopted was incompatible with the 'community approach' that inspired *Back from Beyond* organisers.

Basic awareness of local sociomusical principles would have led to a celebration of local creativity and character instead of their restriction and caricature. Finally, the NTS was not an exception. Uninformed cultural insensitivity and lack of curiosity are common among outside production crews who arrive with an 'I am a professional' attitude. They rarely develop personal relationships outside of prestige and ambition-oriented

environments, where widespread competitiveness makes the creatively stagnant struggle for authority and status seem natural (see Wilf 2014). Once in a while, television and film production crews come to Shetland with someone better attuned to act with horizontality in interpersonal and intergenerational engagement. As hired hands in rushed projects, outside production crews usually do not have enough time in Shetland to get involved with locals.

The NTS produces a series of ‘community theatre’ projects, *Ignition* being its last incarnation in Shetland. *Ignition* included a massive budget, a professional production crew, and outsiders in charge of creative decisions. As branding device and marketing tool, the ‘community theatre’ label obscured the cultural insensitivity that characterised its historical and sociomusical elements. *Ignition*’s presence in Shetland’s sociomusical scene was generally discordant. Some participants characterised its approach as disorganised, extravagant, exploitative, authoritarian, and culturally insensitive. However, they emphasise that they learned from the experience and enjoyed playing together. In addition, those outside this sociomusical circle might have greatly enjoyed working with *Ignition*.

Alternatively, local musical therapist Alice Mullan, and Emma Perring envisioned *Back from Beyond* to follow a ‘community centred’ approach. For them, ‘community’ was a core epistemological principle. In January 2014, I talked on camera with Alice, and in June with Emma. By trusting local artists to make their own creative decisions, they fostered what I call creative multiplicity, that is, supporting participants’ artistic freedom led to a horizontal distribution of creative decision-making power and a number of voluntary artistic contributions. The principle of resourcefulness inspired this achievement. Alice and Emma drew opinions and impressions from local intergenerational sociomusical networks to shape BFB’s development, making sure all participants would ‘have a say’. A continuous, positive flow of creative activities and communication characterised its operations. About 64 active local musicians became involved with *Back from Beyond*.

They volunteered as performers, organisers, film makers, recording and live sound engineers. *Ignition*, on the other hand, working with a budget at least ten times larger than *Back from Beyond's*, managed to convince three local musicians to participate, hesitantly.

The NTS operated through a hierarchically segmented power framework, requiring strict adherence to orders and subjection to non-dialogic directing. We experienced low flow and time drag with *Ignition*. Shetland's epistemological tradition of music making kindles creative freedom and nuance of character appreciation, frowning at automatic conformity to authority figures. Working for the NTS, epistemologically confined to an environment of hierarchical-managerial and competitive professionalism, was more like working for a corporation than participating in a Shetland style artistic collaboration.

Ignition drew on some local cultural symbols, such as knitting and folklore. Originally inspired by a fatal motor accident, *Ignition* was supposed to improve road safety education. Instead, NTS directors modified this intent. *Ignition*, we were told, explored Shetlanders' relationships with cars and roads. From a mobilities perspective, *Ignition* seemed promising. Eventually, as participants talked about *Ignition*, epitomised *how not* to conduct a collaborative creative project in Shetland, where mutual horizontality and interpersonal knowledge sparkle and kindle intergenerational social integration.

Overall, *Ignition's* 'community theatre' lacked creative and artistic flexibility, and was unwilling to learn from established local models. It is puzzling how the NTS branded *Ignition* as 'community theatre' but overlooked local sociomusical values. The key principles of creative power distribution (i.e., horizontality), resourcefulness and freedom that characterised *Back from Beyond's* 'community' were not included in *Ignition's* conception. Eventually, the resourceful and low budget *Back from Beyond* overshadowed the extravagant and expensive *Ignition* in various ways. *Back from Beyond* afforded the

production of various original songs, poems and videos, and its single final concert was better attended than all seven *Ignition* performances combined.

Sociomusical locals appreciate the unique characters of seemingly ordinary persons. They admire iconic characters like Peerie Willie and Billy Kay, and recognise their invaluable contributions to Shetland's sociomusical community. Willie and Billy remained personable, supportive and unmoved by credentials until their passing.¹¹⁹ Their legendary incorruptibility by delusions of grandeur, evident in stories people tell about them, became a model for personal relations. Those who fall prey to delusional egocentrism transgress the principle of horizontality. This stunts the growth of mutual character appreciation and interpersonal knowledge networks, essential to Shetland's epistemological tradition.

Back from Beyond proved that the hierarchical centralisation of creative decision-making power spoils a collaborative project's 'Shetland feeling'. As residents, BFB organisers were taking a social risk. The violation of local norms could have lasting social consequences for them. *Ignition* directors, having no significant local relationships, may not learn local principles and break them without consequence. *Ignition*'s 'community theatre' ignored local epistemological principles. More attention to operational logics behind interactions in particular situations (de Certeau 1984:21), i.e., ethnographic knowledge, would have improved *Ignition*'s approach and local reception.

5.2. *BECOMING INVOLVED WITH IGNITION*

The first thing I learned about *Ignition* was that it ‘explored Shetlanders’ relationships with cars and roads’. NTS production used this tagline when *Ignition* appears in my fieldnotes. It intrigues me that *Ignition*’s musical element did not feature experienced Shetland musicians in any capacity, but only Mareel students. This well funded, self-styled ‘community theatre’ project somehow did not involve any established local composers and musicians, and there were many to choose from. *Ignition*’s elements seemed scattered and confusing to many people, who thought it lacked unity. When my fieldwork began, on January 28th 2013, Lerwick *Up Helly Aa* celebrations were underway. People commented that a ‘silly’ car had something to do with the ‘*Ignition* thing’. *Ignition*’s promotional car was parked right at Mareel’s entrance for weeks, covered with a hand-knitted woollen mantle. Natalie Moffat, a Shetland singer-songwriter and sociology student at the University of Glasgow, remembered the knitted car as a bizarre artefact. She told me that, for many locals, *Ignition*’s car ‘debased knitting’ with the message that ‘anything goes’ with this traditional craft.

Hugh Nankivell, *Ignition*’s musical director, invited me to join the band as guitar player on March 10th 2013. Two close research participants joined *Ignition*’s band: bass player Hayden Hook and saxophonist/pianist Norman Willmore (both then 17). We started playing jazz together months before at WobblyGang. I first performed in Shetland with Norman and Hayden at Town Hall for the Jazz Club in December 2012, with Stevie and Amanda running the live sound. We played three 45-minute sets of Sunday Jazz at Mareel’s Café Bar, and afterwards, Hugh invited me and I accepted. When I asked what *Ignition*’s theme was, Hugh repeated the tagline: ‘*Ignition* explores Shetlanders’ relationships with cars and roads’. Rehearsals would take place on the following day at Mareel’s auditorium, expensive to hire, and excessive for the music and band size.

Only a few musicians showed up for the rehearsal at the 600 people capacity auditorium. *Ignition* was struggling with its musical aspect, as other students were jumping ship.¹²⁰ *Ignition*'s hired writer even joined the shrinking singing choir. One song repeated countless times the phrase 'our home Shetland'. From the stage, the English musical director and composer led the choir and an actress played, with an English accent, the folkloric White Wife from Unst – paradoxical combinations that made locals cringe. As participants noted, whereas the character was culturally odd, Lori Evans, the actress, counted among the few personable and approachable people in the production. The White Wife appears on the road at night to lonely men. Being from Unst, she should '*spik* Shetland'. When Shetlanders go 'south' or talk to outsiders, they often have to *knap*, meaning they 'speak' English. As some observed, a local actress would better fit that folkloric role while Lori's role as English hitchhiker would have greater cultural resonance. She could have investigated road safety in her hitchhikes and reported as an outsider. As the 'Brazilian' guitarist, hearing the chorus repeat 'our home Shetland' beside the non-resident English composer and actress also made me uncomfortable. Repeating 'our home Shetland' did not make it true.¹²¹ Perhaps I could believe the statement, as I was living in Lerwick since October 2012, and this was March 2013.

Joe Watt, then a 16-year old student at the National Certificate (NC) music course at Mareel, who would become a collaborator, and band mate in *SpoorHawk*, was the first to tell Hugh that Shetlanders have been writing songs about Shetland for a long time, so it would be of poor taste for someone without strong local connections to write and perform Shetland songs. Puzzled, Hugh doubted this assessment, unaware of the extent of Joe's immersion in the music scene. Despite the age difference, Joe had far more experience with the local music scene than Hugh could ever have appreciated. Joe is known as 'Sheila's boy' because of his mother, singer-songwriter Sheila Henderson (now Sheila

Duncan by marriage). Impressed, Hugh wanted Joe to join *Ignition*'s musical element. Joe concentrated on his work with *Wind Up Projectiles* (2013a, 2013b), featuring original songs that reflected meaningful, personal and social experiences. Noticing that *Ignition* would waste creative time, Joe stayed away. Singing 'our home Shetland' a hundred times and reciting bus stop names would horrify him. So 'why did we do it?' I wanted to understand how *Ignition* worked and how my jazz collaborators experienced it. Norman and Hayden knew that if they left, the live music would be ruined, so they stayed.

After a few rehearsals, I approached Hugh about *Ignition*'s music. I thought it could easily represent the variety and fluidity of local musics better, or at least give Norman and Hayden more space. Hugh told me it was too late to deviate from the pre-ordained plan. Still, we committed to seven performances, all but the last. Apart from four nights in Brae and three in Bigton, organisers scheduled a final performance in a stone quarry in Yell. This was too much for Norman, Hayden and for me, so we let the organisation know immediately that we were not doing it. They expressed disappointment. This struck us as odd. After all, they were on salaries and we were volunteering. Friends noticed that such 'guilt-tripping' effort is rare in Shetland, where potential musical collaborators understand that people have a host of other responsibilities and that commitment to musical projects hinges on a sense of friendship instead of prestige and profit. The NTS never considered how other commitments and responsibilities affected us. Hayden played the upright bass with *Wind Up Projectiles*, and studied at Mareel with Norman, who worked full-time. In addition to seven live performances, *Ignition*'s band committed to a technical rehearsal, a dressed rehearsal, and an exclusive performance for mainstream press reporters whom the NTS flew in from mainland Britain to cover the event. On the long run, hired newspaper praise covered up *Ignition*'s resource mismanagement, conspicuous only to locals.

5.3. *BACK from BEYOND: CREATIVE MULTIPLICITY and APPRECIATION*

Ignition's missing qualities were foundational in *Back from Beyond*, which many interpreted as Shetland's response to *Ignition's* extravagance. For them, *Ignition's* transgressions inspired BFB. *Ignition* was already over by the time BFB started taking shape. The name *Back from Beyond* evoked the ethnographic process cycle: immersion in difference and return to a place of reflection. Going into the unknown and returning transformed by making art about the experience. Inspired by sponsored journeys to natural heritage areas in Shetland, participants were encouraged to explore artistic, music making and video production skills. Recognising that everyone is creative, making and sharing art for personal growth and intergenerational integration were fundamental BFB values.

Emma told me that Alice and her proceeded with caution, and 'never said this is what we're doing'. They approached 'people as sounding boards' to gauge 'whether they thought [BFB] was a good idea and whether or not they would be involved and how it sounded to them'. They thought that 'if it was good and people liked it, it would start growing', Emma recalled. She explained that the project's horizontal spirit required commitment to face-to-face communications with potential participants. Emma and Alice sought and considered multiple opinions before making decisions. They drew on the social momentum of Shetland's cultural calendar, as supporting other local events would inevitably strengthen *Back from Beyond*. The creative multiplicity they achieved was contingent on this mutual support strategy. By making community well being an overarching principle, BFB became relaxed and easy to work with.

Back from Beyond funded trips for musicians, poets, and filmmakers to explore and express their feelings about a Shetland location. Trust and commitment to complete our creative projects were the only *moral* controls. Emma noted that 'community development approaches' require you to engage a 'community through word of mouth, gauge people's

opinions [and] adjust the project'. BFB organisers 'refined the project as [they] went along, based on what the temperature of the community was saying'. *Back from Beyond* would only pursue projects outside Shetland with support from well-respected local collaborators, who have a 'finger on the pulse' of their communities. As Emma remarked, 'we wouldn't turn up in Fife and say, we've got money to do this project, and this is what it is!'

For Emma, overlapping sociomusical network interconnections contributed to *Back from Beyond*'s success. She noted that Shetland's 'musical networks' are 'multilayered', so people can cross over genres in a productive 'interplay'. Her daughter Martha and husband Ewen have *spreeing* 'folky' and 'metal' connections, and so does Alice's partner Jonathan, who recorded *The Revellers*' album and used to perform with *Fiddler's Bid*.

For Norman, *Back from Beyond* 'was all about music' and 'much more focused on the sound', and the 'production staff' was 'really nice to us all the time'. Working with Jonathan Ritch and Mareel's live sound staff, 'was amazing' – they went 'through a lot of effort to make it sound good' and 'really wanted it to be good', Norman noted. But 'we were kind of atmospheric' in *Ignition* which 'wasn't all about the music'.

As Alice Mullay noted, locals often have difficulties connecting to creative projects that strike them as 'just some arty farty thing'. She often wondered why locals felt some projects were not for them. Such discordances inspired Alice and Emma. 'We did have that in our minds,' Alice told me, 'we wanted to do something that connected with people in a real way' and that felt 'relevant to them'. For her, their ultimate objective was bringing people together and proving 'how important the arts are'.

In one of three BFB trips, I accompanied *Teevliks* to the Isle of Noss, a bird sanctuary in June 2013. We took the ferry from Lerwick to Bressay. We crossed with our luggage to Noss on a powerboat and set up our tents in a grassy area protected by old rock walls. Until the next afternoon, I documented the five *Teevliks* members Martha Thomson,

Patrick Mainland, Norman and Hayden, Max Tyler and his partner Rachel Samson, as they visited Noss and composed their BFB tune. Hayden brought a bass and battery powered amp, Max a melodica and trumpet, and Patrick an acoustic guitar. Norman had bongos, Martha had her fiddle and camera, and I had cameras and a digital sound recorder. Emma accompanied us to Bressay, but returned to the mainland, while Glen Tyler, Max's father, spent the night at the ranger's cabin in Noss, behind our tents.

We followed Glen uphill toward the cliffs, avoiding bonxie nests as we stomped the heather. As we walked uphill, Bonxies hovered above in the gale, guarding their nests. The thick fog hid the cliffs from our view. The walk up took over an hour. My inappropriate leather boots, reinforced with plastic grocery bags, were soon soaked. Yet, the relentless uphill walking soon warmed the water around my feet. By the cliffs, Max played trumpet, Norman and Hayden danced, and after the exhausting walk back, we shared stories and played music in our tent into the night. In the next morning, after breakfast, we gathered at Max's tent, and *Teevliks* composed elements of their tune. They attempted to encompass different stages and aspects of the journey, the boat crossing, setting up tent, the long climb to the cliffs, the damp fog, and the night of conversation and music under the rain and wind. *Back from Beyond* produced and released this tune, and I edited the video. On November 23rd 2013, at Mareel's auditorium, *Teevliks* talked about their Noss experiences to a live audience and performed their composition while the video was projected.

5.4. 'YOU DON'T KNOW UNLESS YOU'VE LIVED IT'

Ignition insisted on hiring a non-resident to write Shetland 'community theatre' music, and approached music students as free assets, driving potential participants away. Yet, living in Shetland and becoming involved can afford the experiences outsiders need to appreciate the multiple interconnections and nuanced overlaps between family and

sociomusical-artistic networks. For Norman Willmore, ‘cultural difference’ was part of the problem. The interconnected complexities of local social realities are initially unknown and inaccessible to ‘metropolitan type’ outsiders (Simmel 1971:326). Norman explains,

People who aren’t from Shetland don’t really know how Shetland works. And it takes a long time to figure out how, like... people integrate with each other, and like the longstanding relationships families have with other families, and then there’s some things you can’t do, some things are okay. And for people coming from south, to just try and disrupt everything, and just not really understand the cultural or social implications or whatever... ‘cos you don’t know unless you’ve lived it, kind of thing...

As Norman suggests, uninformed outsiders have unwittingly disrupted longstanding harmonic relationships in intergenerational circles integrated by interpersonal knowledge. Such disruptions may have social repercussions. I point to Norman that NTS producers could have made better use of the historical and ethnographic literature available before executing their plans. Norman responds, ‘they could have talked to us more’, and

asked for a meeting at the start, with us all there, and be like, ‘this is what we have planned out’, the whole plan, from the very first idea to the performance, how it was going to go, what they wanted from us, what they actually wanted us to do, so we’d know what we were doing before being told different things from different people and then getting more and more elaborate in our minds and no one actually telling us what was happening. And then, being a bit of a let down when we actually got there.

For Norman, ‘there wasn’t enough communication’ with the NTS, and ‘maybe they thought we didn’t deserve as much’. He reasons that ‘it is hard for people who aren’t from Shetland to try and do something that big’. Norman compares *Ignition*’s communication approach with *Back from Beyond*’s. ‘Martha’s mom [Emma], and Max’s mom, Gina, are *like* Shetlanders’, he noted. Like Alice, who was ‘just amazing’, for Norman, they are ‘really passionate’, and are ‘not doing it for a job’. Gina, he explained, was also involved, ‘talked to us [Teevliks] a lot about organising dates and stuff’. For Norman, ‘they would have done it for free’, ‘never did it because they want to get paid’,

and only ‘got funding because they had to, to pay for ferries, accommodation, food or whatever’. Emma described BFB’s method as a ‘community approach’. Instead of telling people what to do, Emma and Alice bounced ideas with others slowly to see how they felt about the project, building up momentum. Following this informal consultation process, they harnessed enough confidence to proceed. Soon, all elements took shape and started falling into place seamlessly. Norman remembered how *Ignition* and *Back from Beyond* engaged potential participants differently:

[BFB] wasn’t like, big and long emails that no one wants to read, it was like, just sit down and have a coffee, and just chat about what’s going on, what we’re thinking, and what do you think, give us some ideas about what you think you could bring to the table and stuff... yeah, a lot more togetherness.

This contrast also reflects the interactive differences between both projects throughout our participation. BFB organisers listened and were personable, while *Ignition* was distanced and grandiose, with tiresome emails and inflexible schedules. Norman and Hayden experienced, for the first time, heavy handed *cornering* as recruitment strategy. NTS staff ‘kind of cornered us’, Norman told me. He was standing outside Mareel with Hayden, taking a break between jazz sets, when

This woman from *Ignition*, I still don’t know her name... She came up to us and was like – this was like maybe a couple of weeks after we’ve been sent all of the emails, the huge big email with all the rehearsal schedules that we didn’t really think we could make, because it was so far in advance, we couldn’t really tell if we were going to be free or not [...] and she was like, ‘yes, so can you make all these dates?’ and kind of, I don’t know what the correct word is... almost forced, but she didn’t force us to say yes, it was just very like... very heavy style of... it was like we were being cornered... it was just very forceful.

Her forcefulness struck them as odd. Locals do not approach potential collaborators in abrupt and impersonal ways. Locals noted that NTS directors targeted younger people with disabilities or from perceivably different ethnic backgrounds. Their way of speaking about this raised a red flag among locals. ‘We should *get*’ such a person, because ‘it would

look good’, was a typical formulation that locals found distasteful. As people abandoned *Ignition*’s music, organisers sought participants’ commitments more aggressively. Managed as musicians and volunteers, we were required to follow inflexible rules that restricted our sense of social creativity and freedom. *Ignition* also approached other young HC and HNC student musicians as potential volunteers, such as Max Tyler and Martha Thomson from *Teevliks*, who declined. Peter Keay played at a Mareel rehearsal and in Yell, and Eamonn Watt played the *cahón* a few times, having to ‘wing it’. In BFB projects, collaborators made their own creative decisions, and assumed responsibilities via non-coercive, horizontal, face-to-face dialogues with project organisers. This approach afforded respectful negotiations of project particulars. Horizontality characterised interactions between BFB organisers, production members, and volunteers.

5.5. *PRESTIGE, VOLUNTEERING and COMPENSATION*

Metropolitan types involved with artistic productions often arrive in Shetland expecting celebrity treatment. They also expect locals to be star struck and ‘phased’ with their presence. However, this directly contradicts the principles of interpersonal knowledge and horizontality. ‘One of the things I really love about Shetland’, Emma Perring told, is that ‘Shetland’s not phased by anyone’. She ‘was working on the American production that was up in Shetland the last two weeks’. Some ‘very rich American producers who are used to people running around and serving them’ were making ‘comments about why Shetland wasn’t bending over backwards to accommodate them’. Emma proposed that the reactions of the sociomusically involved toward *Ignition* resonated with horizontal mutuality principles, as ‘we don’t get phased it’s the National Theatre of Scotland coming up’. Similarly, some local musicians are aggravated when SADA treats outside production

crews and artists like celebrities. Their point is that, following local *Sprenciples*, the Shetland Folk Festival approach aims to integrate visiting and local artists.

An NTS crewmember drove Hayden and me to Brae on the night of the first *Ignition* performance. After some small talk, she realised that Hayden participated in a previous NTS project while attending musical high school in Aberdeen. She assumed that his motivation for participating in *Ignition* stemmed from the project's association with the National Theatre of Scotland. She asked, 'so you became involved with *Ignition*, then, *because* of the NTS?' Hayden hummed, and answered, 'no'. Like the other musicians, he was stuck with *Ignition*, after being pressured to commit. Hired production members were being well paid, but remained insensitive to our frustration, which was inconsequential for them. Norman shared mixed feelings about the project. He 'learned a lot' and 'Hugh was really cool', a 'nice guy' with 'talent', but 'it was annoying how they were all getting paid and we weren't and they had such a big budget'. Norman continues,

I don't know how much it was, but everyone was saying, 'it was a really, really big budget', and they are paying their staff for staying in houses in St. Olaf's street ... we wouldn't even get our petrol money to get to Lerwick, or like bus fare, or anything. We didn't get anything. We didn't get food. There was nothing, we just had to do everything ourselves, it was really annoying...

Norman and Hayden saved the live music aspect of the project from failure. NTS directors believed that the privilege of adding *Ignition* to our CVs was enough compensation for our work. At the Bigton performance, Hugh gave each musician a yellow rubber duckling. Hugh had gone around with other NTS people collecting trinkets from country shops 'for fun'. He came across yellow rubber ducks and thought they would make funny gifts for the musicians. Since we got nothing for performing, the ducks were intended as mementos and gifts. Norman, Hayden, Eamonn and I got ducklings. These rubber ducks symbolised the lack of sensitivity to local values underlying *Ignition's* approach to community. For Hayden's parents, Stevie Hook and Amanda Pearson, the

duckling became an offensive artefact, ‘a slap on the face’, mingled with their sympathy for Hugh. As bittersweet joke-insults, the rubber duckling gifts represented what was left in *Ignition*’s lavish budget for our effort.

By approaching the NTS people, I learned that they were there to execute their job and leave. Generally aloof, they rarely asked questions, and seemed only superficially interested in the local artistic scene. Anyone with genuine (or even feigned) interest has at least questions to ask. The NTS crew, as Norman pointed out, had things to tell us, commands to give, but hardly, if ever, questions to ask. For some among *Ignition*’s production crew, Shetland was the end of the world, where nothing interesting happened. Listening, essential to ethnography, was not part of their kind of professionalism.

5.6. *PERFORMING for IGNITION*

Ignition musicians had a number of responsibilities: we had to be at Mareel in time to take the chartered bus to Brae and later Bigton. Upon arrival, we waited backstage, where we sometimes had access to tea. We were actually expected to buy our own food, which we did in Brae. Any sociomusical Shetland shindig would include a *spre* session, but *Ignition*’s ‘community theatre’ featured the swirling ‘English’ White Wife from Unst, who served tea on rare china sets shipped from Edinburgh to the Brae and Bigton country halls for the occasion. As Alice Mullay noted, hiring the tea sets from Edinburgh ‘didn’t sit very well with people in the community’ because people have a ‘different mindset’. She noted that Shetland’s history of geographical isolation engendered ‘resourceful’ locals, who ‘look for solutions on their doorstep’. Musicians, however, were not allowed to socialise at the White Wife’s tea party. Production rushed us onto a bus to Lerwick immediately after every performance. The closest we had to a *spre* were games and singing on the way back to Lerwick during the bus ride.

When we arrived, production crew ignored us, made no welcoming gesture, and continued with their work. In a production set, all tasks are tightly scheduled and everyone must act according to a plan. Those in charge of making sure things work as planned remain under pressure, herding and directing participants into their respective positions at predetermined moments. Every night, the treatment we received was similarly curt.

In the first part of the show, the *English White Wife* from Unst sat on a darkened stage. Behind her, on a screen, an accelerated film, collected with a camera mounted on a car driving through Shetland roads, was projected. Songs from the *Ignition* CD played in the background. Through a microphone, she read from a logbook of phrases that started with ‘have you ever...?’ This inventory approach characterised most of *Ignition*’s presentation of the information Lori collected while hitchhiking. She would ask, ‘have you ever?’ followed by a snippet from something someone told her during a car ride. For example, ‘have you ever been stranded in Yell in 1947’? Some questions were odd, like ‘have you ever killed anything’? The projection said more than the decontextualized inventory styled text. This struck locals as an unsatisfying, even disrespectful presentation of the information collected from people who graciously contributed with their time.

On the dress rehearsal night, Hugh drove Hayden, me, and Elena Piras through the whole *Ignition* performance. Elena, a Sardinian singer, had moved to Shetland temporarily and joined *Ignition*’s vocal choir. The full show required driving to two other locations with hitchhikers aboard for dancing, parkour and theatre performances, and returning to the country hall for the White Wife’s presentation, live music, and tea. The ‘driving around’ approach, some thought, discouraged participation and support, adding to confusion about *Ignition*. Drained, Norman did not attend the final rehearsal. This annoyed Hugh. Norman held a full time job and played with various groups, including function bands, to save for upcoming university studies. Hugh wanted us to experience the *Ignition*

elements we would miss during actual performance nights, when we waited in the hall for the return of the driving audience and only saw the White Wife's performance.

The hitchhiking theatre element was next. We picked up our hitchhiker at the parking lot. He wore a long white gown, similar to the White Wife's. Hayden and I knew the hitchhiker, Joe Christie, who was studying for an upcoming musical theatre audition for college programs. He stayed in character, and we played along. The ride from the Brae Hall to the parkour and dance outdoor performance location took around 10 minutes. Meanwhile, Joe told us a story. His character searched desperately for professor Mishkalov, an expert on skimming stones. This light-hearted, comic story had nothing to do with road safety, or Shetlanders' relationships with roads or cars. Personally, for Joe, who wished to become a professional actor and performer, it was a valuable acting exercise. He spent months polishing this role. As Hugh tried to make up small talk about skimming stones, Hayden remarked that it would be nice to skim stones on a choppy sea. Thanks to Mishkalov's research, Joe remarked, we can learn how to achieve that. We arrived at the first destination, and the hitchhiker stepped out of the car. A production crew showed up, and instructed us on how to tune the car radio to the right channel, 87.5 FM, and said 'enjoy your show and please remain seated in your car'. Now we hear the soundtrack to the performance about to begin. Hugh asks, 'do you know what's going to happen here?' We are listening to car noises, synth pads and other special effects in the radio. Elena Piras is visually impaired, so Hayden volunteers a description, 'yeah, there's a car in front of us, parked... projecting a film of the sea'.

'Oh my god', reacted Elena, 'I wish I could see'. A couple danced outside, as youth performed parkour stunts over the car. After this, we picked up another hitchhiker and headed to the next location, the Delting boating club, where the vehicle theatre sets were parked. This time, the hitchhiker's depressing tale proved hard to engage. After ten

awkward driving minutes, we arrived. As the hitchhiker stepped out, Hayden remarked, ‘Good they’re getting practice’. I asked, ‘do we ever get out of the car too?’ ‘Yes’, Hugh answered, ‘someone is going to lead us somewhere else’. We waited for other cars to arrive, and saw that only about 15 vehicles, around 60 people, could attend *Ignition*. There were more cars than hitchhikers, as many could not commit to all performances. People in cars without hitchhiker actors were supposed to listen to songs from the *Ignition* CD.

Hugh, volunteers an explanation of *Ignition*’s concept, ‘you know, this is all based on Stuart’s... a kind of a memorial of the guy who died’. ‘5 years ago’, Hugh tells us, a ‘member of youth theatre in Shetland’, Stuart, died in a car crash. I knew that this tragic event mobilised locals to campaign for road safety education, setting *Ignition* into motion. Yet, Hugh remarked, the NTS decided to make the project much ‘bigger’ and more ‘interesting’ than just about road safety. Making it ‘bigger’ meant including ‘cars’ and ‘oil’. Supporting the oil industry with an artistic project is controversial among environmental minded local artists. *Ignition* seemed to celebrate Sullom Voe, the oil and gas terminal, with performances in Brae and Voe. Moreover, the name *Ignition* itself sparked this connection, reinforcing the idea that the terminal is an essential and perennial Shetland feature. Poet and singer songwriter Lise Sinclair (1971-2013), from Fair Isle, her cousin multi-instrumentalist and singer Inge Thomson, and fiddler Debbie Scott exemplify this environmental approach.¹²² Debbie Scott composed *Selkies’ Song* (2007), according to Peerie Willie (Scott and Johnson 2007), out of concern with the exploitation and destruction of seals. Even if *Ignition* was not explicitly promoting cars and oil, its ‘drive around’ theatre approach reinforced this interpretation. Driving to Brae or Bigton, then from the hall to two parking lots and back could take over two hours of expensive gas, making *Ignition*’s ‘community’ more exclusive. Locals promptly questioned the

resourcefulness of this model. Historically, socioeconomic resourcefulness has characterised Shetlanders' approach to resource scarcity, harsh weather and isolation.

We drove into the 'vehicle set', a parking lot with one bus, a camper van and a few cars with volunteer actors inside, powered by a loud generator. Wearing sparkly yellow jackets, the crew directed us into different vehicles. Hayden and I ended up on the bus. Faint blue lights decorated the interior. We got wireless headphones with a pre-recorded soundtrack from the crew. An unusual theatrical presentation took place around us. We noticed that others on the bus were not wearing headphones. They were the actors. They stayed silent and did not interact. Each got up and slowly moved around. In our ears, different voices read wistful words, supposed to describe their sights and thoughts in melancholic, even bitter tones. The nostalgic approach seemed socially empty, reflecting the writer's inexperience in Shetland. As sound enthusiasts, Hayden and I held on to the excellent audio production quality. Yet, this wistful ride did not resemble any bus trip I took in Shetland, where many riders usually know the bus driver and one another, and chat throughout the trip. Objectively, we were listening to a recording through headphones as we sat inside a parked bus. The text was not captivating, and much effort was required to pretend the bus was moving along. As a result, time began to drag. I turned off the camera to save battery, and turned it back on when we returned to the car with Elena and Hugh.

Hugh described his experience: in a post-apocalyptic Shetland, a character lived in a car, using artificial sunlight for vitamin D. A volunteer appeared and told us to drive back to Brae hall. We got no hitchhiker this time. On the drive back, Hugh told us more, 'do you know Davie? A really big, round, lovely man... looks like a fisherman. He's in a car on his own and tells a story'. It was Davie Gardner, one of Shetland's most respected and active promoters and supporters of the arts. It was odd that Hugh did not know this. Hugh asked us about the bus and Hayden volunteered a description:

Basically, you're all sitting there with headphones on, and there's people on the bus. A few people went in, and then... there's already people sitting there. We thought they were just listening to it as well, but we were listening to stories of their thoughts. So it's basically like... 'I can see my reflection'... 'I was talking to my brain today'. So, basically, you're hearing all of people's thoughts you're seeing and someone would stand up and it would be what they were thinking, and then another person would stand up and did this dance type thing.

The inner dialogues of introspective brains seemed odd to an extrovert and socially connected Shetlander. I pointed out that 'inventory', listing things, was an approach they were fond of: 'I see sheep, I see people, I see the road'. Hugh told us that Rob, the hired *Ignition* writer, selected more themes for him to adapt into music. That was too ambitious, so an inventory-based soundscape with what they imagined characters would see became a solution. Hayden and I nodded in agreement that the result was 'kinda sad' but remarked on the high quality of the recording. Finally, we arrived at Brae Hall to perform.

Whereas earlier the floor was arranged with worn out White Wife dresses on headless mannequins and listening stations for hitchhiking stories, now the hall had been converted into a makeshift teahouse. Foldable tables and chairs covered most of the floor. As the attendees returned and found their seats, the band played an instrumental intro. With the audience seated and the band onstage, the chorus, until then posing as audience, got up and walked around, singing. Meanwhile, the White Wife went around the tables, twirling around and serving tea from a large iron teapot. There was something about it that 'made you cringe', Hayden told me. There were no unifying thematic links between *Ignition* elements. The repetitive music and lyrics became increasingly annoying. The 'nursery rhymes' missed social educational elements that justified *Ignition*. Hugh did not focus on getting involved with the active sociomusical scene in Shetland. He played original compositions at the Singers and Songwriters night once. He also visited primary schools and 'composed' with the children. Local Tom Jamieson participated once. Since

‘they were only beginners’, doing ‘their thing’, Tom did not ‘want to ruin it for them’. Tom was expected to just play chords and have no creative input, so he just ‘left it with them’ after one rehearsal in Sandwick.

5.7. *ONSTAGE with IGNITION: TIME DRAG and PARODY-FLOW*

After tea was served, we played *Road to Yell*, the main theme for the paradoxical English accented White Wife from *Unst* folklore. Nobody frowned at the idea of an outsider learning about Shetland while hitchhiking. Yet, this hybrid *Ignition* character reflected a level of cultural, historical, and linguistic insensitivity. Local ways of speaking were not included in *Ignition*’s ‘community’ formula. Shetland’s history of linguistic oppression with English parallels indigenous experiences with colonialist homogenisation efforts such as residential schools, albeit not nearly as violent. As Marina Irvine told Millar in Whalsay in 2005, ‘ye really got into trouble fir no spikkin English’ (Millar 2007:152).

After *Road to Yell*, the White Wife described her role in the production. She arrived in September 2012, hitchhiked and collected stories. *Ignition* produced short promotional videos featuring her activities. From a script, she read snippets of ‘happy and sad’ stories that people told her between hitchhike stops. Over the song *All the Journeys We Made*, she declaimed an inventory of places that people visited or wanted to visit. As the chorus sang ‘all the journeys we made... all the places we’ll go to’, the White Wife read from a collection of place-names. Listing places provided a picture devoid of contexts and tangible experiences. The monotony inspired musicians to spoof the lyrics and melodies in spontaneous ways, subverting them with humorous improvisations. The formula ‘all the [x] we [y] and all the [z] we’ll [w]’ afforded ample room for word play. The impetus to parody and ridicule the repetitive refrains seemed almost irresistible, relieving the tension and restoring some flow. Lyrical subversion is widespread in Shetland. Songs like *On Da*

Piss, and Steven Robertson's *I Canna Spik Whalsa*' (Robertson 2013), an adaptation of a popular song into Shetland dialect humour, had been paradigmatic in my 2013 SFF experience.¹²³ We were unwittingly restoring creative flow among us, working against the time drag of *Ignition*'s repetitive lyrics, inflexible arrangements, and social insensitivity. Norman felt ambiguous about the musical content and the 'outfits' we had to wear. Although he 'almost felt embarrassed playing' the music, Norman felt 'nothing against Hugh', who 'was just doing his job'. Norman continued,

The tunes were basically nursery rhymes because primary school children had written them, and for the kind of people who went, like the kids' moms and dads, it was probably really nice for them to think, 'oh, my little boy wrote that', but for us, like, having some kind of clout in Shetland as musicians, to then stand onstage for seven nights, and play nursery rhymes and not even be able to kind of push the boundaries a little bit, have to be pretty restrained. Yeah, it did feel kind of embarrassing, and then being told like, we 'need to wear these outfits', and giving us shirts and stuff... [white shirts tucked in]... it was just like... it was just a weird vibe, I really didn't like it.

While we played, Norman pondered onstage, 'if there's anyone out there who like actually knows anything about music and hears us', they may 'think it's bad'. He did not want that 'kind of reputation'. He joked that 'after playing with *Teevliks* at *Back from Beyond*', he was still 'kind of embarrassed' for 'playing drums', but 'felt a lot better'. After *Ignition*, Norman noted, 'we were rushed' to 'just pack up our stuff' and 'get on the bus back... a sterile and stale environment'. As time dragged, we struggled to flow. As Csikszentmihalyi suggests, *Ignition* disrupted our personal goals and priorities, preventing the flow of excitement and motivation (1997:37). Overtime, 'inner disorder or *psychic entropy*' may 'weaken the self to the point that it is no longer able to invest attention and pursue its goals' (1997:37). Reviewing my footage, packed with fifteen months of events, I realised how short *Ignition* performances actually were, in contrast with longer activities

that flowed, such as the *Back from Beyond* trip to Unst with *The Revellers*, characterised by the continuous timelessness of harmonic flow.

Ignition's music incorporated nothing remotely resembling local sociomusical *sprees*. We were expected to keep quiet, perform, and leave swiftly. As Tsioulakis suggests, the hierarchical control of creative decision-making power disrupts the 'flow of energy between freely communicating musicians' with 'an advanced structure of obligations' that represents 'an extreme example of musical labor' (2013:219). Three days with *The Revellers* in Unst for *Back from Beyond* seemed faster than any *Ignition* performance. As the video *Lower the Rope (The Revellers 2013)* shows, filmed mostly during this BFB trip to Hermaness in Unst, our interactions were harmonised into an uninterrupted flow of interpersonal knowledge, horizontal mutuality, and conviviality.¹²⁴

5.8. *SPREEING against CREATIVE STERILITY*

The absence of a sociomusical *sprees* contributed to *Ignition's* creative sterility. As noted before, during the Shetland Folk Festival, sociomusical *sprees* dissolve tensions that musicians might experience from their live onstage performances. Nothing except its directors prevented *Ignition* from incorporating a Shetland style sociomusical *sprees* after every performance. As with most musical suggestions we made to Hugh, noting that *Ignition* should engage and include *sprees* and *sprees* was pointless. Later, *Back from Beyond's* final concert was followed by an *impromptu* sociomusical *sprees* open to all attendees. Whenever experienced *sprees* like Ewen Thomson, Maurice Henderson, *The Revellers* and others participate, sociomusical *sprees* naturally follow. For them, performing exclusively to paying audiences makes little sense. Backed by a lavish budget, *Ignition* directors somehow overlooked Shetland's most cherished musical practice, central to the SFF. For Norman, the genuine local character of *Back from Beyond* operations

afforded mutual appreciation among people of different musical backgrounds. This diverse and welcoming artistic convergence infused BFB productions and interactions with vitality and social meaningfulness, affording creative multiplicity. While BFB recognised all participants for their personal creative potential, *Ignition* demanded, without proper compensation, conformity to a repertoire that we felt openly ambiguous about.

Ignition's failure to engage local audiences intensified as locals wondered about its budget. *Ignition*'s spammy marketing flooded Mareel, where the unexplainable 'knitted car' was parked. Frustrated artistic observers noted that, with a fraction of *Ignition*'s budget, locals would do much better. *Back from Beyond*, later on that same year, showed that this critique was correct. Finally, after the end of *Ignition*, creative flow was restored as musicians had time to pursue projects that valued their personal contributions.

On November 23rd 2013, the *Back from Beyond* concert was followed by a sociomusical *spree*. It incorporated various original locals musics inspired by Shetland landscapes, with the intent of teaching about learning with others as creative individuals growing in mutuality. BFB celebrated the idiosyncrasies of equals, and personal ways of making music and art. Organisers only provided the framework of 'local environment as inspiration' and facilities like transport, accommodation, recording, the concert, and the website. Norman's reflections as BFB participant highlights the principles of intergenerational engagement, experimentation, social support, and artistic freedom elementary to Shetland's epistemological tradition:

I was kind of inspired by the older generation of folk fiddlers. They probably heard us and were like, 'oh, there's something in that as well', like, 'we can take this thing called jazz or whatever, and put that into our music as well...' as like... well, we've done the other way kind of thing? I think they must have got something out of what we played, because everyone said, 'oh, that was really good', and it seemed really genuine.

This genuine appreciation was missing in our *Ignition* interactions. If Shetland's sociomusical community felt engaged and included, even the simple but vital theme of 'road safety' would have afforded myriad creative expressions, with stronger social resonance. Road safety is not a cheerful theme. Unfortunately, since automobile accidents are common in Shetland, this theme will continue to be relevant. The NTS underestimated this and failed to catalyse its creative potential. Shetlanders follow community principles during grieving periods. In general, when anyone dies close to the place of an upcoming event, that event is cancelled. When someone dies in Whalsay, all gigs are off. Similarly, *spreers* refrain from making musical releases during grieving periods. The depth of interpersonal knowledge among families and face-to-face friendship networks foster profound connections across generations, throughout the islands.

If the NTS allowed resident musicians to have 'a say' in *Ignition's* music, the project would have attracted larger audiences and generated original music that would become part of local repertoires, as it happened with *The Revellers* and *Haltadans in Back from Beyond*. Very few people attended *Ignition* performances, which had more volunteers and production people than audience members. This gave hired directors and production crew much tension and anxiety. Hayden's parents did not show up to *Ignition*, Norman's parents or siblings did not show up, and none of the other Shetland musicians we knew showed up. In contrast, the *Back from Beyond* concert, on November 23rd 2013, involved 65 local musicians (as performers, sound engineers, filmmakers, poets, fine artists), and packed Mareel's auditorium, helping to fund the project further. Similarly, the Fetlar *spreer* of July 2014, organised by Maurice Henderson, Lewie Peterson and Lois Nicol, attracted, on a single night, to one of the farthest islands, a larger audience than *Ignition* managed to attract with seven performances. In 2013, I attended the local Drama Fest and the Pantomime with Amanda Pearson, when Norman Willmore was the musical director, so I

know that locally organised theatre events sell out. Intergenerational audiences curl up in laughter and leave with huge smiles on their faces. No such reactions happened with *Ignition* – staff, performers and volunteers outnumbered the audience and were expected to do the same thing night after night.

5.9. *IN STUDIO with IGNITION*

In neoliberal environments, while artistic commercialisation models remain seductive, the apparent achievement of power and success undermines lifelong friendships, creative freedom, epistemological growth and fluidity. The hybridisation of music making and commercialist exploitation engenders such pitfalls (see Boon 2000).¹²⁵ In Shetland, commercial imperatives in artistic projects have underestimated the creative multiplicity of interconnected familial networks marked by horizontal mutuality and interpersonal knowledge. Norman discussed his expectations and experiences with *Ignition*'s music and CD recording at Mareel's studio. He thought there would be 'much more writing involved, that we'd actually get a chance to write some music, and have our say, but it was all Hugh's music'. The *Ignition* CD was nominated for a critic's award. The nomination, which mentioned only Hugh, seriously annoyed residents who helped to produce the CD and felt that they had not been properly credited. Yet, since *Ignition*'s conclusion brought relief to sociomusical locals, they thought that claiming credit would be useless. Norman remembered that 'when we were in the studio' recording the *Ignition* CD,

I did a solo and then Hugh was like, 'don't play so much like Michael Brecker, try and play more like... easy to listen to', like, 'play simpler', and like restraining me, which in some ways in rehearsals and stuff is a really good way to like getting new ideas out and stuff, like if you've got a strict set of rules, you're going to use five notes to improvise with, then you'll come up with more inventive ideas, but like when it comes to actually recording it, you shouldn't be restricting... I don't think one should be restricting people like that and telling them how to play... you can give people ideas for sure, and say like, 'this is what I had in mind', but

I don't think you should tell people, 'this is how you have to play in this recording', kind of thing... and then, to not even pay us...

Everybody should be allowed 'to have a say', to make their own statement, according to Norman's logic and the principle of horizontality, especially when artists commit time to creative projects. Well paid, Hugh was pressured to deliver the final project as prescribed, which entitled him to order musicians around. For Norman and me, the reference to Michael Brecker goes back to a Tommy Smith concert at Mareel that we attended in 2012. I felt that Smith's tenor playing sounded a lot like Brecker's, a double-edged compliment-critique. Brecker was among his generation's most influential players. Yet, when anyone imitates him closely, it is like a number of well-known quotations were rearranged in disengaging pastiches. Hugh probably meant to say Norman was playing it all too jazzy and freely, with character rather than 'easy listening' precision.

5.10. *THE 'PROS DON'T SEE YOU' COMMUNITY THEATRE FORMULA*

During *Ignition*, hired production crew seemed aloof and managed participants as collective categories, the parkour guys, hitchhikers, musicians, choir, volunteers, and so on. With priorities attuned to commercial imperatives, outside producers hardly ever care about small communities and their members. Even when they wish to care and be respectful, relationships need time to grow. Sustained participation and involvement are required for cultivating relationships beyond the superficiality of first impressions and presumptions. Norman told me that hired NTS crew would be,

Even just saying things like, 'don't touch any of the microphones', and telling us really silly things about microphones, and mic stands, and how the PA works... We know all this, I've been doing gigs since I was 13, and I know how not to point a microphone at a speaker. I'm not stupid enough to do it, but just things like... treating us like we had never seen a microphone before, because we're from Shetland. Not as extreme as that, but like, they were just very like looking down on us the whole time. They just treated

us like we were small, and not really an integral part of the show whatsoever... they could have done it without us kind of thing...

Norman had been spending time around Hayden's live sound engineer parents for years. About a week before *Ignition* performances, on March 16th, Norman helped Stevie and Amanda set up the sound at the same Brae hall for the Brae and Delting *Up Helly Aa* hop night, featuring *The Revellers*. Whereas *Ignition*'s sound equipment consisted of a couple of microphones, the Brae hop involved transporting and setting up a large PA system, onstage monitors, microphones for four vocalists, full drum set, mandolin, banjo, acoustic and electric guitars, bass, and fiddle. We even helped to clean up the hall from drinks and trash with other volunteers afterward. For the NTS production, Norman was just some kid who played the saxophone and nothing else. In contrast, when Norman first came out with a saxophone from Clousta to a jazz workshop, Jonathan Ritch, the BFB sound engineer, attended with Stevie Hook, long before Norman was publically recognised as young Shetland musician of the year. Jonathan witnessed Norman's musical growth. Their friendship always reflects interpersonal knowledge and character appreciation. Mutual and genuine caring, a core epistemological principle in *Back from Beyond*, afforded grounds for creative multiplicity to emerge from existing social relationships.

BFB organisers championed an unwavering commitment to Shetland's sociomusical community, engendering what Norman called a 'home-grown' kind of 'Shetland feeling'. When I asked Norman whether he 'had complete creative freedom' working with BFB, he noted 'it was much more relaxed', while *Ignition* was 'so strict and hard-heavy going'. Diverse approaches to musical creativity guided each project. *Ignition* demanded that we played arrangements as the director conceived them. Hugh's creative authority did not flow from sustained involvement in local sociomusical networks. Rather, it stemmed from the job that the NTS hired him for, and on previous musical theatre experiences elsewhere. Shetland's sociomusical community was not involved in this decision. Curiously, Norman

was the musical director for the 2013 Pantomime season, performing every night. His partner Jane McLaren is a musical theatre performer and educator. Shetland's community theatre tradition is vibrant and intergenerational. NTS directors overlooked this simple fact of Shetland cultural life, separating instead of integrating *Ignition's* music and theatre elements. *Back from Beyond* organisers, alternatively, trusted the decisions of artist participants, acting in harmony with the local epistemological principles of artistic freedom and nuance of character appreciation.

5.11. SPIRITUAL CATHARSIS and NATIONAL EXPOSURE

In a conversation with Norman Willmore, I noted that many people were crying during the first act of the *Back from Beyond* concert, when the Mareel Music Makers came onstage – a collaboration between music students and people with disabilities. 'They were amazing – that was probably my favourite bit', Norman exclaims. He noted how *Back from Beyond* brought different musicians together, inspiring mutual appreciation between different styles. Norman was impressed with the *Haltadans* set, which was 'inspiring'. Their tunes and video, composed in Foula, were 'amazing' for Norman. Most importantly, noted Norman, the audience 'really enjoyed it', as opposed to '*Ignition* where seven or eight people showed up to the performance'. He found it ironic that *Ignition* 'got a really big' and 'really good review on the paper'. Norman observed, as others had, that *Ignition's* 'whole big marketing scam' tactics covered up its mismanagement of public funds.

Norman highlighted two contrasts between BFB and *Ignition* that were hard to miss for participants in both projects: BFB attracted a sizable local audience who were transfixed and mesmerised. The Mareel Music Makers performance drove most to tears. *Ignition* did not attract many locals, but paid journalists to attend one performance and

write positive reviews. National press coverage legitimised *Ignition*'s community theatre model, covering alleged budget mismanagement trails.

As local projects are rarely mentioned in the national press, the exposure soothed some observers. One told me that 'it placed Shetland on the map', which was good enough for him. The critical silence suggested that the NTS came to Shetland to teach locals what proper community theatre was all about. *Ignition* offered the social prestige of association with a National Theatre of Scotland production. This privilege attracted residents eager to participate in collaborative projects and learn from companies with national exposure. *Ignition* helped some feel connected to the community although the directors with creative power over the project were not community members of any standing. Those who felt socially isolated took part in a community simulation that provided opportunities to meet new people or pursue artistic careers. *Ignition*'s budget was large enough to spam Mareel, keep staff in expensive houses, fly journalists in and out, but not enough to feature established composers or to compensate young musicians whose artistic freedom was restricted in *Ignition* performances.

5.12. EPISTEMOLOGICAL DISCORDANCE and LOCAL PRINCIPLES

Chloe Garrick, now Tallack by marriage, reported discordant experiences with NTS directors. Chloe worked as a photographer in the earlier phases of *Ignition*. In September 2012, Chloe documented actress Lori Evans hitchhiking and collecting stories, and some of the knitting element. 'I've seen a lot of the different sides of the project', she tells me, 'they didn't connect to each other'. 'I just find that the whole communication was just ridiculous between them with each other', Chloe noted, 'they obviously didn't know really what was going on'. Once, production crew even tried to stop her from parking at the Brae Hall, arguing that the space was reserved to the audience that never came. The information

collected in Lori's hitchhikes, of ethnographic and historical importance, disappeared.

Chloe explains,

I joined them for the hitchhikes, for Lori, which was really fascinating, but it seemed like such a shame that the work that she put, she put in a huge... I think she put in the most hours out of the lot of them, and that [was] really personal... she was walking for miles, but like it was fascinating some of the information that she got, and then it's a shame that they [wouldn't use it] – it could have been on the radio.

Ignition directors reduced the hitchhiking stories to inventory lists and did not make them available in a database or publish them in a collection. During the first part of what the crew called the '*Ignition* experience', attendees had some minutes to listen to snippets from stories on small computer speakers. 'That's not probably how I would have wanted to present it', Chloe told me. *Ignition*'s snippet presentation obscured the stories. For Chloe, stories that were once 'fascinating' became just 'a snip'. Many remarked that Lori's stories could have played a more central role in *Ignition*.

Chloe told Norman and me about the 'final *Ignition* event', which most band musicians could not attend. For Chloe, 'in the beginning, it was fine', as residents John and Jackie delivered quick speeches explaining *Ignition*'s original conception. However, NTS directors followed up with radically different, lengthy, 'Oscar like' ceremonial speeches. They 'went on for ages, saying how amazing it was that they got to be involved and that they got to do the project', Chloe recalled, and it all 'ended up being about *them*'. As she lingered on this sour note, Norman hummed an ironic, elongated tone. The last *Ignition* 'community theatre' event gave NTS directors grandstanding platforms. They had little to say about the local community, since they were not involved. For Chloe, 'it just seemed so far away from the point of it', that is, community theatre.

When an NTS director, who visited twice before, flew in for his final event speech, Chloe drove him up to Yell. She was struck that 'he had no concept of the project', which

she ‘kind of explained to him in the car on the way up’. We laughed at how directors could take credit for a project they knew so little about. Yet, their lavish use of public funds in an age of austerity cutbacks in arts funding was disturbing, especially for local artists. This director seemed as distant as the *American Idol* television producers whom Meizel encountered during fieldwork (In Cooley et al. 2008). He returned to Lerwick for a quick feedback session that I attended with Amanda Shearer. The NTS was only interested in positive feedback shared in minimalistic post-it notes. As Chloe noticed, ‘it was almost like they were using the public, instead of inviting them in’. Such projections of impersonality (Weber 1958[1921]:65), typical of the metropolitan type (Simmel 1971:326) do not resonate harmonically with local sociomusical principles. Though ‘they must be a brilliant organisation when they are doing their own thing’, Chloe noted, ‘they were completely out of their depth here’. Ultimately, the NTS holds the stories that Lori collected. The NTS had enough resources to engage sensibly Lori’s hitchhike stories, strengthening *Ignition*. Locals aptly deconstructed *Ignition* regarding its budget use, organisation, communication, and approach to local volunteers and musicians.

The NTS followed industry standards for getting jobs done. They hired outside musical and theatre directors, a main actress, and production crew for seven performances. This contradicted the local principle of resourcefulness, as several residents could fill those positions. For Norman, *Ignition* represented ‘the industry’. Norman realised that ‘if you’ve got something to offer, they will try and take that from you’. The ‘industry’, he noted, ‘they kind of take you for a ride’ to ‘see how much they can get out of you for free, if you’re talented or whatever’. Looking back, Norman is ‘not that bitter about it really’, for he ‘did have fun’. Engaging this ‘industry’, however discordant, was a learning experience that inspired Norman to confirm his commitment to the core values and principles of the *sprea*. As he noted, ‘we got to play together, which is always the best’. Outside production

professionals are usually not interested in developing reciprocal relationships with locals and being integrated in the community. Enthusiasm about *Ignition* or Shetland was not required from them. In *Back from Beyond*, enthusiasm was the key ingredient for a professionalism attuned to local sensibilities. Organisers and production crew were engaged, invested and involved in the community for life, as residents born or married in Shetland. BFB's productivity flowed from longstanding, mutual sociomusical relationships that kindle potential for creative multiplicity.

However, two *Ignition* participants, unwilling to adopt detached professional attitudes, cultivated meaningful relationships in Shetland. Chris Grant came to Shetland from Glasgow to work as the *Ignition* parkour director with his partner Roo Callahan. They showed that professionalism, cultural sensitivity, and caring can develop in parallel. Having arrived several months earlier, Chris and Roo were more independent from the NTS than production crewmembers and directors who focused mostly on the performances and made no local connections. Parkour teaching requires face-to-face interactions exploring townscapes, providing a base for interpersonal intimacy and involvement. As they spent more time with residents than among *Ignition* crew, they soon became integrated. Chris was even invited to guize at the Lerwick Up Helly Aa. They have since moved permanently to Shetland.

CONCLUSION:

5.13. *The FLOW of CARING and INTERPERSONAL APPRECIATION*

This chapter shows that the presence or absence of *caring* can have tangible effects in artistic collaborations. As Titon (2008:40) observed, friendships based on a ‘musical being-in-the-world’ can ‘involve both mutual gain and caring for the other’. In contrast, cold professionalism is double-edged, for emotional divestment affords automatic disconnections. In Shetland’s sociomusical scene, most believe that creative work deserves compensation, but if profit becomes the only reason for collaborating, the result is less meaningful, devoid of emotional investment. Putting one’s ‘heart into it’ is paramount. Seeking for prestige, profit and self-aggrandisement may distance and sever connections.

Professionalisms dependent on hierarchical authority and control, secured by monetary compensation, are devoid of caring. As Tsioulakis observed among Athenian instrumentalists, the egalitarian mutuality of a scene might be ‘replaced by a complex web of authority and convention’ as soon as someone is designated as the ‘bearer of authority and directs the performance’ (2013:218-219). As performers in *Ignition*’s band, we engaged distancing, hierarchical social structures in which the distribution of creative decision-making power was not appreciated. These experiences disrupted the flow of our lives with discordances that were nevertheless productive on the long run, inspiring reflections on local principles and affording exposure to the practices and values of what Norman called the ‘industry’. During the *time drag* of *Ignition* performances, the band often parodied the show, restoring a sense of flow. Alternatively, *Back from Beyond* experiences were intensely social, mutual and harmonic, enhancing the flow of our lives, aligning our goals and objectives with creative tasks.

Caring and not caring attitudes distinguished the modes of professionalism I analysed in this chapter. *Ignition*’s hired staff members were rarely interested in engaging locals in genuine, personal ways. Chris and Roo were the only exception. Most never came

back. *Ignition*'s performance production crew was hired exclusively from outside. For them, visiting Shetland was just another chore. Their visible lack of interest in local characters and aloofness contributed to the resonance that Norman called *Ignition*'s 'sterile and stale environment'. As *spreer* Lewie Peterson noted, professional musicians may 'lose their love of [music] quite quickly' and 'it becomes a bit of a chore'. *Back from Beyond*, which included Lewie's band *The Revellers*, followed socially appropriate modes of engaging and securing commitment, making sure that participants only became involved because they really wanted to.

As Csikszentmihalyi noted, 'all flow experiences' involve a 'mutual relationship between goals and the efforts they require' (1997:224). Local epistemological principles harmonised the goals and efforts of *Back from Beyond* participants. BFB's frugality, financial and social resourcefulness were prodigiously effective ingredients in a recipe for kindling creative multiplicity. By cultivating mutual flow among collaborators, production, and organisers, BFB unleashed the creativity inherent in Shetland's interconnected sociomusical networks. Ticket sales for *Back from Beyond*'s final event covered all budget expenses. In contrast, *Ignition*'s extravagant performances were poorly attended and the project forgotten. Finally, adopting a sociomusical 'community approach' principle, *Back from Beyond* activated productive mutuality and artistic freedom, affording the emergence of creative multiplicity.

CARING for VOICE: CREATIVE MULTIPLICITY and MUTUALITY

Shetland creative projects usually take all participants into consideration: collaborators are not expected to do anything they find annoying. Emma and Alice were responsible for making *Back from Beyond* fulfil its mission and let the artists do whatever they felt was appropriate without undesired artistic direction. Note that Emma is a

classically trained violinist and Alice is a musical therapist, music teacher, pianist and flautist. Other local collaborative projects also followed open approaches. Considering, listening, and valuing creative input from others is common to Shetland musical collaborations in multiple genres. Michael Williamson composes the original music material for the rock group *North Country Fair* (NCF), which he founded. Michael has the final word on the aesthetics of the albums. Yet, he takes into consideration creative input from friends and shares new compositions with them. Ewan Nowak composed the music for *SpootHawk's A Good Haul* (2015), and made all production decisions, epitomised by meticulous editorial control of all tracks. Yet, band members made suggestions unrestrictedly, contributing with something of their own to the album (see Guest 2014a). We tried out ideas that were eventually developed or discarded. Yet, the person with most responsibility for the project, which includes funding the recording, editing, mixing, mastering, artwork and release, usually has the final word.

The professionalism that *Back from Beyond* and other *spree* principled institutions, such as the Shetland Folk Festival, manifested, is characterised by face-to-face interactions, friendship-oriented relationships, and the horizontal distribution (*not* the hierarchical centralisation), of creative decision-making power. Its epistemological fluidity is contingent on an appreciation of individual potential that fosters mutual autonomy and trust. In other models, professionalism presupposes following orders and delivering products and services in consistent, regulated, and systematic ways. In creative projects that follow the principles of Shetland's epistemological tradition, encapsulated in the *spree* form, being personable, respectful, convivial and helpful is paramount. Work flows easily when collaborators feel they belong in the project and share responsibility for its success.

FREEDOM and the COMMUNITY PRINCIPLE

Shetland's sociomusical world is characterised by complex interpersonal connections that span generations. These connections are largely invisible for outsiders and are maintained through constant and vibrant lines of communication. As such, they promote a deepening of interpersonal knowledge, ensuring that relationships kindle harmonic resonances. Incoming production crews have historically ignored these dynamics. The NTS was not exception to this rule – they were analogous to the overbearing and arrogant tyrant warrior in the Chukchee tale that villagers seek to 'free themselves' from (Boas 1955[1927]:329-330). Shetlanders prefer having egalitarian face-to-face interactions to following those defined by hierarchical power structures. This trend that Cohen (1985) noticed in Whalsay is still alive in Shetland, holding back structural forces that undermine the strength of local social networks. Taking part in *sprees* is important for keeping the preference for genuine face-to-face interactions alive, undermined as they are in the corporate, hierarchical and impersonal age of neoliberalism (see Ganti 2014, Wilf 2014).

The most significant structural and practical differences between *Ignition* and *Back from Beyond* manifested in each project's approach to the distribution of creative decision-making power. Trusting the social and creative resources of local artists, BFB achieved creative multiplicity. This stemmed from BFB's integration in the community and its harmony with local principles of horizontality, interpersonal knowledge, intergenerational engagement, creative freedom, personal artistic development, and nuance of character appreciation. *Ignition* directors, alternatively, feared that locals could spoil their 'professional' production and rarely consulted them, insisting on keeping full authority and creative control over the project. They forced musicians to perform music without giving them the opportunity to, as Norman put it, 'have a say'. While working for *Ignition*, we experienced 'a structured scheme of authority and power' (Tsioulakis 2013:219) that was

at odds with the local epistemological tradition. Overall, the National Theatre of Scotland's communication poverty clashed with Shetlanders' matter-of-fact convivial mutuality.

Expecting locals to line up and serve them is not exceptional among outside production crews. Seen from the perspectives of resident participants, outside production projects, not attuned to local principles, represent a permutation of what Simmel (1971:326) called the 'metropolitan type'. Shetland sociomusical scene inhabitants know this, but are usually tolerant toward visiting producers, preferring to avoid discordances. As Laughey argued, in 'metropolitan impression-making' contexts, the 'cosmopolitan attitude' of 'higher social classes fuelled a fashion system that enabled them to differentiate their identities from those of the lowly majority' (2008:94). Outside production professionals like those in charge of *Ignition* have brought similar attitudes to Shetland, preventing the growth of meaningful personal and social relationships.

Emma and Alice, like most *spreers*, believe creative collaborations should never be experienced as chores. *Back from Beyond* supported individuals and groups with artistic freedom and facilities for developing and sharing personal voice and character, and for being appreciated by appreciating the creative efforts of others. *Ignition*, however, is neither the first nor the last production to come to Shetland projecting readily perceptible insensitivity to well-established, interactional mores.

CHAPTER 6: EXPERIENCING CREATIVITY

6.1. INTRODUCTION: CREATIVE REGULATION

This chapter presents the voices of young Shetland musicians, and their perspectives as reflections of their social world and personal situation at that time. The following ethnographic sketch reveals how young Shetland musicians who also study and play jazz talk about personal experiences with music education, in academic and social settings, and how they see their evolving sense of musicality developing in close contact with the local folk tradition. For the young Shetlanders featured in this chapter and who were born already immersed in the music scene because of their parents' committed involvement (i.e., Joe, Hayden, and to some extent Lewis), music making began as an informal, social activity. Hayden went on to get his 'grade 8' certificate in classical cello, and then moved on to an institutionalised educational setting in Aberdeen. There, 'academic' music became 'boring' for it did not seem to encourage the free development of one's own voice. Hayden returned to Shetland and started the group Troppo Funk, playing electric bass with Norman Willmore on sax, Joe Watt on guitar, Max Tyler on keyboards, and different drummers, starting with Bobby Sutherland (who played at the 2011 Tall Ships festival in Scalloway), Finlay Jamieson, and eventually Lewis Murray.

Norman first started studying music academically, but soon afterward began playing live gigs regularly. Norman became gradually immersed in an intense social world, characterised by strong friendships with a number of more experienced older musicians, whose personal stories Norman approaches as a treasure trove of sociomusical knowledge. In a recorded conversation, I asked Norman and Joe how many gigs they have played to live audiences. Their lower estimate was about 700 each. Hayden 'started off' expanding his knowledge of music through what his father showed him, but soon began exploring musical materials alone, making his own meaningful discoveries and trying them out on the instruments he plays. Yet, parental support, as Brandon noted, is a major factor in the

formation of devoted musicians. Many other Shetland musicians I know grew up in families that constantly encouraged their musicianship, such as Martha Thomson, Chloe Robertson, Kaela and Astryd Jamieson, Ewan Nowak, Arthur Nicholson, Maggie Adamson, Lewie and Erik Peterson, and many others.

Norman, Joe, Lewis and Hayden recognise that Scottish and Shetland traditional musics contribute to their musical formation. It was inevitable that they would grow up immersed in the local traditional music ‘vernacular’, as Joe called it, and exposed to various other musical genres. Hayden, inspired by Ray Charles and Fats Waller, formed a blues band when he was only 10 years old, playing piano and singing with other friends his age. He called the group the Two Pot Screammers, an Australian slang idiom that Hayden picked up during a visit to his mother’s brother, a radio disc jockey there. It refers to people who get wasted after having just two pints of beer.

In the conversation featured in this chapter, Joe Watt found the academic side of music ‘irrelevant’. As Brandon put it, the point of making music is pursuing the musician’s ‘own personal thing’. For Lewis, ‘music sounds better when it’s coming from you’ and has ‘your own twist’ than when you’re ‘playing by the book’. For him, there’s a ‘total difference’. Clearly, the difference is the feeling of freedom from perceived restrictions, even while adhering to certain parameters, like keeping time and listening closely to other musicians. The ‘realm of “saying something”’ in jazz is ‘beyond technical competence, beyond the chord changes’ (Heble 2000:219). Experienced jazz musicians look at chord charts not simply as absolute restrictions on what notes they can or cannot play, but as potential maps that can lead to interesting alternative harmonisations that may happen spontaneously during a performance. And it seems very obvious for Joe that ‘intense musical tuition’, as Brandon suggested, generates what Hayden experienced as boring constriction. They all talk about ‘funking up the trad’ – and how that drives them as a

living model of creative engagement. *BongShang* and *Fiddler's Bid* started 'funking up the trad' when their members, such as Bryan Peterson and Maurice Henderson, now approaching their forties, were still teenagers. These older musicians would refer back to their teenage years and point out that they were like the present day 'Troppo Funkers' as they are known in Shetland. And, as Hayden notices, even those bands that achieved a certain success outside Shetland were not making commercial decisions in order to conquer the market, but playing 'for the people of Shetland'. As Norman pointed out, 'music is developing all the time' and that is one of the reasons why people do different things. Doing 'your own thing', as Joe pointed out, is still important. And, as Hayden retorts, it is 'still accepted'. And then, they finish off their conversation with Brandon by mentioning Harris Playfair's big band project, which brought 'jazzers' and 'folkies' together into a 'fucking brilliant' and 'awesome' mix. As Hayden characterised it, 'the feel was perfect'. Peerie Willie is known for introducing the gypsy jazzy feel into Shetland's traditional music, modifying the whole culture through experimentations with musics from his period and participation in the local *spre* scene. Peerie Willie acted according to the integrative resourcefulness and engagement with past and present that is at the core of Shetland's epistemological tradition of music making, just as we see with Troppo Funk.

The principles of the *spre* support the development of personal character and encourage all present to engage freely with musical materials they enjoy. They support the legacies of previous generations of local musicians who are valued for what their characters and life stories represent to the living, and how these stories connect the trajectories of musicians and music lovers around them. We may characterise this approach as a type of jazzy integration, that is, learning new materials in order to recast them into various different improvisations, present personal positions and their perceived circumstances, and discover inspirational paths for developing one's own approach.

For the Shetland musicians featured in this chapter, the wilful transgression of stylistic boundaries and traditionalised aesthetics or repertoires is a form of creative freedom and engagement with cultural materials that develops one's sense of personal character by extending the potential range of their expression. Musical knowledge can extend and restrict, and jazz musicians have found methods to avoid being 'condemned to recreate' (Werner 1996:56). As we see in the personalised method that guitar instructors in Shetland, such as Stevie Hook, Brian and Arthur Nicholson, have adopted in their work with young pupils, horizontality fosters friendships between instructors and apprentices, giving power to the reciprocal, reflexive and mutual development and appreciation of nuances of personal character. This mutual appreciation is also a strong feature of these students' relationships with music teachers and engineering staff at Mareel, Bryan Peterson, Fraser Mouat, Alice Mullay and Jonathan Ritch.

In Shetland, musicians have often expressed their annoyance at how visiting production companies have treated them as having to fit some stereotypical musical mould that is at odds with their views of themselves. Music making can also afford experiences of creative constriction, depending on the power dynamics that exist between musical collaborators. Norman Willmore articulated this point while describing the contrast between *Back from Beyond's* attunement to local principles and the discordant neoliberal *modus operandi* that the National Theatre of Scotland adopted in its vision of community theatre, *Ignition* (Chapter 5). Jamming among friends who value one another as equals does not feel like working under the artistic direction of an unfamiliar producer in a studio.

6.2. *JAZZY SPREEING and CREATIVITY in ANTHROPOLOGY*

Current discussions of creativity in Anthropology would benefit from a focus on the social dynamics of character formation and appreciation, which would explain how people develop their own idiosyncratic voice and personal touch while immersed in a familiar social world and experiencing a trajectory infused with systemic constrictions. Institutionalised regimes of homogenising, naturalised symbolic violence, and bureaucratic control are challenges that individuals engage with in personal ways. In other words, the notion that creativity is the exclusive realm of ‘highly exceptional individuals’ obscures the ‘social dimensions of creativity’ (Wilf 2014:398). According to Wilf, a mainstream narrative, instituted as ‘part of the fabric of the popular imagination in the West’, views poetic inspiration as ‘sudden, effortless, and complete’, i.e., emerging from the ‘inborn inner nature’ of the exceptional individual (Wilf 2014:398).

For Runco and Jaeger (2012:95) a ‘standard definition of creativity only pinpoints which criteria must be used’ and ‘it does not say anything about who is to judge each, and who is to judge the judges’. They note, however, that ‘surprise’ is often one of those criteria, and that ‘novelty’ and ‘originality’ are ‘vital for creativity’ (Runco and Jaeger 2012:95). Ingold and Hallam’s (2007) conception of creativity is more open, viewing every engagement with materials as part of a creative improvisation process. Publications that predate the 20th century note ‘originality and usefulness’ as elements of creativity (Runco and Jaeger 2012:95). They argue that ‘creativity benefits from permeable cognitive structures’ or greater emotional, affective, and intellectual flexibility (Runco and Jaeger 2012:95). My experiences with young Shetland jazz musicians and older connoisseurs suggest that their experiences of creativity, freedom and spontaneity are intimately associated with the development and appreciation of personal character and musical voice, through the conscious creative transformation of musical materials (as opposed to

imitation). Other factors include inspiration from social life, Shetland locations, freedom to search for the surprising and unpredictable beyond prescribed aesthetic forms, without rejecting established aesthetic forms. Shetland's epistemological tradition, encapsulated in the *spree*, kindles resonances among people, fostering social creativity.

Over time, my gradual and personal involvement in the sociomusical worlds of Shetlanders allowed me to transcend the limitations of approaches that seek to 'identify the meaning of texts, performances, or entire genres in terms of purely symbolic, context free content' – by living with them, I began to understand the 'multiplicity of indexical connections that enable verbal art to transform, not simply reflect, social life' (Bauman and Briggs 1990:69). Music, as a verbal art with poetry and lyrics is deeply entangled with the everyday 'fluidity' of communicative practices in the social world (Lord 1960:100). By producing melody and speech, music is inextricably intertwined in semantic-experiential dimensions of voice, 'inner reverberation' and 'engulfing sonority' (Wagner 2001:137), manifesting the 'interpenetration of the outer and inner worlds' (Stoller 1989:120).

Creative processes are ubiquitous in social dynamics. As 'communicative and improvisational events with real-time emergent properties', they involve 'human and nonhuman agents in the context of pre-existing yet malleable genres and constraints' (Wilf 2014:397). According to Wilf, ethnographers should consider the 'role of socialization, apprenticeship, and pedagogy/learning in the making of creative individuals, implicating the process of social reproduction' and how 'exemplars of creativity' actually 'acquire their value' (Wilf 2014:398). The sociomusical formation of personal character manifests through those who produce, 'interpret, circulate, and reanimate' them, 'communities of listeners' that procure 'public spaces' where 'technologies of reproduction, amplification, and broadcasting' make 'them audible' (Weidman 2014:4.9).

In Ingold's (2013b) discussion of creativity, originality and innovation are not defining characteristics of creative processes, and imitation is considered to be just as creative as inventing something new. This logic proposes that being in the world is already a creative act, and that the process of making something, even if by imitating and following pre-established scripts, brings something original and unique into the world, linked to that very moment, to those present, and so on. Therefore, the same Bach cello suite played a hundred times will sound and feel always different, and therefore, at least according to its context, original and creative, as long as players and listeners experience it as original and creative. Nicholson's (2005, 2014) interviews with experienced jazz musicians provide an alternative set of relationships between imitation, freedom and creativity – for them, imitation can become a problem restricting one's sense of creative freedom and the development of a personal voice and character.

Many musicians find that the taste for musical novelty is a driving force in their musical trajectories, and the thought of repeating and imitating is eventually substituted by the drive to create and to invent. Learning bits of solos, phrases, harmonies and melodies, becomes like a way of exploring a language. As in academic scholarship, orthodoxies and cliques form, and specialists defending a narrow vision, telescoping and directing the access to content and its evaluation as traditional or not, canonical or not, authentic or not, emerge and gather momentum. Eventually, these models fail to hold people back from creatively adapting to and engaging with the living world.

Jazz has become an important element of Shetland's epistemological tradition of music making, mostly because of its attunement, as an epistemology of freedom and involvement, with the principles of the *sprea*. Peerie Willie, as Brian Nicholson pointed out in our conversation, changed the local music culture, and his inspiration was the jazz that was emerging in the 1940s and 1950s. The urge to experiment, to make music

personal, and to think that power and class differences are irrelevant, are key features of Peerie Willie's musical character, compatible with the epistemology of early jazz. Seeking to integrate musics, musicians, rhythms, harmonic and melodic ideas from anywhere made sure jazz retained its international character. Strong jazz roots were quickly established in Europe as the music spread. Miles Davis, Dexter Gordon, Eric Dolphy and many others spent long periods in Europe, collaborating and interacting with local musicians, sound engineers and music lovers. As socioeconomic and political interests came into alignment with the music, canonical and stylistic restrictions were promoted, marketed and imposed. Those who adhered to them benefitted economically from the privilege of being associated with the style of the *status quo*, which, for one thing, tried to sanitise jazz from fusion.

The epistemological tradition of Shetland music making and jazz models that integrate rather than exclude are principled practices that seek to transcend the limitations of highly patterned, classist and racist societies. They form a culturally relativistic bridge between people who would otherwise be considered fundamentally different and not fit for interacting. The classic example I have chosen is the lifetime friendship between Billy Kay and Peerie Willie, for whom class differences were absolutely irrelevant. Wilf's 'ritual of creativity' refers to a type of institutional jazz pedagogy that compels students to imitate, transcribe, memorise and perform 'precise replications' of improvised solos of 'past jazz masters' in 'synchrony with the original recordings in the classroom' (Wilf 2012:33).

Since the 'subject of imitation' is the 'individual creativity' of canonized jazz masters, Wilf argues, those who replicate those solos experience something 'deeply creative' (Wilf 2012:33-40). Yet, jazz musicians have historically wanted to invent and develop their own voice, rejecting a static canonized tradition. Jazz lovers continue to long for the 'sound of surprise' (Nicholson 2014:35) and actuality. They want to hear engagement with life, not failed attempts at re-enacting inimitable characters. Pat Metheny,

who rejects the notion that jazz is ‘America’s Classical Music’ as a ‘myth’, urges musicians to be involved with ‘what the music can become’ not what ‘it has already been’ – ‘emulating what’s already been done’ violates the principles of extension and immediacy in the music (*In Nicholson 2005:102-104*). Learned jazz audiences find that tribute bands, mired by nostalgia ‘for an art form that is still largely in the present’, provide but ‘a pale imitation of the original or a half-hearted reinterpretation’, because musicians are trying to do ‘someone else’s thing instead of their own’ (Klopus 2009 *In Nicholson 2014:36*). The jazz education system is becoming ‘increasingly codified and standardized’ and the ‘tendency to over-organise jazz pedagogy’ is an obstacle to those striving ‘to develop their own voice’ (Nicholson 2005:101). The ‘jazz education production line’ generates stylistic homogeneity, ‘passionless’ performances, as ‘idiosyncrasies get ironed out’ (Nicholson 2005:101). Recording technologies turn any spontaneous moment into a fragment that can be isolated, analysed, copied and reused. Standardised pedagogical approaches proliferated in curriculum-based, homogenised music teaching, and negative power dynamics in pupil-teacher interactions can spoil pupils’ music making experiences, making what should always be a pleasure something boring and constrictive. For banjo player Lewie Peterson, the absence of social pleasure in music making would spoil it.

Many students who had demanding, overtly formal music teachers that emphasised drills and exercises over personally meaningful musical content seem to eventually lose interest. Yet, as fiddler Mary Rutherford and Joe Watt pointed out in their interviews, there are pupils who are stimulated by competitive and regimented approaches to teaching. Watt’s experience with Margaret Scollay, who is considered a very serious teacher, was not so easy, but it taught him a certain discipline towards music that he finds absolutely invaluable and is very grateful for as an improvising musician. Rutherford’s engagement with competitive fiddling was just another stimulating aspect of playing, which was mostly

non-competitive. Most local *spreers*, including Joe and Mary, prefer the ‘social aspect of playing’, i.e., ‘bonding with people over it’ with the music and the ‘conversations’ that follow, as Lewie Peterson articulated. If the personal and social relationship with the instructor is too unpleasant, music becomes a chore. In Shetland, the *spree* is an ideal conduit for strengthening interpersonal knowledge and forging sociomusical relationships. As such, *spree* participation uses ‘the connections, the alignment, to words or sounds of the soul’ to generate lasting collective joy through music making (Turner 2012:223).

6.3. *FOR FREEDOM in INVENTION*

Stuart Nicholson (2005) compares ways of teaching jazz with the history of the art and its entanglement with the growth of the commercial music and educational industries. The freedom of improvisation and the joy of musical communication provide jazz players and young jazzy Shetland *spreers* with memorable, personal and social creative experiences. However, their art is technically and theoretically passed along through a variously codified lingua franca, constructed around rhythms and melodies over chord progressions that serve as a matrix for improvisation. Technical mastery over an instrument and the practical-conceptual understanding of harmony are, ironically, essential for achieving a fluid sense of creative freedom within the jazz idiom. Without the freedom to invent (or to claim experiences of invention), there is no feeling of creativity, even if that freedom comes with prescribed parameters, as in the case of most jazz forms. For jazz musicians, ‘the melodies and harmonies of a song are only the bare-bones framework within which a musical process – the improvisation – evolves’ and the chart is simply a ‘pretext for a different kind of music making’ (Théberge 1997:182). Jazz musicians experience creativity through the feeling of freedom that improvisation and experimentation afford precisely when not all the notes are predefined. However, they

must achieve a certain level of technical mastery over their instruments and musical knowledge in order to become fluid. Musicians of the Indian Classical music tradition, as Khan (2005) details, explore improvisational freedom by attending to the immediacy of the ineffable (Stoller 2013:165). They respond sensibly to interpersonal and spiritual resonances and architectural reverberations, so that written scores become irrelevant.

Nicholson (2005) notes that European jazz instruction methods have tended to emphasise personal artistic development, associated with character, voice, creativity and originality. This contrasts with the focus on the ability to imitate and replicate demanded in American programs. In short, learning improvised solos, note by note, and performing them to judges and peers is fundamentally at odds with the apprenticeship system of knowledge transmission that, ironically, is part of the personal trajectories of all canonized jazz masters. ‘Now we got to the point where we don’t want to be free anymore’, argues legendary jazz saxophone player Sonny Rollins (2014), ‘we want somebody to tell us what to do, tell us when to wake up in the morning, tell us what to eat’. He asks, ‘you want to be a person that’s led around by a guy with big pockets who’s trying to make money? Okay, but everybody doesn’t think like that – people who like jazz don’t think like that’ (Rollins 2014). Jazz people, he tells us, ‘constitutionally, they feel that there is something wrong with being led around – it’s not freedom – America is supposed to stand for freedom and that’s why jazz is supposed to be America’s music, you get it? So, trying to satirize jazz is something sinister about it’ (Rollins 2014). Rollins found a Mad Magazine satire that used him as a mouthpiece to attack jazz distasteful because ‘jazz musicians live a tough life just trying to get accepted in this society where nobody wants to acknowledge the genius of the music’ (Rollins 2014). ‘There are not a lot of real things left in the world’, argues Rollins, and ‘jazz is real’, it is ‘suffering now’ and ‘still on the bottom’ (Rollins 2014). For Rollins, ‘jazz used to typify America’ as ‘free music’, through ‘its syncopations, its melodies, the

way you improvise’ by pulling ‘things out the air’ – ‘that’s genius’, he tells us, ‘and that’s jazz – people can have that any place in the world’ (Rollins 2014). For jazz students and aficionados that I met in Shetland and around the world, experiencing this freedom, developing and appreciating nuances of characters and personal styles are essential elements of meaningful creative experiences.

The young Shetland artists featured here agree with Sonny Rollins, and have struggled with restrictions to their creative freedom through their engagements with rules, regulations, producers and directors guided by commercial imperatives. Among them, only Joe Watt decided to study commercial music in college. Yet, he continued performing his own material and coming back to Shetland. He learned that the commercial music world is ‘soul destroying’ – reducing everything to consumer research and statistics, driven by commercial trends and the question of how to best select and market artists that conform to profitable models.¹²⁶ Joe Watt’s creative project *Shetland Phony* does not rely on fixed arrangements or group configurations. Joe’s compositions can be performed in different ways with different groups without compromising the project’s integrity. By playing together, these young Shetland jazzers appreciate each other’s contributions and negotiate musical arrangements, enjoying personal freedom and mutual encouragement.

6.4. *BRANDON, NORMAN, HAYDEN, LEWIS and JOE: FUNKIFIED TRAD*

Brandon Cole was preparing his portfolio to apply for university – he wanted to work with film and asked if he could use my camera to film us playing and to interview Hayden Hook, Norman Willmore, Joe Watt and Lewis Murray. I agreed to Brandon’s proposition, and only asked him to share with me the footage that he collected, which he did. They were all around the same age at the time, in their late teens. Max Tyler, for some reason, was not around for this interview. Throughout the time we played jazz together, which

lasted for over a year, I would often play just with Norman or Max – On those occasions, I would play the electric bass, and when Hayden was around to play the upright, I would play electric guitar. Joe would join us in the vocals when we jammed at WobblyGang, and he did not play jazz with the others at the Mareel Café Bar, but he did show up to listen to us play few times – the Heavy Metal Buffet crew would often show up to listen, Dirk and Marjolein Robertson, Jamie Hatchbar and Jamie Dalziel, accompanied by DJ Lyall Halcrow, all playing their own role supporting the local music scene.¹²⁷

Those Sunday Jazz sessions at the Mareel Café Bar were like study workshops that contributed to keeping Norman, Hayden and Max prepared for a jazz program. We had no predetermined set to follow – we just picked up tunes from the ‘Jazz Real Book’ and ‘winged them’, slang for tackling tunes without much preparation. Max preferred to study physics in Edinburgh, although he could have easily entered a university jazz program just with the practical results from his experience with the National Youth Jazz Orchestra of Scotland (NYJOS). Hayden joined the jazz program at the Amsterdam Conservatorium in 2013, and Norman received a scholarship to study jazz at the Royal Conservatory in Cardiff, Wales in 2014 after completing a yearlong collegiate course at the University of Saint Andrews and receiving a performance prize. At the time of their conversation with Brandon, Hayden and Norman were Higher National Certificate (HNC) students and Joe was doing the National Certificate (NC) music course. Joe went on to join a commercial music program Ayr in 2014. For Sunday Jazz at the Mareel Café Bar, Norman and Max would play keyboard with me on the bass as a duo, and when we were all playing together, Max would usually play the keys, and Norman would play the saxophone and occasionally take up the keys so that Max could play trumpet – his instrument at NYJOS.¹²⁸

One feature of note in this conversation is that I was not present. This meant that the issues they brought up were those they found important rather than those that may have

directly concerned my research questions. The spontaneity in this material is something that I could not have reproduced as a guide to conversations at that time, so this piece of media is unique in my collection. Throughout fieldwork, I actively sought to capture spontaneity in my engagements with research participants, as residents often noticed.

6.5. FEELING COMFORTABLE in the MEDIA ROOM

They take their places in the Mareel media room, forming a semi-circle around Brandon. Here, students have access to a host of computers, sound production equipment and receive NHC and NC lessons. The media room functions as a classroom that can become a production workshop, hang out and study place after school time is over. The media room was also Max's trickster laboratory, where he would pull pranks on anyone who left their computer unattended while still logged on to Facebook – Max started a number of notorious 'relationships' on Facebook, by getting into two accounts, and sending a relationship notice and accepting it – the result was a post on both pages announcing the new relationship on Facebook, with a collection of pictures in which both are 'tagged'. This is typical 'fraping' behaviour, and it always drew laughs and was never taken seriously. 'Fraping' refers to a rather hyperbolic metaphor – 'Facebook-raping'. Joe was also very active on this front, and his mom was often the victim, and she always took it as a funny joke. Posting as his mother Sheila, Joe once announced a new pregnancy, 'I'm having my third!' He knew that such life changing events, like births, marriages, pregnancies and graduations are quickly overwhelmed with 'likes' and congratulatory comments on Facebook. I even fell for this one and 'liked' it, because it seemed entirely possible. She only had time to correct it after the post had been inundated with 'likes'. After I was targeted once, I started locking my screen anytime I left the computer to get a

coffee, because I knew that if I was not in high alert, someone would just automatically make up something ridiculous, like another relationship with Peter Keay.

‘Fraping’ was something to be expected, and these events were discussed socially for a good laugh on someone’s expense without malice. It could not be taken seriously as some sort of insult, and it never was. If anything, it pressured people to remember to log off from their accounts and take precautions with their personal computers. After all, they let them do it, and for doing so, they deserved it. In his study of the Isle of Unst, where I visited with *The Revellers* as part of *Back from Beyond* in 2013, Goffman argues that ‘[p]ractical jokes and social games are played in which embarrassments which are to be taken unseriously are purposely engineered’ (Goffman 1956:7).¹²⁹ Interpersonal knowledge affords this playfulness to emerge as a pleasurable game that only strengthens those connections. A deep tone of free-spirited playfulness and immersion in the immediate social world of common friends underlies most interactions between musicians who enjoy the fruits of interpersonal knowledge. Norman begins,

NORMAN: ‘Alright, music... I don’t know, it probably it just all starts with school, isn’t it... primary school teaching, it’s just kind of kicks off from there.’

HAYDEN [brings up an aptitude test that he took and which supposedly told him he was not good for music]: ‘there’s a thing at school – it’s like, you have to take *the test*’.

JOE: ‘Oh yeah’.

Everyone speaks at the same time, and Brandon summarises the point of the test.

BRANDON: ‘To see if you can actually play music?’

HAYDEN: ‘I failed it’.

NORMAN: ‘Really?’

BRANDON: ‘That’s insane’!

HAYDEN: ‘Yeah, I didn’t get any lessons... and then my mom phoned up, pretty angry [everyone laughs] and then I got lessons. It turned out I could play music in the end’.

Everyone laughed at the idea of such a test. Some locals may find it abominable that there is a system that imposes tests on children that supposedly tell them about what they can or cannot do – a test that imposes the belief on a personal limitation from a supposedly authoritative reductionistic questionnaire. In this case, the test was supposed to determine whether or not children get access to music tuition in the school system. Obviously, the result was so preposterous and Hayden was already so involved in the music scene through his parents and their friends that the test had no effect. Yet, children who do not have such unwavering support from their parents could be quickly pushed away from developing musical skills through such an unjustifiable test. Unwavering support for the creative pursuits that their growing children felt excited about learning is the key element that the parents of all these young musicians share, and which enabled them to follow their own trajectories, developing personal character and voice.

Hayden’s father, live sound engineer and music teacher Stevie Hook, worries when the educational system forces him to assess his grade school music students, mostly children, in writing – a bit of annoying bureaucracy that the school system requires. Stevie is very aware of how the words of a teacher can have a profound impact, especially on children. He believes that music making skills can be cultivated for a lifetime, and what matters the most to him is to encourage children to play and love music. Brian and Arthur Nicholson follow the same support strategy, bringing some balance to the neoliberal mentality that dominates the music industry, constantly challenging the notion of fostering an engaged sociomusical community and developing personal character through musical practice. In other words, the commercial mentality and its imperatives make music into a product designed to conform to market trends – what is selling, not what is personally

meaningful and feels good. Thus, music production strictly for business, organised around a profit principle, directly undermines the personal by conforming to commercial imperatives and letting them influence and direct the creative process.

Often, musicians who become professionals in the recording industry as session players are valued for acquiring chameleonic abilities (i.e., proficient in a variety of styles and feels that a producer may require, and become ‘professional’ in that they are able to quickly record tracks exactly as the producer prescribes). What Cottrell (2002:61) calls ‘deputizing’ – ‘the substitution of one musician by another for a particular performance event’ – is common in Shetland, but not necessarily because of the cash rewards involved. There are bands that operate with a variable number of members, such as *North Country Fair*, but they rarely ever get paid for performing. *The Revellers*, who do get some dividends from their performances, have often relied on ‘subs’, and had different people prepared to play the bass if needed, for instance. Nobody is a professional musician in *The Revellers*. Some of the members are not always required and may not be available to perform on certain occasions, generating the necessity for having friends around familiar enough with their material to play it without much notice. However, this is not a job for any professional who can learn the songs and perform for a fee. Rather, such opportunities are reserved for close friends well attuned to the principles of the *spree*. This is yet another difference between Shetland *spreeing* musicians and professionals more abundant in urban centres. To Shetlanders like Erik and Lewie Peterson, having a day job provides economic security, leading to freedom in terms of what music to make, when and with whom. For them, rehearsals, performances and recording dates are aspects of the many social and educational pleasures of music making. For Erik, Lewie and other *spreeers*, competing with musicians for dominance is like missing the point of music making altogether.

Young musicians who study to become professionals in college courses designed with the industry in mind often believe in the myth of becoming the ‘best’ musician in the world, and may hold fast to the belief that becoming such a musician is possible. This form of what I call the ‘superlative syndrome’ permeates social worlds in which ranking, grading, and quantified comparisons are valued. Anthropologists and other social scientists have been among the most critical of reductionist, ungrounded statistical studies, quantifying epistemologies. Anthropology departments and postgraduate courses have often abolished grading for a ‘pass’ or ‘fail’ system. As bureaucratic inventions founded upon an epistemology of curricular homogeneity, prescriptive excellence, failure and exclusion, and standardised tests, conventional school systems often impose pre-established expectations and hurdles for students to overcome instead of affording means for individuals to learn in their own ways. Very much like ‘the institution of science’, music courses have developed a ‘system for allocating rewards to those who variously live up to its norms’ (Merton 1957:642 *In* Bourdieu 2004:11). The social aspects of music making in Shetland give people space and support for overcoming such conventions.

JOE: ‘I ended up getting piano lessons, but I gave up, ‘cos guitar was too much fun’.

NORMAN: ‘Yeah, I started off with piano lessons at school, so...’

HAYDEN: ‘I started off on piano too!’

JOE: ‘That’s interesting’ [all laugh].

BRANDON: ‘Do you think there’s a reason for that?’

NORMAN: ‘I think that if you want to go anywhere with music, then you need to like have a decent knowledge of how the piano works’.

HAYDEN: ‘Why did you start piano though?’

NORMAN: ‘To piss off my sister’ [all laugh].

BRANDON: ‘So you wouldn’t have started music if you didn’t want to piss off your sister’.

NORMAN: ‘Probably not’.

JOE: ‘You got your sister to thank’.

NORMAN: ‘Yes, ‘cos my sister was quite good at piano, and I just wanted to annoy her... I started out and then got...’

BRANDON: ‘...better than her’.

NORMAN: ‘I found out I really love it’.

Brandon brings up the issue of music tuition, and how it may affect musicians. Their musical trajectories start with stories about listening, usually with their family – then the musical world starts opening up above and beyond their earlier listening experiences and they explore and uncover a musical path of their own making, to find materials that inspire them, affording them with potential paths for developing a personal voice and style. Joe and Hayden were born into the scene, with very involved parents. Brandon questions the notion of ‘forced’ music tuition in Shetland schools.

NORMAN: ‘I think we are quite lucky’.

JOE: ‘But that’s not how I really got into it... you guys, definitely your theory and understanding of theory is much better, given that [music] was introduced to you that way, whereas I just played with my parents, and people, and friends, and family.’

NORMAN: ‘We’re just like most people, well, a lot of people get started in Shetland [with school tuition]’.

HAYDEN: ‘I’ve started playing with my dad [Stevie Hook] as well, ‘cos I kinda played a little bit of bass, and then I started getting piano lessons, ‘cos I liked listening to... all that kind of... Fats Waller and stuff, and then Ray Charles – I don’t know why... that was just, yeah Dr. John – that was a lot of stuff that my dad played to me... I always wanted to play double bass, but I was too small, so when it came to school lessons, ‘cos I got private piano lessons... ‘cos, like, it was primary three or something – you only get lessons when you’re in primary five. But when it came to like, school lessons, then I just took up cello, ‘cos I thought that it was just the same as bass’.

JOE: ‘Just the same!’ [jokingly]

HAYDEN: ‘Just the same as double bass’.

NORMAN: ‘That’s quite good, [to Joe and Hayden] you guys both have really musical parents’.

BRANDON asks them whether their parents and upbringing ‘completely affects your appreciation of music?’

HAYDEN: ‘That’s how it started off, that’s definitely how it started off’.

The key point here is that, while recognising the influence of their parents, they also recognise their own paths and trajectories, which the musics they have discovered personally have helped them to develop.¹³⁰ This path is continuously shifting, growing, bringing people, places, sounds and experiences together again and again over extended periods of time. Their parents provided support, and showed them how to enjoy music socially at an early age. This is also the case for a number of Shetland musicians I know who born in the 1980s and 1990s, including Arthur Nicholson, Maggie Adamson, Martha Thomson, Joe Watt, Hayden Hook, and many others.

Undoubtedly, the most important engine behind this culture of musical appreciation is the Shetland Folk Festival, where local musicians ritually converge every year, regardless of whether or not their parents are musical socially – even some of the more rarely seen, secluded musicians, may come out for the SFF. Therefore, regardless of whether one has musical parents, the SFF will demonstrate, year after year, how to be social through music in the local way, and provide many potential channels into Shetland’s sociomusical world for participants, regardless of their background. Brandon comments on parallels between his own background and Norman’s, whose parents were not musicians:

BRANDON: ‘I’m the same as that – my parents were never musically inclined, none of my family ever were, and I think that’s part of the fact that I never really got into playing music, ‘cos I was

never kind of, not forced, but kind of like pushed from my parents...’

JOE: ‘You never had a sister to piss off!’ Everyone laughs.

Joe’s experience growing up was different, more comparable to Hayden’s and also Arthur Nicholson’s – surrounded by local and visiting musicians all the time. According to his father Brian, Arthur Nicholson does not even remember when he *did not* have a guitar in his hands – he started performing live as a child. Having an older musical sister to outdo, in a family without musical parents, was one of Norman’s motivations for studying classical piano and saxophone. He wanted to ‘piss her off’ and play better than her, but soon he discovered that he just loved music and that’s what he wanted to do for the rest of his life. When Joe Watt was born, his mother Sheila was already an established local singer songwriter. Similarly, when Hayden Hook was born, his parents Stevie and Amanda were already doing live sound for years. Supported by his friendship with Billy Kay and others, Stevie was one of the pioneers of professional live sound engineering in Shetland. For Watt, ‘the people who played music were always the people who were cool and fun...’

NORMAN: ‘I never went to gigs... until I started playing with *Love Shack* and stuff, that’s when I started going to gigs. I started off with school things, playing in local halls and shit.’

HAYDEN: ‘Music festivals, school music festivals?’

NORMAN: ‘Yeah, music festivals, more like...’

HAYDEN: ‘Competition.’

NORMAN: ‘More like competition, academic music, and then... I don’t know, I kinda found jazz somehow, and changed’.

Everyone laughs at this change of ways. Norman added a jazzy way of being to his sense of identity, pointing to Kearney’s (1995:558) ‘both-and-and[n]’ logic. This change, evidence for epistemological growth, modified Norman’s outlook on life and way of being

social, making the competitive playing common in academic music unattractive. Norman started playing sax in the ‘second year’, when his mother gave him an alto saxophone.

LEWIS: ‘I did not take drums lessons or any kind of formal tuition until I was about fifteen... that’s five years of, you know, social playing’.

NORMAN: ‘I wanted to, but I did not start playing it more socially until I was fifteen’.

LEWIS: ‘I played drums for a bit, and then I got drums lessons through the school, and I’m still getting drums lessons [from Russell Gair]... [music is] definitely a more social thing’.

JOE: ‘I think, though, that... like... your academic... what gets you into the playing the instruments is maybe... it’s irrelevant to what you actually end up playing, because how you get into it is how you get into it.’

NORMAN: ‘There’s so many different ways...’

JOE: ‘It’s when you learn to make the sounds you want to make with the instrument, then that’s when you decide to...’

BRANDON: ‘So it’s completely more of your own personal thing’.

NORMAN: ‘Yeah, totally’.

JOE: ‘Yeah, what you feel, and it’s different for everybody, how you feel’.

LEWIS: ‘There’s a total difference between playing music by the book, and playing music the way you want and play it. And it’s just like... I [find] that music sounds better when it’s coming from you, and it’s... like your own twist’.

JOE: ‘Yeah’.

NORMAN: ‘Find the style you want to do, just through listening to lots of music. The older you get, the more stuff you hear’.

HAYDEN: ‘That’s why I came home, because when I went away to Aberdeen, then I was just playing classical all the time, I thought that’s what I want to do, play in the orchestra and stuff, and that is all cello. And then I just gradually felt more and more, sorta bored. I felt really constricted. But I’m just like having to play exactly what’s on the music all the time, and then they started a jazz band at school, and so that’s when I started playing double bass, ‘cos

there was no bass players in the school at all. I played a bit of electric anyway, but it was always just a bit of fun’.

BRANDON: ‘Do you think that that kind of intense musical tuition almost makes you want to do something else’?

JOE: ‘Haha, yeah’.

NORMAN: ‘Yeah, you just want to break the rules, especially like a teenager as well’.

BRANDON: ‘Yeah’ [whispering in concordance].

NORMAN: ‘I love classical music even now, but when I found jazz and started doing gigs, then... I love doing that, but I love classical music so much as well, [it’s] a big part of my life’.

A key point here is that playing ‘exactly what’s on the music all the time’ gradually became too boring, so Hayden went back to Shetland where he encountered support for the creative freedom and social engagement he was longing for. Yet, classical music is still a source of inspiration. The conversation shifts toward the issue of tradition, and whether it holds people back by patterning them according to ‘trad and folk’ aesthetics. Hayden noted that before the 1990s, ‘there was a lot of folk, but it was all very, very traditional’. ‘And then in the nineties’, he continues, ‘it was, like, *BongShang* and stuff like that’, people who ‘were like our age, took folk music and kind of danced it up, with electric guitar and bass’.

LEWIS: ‘Just putting their own spin on it’.

JOE: ‘I think we sometimes forget that like, some of the trad stuff that happened like, over the last forty years was actually pretty fucking cutting-edge, like it was actually cool [everyone laughs in agreement] like the stuff that Margaret Scollay, and stuff like that it’s been happening, it’s actually pretty cool’.

HAYDEN: ‘Three years ago, like, the Folk Festival was pumping.’

JOE: ‘Oh yeah’.

HAYDEN: ‘Shetland... loads of Shetland bands. But that was like the beginning of like this proper Shetland folk scene, *Fiddler’s Bid* and that’.

NORMAN: 'It [*Fiddler's Bid*] is a proper export'.

LEWIS: 'Yeah, it is'.

JOE: 'We also still play trad, though, to some extent – it is still part of our, somewhere, of our vernacular'.

NORMAN: 'yeah, probably just 'cos it's like'.

JOE: 'Just 'cos it's there'.

NORMAN: 'Yeah, well, not even that – it's just 'cos, no matter what'.

LEWIS: 'It's almost like a done thing'.

NORMAN: 'You grow up in Shetland, you're going to get it [trad music] and you're going to play it at some point'.

JOE: 'We try and funk it up a bit, like I play in a funky trad band, you play in a funky trad band'.

LEWIS: 'We all play in a funky trad band, but I also like to funk up the trad'.

Norman reminisces about their participation in a National Geographic production, which brought a German crew to Shetland. The next subject of conversation parallels Emma Perring's experiences with the American production crew and our experiences with NTS, discussed in Chapter 5. The theme of self-important media production crew parachuting into Shetland and assuming that people should just go along with distorted versions of the local tradition. Their attitudes towards locals are similar to those of celebrities and production crew that Meizel found in her fieldwork on the social practices surrounding the mainstream television program *American Idol* (In Cooley et al. 2008).

NORMAN: 'This German TV people were filming for National Geographic, and so they wanted us to do a folk tune, but make it funky, so we did this funk arrangement... and then they asked us to make it less funky' [all laugh]. Looks like all they wanted was a folk tune, but played on a different instrument to usual'.

JOE: 'Oh yeah, yeah, this German film crew'.

LEWIS: 'But then we took it to the end, like just the most intense funk ever' [laughs].

BRANDON: 'Too much'.

LEWIS: 'A three minute sax solo in the highest register possible' [demonstrates screeching noise].

JOE: 'Stop being so fucking funky' [parodying the German crew].

NORMAN: 'They were really annoying actually, I didn't like that'.

HAYDEN: 'Not enough communication'.

LEWIS: 'German TV, Stevie'.

JOE: 'Yeah, no. That was, that was cool. The *discovery* channel'.

HAYDEN: 'Nat-Geo'.

They laugh together, coming up with various overlapping word puns that become hard to distinguish in the recording. Curious, Brandon wanted to know how and why local musicians are compelled to 'want to do something different'. Is it because, he asked, they want to do something different, or because they 'love the genre so much they want to kind of broaden it?' They pitched in their impressions,

LEWIS: 'Hmm, I'd say it's about both, to be honest'.

NORMAN: 'It's just like, music is developing all the time'.

JOE: 'Sometimes it's because of the universal sound, because it's such a... because it's an export...'

NORMAN: 'Yeah'.

JOE: 'Then you can do your own thing with it, and it's actually'.

HAYDEN: 'And it's still accepted'.

JOE: 'Yeah'.

Brandon hypothesised that, since trad music is so popular in Shetland, trad musicians would be afraid to venture beyond it. However, that is certainly not the case, as I have

noted (Chapter 2). Although love for traditional music is widespread, from the mid 19th century onwards at least, Shetlanders have been deeply interested in and engaging with various musical genres from beyond, and were welcoming them through the available maritime routes. I rarely ever encountered anyone who only valued, played and listened to Shetland traditional music. Fiddlers Martha Thomson, Marjolein Robertson, and Chloe Robertson were assiduous frequenters of metal and folk gigs.

Martha also played piano and led the fusion group *Teevliks*. Marjolein played bass with the band *Beef Cleaver* and was very active with the Heavy Metal Buffet podcast and events. Chloe composed and performed original compositions on acoustic guitar and voice regularly. Fiddler Mary Rutherford had encountered no difficulties in learning and recording with Hayden (bass), Finlay (drums), and me (electric guitar), the Brazilian Chorinho tune *Doce de Côco* by Jacob do Bandolim. Peerie Willie fused traditional music with gypsy jazz in Shetland. Moreover, in Whalsay and later in Yell I saw the octogenarian fiddler Alan Tulloch perform, whom Cohen (1987) mentions as one of the saviours of a so-called Whalsay fiddle tradition from a supposed country and western craze. I found that Tulloch's repertoire consisted mainly of Appalachian and Cajun tunes. Country and Western became just as acceptable and widespread as traditional in Shetland. Heavy rock, and especially bands like *Metallica* and *AC/DC*, are often associated with Whalsay and Yell, where rock and roll has been accepted and cherished since its arrival in Shetland.

The notion of a Shetland fiddle tradition that does not engage with technological developments and other instruments is unrealistic at best. Historically, before the arrival of the accordion and other instruments, Shetland fiddlers had to find a way to lead dances alone and without amplification. Yet, every technological innovation that appeared in Shetland in association with music, from the accordion to the distortion pedal, the kazoo, computers or whatever else, was brought into musical practice as a creative tool. Fiddlers

in the ‘auld days’ played alone without amplification because alternatives were not available at the time. Now, the most widely used technological development that local musicians of all ages use extensively for researching and sharing musical forms is the Internet, whereas for Peerie Willie and Billy Kay’s generation, the radio, vinyl records and reel-to-reel tapes afforded fundamental materials for inspiration.

In 2014, jazz pianist and vocalist Carol Jamieson, who leads the function band *Love Shack*, shared with me some of her informal recordings with renowned fiddler Debbie Scott, one of which was a fiddle and piano tribute to *Iron Maiden’s Number of the Beast* (1982). Many of my older friends, including Brian Nicholson, Michael Williamson, Jim Quinn, Stevie Hook, Gary Peterson and others, are involved with rock and a wide range of other styles, challenging easy generalisations.

Amanda Pearson, who was born in Lerwick in the mid 1960s, and whose father is one of the most well known and active supporters of the Shetland Country and Western scene, enjoys a wide range of music, from classical to jazz, folk, country, funk, dialect music, and everything in between, but with a ‘punk rocker’ heart and soul. She attended a punk festival in Manchester in late 2014, and a rock festival with 15 bands was organised for her fiftieth birthday in 2015.

Ewan Nowak, who composed all the music for *SpootHawk’s* release *A Good Haul* (2015) and studied guitar in London, composes in various styles, and records elaborate and technically sophisticated guitar music. Once he picked up my Brazilian *bandolim* (similar to a mandolin) and immediately started playing Shetland reels as if it was second nature to him. Back to our conversation: Brandon’s question provokes an opportunity for humour. Shetlanders have a taste for coming up with hyperbolic contrasts and inventing impossible, sometimes surreal tales ‘for a laugh’. In this case, the iconic fiddler Aly Bain, who only occasionally comes to Shetland to perform, comes up, generating laughter:

NORMAN: 'I wonder what Aly Bain listens to in his spare time'.

JOE: 'Death metal'.

LEWIS: 'Aly Bain, trip hop'.

HAYDEN: 'I think that a lot of these kind of funky up folk bands and stuff – is something that makes it a bit more. Yeah, a bit different, and like, something that is more for the people of Shetland as well, rather than... 'Cos we've all heard the traditional folk and it's like, 'yeah, that's great, that's cool'.

NORMAN: 'You walk down the street and hear it blurring at High Level'.¹³¹

HAYDEN: 'But like when, 'cos these bands are bringing it more to the crowds of Shetland, and then they go out to the world'.

JOE: 'I think it's a constant thing, where it's like, non trad people trying to bring the funk to trad people and trad people trying to bring trad to funk people'.

NORMAN: 'Then there was that whole Harris Playfair thing – that was really cool'.

JOE: 'Yeah, he's fucking brilliant'.

NORMAN: 'He just came up, and basically made a big band out of fiddles and saxophones, and that was awesome'.

LEWIS: 'Shetland musicians'.

NORMAN: 'Just did really cool jazz arrangements of Shetland tunes, and everyone – 'cos they had like, the jazzers in the back and the folkies in the front, but like, we all got on really well'.

JOE: 'Yeah'.

NORMAN: '...the music was really good'.

HAYDEN: 'Yeah'.

NORMAN: 'And both parties enjoyed the music, and'...

HAYDEN: 'It didn't sound like, cheesy either'.

NORMAN: 'Or too way out either'.

HAYDEN: ‘Like, the chords and everything worked really well, and the feel was perfect’.

JOE: ‘That was really good – that was fucking awesome’.

For Hayden, Norman and many other jazz musicians, like Sonny Rollins, creativity is associated with freedom of expression within a form. Creativity, in this case, is a musical experience that is delicate and vulnerable to formal restrictions. Feeling comfortable and free to communicate and engage with others through music is a key component. *Spreeing* is how ‘knowing selves’ enmeshed ‘in reciprocity’ (Titon 2008:37) harmonise interpersonal resonances in a ritual of reverberation. Creative experiences grow in dimension alongside the social support for musicians well attuned to local principles. Their interpersonal familiarity and concurrent involvement with sociomusical *sprees* practices help to sustain and afford their attunement.

The presence of familiar supporters with whom *spreers* share personal and social relationships multiplies the potential for and intensity of creative experiences. Alternatively, *spreers* may embark on periodical retreats from social worlds in order to restructure their creative voice, reorganise, regroup, recompose. In relative isolation, they concentrate on works that will later further shape their personal sociomusical character among others. They may also compose, practice and produce original musical materials that will later circulate among friends and shape the social aura of creators among their peers, as the rules of a proper nuance of character appreciation sense would require. The circulation of this material generates a genealogy of influences and a personal history, as well as material that contributes to the formation of the creator’s voice in the public imagination. The musical creation then becomes a ‘symbolic element’ and an ‘innovative extension’ (Wagner 1981:36) of the composers and of those involved in recording and performing, helping to shape their perception among associates. They will listen to these

songs together and talk about them, thus producing their own conceptual spin on their reactions on the music and all it means to them socially.

The publication of the musical material leads to various personal interpretations among listeners that obscure the personal and social relational aspects behind the creation of a song, tune, video, album and so on – the creative process and how it is embedded in social relationships and entangled in composing and producing skills developed slowly with continuous practice. During *SpootHawk*'s album recording at Mareel's studio, I filmed some of the extremely meticulous editing work on the computer screen that Ewan Nowak had spent over 400 hours preparing, and the house sound engineer immediately joked that I should not be revealing the 'magic of the process.'¹³² An idea for a song or tune might originate from an improvised jam, and then be selected and carefully developed alone or with others. It will eventually be shared with experienced musicians and supporters who will respond with their personal impressions and opinions, sometimes inviting the composer to think in different ways and to modify the composition by incorporating suggestions. In this manner, musical materials take personal meaning for those who become entangled with them through their relationship with the composer.

6.6. *DISCUSSION: CREATIVITY and FREEDOM from the GROOVE*

Julie Cruikshank argues that historical narratives and storytelling 'are not just abstract objects of study, texts for analysis' – rather, 'their telling is bound up in social-historical and power relations' (1998:73). 'Universalizing classification systems', notes Cruikshank, have 'accompanied colonial expansion' and 'have inevitably threatened to dislodge or trivialize local systems of meaning' (1998:xiv). 'Ethnographic research', as Cruikshank argued, 'is an interactive business and a humbling one' (1998:161). Listening 'closely to the stories we are told' makes us realise that 'communities everywhere are

diverse and complex’ and that stories told today can seem ‘naive or wrongheaded to others’ in the future (Cruikshank 1998:161). The same is true of ‘anthropological narratives we have absorbed’ when the ‘theoretical perspectives that animate one generation of scholars are frequently reinterpreted by the next as the dead hand of history’ (1998:161). For Cruikshank, experiences with friendships developed during fieldwork, ‘connect with similar experiences in the universities’ and ‘lessons from one setting may transfer to the other’ (1998:xvii). Cruikshank’s insight, grounded on decades of engagement with Yukon elders and anthropologists, exposes limitations in how scholars privilege theories that often prevent them from understanding and accommodating alternative takes on the world. There is a tendency to hold fast to concepts and understandings assumed to be true without adopting critical reflexivity to kindle more permeable and dissolvable tautologies. In this way, academic anthropologists can manifest a presentist bias with potential trappings that we should be careful about.

Returning to earlier theoretical discussions, we are touching upon the limiting power of the ‘groove’ of knowledge to instil a sense of truth within a limiting horizon of cognition. Philosopher Krishnamurti asked physicist David Bohm why the mind is always following a pattern and falling ‘into this groove of pattern seeking’ (*In* Krishnamurti and Bohm 1985:223). For Bohm, ‘the groove is inherent in the nature of accumulated knowledge’ (*In* Krishnamurti and Bohm 1985:223). He continues, ‘the groove, or the accumulated knowledge, seems to have significance far beyond what its significance is’ (*In* Krishnamurti and Bohm 1985:223). Bohm argues that part of the issue is that knowledge is relative but its significance is taken as absolute (*In* Krishnamurti and Bohm 1985:224). Krishnamurti wondered how one could escape the direction that this groove of knowledge imposes on a life path, and Bohm suggests that being is different from knowledge (*In* Krishnamurti and Bohm 1985:225).

For Bohm, ‘knowledge is extremely active, meeting and shaping every moment according to past knowledge’ (*In* Krishnamurti and Bohm 1985:227). Bohm ponders over how ‘to break down the groove, because it creates the imitation, or a pretension, of a state of being’ (Krishnamurti and Bohm 1985:226). Finally, Bohm argues that ‘thought is always limited by its own contradictions’ while ‘freedom is the highest value’ (*In* Krishnamurti and Bohm 1985:246-247). Regarding the sociomusical *sprees* in Shetland, the ‘groove of knowledge’ it creates is anti-hierarchical and designed to support creative endeavours, to level creative relationships whose delicate harmonic resonance powers could be easily damaged by differential, exclusivist and naturalised power relations, socioeconomic status, age and gender differences and other divisions that making and sharing music in the spirit of the *sprees* can dissolve.

As Lakoff and Johnson note, ‘the people who get to impose their metaphors on the culture get to define what we consider to be true’ – a dynamic that the ‘myth of objectivism’ supports (2003:160). They argue that ‘truth is always relative to a conceptual system that is defined in large by metaphors’ (Lakoff and Johnson 2003:159). Cruikshank points out that, ‘as in any other form of storytelling’, in anthropology, ‘theory is tremendously helpful when it generates new questions and is utterly constraining when it predetermines answers’ (1998:165). Ideas may be pushed away from the mainstream and left ignored, sometimes for centuries, until someone finds a personal, novel and socially relevant way of applying them. In Nietzsche’s case, most of his contemporaries ignored his works, which became influential decades later in anthropology and other disciplines. If we adopt the Nietzschean opposition that Ruth Benedict popularised in the anthropological world, Shetland’s festivals, especially *Up Helly Aa*, may seem Dionysian at first sight, an ‘ecstatic cult’ that involves ‘drunkenness and sexual excesses’ (Metcalf 2005:168).

Moreover, Shetlanders' devotion to fostering lifelong friendships fits very well what I call an Epicurean model. Among the most important values of Epicureanism, historically misunderstood by its critics as a type of vulgar hedonism, we find friendship (*amicitia*), freewill, personal character, individuality, the erosion of artificial hierarchical and gender differences (i.e., Epicurus considered slaves as equals). Living by these principles led to tranquillity and katastematic pleasures, achieved with balance or equilibrium. For the poet Lucretius, one of the most eloquent and passionate exponents of Epicurus' philosophy, sublime pleasures were found in simplicity, frugality, wisdom and friendship, whereas the desire of power, honour and wealth, i.e., ambition and avarice, led to the perpetuation of a cycle of pain (see Smith 1992:xl-xlii). For Epicurus, philosophy must 'banish the suffering of the mind' or be considered useless (Smith 1992:xlii). Therefore, Epicureans avoided politics and public life, valuing personal engagement and face-to-face interactions instead. Epicurean wisdom was about loving friends as oneself (Smith 1992:xl-iii). For them, friends 'share the connection that the most important thing in life is to join together in studying the true philosophy' (Smith 1992:xl-iii).

For Wilf, 'producing a synchronous iconization of a master's solo while its recording plays in the background is a deeply creative act' (2012:40). Nevertheless, the evidence that the young Shetlanders and jazz musicians provide us with emphasises the importance of a sense of freedom for enabling experiences of creativity (e.g., Khan 2005, Nicholson 2005, 2014, Rollins 2004, Werner 1996). If we uncritically adopt the idea that humans are always creatively improvising, we might ignore the nuances of how creativity is experienced, accepting a tautological truism that ignores power dynamics. We should avoid bringing 'field data' as 'an afterthought, merely to illustrate concepts earlier arrived at' (Goffman 1953:9). I agree with Fischer that our role as ethnographers 'is to develop translation and mediation tools for helping make visible the differences of interests, access, power, needs,

desires, and philosophical perspective’ (2007:43). Similarly, Lévi-Strauss argued that humans have ‘reduced’ their relations with the ‘natural environment’ to concepts’, compounding them ‘to arrive at a system’ that ‘is never determined in advance: the same situation can always be systematized in various ways’ (Lévi-Strauss 1966:95). As Ingold noted, ‘familiarity with indigenous, non-Western understandings’ predisposes anthropologists ‘to adopt a critical attitude towards the foundational assumptions of Western thought and science’ (2000:170). Ingold’s (2000:153-288) dwelling approach suggests that, as beings grow, worlds unfold from their experiences. In this work, ‘dwelling’ also seeks inspiration in critical paradigms that highlight tensions of symbolic power, scientific doxa, and architectural-reverberative social patterning (e.g., Bourdieu 2004, Foucault 1977, Lefebvre 1970) Although Wilf’s (2012) vision of creativity avoided questioning classroom power dynamics and the historical construction of the ‘jazz canon’ and its sociomusical, political and economic consequences, he later supported critical ethnographic engagement with neoliberal constrictions (Wilf 2014).

Ingold and Hallam (2007:5) argued that copying or imitation ‘is not the simple, mechanical process of replication that it is often taken to be, of running off duplicates from a template, but entails a complex and ongoing alignment of observation of the model with action in the world’. Similarly, Boasians who explored questions of art and style, song and storytelling were interested in complex relationships between models, actions, and material transformations. For instance, Boas noted that ‘imported stories’ are borrowed and ‘quickly adapted to the prevailing mode of life’ (1955[1927]:332). Although a ‘plot may be old and taken from foreign sources’, its adoption ‘undergoes radical changes’ (Boas 1955[1927]:333). Boas argued that songs and narratives are ‘thoroughly integrated in the life of a people’ and ‘given an interpretative significance that is quite foreign to the original’ (1955[1927]:336). For him, the ‘style of the interpretation of a tale depends upon

the cultural interests of the people telling it and, accordingly, assumes distinctive forms' (Boas 1955[1927]:336). Thus, 'the explanatory meaning of art forms shows much greater individuality' (Boas 1955[1927]:336). Lord argued that scholars experienced 'real difficulty', being unfamiliar with 'thinking in terms of fluidity' (1960:100). Epistemologically unequipped 'to grasp something that is multiform', they find it 'necessary to construct an ideal text or original', remaining 'dissatisfied with an ever-changing phenomenon' (Lord 1960:100). For Lord, since 'each performance is an original', it is 'impossible to retrace the work of generations of singers to that moment when some singer first sang a particular song' (1960:100). Similarly, the Shetland *spree*, as a way of being, is a locus of original fluidity and nuance of character appreciation. Having emerged from a fluid social world, it does not have an original inventor.

6.7. *BOUNDLESS MUSICAL WORLDS – ENGAGEMENT and INTEGRATION*

As Nicholson (2005) shows, influential jazz personalities travelled to Europe and other places, collaborated with European musicians, brought Cuban musicians to America, adopted Brazilian Bossa Nova into their 'standard' repertoires, and so on:

In the post-war years, the influence of American jazz on the flourishing Danish jazz scene was reinforced by several important American jazz musicians taking up residence in and around Copenhagen, including Dexter Gordon, Ben Webster, Ella Fitzgerald, Stan Getz and others (Nicholson 2005:209).

A number of jazzers even moved to Europe and never returned to America, like Eric Dolphy, known for his unique style. Having started out as an exceptional, classically trained musician in Los Angeles, he soon realised that black musicians were not allowed in orchestras. This experience with institutionalised racism transformed Dolphy, who, from then on, focused intensely on developing his unique voice on the alto saxophone, flute and bass clarinet. While unacknowledged in the United States, his style was immediately

appreciated in Europe, where he toured extensively with Charles Mingus.¹³³ As saxophone player Cannonball Adderley said while presenting the Austrian pianist Joe Zawinul (1932-2007) to the German public in 1963, ‘here’s evidence of the growing internationality in jazz – I’m sure you know this young man well, Joe Zawinul at the piano’ (Adderley 2008).

Jazz musicians often learned phrases and harmonic ideas from one another and various other sources. They listened to recordings, including classical music (Charlie Parker was enthralled by Bach and Stravinsky). Yet, they embarked on personal and social journeys into creative worlds to find materials that they could transform through their own voice, developing and moulding them with recognisable character and style.¹³⁴ Many musicians I know sing along with recorded solos as they play in order to feel them, but not so that they can prove to their instructor and the class that they can do it, or for getting a grade, passing a course, or competing with others. They sing for the pleasure of singing and learn about feelings that can only be accessed by enacting recorded solos.

‘I’ve never heard any player of note who plays in any style but his own’, notes jazz pianist and educator Kenny Werner (1996:55). Experienced players manifest their personal style and voice through a coherent, recognisable redundancy that ‘comes out as “their voice” rather than sounding repetitive’ (Werner 1996:55). For Werner (1996:56), you ‘deny your birthright to create, and are condemned to recreate’ by adopting the imitation approach that Wilf’s (2012) participants report being ‘deeply creative’. Werner notes that most players ‘settle for being able to recreate’ the masters but ‘never do it convincingly’, while the ‘fear of overstepping the bounds of that style’ and ‘appearing foolish’ restricts them considerably (Werner 1996:56). As an added pressure, notes Werner, ‘those fellow students sit there biting their nails and actually hoping you don’t sound good’ (1996:56).

If improvisation is the ‘courage to move from one note to the next’, as singer Bobby McFerrin posited (Werner 1996:56), one must conquer the fear of sounding foolish and the

need of matching the expectations of others. The ‘empty echoing of old styles’ is ‘tragic’ for the jazz tradition that integrates ‘creativity, innovation, individuality, and personality’ as values (Nicholson 2005:208-210) and modes of developing character. For Werner, jazzers should ‘learn to let go’ and love whatever comes out through a ‘method of deprogramming and reprogramming’ (1996:131-132). The method of forcing students to learn and perform recorded solos is aligned with the institutional imperatives of grading, patterning, privileging and judging. Approaching the solo as the ideal model for imitation makes the institutionalised educator’s job easier. It is easy to identify students’ mistakes in a performance, and tick off mistakes to lower their grades. The successful music teaching pedagogies I have encountered in Shetland emphasise personal and social aspects of music, and are never judgmental. They welcome and accept each person’s unique way of learning, and appreciate being involved with the formation of others’ musical personalities.

William F. Hanks notes that the ‘demanding instructor’ and ‘motivated student’ are ‘positions in the academic field’ that are ‘taken up in the course of such situated activity as seminar discussion, grading, and evaluation’ (2005:72). The field of ‘artistic production’ is a ‘dynamic form of organization’ instead of a ‘fixed structure’ (Hanks 2005:72). ‘From a language perspective’, notes Hanks (2005:72), ‘*habitus* corresponds to the social formation of speakers’, their ‘disposition to use language in certain ways, to evaluate it according to socially instilled values, to embody expression in gesture, posture, and speech production’ (e.g., Arno 2003, Ruthrof 2000, Streeck 2003). Wilf (2012) does not discuss how these dynamics operate in jazz classrooms, or in colleges as hierarchically organised systems of relationships. Yet, in Wilf (2014), a more thorough review, he argues for critical engagement with social phenomena associated with neoliberal forces. The present ethnography addresses issues of power and knowledge through the personal musical

trajectories of research participants in various social settings, parsing out the differences in operational principles and values that emerged from those experiences.

By overvaluing emulation and competition, the academic jazz education system can cause embarrassment and humiliation for students who fail to reproduce the original improvisation well enough while others watch. For Werner (1996:127), the musical ordering of things ‘is confining our spirits’ with an exaggerated and restrictive sensitivity to the rightness or wrongness of notes, whereas ‘a note is only as powerful as the player believes it to be’. For Werner, ‘the only sound in the twelve tone system that still has any illusion of dissonance is the flat 9 interval’ – ‘a good place to start’ forming a ‘personal relationship with every interval, every chord’ in order to transform that clash into ‘the sweetest sound’ (1996:127). Werner likens the ‘liberating’ freedom one experiences by transcending prejudiced feelings of ‘discomfort and distrust’ toward other ‘ethnic and socioeconomic groups’ with the transcendence of ‘musical barriers’ – ‘You feel as if you are breathing rarefied air, and it’s exhilarating’ (Werner 1996:128). This is similar to what Hayden felt when he was not forced to be reading the notes from a page anymore or trying to memorise entire pieces. The internalisation and performance of classical pieces can also become enjoyable, transformative experiences. However, the order of the notes does represent a constriction. In Salles (2003), world-renowned concert pianist Nelson Freire watches, delighted and transfixed, jazz pianist Erroll Garner, who had no formal training. Freire tells the audience that he wishes he could play like Garner, whose free and joyful playing is irresistible to him (Salles 2003).

6.8. *INSTITUTIONALISED JAZZ EDUCATION and SOCIAL DYNAMICS*

What made jazz attractive in Sweden, according to Johan Fornäs, a professor at Linköping University, was the ‘fact that large groups of musicians and dancing listeners were at the time looking for difference, novelty and surprise and for cultural forms capable of expressing the new sensibilities and values of modern life’ (In Nicholson 2005:200). In Shetland, Peerie Willie and Billy Kay and many of those around them were drawn to jazz for some of the same reasons, and Willie became a local icon precisely because he was ‘always experimenting’, as Billy told me, and reflecting with his way of life the ethical principles of Shetland’s sociomusical tradition, strongly supported by *spree* practices. Nicholson (2005:101) points out that, ‘in contemporary times, there appears to be more players lacking individuality than in the past, a belief that has grown rather than receded in recent years’. Wilf (2012) curiously avoids the key issues surrounding the ‘homogenization effect of jazz education’ (Nicholson 2005:101).

‘Everybody’s bitching these days about how the new students and young players all sound the same’, points out pianist and educator Hal Galper, who worked as sideman with ‘Cannonball Adderley, Stan Getz, Phil Woods, and Chet Baker’ (Nicholson 2005:101). For Galper, ‘jazz education today is being destroyed by the profit motive and an overloaded curriculum’ (In Nicholson 2005:103). Nicholson (2005:106) points out that, for critics of the standardised educational system, ‘what jazz has gained in mass production it has lost in individuality and creativity’. As Frank Griffith, an American sax player who teaches at Brunel University in London noted, ‘there is too much studying the masters and not enough time studying yourself’ in American jazz programs (In Nicholson 2005:106). The sociomusical environment that the Shetland *spree* kindles supports precisely the development of this idiosyncratic individuality. In his late 20s, banjo player Lewie Peterson, whose father Gary Peterson is a legendary Shetland banjo player, one of the

musicians responsible for introducing Stevie Hook to the local scene in the 1970s, tells me that his style is quite different from his father's. Cohen (1987:191), whose main ethnographic concern was not music, pointed out that Shetlanders reject the notion of a 'Shetland fiddle style' as a monolith applied by the Scottish, whereas in fact locals understand their style as being 'distinctively individualistic' (Cohen 1987:191).¹³⁵ Bryan Gear does not sound like Maggie Adamson, and Debbie Scott does not sound like Maurice Henderson, and Ewen Thomson does not sound like Peter Gear or Mary Rutherford, and so on. They all play in their own particular way and have developed a personal tone. Maurice, other experienced fiddlers and music lovers understand the personal styles of every associate well enough to identify, on blindfolds, each sound in a crowd of musicians.

Nicholson notes that when bebop was at its height, 'in the 1940s and 1950s, when improvisers created something exceptional they were imitated by other members of the musical community, and quickly assimilated into the broader syntax of the music' (2014:35). There were 'certain key phrases or licks' that conformed to the 'bebop style' and became 'widely disseminated and imitated' (Nicholson 2014:35). This generated a 'narrow repository of stylistic inspiration' from a 'pantheon' of 'fewer than fifteen musicians' and the result was 'similarity of concept and execution among many musicians' (Nicholson 2014:35). This 'proliferation of a style or genre' generated 'its devaluation, and boredom becomes a possible response' (Nicholson 2014:35). While certain 'tribute bands' might be 'interesting to behold, they are seldom able to offer the sound of surprise' (Nicholson 2014:35). These 'tribute bands often fail to live up to expectation and appear to reinforce the impression that jazz is now more about the past than the present' (Nicholson 2014:35). In the classical tradition, Claude Debussy was fascinated 'with modes that were neither major nor minor and the music he heard at the World Exhibition in Paris in 1889 by Javanese and Vietnamese musicians' (Nicholson 2014:113). Still, Debussy and other

‘nationalist composers’ have not ‘merely imitated folkloric sources, but used their creative resources to develop techniques that answered their own needs’ (Nicholson 2014:113). ‘Composers such as Stravinsky and Bartók’, Nicholson argues, ‘refracted’ folkloric ‘influences through the creative prism of their imagination where they emerged creatively distorted, reshaped, and reimagined’ (Nicholson 2014:113). This perspective sees the works of composers inspired by various other musics as something analogous to Bateson’s ‘transducers or pathways to information’ (1972:324). They engage freely with many of the world’s cultural creative materials, continually transforming themselves and their music in the process. Similarly, the spirit of experimentation incorporated in Shetland’s sociomusical *sprees* practices is a driving force behind the gradual formation and appreciation of personal character in social settings.

Figure 7: DJ Lyall performing a hip-hop duo with Marjolein Robertson (not shown) and *Troppo Funk*, and engaging with the audience, at the Lerwick Legion, on August 16th 2013. Sigmund Danielsen (right) is one among many of Lyall’s friends in attendance.

CONCLUSION

6.9. *CREATIVE COMPLEMENTARITY and INTEGRATION*

Several values featured in this chapter are common to jazz, storytelling, and Shetland's sociomusical epistemological tradition. They include adopting a position that appreciates the idiosyncratic nuances of various known characters, and being routinely involved with the social pleasures of making music together and sharing personal experiences. The Shetland Folk Festival inspires, sustains, and kindles the local sociomusical scene. Ambivalence toward approaches that emphasise competition, judgment and perfection in imitation, instead of creative complementarity and enjoying making music together, is widespread. Young Shetland musicians engage with difference by selecting, blending, mixing and experimenting with musical materials. Positive support from parents has been a fundamental incentive in the formation of the musicians discussed here. Their shared interpersonal knowledge and extensive social relations have contributed in strengthening and broadening Shetland's music scene, and its 'folkie' *spreeing* and mixing core. The epistemological tradition, and the 'trad' ways of making music that emerged with it, highly value and actively support sociomusical environments that afford creative multiplicity, collaboration and the distribution of creative decision-making power. Participation in sociomusical *sprees* engenders long-term relationships and promotes face-to-face interactions founded upon horizontality and nuance of character appreciation.

CHAPTER 7: THESIS CONCLUSION

7.1. CREATIVITY and FREEDOM: *SPREE* RESILIENCE

This thesis shows that people's sense of creativity and personal freedom are intertwined and entangled into experiences that neither term alone can grasp; that the Shetland *spree* is a resilient tradition of sociomusical engagement that facilitates and encourages creativity, resists its own dissolution by the threat of externally imposed commercial models and regulations; and, most importantly, that the *spree* is the central practice of a sociomusical epistemological tradition that is so soundly principled that it can preserve its own historical musical core heritage while engaging with musics from all parts of the planet with enthusiasm, without fearing its loss or assimilation. This epistemological tradition is the result of the collective efforts of individuals working together through their love of music making and of each other's company. They ritually seek to establish a 'total communion with one another' and to become immersed in a 'transformative experience that goes to the root of each person's being and finds in that root something profoundly communal and shared' (Turner 1969:138).

As I have reviewed in chapter 2, ethnographies focusing on 'ethnicity and regional identity', which make up the bulk of those about Shetland after Goffman (1953), have often 'stagnated into banality and repetitive simplistic questioning about sociological boundaries' (Marcus and Fischer 1999:155). This type of theoretical stagnation, still far from uncommon, reflects practical-professional needs to conform to theoretical paradigms and fashionable personal preferences so that resulting writings would be supposedly more acceptable for publication. To overcome this epistemological issue, Marcus and Fischer argued that ethnographies should aim to explore empirically the 'historical and cultural conditions for the articulation and implementation of different values' (1999:167).

Shetland musicians enjoy an extensive, closely-knit, eclectic social support network that frees them from canonical control restrictions to explore their own personal musical

preferences. In Shetland, attempts to restrict and confine the tradition with canons of prescribed stylistic boundaries have failed. Individuals are highly valued for their character idiosyncrasies, but those who single-handedly seek to define *the* model for local tradition contradict the principle of horizontality, working against the flow of dialogical interactions characterising local relationships based on intergenerational and interpersonal knowledge.

Shetland *spreers* have cultivated a sociomusical practice that exemplifies an Epicurean approach to life as rendered in poetry by Lucretius (1992). Tranquillity of mind and body, for Lucretius, generates the analytical distance from which to compare one's own practices to those found commonly in the world – patterned ways of knowing and doing things. His outlook, in this sense, reflects a form of social science focused on deconstructing patterned behaviour. He notes the intellectual pleasure in perceiving the 'ills you are free from' (Lucretius 1992:95). From the analytical distance of the 'teachings of the wise' one could see from above the erring patterns of humans going 'astray' through competition, 'the strife of wits, the fight for precedence', and constant labouring for 'riches and to lay hold on power' (Lucretius 1992:95). For Epicureans, studying philosophy (as learning how to live) with friends was 'the most important thing in life' (Smith 1992:xliv). In Shetland's case, the study of 'true philosophy' emerges from *sprees* and lifelong personal friendships. As Titon noted, 'visiting' and 'friendship' are 'products of a music-making epistemology' and 'ground fieldwork in a musical being-in-the-world' (2008:38).

Similarly, Sapir's focus on the community's spiritual consciousness drew on a 'Nietzschean understanding of the proper relationship between individual and collective' (King 2009:146). For Sapir, conformity with spurious traditions – 'models that fall into nationalistic traps of essentializing specific traits, or insist in the correspondence of race, language, and culture' (King 2009:146) – must be dispensed with so that one can live according to the 'essential nature of one's personality' (Sapir 1924:422). As Goulet learned

from the Dene Tha, ‘true knowledge is personal knowledge’ and all claims that people make about the world are ‘based on an epistemology’ (1998:246-247). Shetland *sprees* practices and principles are compatible with practices and principles found elsewhere, especially those that promote community well being through forms of what Victor Turner (1969) called *communitas*, a space of freedom beyond regulated worlds, like those which neoliberal parasitism engenders.

Anthropologists have brought the concept of neoliberalism into their ethnographies in various ways: mainly as a ‘structural force that affects people’s lives and life-chances’, an ‘ideology of governance that shapes subjectivities’, and as ‘sites and agents of neoliberal practice’ (Ganti 2014:7.2). As with any other concept, neoliberalism and its various theoretical formulations have been critiqued for being limited. Ignoring the concept’s ramifications is not a viable solution, while focusing on it excessively is just as problematic. Every conceptual lens is invariably limited, as it implies *focus*. A fundamental question is whether our epistemology itself is reflexive, critical and creative enough to stretch and expand beyond its present limitations and horizons, tackling its core principles with the challenges of its own growth.

Anthropologists ‘are anxious about the popularity of neoliberalism as a concept but are unwilling, however, to completely dispense with the term’ (Ganti 2014:7.12). For Ganti, ‘the debate over the use (or overuse) of neoliberalism’ reflects the earlier ‘disenchantment with the perceived limitedness of the culture concept’ (2014:7.12). Spreading limitations, practices inspired by exploitative epistemological principles, such as neoliberalism and its various parasitical ramifications, damage and run against our own (i.e., ‘Western’) cultural stream of wisdom knowledge (e.g., Epicureanism). We should work to revoke such deleterious epistemologies and their effects, as creative and critical

scholars engaging present worlds, even if scholars elsewhere may find their effects pleasing, invisible or inconsequential.

As rituals of conviviality, the sociomusical *sprees* of every local festival manifest alternative ‘nonofficial, extra-ecclesiastical, and extra-political’ aspects ‘of human relations’, constructing an inclusive and temporary ‘second world’ (Bakhtin 1993[1965] *In* E. Turner 2012:33). *Sprees* are also aligned with principles of community-oriented conduct that Victor Turner found among the Ndembu: their chief must ‘laugh with the people’ in a relationship of ‘fellowship and good company’ that connects the worlds of the ‘living and the dead’ with a ‘seamless web of connection’, leading to the ‘fruits’ of ‘health, strength, and all good things’ (Turner 1969:104). As a way of being, the *sprees* resist ‘the national-political unit [that] tends to arrogate culture to itself’, and which, Sapir argued, manifests in ‘serious cultural impoverishment of vast portions of its terrain’ (1924:428). By *spreeing*, locals celebrate ‘individuality’ as ‘the very breath of life’ of culture (Sapir 1924:428).

‘Canned culture’, however, being ‘wound up in the machinery’, as Sapir characterised the spurious, ‘is so much easier to administer’ but overlooks the ‘minute increment of individuality which alone makes culture in the self and eventually builds up a culture in the community’ (Sapir 1924:429). These ideas resonate with the experiences and encounters I had in Shetland, as a participant in countless sociomusical *sprees* sessions, working at the main SFF stage at Islesburgh Centre with Stevie and Amanda in 2013, and as a performer alongside Jim Quinn and others with the Quinttet in 2014. People often creatively transform source materials, making them relevant for themselves and others in the present. The social extensions of personal trajectories, carved through various interpersonal bond-strengthening gatherings and sociomusical events, locally and beyond, provide materials that inspire original compositions and genuine reflections on life.

Shetland's epistemological tradition of music making contains anarchic elements, for it challenges highly controlled, hierarchical forms of social organisation, personal relationships and artistic collaborations. Innovation is not the tradition's main concern, but its natural consequence: *spreers* experiment with and transform the world, by playing, moving, and living. Everything they create reflects their current position in the world and the relationships that their present personal positions entail at that moment, reflecting past and future experiences. Similarly, people in Kamchatka 'recognize the personal and moral strengths of diverse traditions and the multiple possibilities for innovation and play with Koryak culture' (King 2011:238). As Sapir noted, Navaho weavers deliberately changed sacred 'sand painting designs here and there' in order to 'ward off the curse which follows a tampering with holy things', when transferring designs from sand paintings made in healing chanting ceremonies into blankets meant for white market demands (Sapir 1935:609). Although the 'blanket decoration looks like a genuine sand painting to the white man', knowledgeable Navaho 'put the blanket into the class of profane objects' for lacking 'ritualistic accuracy' (Sapir 1935:609). Yet, makers of such profane objects remain Navaho, and transform materials creatively according to present circumstances, like Shetlanders making rock and roll, country music, electronic house trance, 'funkified trad' – as Joe Watt said, 'I play in a funky-trad band, you play in a funky-trad band'. Indians 'do not stop being Indian when they eat pizza, despite legal rulings to the contrary', reasons King (2011:238) following Ridington (2002).¹³⁶ Similarly, social changes inspired from the outside in Whalsay do not make people 'become any less 'Whalsa'' (Cohen 1985:309).

As Cruikshank points out, Yukon elder Mrs. Sidney, reflected on 'ideas from other cultures, adapting them' and 'making them part of her repertoire of ideas' (1990:355). Sidney's 'intellectual drive to formulate consistent links between "old ways" and "new ways" permeates her entire account' (Cruikshank 1990:355). In the first century BC,

Lucretius found that ‘the imperceptibility of the atoms necessitated the employment of numerous analogies from the perceptible world to prove their existence and illustrate the nature of their movement’ (Smith 1992:xliv). Using texts penned by Epicurus as source, Lucretius ‘arranged his master’s teachings in a new way’ that was ‘relevant to contemporary needs’ (Smith 1992:li). Therefore, Lucretius produced ‘an original treatment of Epicureanism’ (Smith 1992:li). Edith Turner points out that it would not be ‘fair’ to ‘see to it that the Eskimos are preserved in their traditional ways and become enclosed in a pod of living history’ (1992:101). She observes that, even with the effects of colonialism – the ‘whites’ who keep on ‘whittling down their rights’ – Eskimos ‘are doing their own organizing well enough’ (Turner 1992:101). Their feasts, very much like the Shetland *sprees* and the Folk Fest, are a ‘sign of inner regrowth of the people themselves’ (Turner 1992:101). In Shetland and Alaska, revivals may not please purists, but exemplify local ‘self-determination governing what should take place’ (Turner 1992:101).

As Hill noted, at the Sibelius Academy in Finland, folk musicians can create and perform ‘their own personal, original (folk) music’ with ‘the freedom to develop folk music as an art’ (2009:89). For *spreers* who play jazz, rock, classical, and folk in Shetland, ‘creative process and artistic freedom’ are also closely aligned (Hill 2009:89).¹³⁷ Having reached Shetland by radio during World War II, jazz inspired Peerie Willie to experiment and innovate. Shetland’s sociomusical world, propelled by the affective power of *sprees* practices, infuses vitality, dimension, and motion into the creative pursuits of its inhabitants. The exercise of freedom engenders the creative processes of *divergent* thinking (Hill 2009:89). *Convergent* thinking, however, refers to the ‘process of following rules and specific set models to obtain the only acceptable outcome’ (Hill 2009:89).

The concept of creativity as a ‘generative activity requiring divergent thinking’ (Hill 2009:89) is useful to understand young Shetlanders’ reflections on local *Spreinciples*

and on their involvement with the commercial entertainment industry and institutionalised, curricular, canon-based musical education. For Norman Willmore, breaking taken for granted rules afforded feelings of creative freedom, developing critical social awareness, personal character and voice. In our experiences with *Ignition*, since personal creativity was discouraged, playing music made time drag in slow flow. For Hayden Hook, following strict rules, notes on pages, technical drills, and imposed repertoires, affected adversely the delicate harmonic resonance between creative freedom and personal growth.

7.2. EPISTEMOLOGICAL GROWTH and CULTURAL-CREATIVE INTEGRATION

As Whorf argued, conceiving new theories affords higher awareness of ‘linguistic devices’ (1940:2). The acquisition of concepts outside one’s native language improves one’s ‘conceptual ability’, opening up epistemological pathways for a potential ‘advancement of science’ (Whorf 1941 *In* Lee 1996:26). As Stoller noted, the doctrine of relativism ‘enabled anthropology to emerge from the shadows of racist evolutionary thinking’ (2013:159). With ‘innovative extensions’ (Wagner 1991:36), one may exercise reflexive linguistic awareness and achieve ‘individual cognitive growth’ (Lee 1996:224).

The notion of epistemological resonance investigates how, while making music together or interacting socially, some people experience a warping of time – dragging (in discordant interactions) or timelessness (in harmonic interactions). During the ‘optimal experience’ of flow, concentration ‘is so intense that there is no attention left over to think about anything irrelevant, or to worry about problems’ (Csikszentmihalyi 1990:4, 71). In flow experiences, ‘[s]elf-consciousness disappears, and the sense of time becomes distorted’ (Csikszentmihalyi 1990:71). Similarly, in sociomusical *sprees*, ‘the sense of time bears little relation to the passage of time as measured by the absolute convention of the

clock' (Csikszentmihalyi 1990:66). *Spreers* achieve this intensity by cultivating horizontal relationships founded on interpersonal knowledge and mutual support.

Conformance to fashionable theoretical paradigms can restrict creativity among scholars and musicians, preventing epistemological growth as the transcendence of unwittingly adopted paradigmatic limitations.¹³⁸ If all we do is creative improvisation, how do we address the negative effects of symbolic and structural violence on creativity? For jazz and folk musicians, stretching expression beyond the confines of strict paradigms generates creative experiences, affording the satisfaction of reflexive personal growth.

What listeners perceive as original is contingent on their exposure to specific musical forms and materials. Thus, judgments of musical originality are relative. Often, inexperienced listeners cannot recognise influences in compositions or nuances in improvised solos – the epitome of personal expression in jazz. Experienced listeners, like Shetlander John 'The Wolf' Polson, perceive historical influences and nuances. John references such nuances by drawing on his extensive jazz music collection. Once, at Aitkens, we were listening to saxophonist James Carter in the track *JC on the Set* (1994), when John noted an Illinois Jacquet (1922-2004) phrase that Carter cited and reworked. Being unfamiliar with Jacquet's work, I did not recognise the reference. John later showed me Jacquet's recording, proving the link. Similar transformations of materials emerge in anthropological theories and debates. Yet, replete with frictions and fissures, cognitive gaps, discordances, tensions and mistranslations, our theories suggest that everyone produces somewhat unique takes on field phenomena.

For Brightman (1995), scholars who attack the culture concept merely extend it by adopting hipper, yet less effective, terminology. As the 'culture concept' is 'unavoidable', King reasons, anthropologists should take responsibility for presenting a 'dynamic theory of culture connected to the way people live their lives' or face the worst case scenario –

‘let sociologists, political scientists, or (worse still) politicians define culture for us’ (2011:244). As Victor Turner argued, symbols can ‘represent many different things’ and be connected ‘by analogous qualities and associations’ (1967:28 *In* Carsten 2011:20). As Carsten noted, while Turner (1967) emphasised the ‘condensed nature of ritual symbols’, Levi-Strauss (1969[1962]:175) drew attention to ‘metaphor as a primary form of discursive thought’ (2011:20). Anthropologists realised that ways of thinking have practical consequences and that personal interpretations complicate them. Thus, *similar*, shared experiences, their insights and realisations, inspire *different* ways of expressing and communicating them. Accepting this multiplicity affords an appreciation of highly variable and contextually symbolic concepts, shapes, metaphors, allusions, places and social beings, their personal trajectories and entangled temporalities.

7.3. *CULTURAL WISDOM, IDENTITY and MATERIAL METAMORPHOSES*

People infuse ageless ideas with social meaning and power, reapplying them in present contexts, as Boas (1955[1927]) and Cruikshank (1990, 1998) noticed, and as young Shetland musicians pointed out in their discussion of ‘funkified trad’ (Chapter 6). Prevailing ‘modes of life’ provide a basis for adapting ‘imported stories’, leading into ‘radical changes’ of ‘foreign sources’, and ‘distinctive forms’ of ‘greater individuality’ (Boas 1955[1927]:332-336). In colonial contexts, as Lempert (2014:387) noted, mimicry and imitation have also been used as forms of resistance (e.g., Taussig 1993, Stoller 1995, 1996), a kind of creativity. Many Shetland musicians, like the Koryak in Kamchatka, exercise their ‘ability to bend old forms into new shapes and to continue in a genuine tradition’ (King 2011:261). Yet, nationalist reporters and museum bureaucrats believe that the Koryak, by changing with the contemporary world, are ‘losing traditions’ (King 2011:242). But since cultures have always changed, intercultural transformations are ‘not

necessarily a *loss*' (King 2011:242). Validating 'contemporary Koryak people's lives and identities as Koryak and not as *assimilated* or *debilitated*' proves that their culture is not 'less than it used to be' (King 2011:242 my emphases). The same goes for Shetland's epistemological tradition of music making. The resilience of the *spre* carries Shetland's sociomusical wisdom across generations, showing that intergenerational engagement and interpersonal knowledge afford the growth of harmonic epistemological resonance.

Ethnographers who are prepared to shed some of their own assumptions and preconceptions will find wisdom in their engagements with difference. Wisdom, for Victor Turner, is finding 'the appropriate relationship between structure and *communitas* under the *given* circumstances of space and time', accepting 'each modality when it is paramount without rejecting the other', and not clinging 'to one when its present impetus is spent' (1969:139). As Wikan argues, 'our cultural models are fundamentally culture-bound and may need refeel-thinking to allow for different constructions of reality' (2012:84). Similarly, for Geertz, anthropologists should not abandon the wisdom of indigenous cultures 'for the restless ambitiousness, the pride and egoism, of mechanical civilization' (1973:358). Yet, academic trend seekers indulge in 'lexical hygiene' to construct the 'imputed conceptual superiority' of their preferred terms (Brightman 1995:534).

The history of anthropology and colonialism teaches us to resist the 'myth of objectivism' of dominant conceptual systems and metaphors that social institutions impose as taken-for-granted, unquestionable models for rationality (Lakoff and Johnson 1998:159-160). As Whorf argued, civilisation and rationality are not synonymous, and 'too much rationality may defeat itself, or arouse some strong compensatory principle' (1956:81).¹³⁹ Shetland's *spreeing* sociomusical community is an invaluable source of wisdom for its inhabitants. Its principles of resourcefulness and horizontality, strengthened by

interpersonal knowledge, afford the growth of friendships and artistic collaborations that challenge the solidity of cultural and aesthetic-stylistic boundaries.

7.4. RISK, INNOVATION, CHANCE, CREATIVITY

Naturalised epistemological conditions often obscure unconventional approaches for living and making art. As Piotrowska noted, creativities that break down ‘regulations and confinements’, generating ‘innovation and novelty’ have been contested and misunderstood (2012:330). In the 19th century, improvisation was seen as the ‘rebellious’ and ‘anarchic’ amalgamation of ‘genius and madness’, a ‘supernatural’, and ‘abnormal deviation’, ‘nervous disorder, illness or even psychosis’ that verged on the ‘unnatural or even inhuman’ (Piotrowska 2012:330). In contrast, composition’s rationality rested on the authority of ‘logocentric rules’, the very act of limitation (Piotrowska 2012:333). Alternatively, in Indian Classical music, improvisers seek to capture, feel and transform the environment, producing the heart-penetrating magic of ‘dream’ and ‘meditation’, transporting them into a ‘different world’, as long as ‘one, two, or three persons of the same quality and nature’ enjoy making music together (Khan 2005:349).¹⁴⁰

What we discover by following closely the lives of young musicians who have been recognised for their supposed talent, like a number of younger Shetland musicians I got to know well, is that they worked very seriously on their craft. They were constantly practicing, writing new songs, performing in different settings, often with various groups in multiple styles. Most importantly, they engage with sociomusical activities such as talking about and listening to music, jamming together, having different projects in various genres, and attending live music events throughout the year, all of which involved in some way or another also a number of their close friends as performers and audience members.

Shetland audiences and performers are very familiar with one another, due to the closely-knit nature of social relations in a small community, and the binding, interpersonal element of music cultures (i.e., the power to connect by affinity).¹⁴¹ In smaller gigs, especially those at the Legion in Lerwick, a large proportion of the audience are artists and know the performers from social relations that may or not involve having musical collaborations. Those who believe themselves to be non-musical but who nevertheless appreciate and support the local music scene, have musician friends, perhaps from non-musical, occupation based social channels, are also welcomed into the same sociomusical circles. There are people who are involved enthusiastically with the Shetland Folk Fest but who are supposedly *non-musical* music lovers and supporters. The two Davies, Henderson and Gardner, and also Amanda and Heidi Pearson come to mind as non-musicians, among many others, who have played a major role in supporting the local music scene. Thus, Shetland's music scene fosters strong bonds among musicians through their love of music making and local *spree* practices, but its success is always dependent on the social participation and inclusion of non-musicians, especially those who share with them the sense of community that recognises equally the vital importance of musical practices and of encouraging their ubiquity and resilience throughout Shetland.

7.5. HOLOGRAPHIC REVERBERATIONS of SPREE CHARACTER and STYLE

In Shetland, by *spreeing* according to the principles of the epistemological tradition, locals grow their sense of nuance of character appreciation. Hence, experienced musicians like Maurice Henderson and others understand, appreciate, and are sensitive to character and style nuances, the particular tonal and rhythmic qualities of voice and sound distinctive to fellow players. Language alone is relatively inadequate to describe such personal musical nuances, so words cannot describe an overarching Shetland fiddling style.

Similarly, logical and translation difficulties arise when we subject sensorial perceptions, such as smell and taste, to language. Direct experience with actual phenomena is the only available pathway for associating particular descriptions and logics with actual sensations. In their appreciation of personal character, Shetlanders are like native Kamchatkans. They have a ‘history of knowing how to speak’ and ‘knowing how to hear many different ways of speaking’ (King 2011:257). Developing a differentiated appreciation for the feeling and movement that each character brings to the music is paramount. Some noted that tunes written in Shetland by anyone can become infused with some local character, but musicians have their own personal styles.

Years of listening, watching, and participating in sociomusical *sprees* can afford mutual nuance of character appreciation and social wisdom. Thus, most Shetlanders with extensive fiddling experience (including listening and playing) recognise Bryan Gear’s style as lyrical, precise, and moving. Connoisseurs almost always note Bryan Gear’s slow airs as sublime. Yet, descriptions always fall short of the experience of listening to Bryan play live, from the heart, and with presence. As musical feeling infuses everything with resonance, the deep, ineffable intimacy between instrument and performer stimulates the audience with an instantaneous, mesmerising effect, intensified by listeners’ familiarity with the players and the stories that shape the tunes they play.

Comparisons in terms of ‘who plays better’ between Bryan Gear and other experienced Shetland fiddlers, like Ewen Thomson, Maurice Henderson, Gemma Donald, Peter Gear or others, make no sense. Neither technique nor capacity differentiates them, but unique style, personality, character, presence and tone, make all equally valuable. By recognising individuals as springs of idiosyncratic logics creatively constructed through worldly experiences, we may distance ourselves from naturalised understandings and the epistemological consequences of predetermined logics. As King noted, Boasian

anthropologists saw cultures as ‘systems of thought and action’ and employed ‘examples learned from fieldwork to critique their own culture’ (2011:234).¹⁴² The ‘deconstruction of otherness’, argued Stoller, ‘is the price of truth’ (2013:160). As Stoller noted, fieldwork experience ‘undermines the foundations of any universalist rationality’ (2013:160).

Maurice Henderson studied and played consistently over many years. He participated in countless *sprees* with more experienced fiddlers, songwriters, and instrumentalists. From the time he was a high school student in Lerwick, to the development of *Fiddler’s Bid* as a group, countless bonding *sprees* happened at Maurice’s Fetlar home. Like many other experienced Shetland musicians, Maurice understands that musical proficiency requires persistence. Commitment to the *sprees* affords, with conviviality, great personal and social rewards. Realising this commitment, expert instrumentalists are enthusiastic supporters of beginners, who will carry on Shetland’s epistemological tradition of music making.

As Stevie Hook told me many times, children who learn to play discover a whole new dimension to their lives. As his students discover their own musical voices and grow into new paths, Stevie feels rewarded. For him, music making is an invaluable gift for a young person. As Stoller noted, through music and sound, the intangible becomes tangible and our ‘inner and outer worlds interpenetrate’ (1989:120). Stevie always speaks of his young music pupils, appreciating their unique characters and potentials. Their mutual entanglement grows immersed in harmonic interpersonal reverberations. Stevie and Amanda invested hard earned savings in their son Hayden’s intensive classical music studies at a boarding school in Aberdeen. In 2013, Hayden became a jazz student at the Amsterdam Conservatorium, more affordable and better equipped than the similar Glasgow program that Hayden’s close friend, drummer Finlay Jamieson, attended. Hayden inherited professional live sound engineering and stage set-up skills, and a hard-working

outlook from his *sprees*-wise parents. Stevie held many odd jobs over the years, but music making gave him lasting gifts, priceless friendships, social delights, and means for expressing personal feelings and memories.

Spreers engage distinct musical styles by co-inhabiting sociomusical worlds that kindle interpersonal knowledge and intergenerational engagement. The entanglements of their growing trajectories reverberate with the creative materials they make and share. For Stoller, reverberations are feelings and sensations linked to ‘the metaphorical aspects of symbolic expression’ (1989:77). Reverberations ‘create sentiments in the eye and the mind of the person who experiences the world’ (Stoller 1989:37). As Stoller noted, the ‘impact of a poem’, for Bachelard (1957), does not lie ‘in its referential content but in how this referential content carries a message that strikes a resonant chord (“reverberates”) in the reader’ (1989:158). *Spreeing* kindles interpersonal, reverberative links among Shetland’s sociomusical world inhabitants. The ‘visible and the invisible’, ‘tangible and intangible’ fuse as sounds interpenetrate ‘inner and outer worlds’ (Stoller 1989:120). Anthropologists have recognised the ‘relevance of the mechanics and effects of so-called invisible or intangible domains, whether these are constituted by spirits, quarks, the law or money value’ (Espírito Santo and Blanes 2014:1). Inhabiting supportive sociomusical worlds, *spreers* transcend spatialised, distancing gazes, in ‘a flowing and dynamic universe’ without clear distinctions ‘between the material and immaterial worlds’ (Stoller 1989:12).

For Stoller, as music ‘reverberates with power’, songs become ‘power, energy, the veritable force of life’ (1989:112). Similarly, Whorf theorized the linguistic ‘n-dimensional realm’ or *manifold hyperspace*, as holographic, organising phenomena and epiphenomena in mutually reflective and coherent dimensions (Lee 1996:37, 61). In holographic perspectives, the body manifests what one knows and feels, in personal, social, and cultural scales. People share the semantic frameworks of ordinary language to generate

idiosyncrasies, becoming portals onto the reality of the culture(s) in which they recognise themselves as active participants. For Wagner, ‘holographic correspondence involves a degree of condensation, of image intensity, and recursiveness that defies reduction to the linear and referential relations necessary for analysis’ (1986:51). Holographic models of culture and language suppose that despite all idiosyncrasies that we may collect about singular individuals, we find that reflections of higher-level cultural and social relations manifested in their ways of being. As Lee notes, the connectionist-holographic logic that informs Whorf’s thinking on language should ‘be of interest to cognitive scientists unaware of this alternate, if submerged, paradigm in linguistic science’ (1996:37).¹⁴³

Finally, epistemological resonance, discordance and harmonisation dynamics, and the growth process of symbolic interpersonal reverberation in contemporality, are ideas that I propose, hoping to inspire other creative-critical ethnographic studies of personal and social epistemological, resonance, reverberation, transformation, growth and temporality. The ‘ineffable’ calls us to ‘pay more attention to experience and incorporate evocative expression in order to understand and describe the spirituality of social worlds’ (Stoller 2013:165). I may understand the process of my increasing involvement as a participant in Shetland’s music community through these terms, but they are not meant to comprise a universal model that transcends culture. Instead, they simply extend an eclectic epistemological holograph that seeks nuanced understandings of interpersonal-cultural dynamics, including how and why certain encounters seem inevitable and preordained.

7.6. *STRUCTURAL 'DAMAGE CONTROL' – REGULATIONS*

Shetlanders have developed their own alternative models for servicing the community with sociomusical and cultural goods through the voluntary Shetland Folk Fest and country hall committees, High Level Music, WobblyGang, Billy Kay's studio, Aitkens, and various *spree*-founded lifetime friendships. Yet, SADA and the SIC have adopted a top-down, rule-bound commercial *modus operandi* that is out of touch with local principles of conviviality. SADA, largely unsuccessfully and unjustifiably to many locals, sought to emulate organisational models imported from London and Edinburgh, or other mainstream metropolitan settings. The SFF committee, the most respected and cherished sociomusical organisation in Shetland, is constantly recognised as legitimate, effective, and attuned to traditional epistemological values. SADA's highly regulated, hierarchical business model contradicts this historical, centuries-old, tradition of conviviality and resourcefulness. Morphed into sociomusical *spree* forms, this tradition is now the heart of successful initiatives and events such as the Shetland Folk Festival, *Back from Beyond*, Glusstonberry, the Buffet, Unst Fest, the Fetlar *spree*, and the High Level Music Gala Concert. As Campbell reported, out of '4500-5000 individuals' who attended the SFF in the 1990s, 'around ninety-five percent' were locals (1997:9). Considering that Shetland's population estimate of 23 thousand people includes thousands of temporary workers who usually remain socially disconnected from the sociomusical world, about 20-25% of the entire resident population attends the Shetland Folk Festival. These figures support the notion that the spirit of the *spree* and its principles are transmitted through SFF activities.

SADA's metropolitan approach clashes with Shetland's epistemological tradition by assuming that local ways cannot provide alternative modes of social and collective organisation. Supposedly incontestable guidelines for best practices, rules, and regulations, take precedence over local logic because they come from 'above'. By interpreting

sociomusical worlds according to lenses provided by official rules and regulations, SADA managers are unable to appreciate how their operating assumptions are not attuned to local realities. The orthodox epistemological framework of hierarchical power concentration that SADA adopted demands strict adherence to rules that locals perceive as logically incoherent and incompatible with traditional ways. Locals constantly parody the loftiness of official regulations to restore resonant, interpersonal flows. As Bakhtin noted, laughter is a ‘permanent corrective’ against the ‘one-sided seriousness of the lofty direct word’, revealing ‘its limitations and insufficiency’ (1981:55-56).

Shetlanders have also developed commercial models and funded projects attuned to local principles. Operations like High Level Music and WobblyGang, and initiatives like *Back from Beyond*, have flourished by adopting local conviviality, horizontal mutuality and nuance of character as a directive for community service and business.¹⁴⁴ Throughout ‘much of the history of civilization’, Turner notes, various peoples who experienced and resisted tyranny ‘were given visionary moments that embodied their hopes of freedom’ and eventually ‘came to trust the gifts of their own culture and sociality’ (2012:86). The sociomusical *sprees* and the epistemological tradition of music making, as social technologies of horizontal engagement, are the gifts of Shetlanders’ own *culturing*. The *modus operandi* of local shops and their *spreer* owners also manifest these gifts. As a form of ‘second life’, the *sprees*, a friendship entanglement-knitting, flow-restoring ritual of creativity, is ‘sharply distinct from the serious, official, ecclesiastical, and political cults, forms and ceremonials’ (Bakhtin 1993[1965] In Turner 2012:33). Hence, local shops and operations are at odds with certain regulations, which waste time with needless tasks. In one case, authorities questioned and inspected whether Fiona at High Level was fit for preparing and serving ‘toasties’, which demand a special ‘hot’ food license!

7.7. CREATIVE MULTIPLICITY and FLOW – DISTRIBUTIVE, SHARED POWER

The flow of creative activities and healthy socialisation in Shetland’s music scene is constant. Participation in it brings one into a closely-knit web of familial support and caring. These dynamics sustain a strong potential for what Edith Turner (2012:45-46) calls ‘prime communitas experiences’ that flow from what musician Eckhart Krupp termed a ‘cultivated closeness bordering on telepathic intuition’ (Turner 2012:48). It is not just the social world that generates this closeness, but how experiences are coloured by an immersion in music as a form of communication that bridges thought and feelings through the sharing in the creative process with familiar others. Creative multiplicity takes place with this communion: the sharing of musical materials, and the selective, friendship-oriented inclusion of others in ongoing and future creative projects, compositions and performances – a possibility kindled by the sociomusical effects of the *spree* approach.

HORIZONTALITY and EPISTEMOLOGICAL TRADITION TRANSMISSION

Personal and ethical harmonisation with the *spree* model, however partial, is achieved through bodily engagement with its principles in practice. It leads to a fulfilling and overwhelmingly positive relationship with music making and the immediate personal-social and physical worlds, increasing exposure to others attuned to sociomusical *Spreinciples*. This shared sense of well-being, produced through various artistic events and the celebration of sociomusical experiences, sustains the healthy transmission of the epistemological tradition into future generations. The horizontal grounding that the dissolution of divisive age, gender, and socioeconomic class differences between *spree* participants fosters, facilitates the transmission process, showing that intergenerational engagement strengthens the collective sense of interpersonal knowledge.¹⁴⁵

The hierarchical approaches of professional, commercial worlds ultimately reinforce a type of prescriptive authoritarianism, veiled by the supposed righteousness and infallibility of laws and regulations. For locals who live with intergenerational engagement and horizontality principles, such logics are demeaning. In rare cases, even residents who are aware of local ethical *Sprenciples* may contradict them in practice or abandon them. Nonetheless, they may still enjoy the sociomusical possibilities that *sprees* afford, and re-attune themselves to its core values. The historical resilience and openness of this epistemological tradition is also reflected in Shetland's ritual acceptance of its 'prodigal' offspring, scattered around the world, and celebrated periodically in Hamefarin' events, for the 'pleasures of recalling', to paraphrase Irvine (2010).

CREATIVE-CRITICAL RESONANCE, EPISTEMOLOGICAL GROWTH and TRADITION

Evens' (1996) study among the Azande 'found a truth that is beyond our capacity to comprehend', argues Stoller, and that 'precipitates a kind of existential learning, which takes something away from us' (2013:161). For Evens, what is taken away is 'the cost of the world as we know it, which is to say, not the enrichment, as one may be used to hearing, but the veritable transformation of our-selves' (1996:30 *In* Stoller 2013:161). Similarly, the 'split-mind vision of culture', argues Wikan, 'impedes the understanding of alternative epistemologies like those based in feeling-thinking as the vital premise and the key of relevance to lived experience' (Wikan 2012:86). Both Stoller and Wikan speak of ethnographers post-fieldwork reflexive disenchantment with the worlds from which we all have emerged, not 'as we know it', but 'as we understood it' – this is one way in which we encounter epistemological growth and expand conceptual horizons, changing our inner resonance and our relationships with the present.

By personally experiencing other ways of being attentively, and becoming socially involved with locals for extended periods of time, our perspective on where we are coming from deepens. This comparative-reflexive deepening depends on how far we have gone in deconstructing ourselves, how we choose to look back, and whether we are open enough to learn and revisit our previous assumptions in the process. In Shetland, the *spree* is a resilient form of social wisdom that allows people to become increasingly familiar with the personal trajectories of others, generating long lasting comfort and support and a never ending string of events in which segments of the community come together. Some are more assiduous, others are busy elsewhere, but most will at some point in time converge in sociomusical events and catch up with one another, following up on what they already know from previous times they shared in various sociomusical environments, from the music shop to country halls and larger venues, from private *sprees* to their travels around the world. As a result, I know that the urban environments that I have lived in (Brazil, United States, Canada, Scotland, Portugal) contrary to lore, do not provide the quality of interpersonal engagement, conviviality and support that Shetlanders can take for granted.

The resonance that emerges through relationships characterised by deep interpersonal knowledge such as those that are common among active Shetland musicians and which I found daily at WobblyGang, at Aitkens, and at High Level Music, at first surprised me, and made me doubt it; eventually, as I became immersed in the scene, it became an enchanting reality, where people are listening and paying attention to who you are, what you say, and value what you can do well, help you with what you can work on. It is indeed a world always full of joy, but also, troubles, sorrows and social challenges that people tackle, full-heartedly, for their love of the music community in Shetland – where making music all night long with friends is the usual offer to honour the life of those who have departed. It is done with the utmost respect and care, with tears and laughter, and

devotion to the musical craft that brought them together in the first place. The same craft that will bind them together as long as they can share and delight in the gifts of long-lasting intergenerational engagement and in the well spun matrix of interpersonal knowledge that makes Shetland a place where friendships still grow and last for a lifetime.

Brian Nicholson, in February 2013, told me that music is like a substitute for religion in Shetland, and he often feels in ‘the presence of music’ and cannot imagine what life would be like without it. He told me that it was like ‘having a mother watching over you all the time’, helping him, through its serendipitous touch when he least expected it. Quoting Peerie Willie, he said,

‘the world would be an awful dull place without music’.

Figure 8: Brian Nicholson (right) and young High Level Music students, in a fundraiser concert for local music education projects. Clickimin Centre, September 24th 2014.

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ENDNOTES

¹ For Laughey, the ‘notion of music scenes’ encounters problems ‘which centre on the suggestion that they are at once defined by their places’, such as a city or geographical area, and ‘spaces such as clubs, record shops, old warehouses and so on’ (2008:100-101). For Laughey (2008:102), scenes that ‘are closer tied to specific localised contexts rather than set against global trends’ seem ‘to offer more promising research routes and disprove the otherwise convincing argument, championed by Hesmondhalgh (2002:128), that the concept of scene does not account for audiences and ‘is unlikely to inspire studies of them’. Shetland’s sociomusical world blurs reified distinctions between audiences and performers, public and private, in various ways. In many events, audiences are composed of very well known others. Shetland music festivals and concerts present a problem for researchers dichotomising between performers and audiences. People can take up various roles on the same event (e.g., audience, organiser, performer, merchandise booth salesperson, sound engineer). More often than not, even in concerts that only feature one or two local acts, a number of audience members have been countless times onstage while those performing were audience members and performers.

² According to the ‘scenes’ model, music ‘has a formative role in the construction, negotiation, and transformation of sociocultural identities’ (Born 2000:31). Here, ‘music engenders communities’ that afford ‘a play with, a performance of, and an imaginary exploration of identities’ (Born 2000:31). Following Kearney’s (1995:558) discussion, I see ‘identity’ and ‘identities’ as formed through the ‘logic of “both-and-and[n]”’ in everyday contexts. This position accounts for the potential fluidity of personal experiences of subject formation without rejecting offhand the possibility for subjects to identify strongly with more limited sets of identity attributes through everyday routines (e.g., storekeeper, lawyer, manager, peasant, housewife, husband, etc). To move beyond the patterning force of identity, achieving creative-critical change, one must recognise the patterns that developed one’s own personality.

³ As Ingold noted, phenomenology inspired anthropological projects (e.g., Jackson 1989) focus on the body as a nexus for experiencing the world, exploring the connections between Merleau-Ponty’s (2002[1945]) ‘concerns with perception’ and ‘Bourdieu’s with practice’ (2000:170). Csordas (1990) sought to establish a phenomenological ‘paradigm for embodiment’ in ‘anthropological enquiry’ (Ingold 2000:170). Bourdieu derived his insight on bodily *hexis* from Eric Havelock (1963), for whom the body ‘is constantly mingled with all the knowledge it reproduces, and this knowledge never has the objectivity it derives from objectification in writing and the consequent freedom with respect to the body’ (Bourdieu 1990:73).

⁴ Various ideas and personal studies influence my theoretical formulations, most importantly Pierre Bourdieu’s (1990) logical triad, *habitus*, *praxis*, and *hexis*; Immanuel Kant’s (1992:268-275) short discussion of the horizon of cognition with an emphasis on the *praefactiones* (thoroughnesses) method and the logical, aesthetic, and practical dimensions; and finally, a detailed reading of Hermann Hesse’s *The Glass Bead Game* (2000[1943]), a work that deserves far more attention than it has received by anthropologists. For Kant, the ‘horizon of cognition’ was the storehouse of associative and affective conceptual materials organised and ruled by epistemological principles. He argued that our horizons ‘can be determined according to the variety of [our] cognitions’ (Kant 1992:275). In Hesse (2000[1943]), a reflexive ethnographic methodology is woven with a phenomenology of transformation through music and scholarship. The book reflects on tensions between fieldwork in the world and academic life, providing examples of epistemological resonance, discordances and harmonisations that support the vision the present thesis synthesises.

⁵ In the past, ethnographers have often ignored the importance of temporality and presumed culture to be transcendental and normative. As Crapanzano noted, Geertz (1973) ignored the particularities of specific performances, and constructed ‘transcending stories’, generating an ‘illusion of specificity when there is no specific temporal or spatial vantage point’ (1986:75-76). To avoid this

error, I analyse experiences from October 2012 roughly until the end of 2014, often presenting them in the words of residents and natives. Attention to the temporality of particular events and experiences is vital for understanding personal trajectories and processes of musical enskilment. The temporality of recordings, rehearsals, performances, travels, and other experiences provide comparative dimensions that grow in significance for participants as time goes by.

⁶ This schematic <<https://prezi.com/fxg9-lzuzxwj/view/>> shows how some of the theoretical elements that I have adopted for the present theory are conceptually interlinked.

⁷ Many Shetland musicians and music scene supporters work or have worked for the energy industry. They are mostly not temporary energy and construction workers. Shetlanders' issues with temporary energy workers cannot be linked to a supposedly prevailing 'anti-modern' identity (Grydehøj 2011), or cultural biases against general 'incomers' (McFarlane 1981). Bevington (2014), Johnson (2014) and Cope (2015) reported on recent tensions involving temporary energy workers linked to construction projects. Such tensions may inspire locals to develop *spree* practices and keep them alive in private, inviting and selecting only individuals whose ways of being are attuned to the principles of the *spree*.

⁸ WobblyGang is a live sound engineering service operated by Stevie Hook and Amanda Pearson. High Level Music is Lerwick's music shop and educational centre, operated by Fiona Adamson and Brian Nicholson, employing various music teachers and serving many young pupils.

⁹ I henceforward refer to 'Peerie Willie Johnson' simply as Peerie Willie, following local usage.

¹⁰ For Bosman, the tradition founded by Diogenes the Cynic calls 'for a life of individual simplicity, self-sufficiency, moral integrity, and freedom' (2007:25).

¹¹ Audiovisual examples showing sociomusical *sprees* taking place, including the pivotal Fetlar *spree*, on July 19th and 20th 2014, are available at <www.shetlandspree.com>.

¹² Gushee (1977) proposed studying these 'empty spots' as a 'science of lacunae' or 'gapology' (*In* Nattiez 1990:193).

¹³ Laughey noted that the 'small proportion' of research accounting 'for intergenerational relations' tends 'to stress their harmoniousness' (2008:83). 'Intergenerational narratives', for Laughey, 'are situated in the interactive local, familial and traditional contexts of everyday youth music cultures' (2008:210). Theorists 'of spectacular, intra-generational youth music cultures operating within a subcultural paradigm' hardly considered the 'familiar surroundings of schools, colleges, shops, revisited holiday destinations, pubs and cafés (Laughey 2008:210). In Shetland's sociomusical scene, intergenerational engagement is normalised. Most gigs, from classical to metal, kindle relationships between younger and older people. Octogenarian Allan Tulloch, after a performance at the Whalsay Boating Club in October 2012, took at least ten minutes encouraging a child fiddle player who had just performed. My Shetland-born participants recognised that intergenerational relationships were foundational for their sociomusical growth.

¹⁴ Holographic models have been proposed to explain how 'the brain's information storage' may operate, as information is 'distributed over collections of neurons' (Churchland 1989:407-408 *In* Lee 1996:50-51). In holograms, 'any part of the plate on which an image has been stored can be used to reconstruct the image as a whole' since 'information about all parts of the image is stored in a distributed fashion in all parts of the plate' (Lee 1996:50).

¹⁵ The 'unconscious' is an example of a naturalised 'commonsense' understanding. Traced back to psychoanalytical theory, it is widely used, taken for granted as self-explanatory, and proposed as

final explanation for social phenomena. For Bourdieu, the unconscious locates ‘finality in mechanism’, as a ‘kind of *Deus ex machina*’ and ‘a God in the machine’ (1990:40). Bourdieu intended to escape the restrictions and limitations of this taken-for-granted psychoanalytical discourse by developing the *habitus*, *praxis*, and *hexis* conceptual triad.

¹⁶ The notions of epistemological resonance and harmonics complement Turner’s ‘communitas’ by drawing attention to the enigma of how harmonised epistemological resonance leads to experiences of timelessness, and investigating its growth temporally. Having arrived in Shetland without any previous connection with the musical community in 2012, now the sense of having become a small part of it cannot be shrugged off.

¹⁷ For Ruskin and Rice, ‘music is not merely a passive reflection of pre-existing social and cultural structures’ (2012:310). They argue that ‘culture and field are better thought of as constituted in and through the relationships of individuals’ (Ruskin and Rice 2012:318). By ‘problematizing’ our own ‘social, political, or economic position’ and ‘using the self as a source of knowledge’ we engage in a reflexive ethics ‘rooted in an intersubjective and dialogical approach to field research, one that sees people not as abstract objects, but as thinking subjects with whom ethnomusicologists share knowledge’ (Ruskin and Rice 2012:311). For Ruskin and Rice, ethnomusicology’s ‘ongoing engagement with individuals has revealed the intensely personal aspects of culture, and the fundamentally social aspects of the individual’ (2012:317).

¹⁸ Theoretically, perfect harmony is conceivable within ideal orthodoxies, sets of *doxa* (Bourdieu 1990), tautologies and abductions (Bateson 1979). Harmonised *doxa* and tautologies can always be challenged, contradicted, and expanded by critical ideas that emerge from changing personal and social circumstances. Thus, epistemological discordances are inevitable resonance phenomena that can, despite their potential unpleasantness, afford social and conceptual-theoretical creativity.

¹⁹ David Harvey argues that the ‘body is an unfinished project, historically and geographically malleable’ (2000:98). For him, thinking ‘about transformative political practices as manifestations of a dialectical and spatiotemporal utopianism is helpful’ (Harvey 2000:252-253). Creative-critical reflexivity and the goal of epistemological growth are propositions from this thesis that respond to Harvey’s (2000) call for alternative ways of thinking and designing the world.

²⁰ Through the ethics review process for my fieldwork project, I was encouraged to think about personal safety. Having grown up in Brazil and attended countless rock concerts, sometimes as performer, I knew that things can go wrong and people might get hurt. When I saw how intensely Dirk Robertson (whom I did not know) and some of his friends were dancing on my first metal event in 2012, I worried. Yet, I was never in danger, and Dirk invited me, on that very same night, to my first local party at DJ Lyall Halcrow’s flat.

²¹ Some readers may subscribe to ideological conceptions of freedom tied to cultural values from their dominant political system. In this work, freedom is linked to agency and the empowerment of the subject. Instead of viewing people as automatically incorporating culturally dominant or academic notions of freedom, I refer to sensations of freedom within regulatory environments. In Shetland case, encouraging personal forms of creativity and expression, and being open to worldwide musical diversity kindled this freedom. Analyses of sociomusical *sprees* (Chapter 4) and collaborative projects (Chapter 5) demonstrate that the horizontal distribution of creative decision-making power affords creative freedom. Hierarchical centralisation of power and bureaucratic-regulatory control structures are antithetical to feelings of artistic freedom.

²² Jazz musicians distinguish imitation from improvisation. For them, imitation is *not* improvisation, and copying is less creative than inventing. Creativity, improvisation, imitation, and tradition are critical issues in jazz thought. For Ingold and Hallam, improvisation ‘seemed like an open book’ while creativity had been hammered from all sides (2007:1). The critical perspective on

imitation and improvisation that grew alongside jazz practice in boundless, living social worlds warrants further attention (e.g., Nicholson 2005, 2014, Werner 1996).

²³ Lack of social support may compel individual creativity elsewhere. Yet, in Shetland, social encouragement plays an important role in the formation of musicians and participation in the music scene affords creative growth. Negative reinforcement does not play a significant role in Shetland's sociomusical scene. As Jorgensen noted, '[c]ultivating morale and motivating members is accomplished best by positive rather than negative reinforcement, by affirmation rather than hard-nosed evaluation' (2008:84). For her, thinking 'the best of people is a safer way of forging high morale than being suspicious of them and noticing only their errors' (Jorgensen 2008:84). Shetland musicians who live and develop musically through successive *sprees* manifest and promote this same notion in practice. The Shetland *sprees*, in this light, ritually reproduces sociomusical encouragement, support, and local knowledge.

²⁴ A section of Lynch (2001) portrays an actress first rehearsing for an audition by almost shouting the script. Later, at the actual audition, circumstances make so that the same text is whispered, providing a contrast that demonstrates the tonal and emotional malleability of textual source materials and the diversity of possible interpretations.

²⁵ For Csikszentmihalyi, although 'flow arises from listening' to music, 'even greater rewards are open to those who learn to make music' (1990:111). However, when parents place 'too much emphasis' on how their children 'perform, and too little on what they experience', they pervert music into 'a source of psychic disorder', the 'opposite of what it was designed to be' (Csikszentmihalyi 1990:112). Parents 'who push their children to excel at the violin are generally not interested in whether the children are actually enjoying the playing' (Csikszentmihalyi 1990:112). They 'want the child to perform well enough to attract attention, to win prizes, and to end up on the stage at Carnegie Hall' (Csikszentmihalyi 1990:112). Ironically, one just needs to be involved with Shetland's *sprees* culture in order to get a chance to play at the Carnegie Hall in Sandwick (e.g., Guest 2014b). Shetlanders always laugh at the comic incongruence between the lofty Carnegie Hall in New York and its parodical Sandwick version.

²⁶ In her report commissioned by the Shetland Arts Trust, Katherine Campbell (1997) interviewed 197 individuals and groups throughout Shetland. The groups she interviewed varied in size from duos and families to larger performing groups and stakeholders. For a comprehensive list see Campbell (1997:34-41).

²⁷ According to Campbell, there is a 'higher percentage of the population involved in music making in Shetland compared to most areas in Great Britain and overseas' which might be 'in part due to the level of instrumental tuition provided in schools as well as to cultural factors' (1997:13). This thesis investigates some of these *cultural factors*.

²⁸ For Campbell, who first proposed the creation of the Music Development Officer position, this individual should possess 'specialist knowledge in music', hold a 'shared appointment with Shetland College', and teach a 'course in music' (1997:25).

²⁹ I would often meet several local musicians at Mareel by chance. Erik Peterson showed me many tunes and new bands at Mareel, including LAU, with singer-songwriter Kris Drever. Originally from Orkney, Drever has since moved to Shetland and married local Louise Thomason, both performing participants at the Fetlar *sprees* in 2014.

³⁰ In a long conversation with a 33-year old fisherman from Whalsay at The Lounge, who turned out to be Michael Anderson from *The Revellers*, I learned that he had attended 'heavy metal' *Iron Maiden* concerts over 15 times around the UK. He brings his guitar to the fishing boat, and spends

up to 3 months at sea. He produced an entire heavy metal album by himself. Using a multi-track recording device and microphones, he recorded bass, guitars, vocals, and drums. He remained active with several bands around Shetland. The singlehanded recording of an original metal album is atypical in most circumstances, especially while employed in a demanding job. Yet, being a multi-instrumentalist and performer and having a profession is not atypical in Shetland.

³¹ For an interactive presentation of current Shetland maps, see <<http://wp.me/p4Go65-5Q>> or refer to the project's website <www.shetlandspree.com>.

³² Johnston (2010:xv) struggled with the abundance of stories of emigrants from Shetland after his request for information started circulating. He decided to concentrate on the nineteenth century and the pre-oil period. For him, since the first Hamefarin was in 1960 and 'oil came along shortly after – alleviating the pressure for emigration and actually initiating immigration', the 1960s 'became the appropriate point to close' (Johnston 2010:xv). Thus, his book on Shetland emigrants does not include stories from the oil period.

³³ For Wilf, the 'ascendance of creativity cannot be set apart from the rise of a "neoliberal agency" that requires subjects to imagine and fashion their own future by engaging with risk and making decisions under constraints of increased uncertainty' (2014:407). The formation of the 'neoliberal subject' is entangled with 'mystifications of creativity that (a) presume the existence of an autonomous inner nature as a compass, (b) make each individual responsible for being in touch with and following this compass, and (c) frame failure to be creative and to transcend present constrains as the result of one's natural predisposition' (Wilf 2014:407). Ethnographic works that contextualise creativity's 'social dimensions' have 'never been more relevant' (Wilf 2014:407).

³⁴ As Ingold argued, instead of being 'literally descended from ancestors' as the 'genealogical model' of analysis presupposes, 'children follow in the way of their predecessors in a process of growth' (2012:87).

³⁵ The adjective '*spreer*' and derivatives, like the verb '*spreeing*', follow local usage. Cohen uses these constructions throughout his piece on the *spree* and the funeral (see Cohen 1985:313).

³⁶ The presence of temporary energy industry workers posed practical problems to Shetland residents. Bevington (2014) reported a 'series of incidents' in Lerwick when 'around 2,000 men working on the Total gas plant construction site at Sullom Voe were given the day off after the sudden death of a colleague [by suicide] the previous day'. A 'young woman was flung over the shoulder of a drunk worker and left close to tears', a worker was 'flashing at a bus full of passengers', and there were 'several men indiscriminately urinating, throwing up and drinking alcohol in the street despite a local bye law against drinking in public in the town' (Bevington 2014). The Harbour Fish & Chip Shop put up a poster banning "'more than four" employees from Morrison Construction, Petrofac and Wood Group in their shop at any one time' (Cope 2015). This measure, the shop management explained, 'was due to a "minority of grown men struggling to behave like humans"' (Cope 2015).

³⁷ Black conducted seventy-four interviews, and did not participate in community activities for her dissertation (1995:305). Her interviews were highly structured, and interviewees received different sets of questions according to gender (Black 1995:307-315). This reflects Black's own assumptions about gender roles in Shetland, cautioning us against an overreliance on predetermined questionnaires. Black only asked women about knitting (1995:308), whereas men were also conspicuously involved in this industry. On November 1st, 2012, I was playing music and talking informally at The Lounge with a couple of middle aged Shetland women (and a couple of English visitors) when the issue of knitting came up. They mentioned casually that both their parents knitted. When I asked whether their 'fathers also knitted', both answered, 'all the time'.

³⁸ ‘Relatively speaking’, noted Lewie Peterson, his day job is enjoyable. Lewie makes music for the love of playing and its ‘social aspect’. Recognition as a community musician also fosters social connections at work, as Lewie explained to me in March 2013,

Everybody is connected usually, so if you play in a band and you’re in the Shetland Times, people very quickly realise that that’s what you do in your spare time. So people are always asking about the gigs you’ve got coming, and it’s quite a good way, I suppose, especially working with young people, it’s quite a good way of communicating.

³⁹ For instance, a look into Maurice Henderson’s Facebook page details the life of a musician, not of a council employee.

⁴⁰ Shetland’s complex maritime history and connections to various places around the globe, with constant movements of people, musical instruments, tunes and styles, implies that locals should have more sophisticated ideas regarding the genesis of the music they play. Reflections on local landscapes may be inspiring. However, songs usually reflect positions in immediate social worlds, personal predilections, and other issues affecting the social lives of composers and performers. Some comedy dialect singers, prominently showcased in Shetland Folk Festivals, transform ‘top-twenty’ pop tracks into Shetland-dialect in-jokes. This delights local audiences and confuses outsiders unacquainted with the ins and outs of local dialects and social patterns.

⁴¹ Ronström (2010:268) claimed, incorrectly, that Forsyth (2007) argued that ‘four legendary fiddlers, living and working in cities like Lerwick and Aberdeen’ were responsible for the development of Shetland’s traditional music ‘after the Second World War’. Forsyth (2007:50), however, mentions ‘four ‘grandfathers’ of Shetland music: Tom Anderson, Ronnie Cooper, Willie Hunter Junior, and ‘Peerie Willie’ Johnson’. She never mentions Aberdeen. Only two of these four musicians were fiddlers, Tom Anderson and Willie Hunter Junior. Ronnie Cooper was a pianist and composer, and Peerie Willie was a guitarist and upright bass player who, according to Debbie Scott (2007) ‘could play any instrument he laid his hands on’.

⁴² The festival programme: <www.shetlandaccordionandfiddle.com/assets/files/saff-programme-2012.pdf>. This programme represents the local mobility of festival participants. The Shetland Folk Festival also takes place in Lerwick and other Shetland locations: see <<http://www.shetlandfolkfestival.com/venues.php>>.

⁴³ Neville (1979:94) argued that community gatherings and festivals are cultural performances, powerful displays of ‘symbols and patterns’ that express ‘part of the cultural inventory of urban, industrial people whose day-to-day community life is enacted in relation to the city, the rational bureaucracy, and the hierarchical nation-state’. For Neville, such events assert local distinctiveness *vis à vis* the homogeneity symbolised by urbanity and the state. Active Shetland musicians are usually critical of state bureaucracies but they are not opposed to inhabiting urban areas. They often visit cities in their travels, collecting stories, adventures, and social experiences that they may retell to friends around the table in Shetland.

⁴⁴ Among ‘professional session instrumentalists of the Greek popular music scene who perform jazz as a side activity for their own pleasure’, the concepts of work and play represent a fundamental dichotomy (Tsioulakis 2011:175). As Tsioulakis noted, ‘play’ is ‘about the pleasure of experimentation enhanced by the negotiation of the structures of authority that traverse the ‘work’ setting’ (2011:187). In Shetland, at High Level Music, WobblyGang, and Aitkens, the lines between play and work are constantly blurred. Jazz is not necessarily valued higher than other musical styles, but tastes for various musical materials are shared to uncover interpersonal

resonances. As I recount in Chapter 7, playing together and yarning is part of the productive way of being at High Level Music.

⁴⁵ For Swing (1991:276), ‘inventions of tradition’ represent a ‘fluid process of continual reinterpretation’. Shetland’s epistemological tradition is independent of repertoire: individuals reinterpret musical materials in personal, fluid, and creative ways, without seeking to *invent a tradition*. They work with the old and new technologies available (e.g., instruments, equipment, software, etc.). No single individual invented the resilient epistemological tradition, still alive in Shetland’s sociomusical world. Instead, the *spre* emerged from widespread conviviality and mutual support. As a ritual complex, it kindles sociomusical relationships, interpersonal knowledge, and intergenerational engagement, promoting character appreciation and mutuality. Many consider tunes and songs of different styles that have been composed either in Shetland or by Shetlanders part of a Shetland tradition. This would include anything from traditional or ‘trad’ music, to singer-song writing, rock and roll, classical or anything else. The Shetland label simply indexes music to geographical location. I also index *spre* practices and understandings to music practitioners who strongly identify with Shetland.

⁴⁶ In jazz, ‘comping’ refers to playing accompaniment parts for soloists, usually chords (harmonies), rhythms and bass lines on piano and/or guitar.

⁴⁷ As *spre*er and banjo player Lewie Peterson told me in March 2013, ‘everybody knows everybody in Shetland, so they instantly try and figure out where you’re from, what you do... Do you play football, do you go to the swimming pool?’

⁴⁸ Shetlanders with a basic sense of local history are keenly aware of how people have not sprout from the land of Shetland, which has no recognisable original inhabitants, but moved there in historical times. People propose different models to explain how one can adopt the Shetlander signifier: they seem to follow the common logic that consistent intergenerational commitment to Shetland would make families become ‘Shetland’, regardless of where they are from. This parallels the *Up Helly Aa* logic of allowing incomers with extended local residency to become guizers. Yet, some lament that few historically unaware locals consider Norse-sounding last names ‘purer’. As noted before, tunes can be considered Shetland if they were composed in Shetland, regardless of the composer’s cultural background.

⁴⁹ According to the *spre* model, differences between Shetlanders and outsiders are played out in a sociomusical game of knowledge between knowing selves (Titon 2008). McFarlane’s (1981) focus on Dunrossness and lack of immersion in the social worlds of his interviewees provides a distance that prevents access to various sociomusical nuances. McFarlane’s research was ‘part of a broader investigation of the social effects of oil related development’ that was ‘financed and sponsored by the Shetland Islands Council, the North Sea Oil Panel of the Social Science Research Council, and the Scottish Development Department’ (1981:135). As such, it focuses on the negative aspects of a relationship, brought to Shetland by corporate capitalism, that was not simply between Shetlanders and outsiders, but between residents, temporary energy industry workers, and their employers. That is, a relationship between personable local ways and an impersonal, economic, ‘structural force that affects people’s lives and life chances’ (Ganti 2014:7.2).

⁵⁰ McFarlane’s (1981) bibliography is thin, with only 12 sources. Among them, Cohen (1978) is the only link between Shetland materials and studies of symbolic boundary making in rural Britain.

⁵¹ I was introduced to Shetlanders as a foreigner, musician, anthropologist and ethnographer in countless interactions. I was not usually introduced as ‘incomer’. I witnessed many verbal lashings of Shetlanders, for humour and for real. I witnessed changes of mind, re-approximations, romantic breakups that did not affect friendships, grudges and bitter arguments. They were not the norm.

Shetlanders can unleash brutal verbal abuse, more so toward fellow locals than toward outsiders. Some inquisitive and enterprising locals tested me against possible worst-case scenarios. Such strategy of assessment makes sense from a small community's perspective. It is a kind of preventive social wisdom that reflects an awareness of negative social consequences in past experiences with newcomers.

⁵² If building trust involves the freedom of making jokes at another's expense and the ability to take well seemingly abusive characterisations in social situations, McFarlane's (1981) focus on negative stereotypes cannot be taken too seriously. Goffman (1953) already described this phenomenon, leaving little basis to suppose that this is a new feature of younger generations. In a culture in which jokes, mischaracterisations and stereotypes are tossed at others for endearment rather than insult, it makes little sense for anthropologists to analyse the recurrence of stereotypical statements. Goffman (1953) described in detail playful interactions among Shetlanders that could be interpreted as offensive but are not. McFarlane (1981) does not account for this.

⁵³ One example is the friendship between incomer Stevie Hook and older Shetlander Billy Kay in the 1970s, and my own friendships with native residents who introduced me to their social connections, characters and music. McFarlane's (1981:127) label of 'older Shetlander' does not provide much clarity. I consider 'older' those who have been around to remember the beginning of the Shetland Folk Festival in the 1980s, and whose ages range from late 40s to, in the case of Billy Kay, early 90s. Natives and other residents that were younger and older introduced me to many eventual collaborators and research participants.

⁵⁴ Cooke notes that 'hardship and tragedy' pressured Shetlanders to engage with 'almost Bacchanalian fervour' with fiddle and dancing in the Yule season, which coincides with *Up Helly Aa* celebrations in the winter (1986:10). In 1881 the 'great gale' drowned 50 men at sea (Cooke 1986:10). For the fishermen spending long periods working at sea and facing potential tragedy, 'a short period of time spent back home in Shetland was a period to be cherished and enjoyed' (Cooke 1986:10).

⁵⁵ As I discuss elsewhere, Grydehøj's (2011) paper was based on short-term research, few direct sources, it bypassed key works, and lacks anthropological theory. In the opinion of Shetland's archivist Brian Smith in 2012, Grydehøj simply did not do the necessary work.

⁵⁶ One 20-year-old Shetlander I met in 2012 worked mainly around Southeast Asia, in Honk Kong for an Israeli shipping company. He travelled through Aberdeen-Amsterdam-Dubai to Hong Kong, and spent months visiting different ports while living aboard a 300-foot ship. Another 18-year-old Shetlander also worked in shipping. He travelled on a mercantile ship from South East Asia to South America, and from there, to Amsterdam. Both were involved with local musicians socially and participated enthusiastically in sociomusical events.

⁵⁷ In Shuldham-Shaw (1947) and Cooke (1986), the adoption of new technologies of music reproduction is viewed negatively, as a distortion to the 'old ways' of learning and a threat to 'tradition'. Swing (1991) avoids this view and looks at 'inventions of tradition' emerging from the institutionalisation of fiddling instruction in schools instead. I investigate how residents engage with different instruments and technologies in creative musical practice, and tend to see new technologies as creative materials instead of disruptions of tradition. As Malm notes, the 'industrialization process' in music production has been 'linked with the monetary economy, with profitability 'laws' relevant to mass production and with the establishment of international music and media corporations' (1992:350). As I argue throughout this thesis, Shetland's epistemological tradition of music making provides an alternative to corporate-industrial profitability imperatives.

⁵⁸ Byron (1983) does not discuss the impacts of World War II on the Shetland population. Stories about the war and post war period in Shetland are common in the sociomusical world. Many local musicians ended up stationed in Unst during World War II, and spent most of their time playing together. For Peerie Willie, according to local lore, the World War II period was formative, bringing new music to his attention, and giving him time to and experiment and develop his personal style.

⁵⁹ Wang et al. (2014:37) argue that ‘globalizing forces and advances in media technologies have made people in the periphery more than ever before aware of differences between themselves and those occupying the center’. The major drawback of this argument is the assertion that ‘advances in media technology’ lead to higher awareness of difference. This view romanticises the role of the Internet and other media technologies as faithful representations of local social relations, whereas people, as storytellers, through their travels and engagement with people of other places, often surpass in quality and precision what is available online. The suggestion that media technologies can substitute face-to-face interactions in the understanding of difference contradicts the foundation of fieldwork as an anthropological practice.

⁶⁰ Alan Barnard argued that political economy approaches like ‘world systems theory’ (e.g., Wallerstein 1974-89, 1976) produce ‘outsider-centred’ views (2004:92). For Barnard, ‘the idea of the ‘world system’ or ‘globalization theory’ is the postmodern concoction of a ‘grand diffusionism, where the global culture of the West stands in relation to the rest of the world as Elliot Smith and Perry believed Egypt had once stood’ (Barnard 2004:92).

⁶¹ The production for *Brandy from a Stranger (North Country Fair 2015)* started in 2013. The album’s release was originally supposed to take place sometime in 2014. Yet, Michael Williamson never hurried to release *North Country Fair* songs and albums. Instead, he waited for the appropriate moment. Such non-commercial projects are freed from the rush to release and make back the money invested. My copy of the CD arrived in November 2015.

⁶² Teit died after a long illness on October 30th 1922, ‘hoping to turn again to his ethnographical studies’ that focused on ‘a comprehensive description of the ethno-botany and ethno-geography of the interior of British Columbia’ (Boas 1923:103). Teit’s death meant, for Boas, that ‘the Indians have lost their most faithful friend’ (1923:103). Teit’s work was responsible for most of what was known about Salish ‘material culture, social organization, customs, belief and tales’ (Boas 1923:102).

⁶³ Wendy Wickwire noted that Teit was an exception among ‘authors of early ethnographic texts in British Columbia’ such as Franz Boas, Edward Sapir and others, all ‘white males living in cities far from the field’, where the ‘female voice was absent’ (1993:539). For her, ‘the most special character of Teit’s work is that he focused on the world of women, including pictography, songs, ethnobotany, and basketry, and sensitive rituals associated with puberty, marriage, pregnancy and childbirth’. Teit’s ‘contribution to anthropology *at-large* has never been credited, overshadowed’ by the ‘work of his mentor and editor, Franz Boas’ (Wickwire 1993:539). For Wickwire, although Teit is known ‘as little other than Boas’ “assistant” or his “informant,” he ‘stands as one of the most outstanding of North American ethnographers’ (1993:540).

⁶⁴ Patrick Shuldham-Shaw (1917-1977) was the first folklorist to visit Shetland in 1946. For him, ‘uncollected folk music’ was a ‘mine’ to be explored and kept for posterity (Godrich 2010:102). He was an English ethnomusicologist, played the accordion and sang, and composed several tunes in Shetland, dedicated to people, places, and even to the *Earl of Zetland*, an inter-island boat that ran from Lerwick to Unst and back (Godrich 2010:121). Shuldham-Shaw’s tune collecting efforts in 1947 culminated in a live performance in North Roe in 1948, when he sang some of his ‘finds’ to delighted audiences (Godrich 2010:107).

⁶⁵ Locals told me that ‘Stickle’ was a German name, common in Unst, brought to Shetland by shipwrecked castaways. Stories about different kinds of castaways washing upon Shetland’s shores are typical.

⁶⁶ Laughey (2008:84) found that, by the 1930s and 1940s, ‘a national and increasingly global network of mass music dissemination already pervaded young people’s everyday lives in Britain’ and elsewhere. This contradicts the ‘widely held assumption that youth music cultures only developed in the age of television and rock ‘n’ roll’ (Laughey 2008:84). As young men in the 1940s, Peerie Willie and Billy Kay were inspired by ‘swing jazz’, which reached Shetland by radio and maritime trade networks.

⁶⁷ The notion of taste can also transcend musical styles when its delectable object is a *way* of playing music, of interacting with others, and experimenting. Experimentation is closely aligned with our sense of taste, growth, and experience, denoting a movement outside of previously established norms. Experimenters try something unconventional, exhibiting a taste for surprise and the unusual. Taste transcends the aesthetics of musical style when it delights on particular ways of being and acting. In other words, taste can be aesthetically relativistic while expecting a standard attitude as its basis (e.g., horizontality and the lack of arrogance in the Shetland *spreed*). On the other hand, a devoted taste for a musical style alone (i.e., for jazz exclusively), is not relativistic. Jazz musicians in Tsioulakis (2011) consider other-than-jazz musics to be work, not play. In Shetland, although some musicians may focus on a single style, most music lovers are eclectic.

⁶⁸ Meghan Forsyth explained to me that Forsyth (2007) is a ‘more polished synthesis of some of the larger ideas’ from her 2005 MPhil thesis that she was unfortunately not allowed to share (email, October 23rd 2012).

⁶⁹ Bateson (1972:100) argues that it is ‘not enough to say that the habit system or the character structure of one sex is *different* from that of another’. Rather, the ‘habit system of each [sex] cogs into the habit system of the other; that the behaviour of each promotes the habits of the other’ (Bateson 1972:100). Indeed, in the halls during Lerwick *Up Helly Aa*, the complementary pattern of ‘spectator-exhibitionism’ is quite clear (Bateson 1972:100). Despite the gender bias critique, hostesses are usually happy to host and not guize. Guizing in Lerwick is far more exhausting than hosting, and the hostesses and guests can stay in one place and watch the 50 squads do their act in succession. In addition, the guizer Jarl praises publically the hostesses in every hall. Hostesses understand that they are playing a gendered role but they are not bothered by it. Some women express their opposition to the gendering of *Up Helly Aa* (Murray 2007).

⁷⁰ ‘Tar-barrelling’ used to happen in Lerwick. Barrels of burning tar were pushed around town, accompanied by other mischief. After the practice was outlawed, *Up Helly Aa* emerged as a substitute, according to Smith (1993).

⁷¹ More recently, Smith (2005:27) argued that although Brown (1998) was ‘the best book on the subject’ it should be read with caution regarding its account of *Up Helly Aa*’s origins. For Smith (2005:29) Brown (1998) caricatures the process with the claim that Lerwick’s unruly youth were suddenly subdued by an ‘alleged evangelical majority’. Smith (2005:27) argued Brown’s (1998) model followed a deterministic ‘old-fashioned account of ‘influences’ and alleged ‘responses’ in history’ based on Brown’s previous work about Scottish religion (i.e., Brown 1997). Smith (2005:30) saw this as a ‘threadbare theory of how societies change’. He also disagreed with Brown’s (1998) representation of ‘the *Up Helly Aa* pioneers as decorous’, and argued that decorum and money only ‘began to play their deadening part in the procedures’ after World War II, leading to ‘the tedious and in some ways unpleasant festival of the present century’ (Smith 2005:29-30).

⁷² See the Equal Opportunities Legislation at <www.eco.org.uk>.

⁷³ For Grydehøj (2011:131), the prevalence of ‘Norse romanticism’ influenced the formation of an ‘anti-modern’ identity that contradicts the official ‘branding of Shetland as a forward-thinking community’. The Cultural Strategy document (SIC 2009) proposed that Shetland’s culture is open to influences from other places, arguing that culture is an economic resource that should be developed. This document proposed ‘culture’ as a source of capital for attracting development investment (as Lee et al. 2005 examine in other contexts). According to my experiences, the inclusivity Shetland’s Cultural strategy (SIC 2009) proposes is more realistic than Grydehøj’s (2011) notion that the ‘prevalent identity’ in Shetland antagonises outsiders. The historical practices of many Shetland musicians reveal a sense of openness to cultural influences and eagerness to incorporate new creative materials. The view that culture is a resource for exploitation is at least partially explainable as stemming from the fear that the oil economy might collapse.

⁷⁴ Having interviewed women and men regarding their roles in the festival, Jenny Murray noticed that the Lerwick hostesses felt confident and comfortable with their roles and ‘wish the tradition of their festival to continue unchanged’ (Murray 2007:47). In the two years in which I attended *Up Helly Aa* celebrations in Lerwick, hostesses invited me. In 2013, I spent most of the night at the Ferry Terminal, converted into an *Up Helly Aa* hall. An alternative interpretation of the gender roles is also possible. Hostesses are complimented and praised on their efforts throughout the night, which are widely and openly recognised. They can dance with all the men that come into the hall, and then spend social time drinking and dancing with the visiting squads, which almost always contain friends and family members. As Murray noted, the festival’s ‘merrymaking in the midst of Shetland’s darkest winter months’, brings ‘the community together,’ only possible through ‘the efforts of both sexes’ (Murray 2007:47). The guizer Jarl, the main ‘Viking’ character leads the ritual praising of the hostesses, and is also the ‘butt or goat of the fun’ (Goffman 1956:320-323), which is not the most comfortable position. In 2013, the Guizer Jarl was targeted for being short and having a tall wife. One guizer squad performed with oversize colour-printed masks of the Guizer Jarl and his wife, and proceeded to conduct a mock wedding to the audience’s delight. Ridicule balances the fake prominence of the Jarl. This also reflects the uses of ritual putdowns (Murphy 2015) in Shetland for the purpose of strengthening and solidifying friendships. The lack of seriousness toward the sanctity of prescribed gender roles is reflected in how ‘at least two squads in the Delting *Up Helly Aa*’ feature Lerwick women ‘wearing their husbands’ costumes from the Lerwick festival’ (Murray 2007:46).

⁷⁵ The practice of bringing fiddles to Shetland as ‘homecoming gifts’ persisted ‘down to the present’ (Cooke 1986:5). The same can be said of any musical instrument. Brian Nicholson, who told me stories about various instruments crossing oceans on boats, also insisted that singing was very strong in Shetland, and widespread, an aspect of Shetland’s tradition that is often overlooked.

⁷⁶ Even mass produced instruments may evoke, for those who use them, a rich history of social interactions, travels and other personal experiences. Handmade instruments are valued higher because of their craftsmanship. Fiddle makers and luthiers in Shetland, such as Kenny Johnson and Ewen Thomson, who are also renowned local musicians, Brian and Arthur Nicholson, and many others, have shared stories about instruments with me. They weave various elements together, such as the instrument’s origin, how it was made, acquired and brought to Shetland, who used it, how it is being used, how it sounds through different equipment and on different stages, how one plans to use it, and its limitations. The instruments and all aspects they can index from experience are closely scrutinised and integrated in daily social life.

⁷⁷ Nolan (1983) reported on the founding of the Northmavine Fiddle & Accordion Club in September 1982. Classically trained violinist Bernadette Porter, the club’s secretary and local violin and fiddle teacher, noted that in the Northmavine club ‘there are no stars, no special

performers – we're just folk who like to get together and give a tune or two'. Such clubs promote intergenerational engagement around music making, in a 'family atmosphere' with 'everyone tapping their feet and getting up for a dance, from the grannies to their men to the seven-year-old girls in their first party dresses' (Nolan 1983). For Porter, Shetland fiddling encourages the development of 'unmistakably individual' styles (Nolan 1983).

⁷⁸ Stevenson notes that the 'hierarchical status' (2004:88) and dominance of the Aly Bain and Phil Cunningham collaboration in the Scottish traditional circuit has led to so many bookings of the duo in festivals that they 'have become the new Andy Stewart' (Stevenson 2004:92). Some believe that this prominence is propelled by a 'commercial imperative to secure the services of popular musicians' that 'results in a homogenisation of the festival scene' (Stevenson 2004:92). The duo's reification as 'big names', Stevenson argues, 'establishes a hierarchical structure which many practitioners argue is antithetical to the ostensibly inclusive and democratic nature of the folk music scene' (2004:105).

⁷⁹ As noted in Chapter 2.7, James A. Teit immediately adopted the sound recording technologies of his period in order to collect songs and stories, working with Franz Boas (see Wickwire 1988).

⁸⁰ As Kaul (2007:716) notes, in the traditional Irish music scene, 'commercialization can coexist, if not always comfortably, with an artist's control over the production of their art form'. 'By contrast', he argues, 'commodification is the near-complete loss of control' (Kaul 2007:716). The freedom to have control over the artistic production, Kaul argued, 'is more important than money' (2007:715).

⁸¹ For Nietzsche (1998:61), 'submissiveness and mimicry' represent a kind of inheritance. For him, 'despotism' overpowers independence and controls people through 'guilt' and the 'rank-ordering of all ethnic elements in every great racial synthesis' (Nietzsche 1998:61-62).

⁸² For Bourdieu, the mass media world is highly problematic, including relations of competition and collusion 'derived from objective common interests' that are 'relentless and pitiless, even to the point of absurdity' (2001:254). For Bourdieu, the 'most important development' of mass communication 'was the extraordinary extension of the power of television over the whole of cultural production, including scientific and artistic production' (2001:255). For the sake of entertainment, 'mindless talk show chatter between "approved" and interchangeable speakers' is favoured at the expense of 'real information, analysis' and 'in-depth interviews' (Bourdieu 1996:3). The social result is 'a patent lack of interest in subtle, nuanced changes', a kind of 'structural amnesia' divorced from 'a network of relevant relationships' (Bourdieu 1996:7).

⁸³ Cohen argues that the 'logic of nationalism is precisely to privilege national boundaries over those to which people more frequently orientate themselves' (Cohen 1996:810). For Cohen, 'persuasive nationalist rhetoric' encounters a 'real problem' when facing the 'individual's personal nationalism' because 'it has to create a discourse with which people of different minds, differently located in a society, can feel comfortable, a difficulty exacerbated when that society – like Scotland – has *well developed* traditions of local distinctiveness and individuality' (1996:810, my emphasis). Similarly, the Shetland *spre* is a 'well developed' epistemological tradition, with principles of horizontality, interpersonal and intergenerational knowledge, and nuance of character appreciation.

⁸⁴ Cohen laments the 'tendency in anthropological analysis and writing to construct people's identities in terms of their structural associations' (1996:802-803). For Cohen, viewing 'identity as being derivable from membership of a nation or a group – be it an ethnic, kinship, or descent group, a sect, class, gender, initiation cohort, or whatever – is implicitly to deny that individuals construe their membership and their selves in very different terms' (1996:803). Cohen's position echoes those of King (2009:146) and Sapir (1924:411) discussed in Chapter 2.12.

⁸⁵ Despite its shortcomings as a construction of a tradition that left most Shetland musicians out of the equation, Tom Anderson's collections of tunes are not rejected, as this would contradict the local principle of resourcefulness. These collections are still valued as teaching and historical materials. However, experienced locals have noted that tunes ascribed to Anderson were certainly not his own compositions. He sometimes visited fiddlers around Shetland, wrote down and published their tunes as his own. Outsiders often consider Anderson's collections to be the primary source of Shetland music.

⁸⁶ Neville (1979:103) found that contemporary ceremonial forms in peripheral Gaelic communities in Scotland have 'symbolically revived', reorganised and emphasised 'selected aspects of previous social organisation'. Similarly, Shetland *sprees* rearrange positive principles of sociomusical life into their adopted way of being.

⁸⁷ Various trusted friends have almost unlimited access to homes in which I have participated in sociomusical *sprees*, referred throughout this thesis as WobblyGang and Aitkens. These friends are given keys that they keep indefinitely. Private homes may host visiting musicians throughout the year, for various events, and become intense interaction sites during the Shetland Folk Festival.

⁸⁸ The audiovisual supplement to this thesis, including links to all videos, is available online at: <<http://shetlandsprees.com>>. See also Ferrari-Nunes (2014).

⁸⁹ In the winter of 2012, before fieldwork started, SADA's director Gwilym Gibbons, having noted my familiarity with Mareel customers and staff (many were musicians), told me that most academic researchers in Shetland, in contrast, have been reclusive and disconnected from the community.

⁹⁰ The ethnographic locations sociomusical map, <<http://shetlandsprees.com/2012/12/20/353/>>.

⁹¹ The neologism '*Spreinciples*' communicates the notion that *sprees* practices and principles are dynamically integrated.

⁹² Most musicians seem to support Mareel as a venue. Many musicians were critical of the SADA's managing style and pointed a number of architectural design issues with Mareel. Even the most critical musicians have attended concerts, watched films, performed, and recorded there. Despite the issues, most musicians recognise the value of the venue for the local arts community. General opposition to Mareel came from 'anti-art' individuals who try to remain anonymous by commenting on online forums. They protested Mareel's £12 million construction budget, but ignored how the SIC provided about £5 million. Some musicians noted that complainers conveniently forget to count the £7 million spent on 'unnecessary' SIC offices across the street. Mareel partially fulfils the needs that the musical community at large identified in Campbell's (1997) commissioned report. Although community members may hire Mareel's studio for artistic productions, and the auditorium for local concerts, the fees are not necessarily accessible.

⁹³ Hesmondhalgh and Baker argue that musicians 'who have not achieved significant success' are considered 'ordinary' and have 'ambivalent' relationships with their audiences, with 'downsides [that] can involve greater levels of alienation' (2011:207). In Shetland's music scene, boundaries between audiences and performers are flexible and 'success' is not a significant factor for establishing sociomusical relationships. Attunement to *Spreinciples* is far more important than a perception of success. In fact, as seen with Aly Bain and Tom Anderson (Swing 1991), success and wider recognition can mean increased alienation from the community. At the Legion, attendees entered the stage and improvised stunts alongside performers. At Mareel, attempting this could lead to one's banishment from the venue. I have filmed audience members crossing the imaginary stage

barrier at the Lerwick Legion several times.

⁹⁴ I have over 4000 ‘friends’ linked to my Facebook profile. Among these, there are hundreds of Brazilian musicians I do not know personally, but with whom I share hundreds of Facebook ‘friends’. My Facebook profile only reflects a faint extension of actual friendships and networks.

⁹⁵ The Islesburgh Centre becomes a ‘festival club’ during the Shetland Folk Festival and the Shetland Accordion and Fiddle Festival. Those without tickets to country hall events stay at Islesburgh’s *festival club*, the centre of the social life during the SFF. At around midnight, buses returning from country hall concerts converge at Islesburgh Centre. Informal music sessions only stop after people are asked to leave, at around 5 am.

⁹⁶ The Final Fling happens on the Monday, after the last open day of the Shetland Folk Fest. It celebrates the work of volunteers, musicians, and hired production crew who collaborated to make the festival happen. Local ‘session artists’ continue *spreeing* as usual.

⁹⁷ The immediate environment (physical, conceptual and social) surrounding musicians must often remain harmonic so that inspiration can flow, otherwise the connective and transcendental ‘magic’ of music is not possible. The Sufi Master, philosopher, and musician, Hazrat Inayat Khan (1882-1927) argued that Indian Classical music vina players feel ‘the atmosphere of the place and the time’ and do not perform when they sense social ‘discord’ (Khan 2005:349).

⁹⁸ For Whorf, there is a ‘kind of affinity’ between concepts (1956:38). Whorf was searching for a term that denoted ‘a kind of connection or relation, approximation, closeness, allied character, between ideas’ (1956:35). In the present thesis, various terms are proposed to nuance relationships between concepts and experiences, i.e., epistemological resonance, reverberation, discordance and harmonization. Whorf envisioned conceptual-epistemological relationships in a ‘mental image’ that ‘is not at all one of ideas hitched together by bonds of attachment which they possess like miniature hooks and eyes’ (Whorf 1956:38). Instead, Whorf’s image was formed through ‘a concept of continuity, with the ideas as relative locations in a continuous medium’ (Whorf 1956:38).

⁹⁹ According to Smith (1977:3), ‘from the middle of the sixteenth century onwards,’ the influx of ‘substantial numbers of Scots to Shetland’ brought about drastic changes. Lowland Scots gradually replaced Norn, giving outsiders a ‘dominant position in the Church and in landowning’. In the 17th century, Shetlanders were often implicated in wars waged by competing commercial powers: the Dutch fished herring in a large scale and faced the English and the French in a bloody competition ‘for commercial supremacy’ (Smith 1977:5-6).

¹⁰⁰ The ‘mobilities turn’ (e.g., Cresswell 2006, Sheller and Urry 2006, Urry 2007), is a current critical and interdisciplinary research trend that focuses on ‘movement, blocked movement, potential movement, and studies of immobility, dwelling and place making’, emphasising the importance of the ‘fluid, fleeting, yet powerful performativity’ of everyday life (Büscher and Urry 2009:99). This perspective connects works from ‘anthropology, cultural studies, geography, migration studies, science and technology studies, tourist and transport studies, and sociology’ (Sheller and Urry 2006:207).

¹⁰¹ Although Cohen’s (1985) efficient structural analysis recognises the importance of the *sprees* in Whalsay, his writing style renders local voices almost invisible. In other words, the sense of personality, of nuance of character appreciation that is an epistemological principle underlying the *sprees*, could be explored in more detail. Cohen (1985) does not discuss the music that accompanied the *sprees* he experienced in Whalsay and what its meanings. Moreover, Cohen (1985) only recognises the *sprees* as a Whalsay phenomenon, whereas, this thesis shows that the Shetland *sprees*

is a vibrant sociomusical practice of wide circulation in the archipelago. *Spree* practices integrate and sustain the principles of Shetland's epistemological tradition of music making.

¹⁰² My friend Michael Williamson, from Whalsay, values Cohen's (1987) snapshots of the period before Shetland's transformation by the oil industry. As a child, Michael lived near Cohen. Older members of Michael's family appear in Cohen (1987) as hyper social *spree* devotees, a detail Michael remembers fondly. For him, the community was more united and autonomous then. However, Whalsay identity is still alive, regardless of so-called 'threats' of modernity.

¹⁰³ For Max Weber (1958[1921]:65) a 'massing of elements' in a 'large locality' characterises the city, a 'dense settlement of dwelling', a 'colony so extensive that personal reciprocal acquaintance of the inhabitants is lacking'. Notions of pinnacle, superiority, pyramidal organisation, and official authority are core characteristics of architectural reverberation in modern cities, originally devised to host the 'patrimonial constitution of the ruling strata' necessary for conducting 'official business' (Weber 1958[1921]:228). Weber's (1958[1921]) critique of city dwellers' impersonal anonymity resonates strongly with Simmel's (1971) notion of the 'metropolitan type'. Shetlanders may be enthusiastic about city life and its motions, but still value Shetland's virtues while away. In Shetland, the fact that everyone knows everyone else's business annoys locals, but they know that anonymity in the city can be dangerous.

¹⁰⁴ Cohen's (1985, 1996) approach to the notion of 'ethos' is not theoretically linked to Geertz's (1973) formulation. Geertz's (1973) 'ethos' is broad enough to incorporate various aspects of culture. Cohen follows a common usage, employing 'ethos' as a way of acting and general feeling. Its generality is useful, but Geertz's (1973) 'ethos' sounds more like a substitute for 'culture'.

¹⁰⁵ Michael Williamson posted on his Facebook wall the following status update on November 28th 2014, writing in Whalsay dialect about some of his musical influences:

Jim Quinn has nominated me for this 5 pieces of music thing i wid say when Dad bought me Rolled Gold The best off The Rolling Stones when i was 12 has never been topped i was also listenin constantly to a copy of The Beatles Help album id found in wir old hoose at the same time. From around the punk era id say The Ramones first album and that dreadful decade the 80s still produced The Jesus and Mary Chain and REM who i must have been among the first in Shetland to get an album of as i had to order it fi Clive s un he d never heard them ! I nominate Gordon Irvine un John Robertson.

¹⁰⁶ The 12-hour-long sailing from Aberdeen to Lerwick adds to the sense of distance. Plane ticket prices are inflated. When the weather is stormy and dangerous for the ferry crossing, supplies often delay to arrive, and people rush to the supermarkets. Stories of heroic feats during periods of weather hardship are common. Some walked long distances in the snow for supplies, safety, or rescuing a loved one in need; others died in the cold, perhaps after having too much to drink and misjudging the danger. This sense of isolation and distance, which air travel makes almost obsolete, is compensated with an interest in things that come from the outside, especially musical people and materials.

¹⁰⁷ Berger (2008:63) notes that 'from the perspective of the jazz theory' that he learned as an undergraduate, 'rock appeared to be simplistic and dull'. Rock struck Berger as 'simple music for people without musical training or sophistication' (Berger 2008:63). Nevertheless, he 'couldn't set aside' the 'affective power that rock music continued to hold' for him (Berger 2008:63). Eventually, he found that among his research participants rock music worked like an 'emotional exploration and a way of confronting the stultifications of daily life in a hostile world' (Berger

2008:74). This parallels my experiences in Shetland. I became deeply involved with the rock and roll scene, and found that it was integrated with more academic musics, such as jazz and classical. Among the young Shetland musicians featured in Chapters 5 and 6, Norman Willmore, Max Tyler and Hayden Hook are proficient in jazz, classical, blues, rock, pop and metal styles.

¹⁰⁸ I employ the term ‘educator’ here simply as a synonym for ‘teacher’. It does not refer to professional scholars who write and research educational and pedagogical issues, but to people who work as teachers. Stevie Hook works for the elementary school system and Brian Nicholson teaches at High Level Music.

¹⁰⁹ Arthur Nicholson operated the mixing board and power amplifiers from the stage with some assistance from other band members. With years of experience as performer, guitar teacher, singer-songwriter, and producer in various recording projects, Arthur also operates live sound equipment.

¹¹⁰ What ‘T.R.O.W.’ should stand for was the subject of lively discussions that always bordered on the profane. We never reached a final decision.

¹¹¹ *Spreer* Lewie Peterson told me he was ‘lucky’ not to have experienced the competitive aspects of playing that Shetland children are often exposed to in fiddler and musician of the year awards and preparations. He plays music for its ‘social aspect’ and the ‘fact you can bond with people over it’. Becoming a professional musician was ‘never part’ of Lewie’s musical plans. For him, making music ‘as a career’ carries ‘more pressure’, high expectations and ‘you have to do a good job’. Lewie and other Shetlanders attuned to the principles of the epistemological tradition find that professionalisation would spoil the pleasure of playing, the flow of interactions, and its potential for fostering meaningful relationships.

¹¹² The prospects of one’s first time performing at the Shetland Folk Festival may generate anxieties, as noted with local Martha Thomson and newcomer Kirsty North. SFF performances are not *sprees* in the sense that they are formal, public presentations. The centrality of the SFF to sociomusical practices inspires local performers, including the most experienced, to take upcoming performances quite seriously. In the preceding months, local musicians busily polish up their acts, and local promoters do not book musical events featuring SFF performers, local or invited. The tensions of stage performances dissolve in the sociomusical *sprees* that spark everywhere, starting on the bus back to the ‘festival club’. *Sprees* are more important than stage performances for local musicians, for they establish and solidify personal relationships. Although SFF stage performances are not sociomusical *sprees*, the festival’s operation, its committee organisation, security, and its treatment of locals and incomers, are attuned to Shetland’s epistemological tradition and principles.

¹¹³ Fiddle Frenzy is marketed to tourists as a ‘course’, employing local fiddlers to teach them. In this sense, it promotes tourism and capitalises on Shetland’s reputation for fiddling excellence. Its commodified, educational form differs from local sociomusical *sprees* in different ways. First, one pays to participate, and local fiddlers are paid to instruct. In 2014, an instructor told me that teaching at Fiddle Frenzy was challenging, with long hours and a detailed schedule that muddled this fiddler’s routine. It was hard teaching work. *Sprees* happen after commercial time. They also spring into life after public performances, occur spontaneously from serendipitous encounters and *ad hoc* decisions to visit someone for a tune. Most *sprees* initiate in social contexts in which interpersonal knowledge and shared experiences sustain a familiar resonance between most participants. Fiddle Frenzy scheduled sessions for its students, and they play tunes that they have just learned as curricular materials.

¹¹⁴ As noted, Fiddle Frenzy mini-*sprees* packaged this experience for tourists and beginners in a commodified form. In genuine Shetland *sprees* like the one in Fetlar (July 2014), interpersonal knowledge and decades of *sprees* were common among organisers and many performers. Fiddle

Frenzy may represent an introduction into Shetland's sociomusical world, as in Gemma's case. The Fiddle Frenzy mini-*sprees* at Mareel follows prescribed hours of operation.

¹¹⁵ For Simmel, metropolitans incorporate rational, 'intellectualistic' qualities to protect their 'inner life against the domination of the metropolis' and its manifestations (1971:326). For him, 'the metropolitan type' which individuals multifariously manifest, creates 'a protective organ for itself against the profound disruption with which the fluctuations and discontinuities of the external milieu threaten it' (1971:326). With 'every crossing of the street, with the tempo and multiplicity of economic, occupational and social life' the metropolis creates 'psychological conditions', providing the 'sensory foundations of mental life' (Simmel 1971:325). Thus, metropolitan types privilege rationality over feeling, minimising emotional elements in 'feeling-thought' resonances (Wikan 2012), epistemological associations, and their practical implications.

¹¹⁶ Titon argued that ethnomusicologists 'have usually sought to explain musical sounds, concepts, and behavior rather than to understand musical experience' (Titon 2008:36). Yet, 'our own most satisfying knowledge is often acquired through the experience of music making and the relationships that arise during fieldwork' (Titon 2008:36). For Titon, 'in our ways of being musical, and in our ways of doing fieldwork, we, like the subjects (people) of our study, are open to transformations through experience' (Titon 2008:36).

¹¹⁷ I followed closely the process of creation and production of albums by bands *SpoorHawk* (2015), *Nomadia* (2013a) and *North Country Fair* (2015).

¹¹⁸ *Ignition* and BFB were larger than my other musical collaborations with bands since they involved dozens of volunteers and external funding. Yet, both followed an overarching theme and ran for a predetermined period. I approached *Ignition* directors for interviews, but only Hugh made himself available. The fact we did play together helped. Others said they would be available but were too busy or not interested. Hugh played a few jazz standards with us one Sunday, and performed a set of original compositions during a Singers Songwriters night at Mareel.

¹¹⁹ When I met Billy Kay, accompanied by Stevie Hook and Amanda Pearson, he was 93 years old. We only left after over an hour of conversation because Stevie had another commitment. The elder Billy would have easily kept the conversation going. Billy told Stevie that he was leaving him some of his recording equipment (i.e., reel-to-reel tape recorders from the 1960s).

¹²⁰ My fieldnotes note that on March 11th 2013 I arrived at Mareel at noon for the rehearsal, scheduled until 5pm. Mareel students Eamonn Watt and Max Tyler were supposed to come but apparently could not make it. I arrived first, followed by Hugh, Hayden and Norman. Peter Keay played electric bass, but did not come to Brae for the technical rehearsal. Peter Keay did not perform in any of the 7 nights. Norman took a break one night.

¹²¹ I resided in Shetland for two years. Eventually, I moved away for work, but remained connected through various creative projects and collaborations, which compel me to return whenever I can.

¹²² Friend Mary Blance wrote that Lise Sinclair's 'radiant personality' will 'be remembered far beyond her native isle' – her loss is 'felt keenly not just by those who were close to her but by people who only knew her through her poetry and music-making' (Blanche 2013). Sinclair's tragic death while undergoing cancer treatment in Glasgow was noted on mainstream UK news services (e.g., Baker 2013, Gilchrist 2013, Marsack 2013, The Telegraph 2013).

¹²³ The Shetland Folk Festivals feature 'dialect concerts', where natives perform 'dialect music', according to everyday local terminology. Performers sing and speak exclusively in 'broad' Shetland forms, not English. Dialect concerts sell out, and provoke streams of laughter. Strictly

Shetland dialect-based theatre acts are also common. Proficiency in English is not enough to understand such plays and their sociocultural references. In the Isle of Yell, rock bands play the AC/DC spoof *Highway to Yell*, and Yell's informal and widely popular 'national anthem', *On Da Piss* by *No Sweat*, a more complex social parody about hypocrisy.

¹²⁴ Access <<http://shetlandspree.com/2013/11/24/the-revellers-lower-the-rope/>>.

¹²⁵ As Boon (2000:424) noted, '[o]ne "theoretical" advantage to showbiz', an expression of commercialism in world of mainstream arts, 'is that nothing even heuristically authentic adheres to such experience'. 'Because', he argues, it is 'a business' and 'it's all show' and it is 'everywhere' (Boon 2000:424).

¹²⁶ For Hesmondhalgh and Baker, 'strong tensions between creativity and commerce' mark many music genres, 'perhaps because music has come to be associated so strongly with authentic and autonomous subjectivity' (2011:206). For Kaul, artistic freedom and control are 'more important than money' and 'commodification is the near-complete loss of control' (2007:715-716). The commercial music course that Joe Watt attended dismissed such questions, approaching music from a strictly marketing-oriented perspective. It relied on consumer statistics to teach how to identify commercial trends and niches, and exploit musical work for profit.

¹²⁷ DJ Lyall is among the most enthusiastic supporters of all Shetland festivals and gigs. In 2014, he brought the Federation of the Disco Pimp to play a sold out gig at the Lerwick Legion. The audience chanted Lyall's name for about 10 minutes and compelled him to deliver a speech.

¹²⁸ SADA insisted in calling our jazz sets 'background music', unaware of how this characterisation is generally perceived as an insult in most jazz circles. As Nicholson (2005:86) points out, the notion of 'furniture music' was 'Erik Satie's term for undemanding background music that filled social spaces'. SADA officials, in their eagerness to emulate metropolitan venues instead of committing to local values, ignored this issue and instructed their management to remind us again and again that we were just supposed to play 'background music' despite the fact that people would often come down all the way from Yell to see us perform, and despite the fact that SADA itself advertised the performances as an event on its own right – 'Sunday Jazz' – in their brochures.

¹²⁹ Goffman described unserious situations that resonate with how Max, Joe and others joke socially, namely 'mimicry' of others (1953:319-320); 'leg-pulling' when someone is the 'butt or goat of the fun' (Goffman 1953:320-323), and a type of role-playing where participants 'have an opportunity to commit just those acts of disrespect against each other that would ordinarily be cause for great offense' (Goffman 1953:324-327).

¹³⁰ In a metropolitan UK context, Laughey found that 'nostalgic affiliation to the music of their youth provided the stimulus for elders who seemed to have significantly influenced the music uses of younger family members' (2008:134). For Hayden and Joe, influences extend to their parents' longstanding friendships with active local musicians, and their assiduous participation in festivals and concerts. As Laughey (2008:218) noted, intergenerational, 'familial and traditional', 'localised' interactions shape how youth experience music and practice musical exchange.

¹³¹ Norman is referring to how High Level Music played music through its storefront into the street as a way of promoting local artists and attracting business. People react differently to this form of public broadcast. The music was a constant reminder that one was in Shetland.

¹³² For Goffman, *backstage* 'illusions and impressions are openly constructed' (1956:69). Repair shops conceal 'the amount and kind of work' that went on fixing the product so that clients cannot 'judge the reasonableness of the fee' (Goffman 1956:71). Revealing the social side of what

happens and filtering out details that would be inadequate to reveal from often-concealed experiences is an important component of fieldwork and writing. Concealments are common in the lives of sound engineers, music-makers audiovisual producers. Recording and editing processes require considerable craftsmanship, focused and sustained attention to detail over long periods of time. Those who engage with the production's final form do not access the creative process. Commercial clients and general audiences are generally unaware of rehearsal and recording dynamics – technical conversations about music, equipment, and production techniques, common among musician-engineers, are beyond their grasp.

¹³³ My main source of biographical information on Eric Dolphy is the documentary entitled *The Last Date*, by Hans Hylkema (1991). See also Pareles (1992).

¹³⁴ Campbell argues that Charlie Parker, who is considered to be 'the greatest exponent of formulaic improvisation, never repeated a solo literally', relying on 'about 100 motifs or fragments' that he reworked 'time and again' (2013:26).

¹³⁵ In Shetland, being 'distinctively individualistic' refers to a form of nuance of character appreciation in a social world featuring strong interpersonal knowledge bonds, and *not* to competition for greater exposure, power, influence or recognition. Individualism is commonly associated with neoliberal mores, but in Shetland, it usually signals depth of character.

¹³⁶ King (2011) argues against the rhetoric of assimilation and degradation of culture, emphasising the resilience and transformative potentials of living traditions. For him, the 'explicit discourse of cultural compartmentalism denies the lived realities of Indians and Koryaks incorporating practices like speaking an European language or using a television into a coherent indigenous culture that we can call Koryak or Cree, for example' (King 2011:238).

¹³⁷ This discussion dates back to the 1950s and continues into the present. In reference to discussions of general creativity, Hill (2009) points to Guilford (1950), Baer and Kaufman (2006), and, in reference to musical creativity and education, to Deliège and Wiggins (2006), Webster (1992), Campbell (1991). Inspired by Lord's (1960) work among 'Yugoslavian bards' and by 'experimental free improvisation from avant-garde free composers', the Sibelius Academy in Finland encourages students to express 'extensive personal variation within traditional idioms' (Hill 2009:110). Their 'simulated oral composition teaching method' values musician's freedom and 'personal expression' (Hill 2009:110). Free experimentation is 'a pedagogical tool' that challenges 'musicians' preconceived limits and judgment systems', giving 'them the ideological tools and social approval to challenge boundaries and claim artistic freedom' (Hill 2009:110). Hill (2009:89) found that, in a Finnish setting, the principles of '*luovuus* (creativity) and *teiteellinen vapaus* (artistic freedom)' were integrated in teacher-student interactions as methods 'specifically designed to encourage creativity and freedom'. In contrast, Wilf (2012) is silent regarding the canon-based model of jazz education in America, and does not assess critically the jazz tradition and its internationalisation. Nicholson (2005:185) notes that 'European "free" improvisers' were 'trying to move beyond the American model of jazz' and 'establish their own identity' already in the 1960s, when Peter Brötzmann's album *Machine Gun* (1968) appeared as 'a seismic shift in the thinking of the European free movement'. For him, 'the Dutch jazz scene' epitomised 'the diverse ways in which "freedom" could be managed' (Nicholson 2005:185).

¹³⁸ As a scholar and musician, I investigate and compare how theory, training, and expression enable and restrict creative experiences. Thinking about theory, musicality and sound, according to the Boasian holism that I adopt in principle (see Wickwire 1993), should not be restricted to ethnomusicology.

¹³⁹ Whorf's (1956) 'civilized modern' resonates with Sapir's (1924) 'spurious' culture, Weber's (Weber 1958[1921]) impersonal city, Simmel's (1971) 'metropolitan type', and Lakoff and Johnson's (1998) observation that metaphors provide bases for rationalities. For Whorf, the 'CIVILIZED MODERN is the unit class of mentality because of the great structural similarity of all the modern civilized Western languages, while over against it are many diverse types of mentality reflecting a rich diversity of speech structure' (1956:80). Westerners judge other ways of being as 'less rational' while no evidence supports this view. As Whorf notes, 'many American Indian and African languages abound in finely wrought, beautifully logical discriminations about causation, action, result, dynamic or energy quality, directness of experience etc., all matters of the function of thinking, indeed the quintessence of the rational' (1956:80). 'In this respect', for Whorf, 'they far out-distance the European languages' (1956:80).

¹⁴⁰ Khan (2005) wrote against what he saw as the superficiality of jazz, which lacked transcendence toward the sublime. He died in 1927, decades before jazz musicians discovered and became involved with Indian Classical and other musics, expanding their horizons. Bebop musicians first 'dismantled the dominant-tonic cliché' and later 'Ornette Coleman's free jazz' led 'functional harmony' to 'be abandoned while the twelve-bar blues form would be maintained as a mold' (Kubik 2005:208). For Kubik, 'this signifies the *de facto* return to a non-Western, probably west-central Sudanic concept of tonality and perhaps to a type of blues structure sung to riff-like accompanying patterns devoid of any functional European harmony' (2005:208).

¹⁴¹ Tsioulakis encountered in the jazz scene of urban Athens a 'rather uncomfortable subculture comprising many more performers than fans' (2011:194). I encountered a different picture in Shetland, with few jazz players and many appreciators, all personally and socially interconnected through family and friendship ties. As active co-participants in the wider sociomusical scene, they were engaged in cycles of *sprees* involving various other musical genres. While jazz is not the most common musical genre in Shetland, features of jazz have been incorporated into local ways of playing traditional music, with its gypsy jazz comping style, and virtuosic improvisations on tunes like *Lady Be Good*, *Over the Rainbow* and other 'standards' familiar to jazz musicians worldwide.

¹⁴² The Chipewyan saw ethnographers Scollon and Scollon as 'a hired apparatus for a knowledge organism' (1979:185 *In* Ridington 1988:104). While they lived according to 'their own academic trust in the written word and the documentary evidence of history', the Chipewyan 'regard the written word as hearsay' (Scollon and Scollon 1979:185 *In* Ridington 1988:104). For the Chipewyan, mediated knowledge 'is regarded with doubt,' whereas true knowledge 'derives from experience' (Scollon and Scollon 1979:185 *In* Ridington 1988:104).

¹⁴³ Shetland residents who remain in relative isolation from the sociomusical community may not reflect *sprees* dynamics in their ways of being. Still, these hypothetical characters would be able to join the sociomusical community. If their epistemologies resonate with local *Sprenciples*, they would find ways to participate by being themselves.

¹⁴⁴ Natives and long-time residents explain the demise of small local shops, especially the fondly remembered Clive's Record Shop, as resulting from TESCO's introduction of low cost, mass produced mainstream CD and video-game media in Shetland. At Clive's, locals would meet, talk about music, and order new releases. This provided great pleasure for different generations, like Michael Williamson, Lisa Ward and DJ Lyall Halcrow, and others.

¹⁴⁵ Friendships formed through the recurrence of *sprees* related events are, according to my personal interpretation and experiences, well attuned to the principled concept of *amicitia* that Epicurean philosopher Lucretius proposed. However, this does not imply a direct historical connection or continuity.